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WHAT DRIVES THE GROWTH OF BLACK HOLES?

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by
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Abstract

There are supermassive black holes (SMBHs) in the centers of most massive galaxies. Observations of nearby systems have found that SMBH masses (M_{BH}) are tightly correlated with host-galaxy properties such as bulge masses. These local SMBH-galaxy relations suggest that SMBH growth is fundamentally linked to host galaxies over cosmic history. Previous studies suggest that long-term average SMBH accretion rate ($\overline{\text{BHAR}}$) is intrinsically related to star formation rate (SFR) for the overall galaxy population. However, we show that $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ is more strongly correlated with host-galaxy stellar mass (M_*) rather than SFR (Chapter 2), and this $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_*$ relation does not depend on cosmic environment (Chapter 3). We further quantify this $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_*$ relation and its cosmic evolution at $z = 0.4-4$ (Chapter 4). However, we find this $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_*$ relation does not hold for bulge-dominated galaxies, and their $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ primarily depends on SFR (Chapter 5). This $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-\text{SFR}$ relation among bulge-dominated galaxies indicates that SMBHs only coevolve with galactic bulges rather than the entire galaxies, consistent with the observations of the local universe.

Aside from the content above, which centers on the theme of “what drives the growth of black holes”, this dissertation also includes my other three works as appendices. These works include studies of photometric redshift (Appendix A), X-ray variability of active galactic nuclei (Appendix B), and fast extragalactic X-ray transients (Appendix C).

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Chapter 1 |

Overview

In the centers of most massive galaxies (including the Milky Way), there are supermassive black holes (SMBHs) with masses (M_{BH}) of 10^5 – $10^{10} M_{\odot}$ [1–4]. Observations of the local universe found that M_{BH} is tightly connected with host-galaxy properties such as stellar mass (M_{bulge}) and velocity dispersion of the bulge [4–8]. For example, the intrinsic scatter of the M_{BH} - M_{bulge} correlation is only ≈ 0.3 dex [4]. These connections are surprising, since M_{BH} is only a tiny fraction ($\sim 1/1000$) of galaxy mass. Therefore, the SMBH-galaxy connection in the local universe likely originates from some fundamental physical relations between the cosmic growth history of SMBHs and host galaxies. Understanding these physical relations is one of the essential challenges of modern extragalactic astronomy.

Tremendous observational efforts have been made to identify these mysterious connections, based on multiwavelength surveys that are able to probe (almost) the full growth history of SMBHs and host galaxies. It has been found that the cosmic evolution of SMBH accretion rate (BHAR) density and star formation rate (SFR) density are broadly similar, both peaking at $z \sim 2$ [9–13]. However, from observations of active galactic nuclei (AGNs, the actively growing SMBHs), the SFR is a relatively flat function of the observed BHAR at a given redshift [14–20]. This apparent lack of a strong SFR-BHAR connection might be caused by AGN variability. While star formation activity is stable on time scales longer than ~ 100 Myr, SMBH accretion could vary strongly on much shorter time scales ($\sim 10^2$ – 10^7 yr) [21–24]. Therefore, an intrinsic connection between SFR and long-term average BHAR might be hidden by this strong AGN variability.

To obtain long-term average BHAR, the ideal way is to observe a galaxy for at least millions of years and derive its time-averaged BHAR during this period,

but this approach is presently infeasible. Practically, it has been proposed to adopt sample-averaged BHAR ($\overline{\text{BHAR}}$) as a proxy of long-term average BHAR [25, 26]. Indeed, observations have found a positive linear $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -SFR connection [18, 25, 26], which is widely interpreted as strong evidence of SMBH-galaxy coevolution.

If this positive $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -SFR relation is fundamental, then $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ should mainly depend on SFR rather than other host-galaxy properties such as total stellar mass (M_\star). However, in Chapter 2, we show, using partial-correlation analyses, that $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ is actually more strongly related to M_\star than SFR for the general galaxy population. This result suggests that the apparent $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -SFR relation is only a secondary effect resulting from the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ - M_\star relation and the SFR- M_\star relation of star-forming galaxies (star-formation main sequence). In Chapter 3, we further show that once M_\star is carefully controlled, SMBH accretion is largely independent of the cosmic environment (≈ 0.1 – 10 Mpc) of the host galaxies, consistent with previous AGN clustering studies [27–30].

Motivated by the important role of M_\star in connecting SMBHs and host galaxies, we quantitatively derived the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ - M_\star relation at different redshifts up to $z = 4$ in Chapter 4. Aided by the galaxy-evolution model from the literature [31], we derive the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ /SFR ratio as a function of M_\star , and find that $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ /SFR rises significantly toward high M_\star . This strong rise naturally leads to a positive dependence of M_{BH}/M_\star on M_\star , consistent with the observations of local systems [4, 32]. This positive dependence contradicts the scenario that the local M_{BH} -galaxy relations are driven by merger averaging, which requires that M_{BH}/M_\star does not depend on M_\star systematically [33, 34].

Despite the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ - M_\star relation being generally supported by observations, it cannot straightforwardly explain the tightness of the M_{BH} - M_{bulge} correlation. The key to the origin of the tight M_{BH} - M_{bulge} correlation might be related to the morphology of host galaxies, since M_{BH} is only correlated with the masses of classical bulges rather than other galactic components such as pseudo-bulges or disks [4]. Therefore, SMBH growth might be related to star formation activity of the bulge only. To investigate this potential SMBH-bulge coevolution, one should ideally study the relation between $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ and bulge SFR in the distant universe. With current facilities, it is infeasible to separate the bulge SFR from total SFR when disks are present.

However, the recent acquisition and extensive development of *Hubble*'s CAN-

DELS fields allow reliable selection of bulge-dominated galaxies (up to $z \approx 3$, e.g. [35–37]), for which bulge SFR \approx total SFR. If SMBHs indeed coevolve with host-galaxy bulges, we expect a strong correlation between $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ and SFR for these bulge-dominated galaxies over cosmic history. In Chapter 5, we focus on such a sample of bulge-dominated galaxies in the CANDELS fields. Indeed, we find a strong $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -SFR relation among our bulge-dominated sample. In contrast, such a $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -SFR relation does not exist for our comparison sample (galaxies that are not bulge dominated), for which M_\star appears to be the main driver of $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$. Our best-fit $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ /SFR ratio is also similar to the typical $M_{\text{BH}}/M_{\text{bulge}}$ ratios observed in the local universe. These results indicate that the growth of SMBHs and host-galaxy bulges are in lockstep. This lockstep growth, rather than merger averaging, is responsible for the observed $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\text{bulge}}$ relation in the local systems.

The above contents are the main part of this dissertation, focusing on the theme of “what drives the growth of black holes?”. Aside from these contents, this dissertation also includes my other three first-author studies, which are conducted during my PhD period. These works are summarized below:

1. In Appendix A, we present a photometric-redshift catalog of 131,678 sources in Hawaii-Hubble Deep Field-North (H-HDF-N, $\approx 0.4 \text{ deg}^2$). These redshifts are derived from a set of point-spread-function-matched photometry of 15 broad bands from the ultraviolet (U band) to mid-infrared (IRAC $4.5\mu\text{m}$). The quality of these redshifts shows an overall improvement over earlier redshift works on H-HDF-N. We make this catalog publicly available.
2. In Appendix B, we analyze long-term (≈ 15 years) X-ray variability properties of the 68 brightest AGNs in the CDF-S. AGNs like those studied here produce a significant fraction of cosmic accretion power; in this sense, they are the typical AGNs of the universe. We perform not only traditional photometric analyses, but also spectral analyses with new techniques. We find that most (74%) AGNs show intrinsic X-ray luminosity (L_X) variability, and the variability amplitudes are smaller for more luminous sources. In contrast, only 16% AGNs show absorption (N_H) variability.
3. In Appendix C, we perform a systematic search of fast extragalactic X-ray transients in *Chandra* surveys, motivated by the recent discovery of two

extragalactic transients by *Chandra* in the CDF-S (CDF-S XT1 and XT2; [38]; Xue et al. submitted). We develop an algorithm that can effectively select fast X-ray transients based on a single *Chandra* exposure, and apply it to *Chandra* surveys of CDF-S, CDF-N, DEEP2, UDS, COSMOS, and E-CDF-S, totaling 19 Ms of exposure. We find 17 transients, including CDF-S XT1 and XT2, and investigate their physical nature with the aid of multiwavelength information. Aside from CDF-S XT1 and XT2, the other 15 transients are all stellar objects. We estimate an event rate of 46_{-30}^{+61} evt yr⁻¹deg⁻² for fast extragalactic transients with peak fluxes $F_{0.5-7 \text{ keV}} \gtrsim 2 \times 10^{-13}$ erg cm⁻² s⁻¹.

Chapter 2 | Black-Hole Growth is Mainly Linked to Host-Galaxy Stellar Mass rather than Star For- mation Rate

2.1 Introduction

The origin of the likely coevolution between supermassive black holes (SMBHs) and their host galaxies remains a fundamental question [4, 39–41]. Observations reveal a linear correlation between star formation rate (SFR) and sample-averaged black-hole accretion rate ($\overline{\text{BHAR}}$) for star-forming galaxies (C13 hereafter). [25] Also, X-ray-selected active galactic nuclei (AGNs) preferentially reside in star-forming rather than quiescent galaxies for samples with matched stellar mass (M_*). [42] and optically selected luminous quasars tend to be hosted by strongly star-forming systems. [43, 44] However, the sample-averaged SFR ($\langle \text{SFR} \rangle$) of the host galaxies of X-ray AGNs do not show a significant dependence on the BHAR in the regimes of low and moderate AGN luminosity, while the potential existence of a positive SFR-BHAR relation at high luminosities is still debatable. [14, 17, 45, 46].

To reconcile the apparent discrepancy, a previous study (H14 hereafter) [26] proposed a model in which the long-term (~ 100 Myr) average BHAR traces SFR linearly, but AGN variability hides the BHAR-SFR relation for individual X-ray AGNs; [42] SFRs are stable over timescales $\gtrsim 100$ Myr, while AGNs are variable

over much shorter timescales. This simple scenario reasonably explains observations, including both the linear $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ -SFR relation for star-forming galaxies and the generally flat $\langle \text{SFR} \rangle$ -BHAR relation for X-ray-selected AGNs.

The H14 model requires strong AGN variability (by a factor of $\gg 10$) on timescales of $\lesssim 10^7$ yr to be commonplace. Although variability studies on the longest available timescales ($\lesssim 10$ yr, rest-frame) do not directly reveal the prevalence of such variability, [47, 48] its occurrence on timescales of $10^2 - 10^7$ yr is plausible from both observational and theoretical points of view. [23, 49] In fact, some observational evidence suggests the typical AGN-phase time scale is $\sim 10^5$ yr, as expected from the chaotic-accretion scenario. [50, 51]. Due to the potential existence of such strong variability, the BHAR derived from direct X-ray observations of individual AGNs might not be a reliable indicator of long-term average SMBH growth rate. On the other hand, $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$, the average BHAR over a sample of galaxies, serves as a proxy for typical long-term average BHAR of the sample (e.g., C13 and H14). Therefore, $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ provides a useful tool to study SMBH-galaxy coevolution.

Another major motivation of the H14 model is that, in the local elliptical galaxies, the mass of SMBHs (M_{BH}) is roughly proportional to the bulge M_* (equivalent to host-galaxy M_* for ellipticals). [4] If the long-term average BHAR is proportional to SFR for all galaxies, then a natural consequence is that M_{BH} correlates with M_* linearly, as long as the accreted mass dominates over the mass of SMBH seeds. [52] However, hints have been found of spiral and dwarf galaxies hosting undermassive SMBHs relative to the $M_{\text{BH}}-M_*$ relation derived from ellipticals, although large uncertainties exist [32, 53–56]. This behavior is not expected from the H14 model which assumes SFR is the only factor determining long-term average BHAR. Also, simulations indicate that the apparent discrepancy between the $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ -SFR and the $\langle \text{SFR} \rangle$ -BHAR relations can be produced by the effect of binning on the intrinsic bivariate relationship between BHAR and SFR, [57] regardless of whether the intrinsic shape of this distribution is produced by an intrinsic long-term BHAR-SFR relation as proposed by H14.

Observations show that the fraction of AGNs above a given luminosity threshold rises steeply toward massive galaxies. [58–61] Furthermore, for M_* -matched samples, the fraction of galaxies hosting AGNs appears to have no dependence on host-galaxy colors. [58, 62, 63] However, apparent galaxy colors might be a poor indicator of SFR,

as high-SFR galaxies might appear red due to significant dust obscuration. [42, 64] Therefore, it is still not clear whether M_* or SFR is the dominant factor correlated with black-hole accretion.

With the advent of deep ultraviolet-to-infrared (UV-to-IR) observations from surveys such as CANDELS, [65, 66], it has become possible to estimate reliably M_* and SFR for the majority population of galaxies with acceptable uncertainties ($\lesssim 0.1$ and 0.2 dex for M_* and SFR, respectively; see Sec. 2.2.2). The uncertainties on M_* and SFR are small compared to the parameter ranges probed (both ≈ 3 orders of magnitude), and thus are acceptable for our analyses. The 7 Ms *Chandra* Deep Field-South (CDF-S, covering the whole GOODS-S region; see [67]; L17 hereafter). X-ray survey has achieved unprecedented sensitivities, allowing the derivation of accurate $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ values for the galaxies in GOODS-S. In this paper, we evaluate the dependence of $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ on both SFR and M_* for galaxies in GOODS-S. Also, we study the efficiency of SMBH growth compared to SFR for galaxies of different M_* .

The paper is structured as follows. We describe the sample selection and measurements of SFR, M_* , and BHAR in Sec. 2.2. In Sec. 2.3, we present the results of our analyses. We discuss scientific implications of our results in Sec. 2.4. We summarize our results in Sec. 2.5.

Throughout this paper, we assume a cosmology with $H_0 = 70 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$, $\Omega_M = 0.3$, and $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.7$, and a Chabrier initial mass function. [68]. Quoted uncertainties are at the 1σ (68%) confidence level, unless otherwise stated. SFR and BHAR are in units of $M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$, and M_* is in units of M_\odot , unless otherwise stated.

2.2 Data Analyses

2.2.1 Sample Selection

We first select all galaxies with $0.5 \leq z < 2.0$ and $\text{F160W} < 28$ in the GOODS-S catalog [69] (S15 hereafter).¹ We do not include sources beyond $z = 2$, because M_* and SFR values estimated from SED fitting (Sec. 2.2.2) suffer from potential biases in that redshift regime [70, 71]. The SEDs of broad-line AGNs often have significant

¹F160W = 28 is approximately the 5σ limiting magnitude of the GOODS-S catalog [69].

Sample (1)	Low- z (2)	High- z (3)	Total (4)	Fig(s). (5)
All	10057	8164	18221	2.1 and 2.2
$0.1 \leq \text{SFR} < 100 M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (A)	6384	7541	13925	2.4
$10^8 \leq M_* < 10^{11} M_{\odot}$ (B)	6445	6669	13114	2.5 and 2.8
(A) \wedge (B)	5224	6236	11460	2.6

Table 2.1: Numbers of Sources in Different Samples. Column (1): sample definition. Columns (2) and (3): number of sources with $0.5 \leq z < 1.3$ and $1.3 \leq z < 2.0$, respectively. Column (4): total number of sources in both redshift ranges. Column (5): relevant figure(s).

accretion-disk emission besides their starlight. Their SFR and M_* measurements from SED fitting have potential large uncertainties [60, 72]. Thus, we exclude the 19 broad-line AGNs reported in the literature [73–75], and discuss the effects of their exclusion in Sec. 2.3.5.1. Applying these criteria, we select 18221 sources (see Tab. 2.1), of which 1305 have secure spectroscopic redshifts, and the rest have high-quality photometric redshifts based on up to 17 bands from the UV to IR (S15). Compared to spectroscopic redshifts when available, the photometric redshifts have median uncertainty $|z_{\text{phot}} - z_{\text{spec}}|/(1 + z_{\text{spec}}) \approx 2\%$ with an outlier (uncertainty $> 15\%$) fraction of 3%.

2.2.2 Stellar Mass and Star Formation Rate

We collect the M_* and SFR values for our sources from S15, who presented SED-fitting results of several independent teams. We adopt the median values of M_* and SFR from the five available teams (i.e., labeled as 2a $_{\tau}$, 6a $_{\tau}$, 11a $_{\tau}$, 13a $_{\tau}$, and 14a in S15). All five teams employed stellar templates from [76] and a Chabrier IMF when performing the SED fitting. Teams 2a $_{\tau}$, 6a $_{\tau}$, 11a $_{\tau}$, and 13a $_{\tau}$ assumed an exponentially declining star formation history (SFH); 14a assumed a more flexible SFH (see S15). Teams 2a $_{\tau}$, 6a $_{\tau}$, 11a $_{\tau}$, and 14a adopted Calzetti extinction law [77]; 13a $_{\tau}$ adopted a combination of Calzetti and SMC extinction laws. The M_* and SFR values estimated by the five teams agree well; their typical deviations from the adopted medians are $\lesssim 0.1$ dex and $\lesssim 0.2$ dex, respectively. These values largely represent uncertainties arising from SED fitting, and additional systematic errors (from, e.g., IMF and SFH assumptions) likely exist. However, such systematic uncertainties should not affect our conclusions qualitatively (see Sec. 2.3). Fig. 2.1 shows M_* and SFR as functions of redshift, and Fig. 2.2 shows the M_* -SFR plane

for all our sources. From Figs. 2.1 (top panel) and 2.2, X-ray detected sources² are preferentially found among massive galaxies [58, 59]. Our sample is roughly complete for galaxies with $M_* \gtrsim 10^8 M_\odot$ and $\text{SFR} \gtrsim 0.1 M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (i.e., the M_* and SFR regimes mostly probed by our analyses; see Sec. 2.3). A more detailed discussion of completeness is presented in Sec. 2.3.5.2.

Figure 2.1: The top (middle) panel shows M_* (SFR) vs. redshift for all our sources. The red squares indicate X-ray detected sources. The blue dashed lines indicate our binning grids in Figs. 2.4, 2.5, and 2.8. The bottom panel presents absorption-corrected L_X (see Sec. 2.2.3) as a function of redshift for X-ray detected sources. The blue stars indicate broad-line AGNs that are excluded from our sample. The overdensities at $z \approx 0.7$ and 1.6 are likely due to cosmic variance [67, 75, 78].

²These are sources presented in the 7 Ms CDF-S main catalog (Sec. 2.2.3), formally defined with “binomial no-source probability” $P_B < 0.007$ (see L17).

Figure 2.2: SFR vs. M_* for all our sources. The red squares indicate X-ray detected sources. The blue dashed lines indicate our binning grids in Fig. 2.6.

The rest-frame UV-to-near-IR SEDs ($\approx 0.2 - 4 \mu\text{m}$, similar to the wavelength range used by S15 to derive M_* and SFR) of X-ray-selected AGNs in the CDF-S are usually dominated by stellar light [58, 79, 80]. In addition, we have excluded broad-line AGNs (Sec. 2.2.1), because their M_* and SFR measurements from SED fitting could be overestimated [81]. Therefore, the CANDELS M_* and SFR should not have significant biases due to AGN activity. Also, we confirm that AGNs do not have biased SED-based SFRs in comparison with SFRs based on far-IR (FIR) photometry (see below).

As demonstrated by S15, the CANDELS M_* values generally have high quality. To evaluate the accuracy of CANDELS SED-based SFRs, which ultimately come from dust-corrected UV luminosities, we compare them with those obtained from FIR photometry. We match our sources with the *Herschel*/PACS catalog of the PACS Evolutionary Probe (PEP; e.g., [82, 83]) survey using a $2''$ matching radius.³ We follow the method of C13 to derive FIR-based SFRs for the matched sources.

³We use the $24 \mu\text{m}$ -prior PEP catalog due to its good positional accuracy.

Briefly, we convert the PACS band flux to total IR luminosity according to the star-forming galaxy spectral template from [84],⁴ and then we scale the IR luminosity to SFR following the relation from [85] (modified for our Chabrier IMF; see C13). We use the PACS 100 μm band for sources at $0.5 \leq z < 1.3$ and the 160 μm band at $1.3 \leq z < 2.0$, requiring photometric S/N > 5 . Using different bands for different redshift ranges is to sample the SED peak ($\approx 50 - 80 \mu\text{m}$, rest-frame; e.g., [84]) of cold dust emission, a good proxy for star formation. The FIR-based SFR estimation assumes that dust absorbs most UV photons and re-emits IR radiation. It is thus robust for galaxies with relatively high SFR ($\gtrsim 1 M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) where dust is often abundant [86, 87], and this is indeed our case, since low-SFR galaxies within our redshift range ($0.5 \leq z < 2.0$) are usually not detected by *Herschel*.

Fig. 2.3 compares CANDELS SED-based SFRs with FIR-based SFRs for *Herschel*-detected galaxies that probe the SFR range of $\approx 10^{0.5} - 10^{2.5} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$. CANDELS SFRs generally agree well with FIR-based SFRs without significant systematic bias: the median offset between them is 0.01 dex. The median offset depends on SFR (the blue solid curve in Fig. 2.3). The offset is small ($\lesssim 0.2$ dex) at low and intermediate SFR, but becomes ≈ 0.3 dex at $\text{SFR} \sim 100 M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$. The median offsets for the low- z and high- z bins are 0.07 and 0.16 dex, respectively. A similar systematic offset in the high-SFR (also high- z) regime is also found by [70], possibly because dust correction cannot fully recover the intrinsic UV luminosity when the obscuration is very strong. Nevertheless, the systematic errors are smaller than our bin width of SFR (i.e., 0.5 and 1 dex; see Sec. 2.3), and thus should not affect our results significantly.

For most sources (80%), the SFRs derived by the two methods agree within 0.5 dex (the dashed lines in Fig. 2.3). The outliers (20%) tend to have FIR-based SFRs higher than SED-based SFRs, possibly because the FIR sample is flux-limited and FIR-luminous outliers are more likely to be detected by *Herschel* (see also, e.g., [16]). There are 6% extreme outliers with SFR offsets larger than 1 dex. For these sources, the SFR measurements from different SED-fitting teams are often inconsistent; their typical deviations from the adopted medians are $\approx 0.3 - 1$ dex, significantly larger than those for the whole sample ($\lesssim 0.2$ dex). The likely failure of SED fitting might be caused by inappropriate model assumptions in SED fitting,

⁴ [84] present two templates at $z \sim 1$ and $z \sim 2$, respectively. Here, we use the $z \sim 1$ template following C13, although the $z \sim 2$ template leads to almost the same results.

e.g., SFH and extinction law. False matches between the CANDELS and FIR catalogs might also be responsible for some of the extreme outliers. Nevertheless, none of these extreme outliers has high X-ray luminosities ($> 3 \times 10^{42}$ erg s $^{-1}$), and their large SFR uncertainties are unlikely to affect our results qualitatively. Notably, for AGN-dominated X-ray sources with $L_X > 3 \times 10^{42}$ erg s $^{-1}$ (see L17; red symbols in Fig. 2.3), the CANDELS SFRs do not show a significant systematic bias relative to SFRs derived from FIR photometry: the median offset is 0.01 dex, similar as the value for all *Herschel*-detected galaxies above. Therefore, the SED-based SFRs are reliable for galaxies with $\text{SFR} \gtrsim 10^{0.5} M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$. In the lower-SFR regimes, corrections for dust extinction are generally low or moderate, and SED-based SFRs are generally reliable [70, 87].

2.2.3 Black-Hole Accretion Rate

We use X-ray observations to derive $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ for our sources. We match our 18221 galaxies with the 7 Ms main source catalog for the CDF-S (L17) using a 0.5'' matching radius, and 395 X-ray sources are matched.⁵ A total of 259 of the 395 X-ray-detected sources have spectroscopic redshifts. The host-galaxy properties (z , M_* , and SFR) of these X-ray detected sources are shown in Figs. 2.1 and 2.2.

We fit their unbinned X-ray spectra (observed-frame 0.5–7 keV) with the Cash statistic [88]. We perform the fitting with a standard absorbed power-law model (i.e., *wabs* × *zwabs* × *powerlaw* in XSPEC; see [89] for a description of XSPEC) to recover their absorption-corrected X-ray luminosities (L_X , rest-frame 2–10 keV; e.g., [48]). The *wabs* component accounts for Galactic absorption with absorption column density (N_{H}) set to 8.8×10^{19} cm $^{-2}$ [90]. The *zwabs* component models intrinsic absorption (i.e., *wabs* at redshift z). The normalization of *powerlaw*, intrinsic photon index, and intrinsic N_{H} are free parameters in the fitting. The allowed ranges of photon index and N_{H} are set to 1.4–2.2 and $10^{19} - 10^{24}$ cm $^{-2}$, respectively. We then obtain the L_X with XSPEC from the best-fit model parameters. The

⁵We use the positions of the L17 optical/near-infrared counterparts rather than the X-ray positions, because the former are more accurate. In the GOODS-S field, there are 704 out of the 1008 X-ray sources in the L17 catalog, and most of them (674/704 = 96%) have CANDELS counterparts. The remaining 30 sources without counterparts might be faint (F160W band) sources not detected by CANDELS, nearby off-nuclear sources (e.g., ultraluminous X-ray sources), or false X-ray detections (L17). 395 of the 674 X-ray sources with CANDELS counterparts are galaxies in our redshift range ($0.5 \leq z < 2.0$) without broad lines reported in their spectra.

Figure 2.3: Comparison between SFRs derived from SED fitting and those derived from FIR photometry. Circles and stars indicate sources in the redshift ranges of $0.5 \leq z < 1.3$ and $1.3 \leq z < 2.0$, respectively. Their FIR-based SFRs are derived from $100 \mu\text{m}$ and $160 \mu\text{m}$ observations with *Herschel*/PACS, respectively (see Sec. 2.2.2). Red symbols indicate AGNs selected by their large X-ray luminosities ($L_X > 3 \times 10^{42} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$; see e.g., L17). The black solid line indicates 1:1 relation between two SFR measurements; the dashed lines indicate 0.5-dex offsets. Our adopted SFRs (from SED fitting) generally agree with those derived from FIR photometry. The blue solid curve indicates running median SFR offsets from bins of 50 sources. For X-ray-luminous AGNs, the SED-based SFRs do not have significant systematic differences relative to FIR-based SFRs.

best-fit L_X as a function of redshift is shown in Fig. 2.1 (bottom). Thanks to the great sensitivity of the 7 Ms CDF-S survey, sources with low X-ray luminosities ($\lesssim 3 \times 10^{42} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$) can be detected up to $z = 2$. X-ray emission at this low level might not be dominated by AGNs, but could also originate from stellar processes.

Our absorbed power-law model is appropriate for moderately obscured or unobscured AGNs; it might result in unreliable L_X for Compton-thick AGNs (CTK AGNs; i.e., $N_H \gtrsim 10^{24} \text{ cm}^{-2}$). However, it is generally challenging to identify *bona-fide* CTK AGNs among the X-ray detected sources in deep fields such as CDF-S due to the limited numbers of counts available, and there is no strong evidence suggesting that CTK AGNs are the dominant population (e.g., [91, 92];

Sec. 3.3 of [80]). We have tested a basic CTK model, $wabs \times zwabs \times pexmon$, on our X-ray detected sources (see [93, 94] for $pexmon$; see App. B of [48] for model parameter settings). Only 4% of sources show statistically significant improvements in fitting compared to our adopted $wabs \times zwabs \times powerlaw$ model, where we use the Akaike information criterion to infer fitting improvement (see [48] for details). Thus, CTK sources are not likely to be the dominant population in our sample. Depending on model assumptions (e.g., obscuration geometry and viewing angle), the CTK models available often have large uncertainties in the derived physical parameters, e.g., L_X and N_H [95]. Therefore, we do not adopt the spectral-fitting results from the CTK models. A discussion on the effects of X-ray non-detected CTK sources is presented in Sec. 2.3.5.1.

For sources without X-ray detections in each sample in Sec. 2.3, we perform a stacking analysis to derive their total L_X following the procedures of [96]. Briefly, we convert the stacked total count rate of the soft band⁶ to total L_X ($L_{X,stack}$) of the stacked sources assuming their median redshift⁷ and a power-law spectrum with an effective photon index of $\Gamma = 1.8$. By setting $\Gamma = 1.8$, we assume the stacked signals are mainly from X-ray emission of X-ray binaries (XRBs) and/or AGNs with low obscuration of $N_H \lesssim 10^{21.5} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (see Sec. 6.1 of [97] for a detailed discussion). Indeed, our stacked X-ray fluxes are similar to those expected from XRBs (see Sec. 2.3.1 and 2.3.2). Even if we adopt a very flat spectral shape of $\Gamma = 1$ (i.e., assume all the stacked X-ray signals are entirely caused by moderately obscured AGNs with $N_H \sim 10^{22.5} \text{ cm}^{-2}$), the resulting $L_{X,stack}$ will be only ~ 0.3 dex higher, unlikely to have a large impact on our qualitative results (see Sec. 2.3). We discuss the potential effects of heavily obscured AGNs that might not be included in our analyses in Sec. 2.3.5.1. Following [96], we exclude sources that are at off-axis angles greater than $7.8'$ or close to X-ray detected sources (see [96] for the specific criteria) in the stacking analyses. Those excluded sources represent a real population of galaxies, and thus their contribution to $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ should be included in our analyses.

⁶Observed-frame 0.5–2 keV. The soft band has larger collecting area and lower background, than the hard band (observed-frame 2–7 keV), e.g., the expected count rate in the soft band is ≈ 2 times larger than that in the hard band for a $\Gamma = 1.8$ power-law spectrum. We have tested stacking the count rate in the hard band. However, the resulting S/N is generally much weaker than that from soft-band stacking, and the hard-band stacked count rates are consistent with zero in many cases.

⁷The median and mean redshifts for our samples (Sec. 2.3) are similar, and they only differ by $\lesssim 0.02$.

We account for the excluded sources ($\lesssim 25\%$ of the X-ray-undetected sources) in each sample by assuming that their mean L_X is the same as that of the stacked sources, and scale the $L_{X,\text{stack}}$ by multiplying $N_{\text{non}}/N_{\text{stack}}$ to obtain the total L_X of all X-ray-undetected sources (Eq. 2.1).

XRBs and other stellar processes in galaxies also contribute to the observed L_X , and thus we need to subtract their contribution ($L_{X,\text{XRB}}$).⁸ The $L_{X,\text{XRB}}$ is estimated as $L_{X,\text{XRB}} = \alpha M_* + \beta \text{SFR}$, where α and β are coefficients as functions of redshift. We adopted the redshift-dependent α and β values from model 269 of [98] [corrected to our Chabrier IMF following the prescriptions from [99] and [12]] that is preferred by the observations of [97].⁹ Our adopted α and β are also consistent with the values from [101]: the differences are ≈ 0.1 dex for both α and β in $0.5 \leq z < 2.0$. The mean AGN L_X for each sample is calculated as

$$\langle L_X \rangle = \frac{(\sum_{\text{detect}} L_X) + \frac{N_{\text{non}}}{N_{\text{stack}}} L_{X,\text{stack}} - \sum_{\text{all}} L_{X,\text{XRB}}}{N_{\text{detect}} + N_{\text{non}}}, \quad (2.1)$$

where N_{detect} , N_{non} , and N_{stack} are the numbers of X-ray-detected, undetected, and stacked sources in the sample, respectively. We do not exclude the 18 radio-loud AGNs identified by [102] in our analyses, although excluding them would have only minor effects on our results. Jet-linked X-ray emission might contribute to their L_X , but, at least for the two X-ray brightest radio-loud AGNs, detailed studies do not reveal significant jet-linked X-ray emission [103].

We convert $\langle L_X \rangle$ to mean BHAR as

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \text{BHAR} \rangle &= \frac{(1 - \epsilon) k_{\text{bol}} \langle L_X \rangle}{\epsilon c^2} \\ &= \frac{3.53 \langle L_X \rangle}{10^{45} \text{ erg s}^{-1}} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1} \end{aligned} \quad (2.2)$$

where we assume a constant bolometric correction factor of $k_{\text{bol}} = 22.4$ (the median value for the local AGN sample with $L_X \approx 10^{41} - 10^{45} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$ in [104]) and a constant mass-energy conversion efficiency of $\epsilon = 0.1$ [105, 106]. We obtain the 1σ confidence interval as the range between the 16th and 84th percentiles of the bootstrapped

⁸X-ray emission from XRBs usually dominates over that from other stellar processes. We assume that all non-AGN X-rays are XRB contributions.

⁹We have also tested a simpler $L_{X,\text{XRB}}$ model [100] in which α is zero and β is a constant (i.e., not dependent on redshift). Our results below only change slightly using this model.

$\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ distribution. To obtain the $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ distribution, we randomly resample the sources 1000 times. In this routine procedure of bootstrapping, each random resampling includes the same number of sources as the original sample but allowing repetition of sources. We then calculate $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ with Eqs. 2.1 and 3.3 for each resampling and obtain the $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ distribution.

From Eq. 3.3, we obtain $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ from $\langle L_X \rangle$. This is because X-ray emission is almost a universal tracer of black-hole accretion [107]. X-rays are also relatively less affected by obscuration compared to the UV/optical bands, and suffer minimal starlight dilution [80]. Nevertheless, there might be uncertainties in the conversion factors (k_{bol} and ϵ) between $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ and $\langle L_X \rangle$. The $k_{\text{bol}} = 22.4$ and $\epsilon = 0.1$ assumptions have been widely adopted in previous studies related to black-hole accretion (e.g., [11] and C13). We have also tested applying a luminosity-dependent k_{bol} [108] for the AGN-dominated sources with $L_X > 3 \times 10^{42} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$ (e.g., L17), and our results do not change qualitatively. Applying the luminosity-dependent k_{bol} to low-luminosity sources requires careful subtraction of $L_{X,\text{XRB}}$ for each individual source, but this correction is beyond the scope of our analyses. For simplicity and consistency over all sources, we adopt a constant k_{bol} in our analyses.

Since we include all X-ray detected and non-detected sources (Eq. 2.1), we are measuring $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ averaged over all galaxies, including systems with both high and low levels of nuclear activity. This is designed to approximate the long-term average BHAR for the entire galaxy sample rather than the instantaneous BHAR for individual AGNs (see Sec. 2.1).

2.3 Results

2.3.1 BHAR Dependence on SFR

We bin our sources in six different SFR intervals (bin width = 0.5 dex, see Fig. 2.1) for two different redshift ranges ($0.5 \leq z < 1.3$ and $1.3 \leq z < 2.0$), and calculate the $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ for each of the 12 bins which together include 13925 sources (Tab. 2.1) using Eqs. 2.1 and 3.3. In the following analyses, we discard all bins that have fewer than 100 sources to avoid large statistical fluctuations, unless otherwise

stated.¹⁰ This selection is the main reason why we cannot probe the high-SFR (SFR > 100 M_{\odot} yr⁻¹) and high- M_* ($M_* > 10^{11} M_{\odot}$) regimes (Sec. 2.3.2).

Fig. 2.4 displays the results. In general, galaxies with higher SFR have higher \langle BHAR \rangle . We perform a least- χ^2 fitting for the \langle BHAR \rangle -SFR relation with a linear model,¹¹ and obtain

$$\log(\langle\text{BHAR}\rangle) = (0.93 \pm 0.08) \log(\text{SFR}) - (3.85 \pm 0.07) \quad (2.3)$$

with reduced $\chi^2 = 1.48$ which corresponds to a model-rejection p -value of 15%. The slope is consistent with unity. To compare with the H14 model which assumes \langle BHAR \rangle is proportional to SFR (\langle BHAR $\rangle = \text{SFR}/3000$), we fix the slope to one and refit the data. This fit results in

$$\log(\langle\text{BHAR}\rangle) = \log(\langle\text{SFR}\rangle) - (3.89 \pm 0.07) \quad (2.4)$$

(the solid lines in Fig. 2.4) and a reduced χ^2 of 1.40 (p -value = 17%). The best-fit intercept (-3.89) is ≈ 0.4 dex lower than that expected from the H14 model (i.e., -3.48 ; shown as the dotted lines in Fig. 2.4); possible reasons are explained in Secs. 2.3.3 and 2.3.5.1. Our intercept is also similar to the value (≈ -3.6) derived from [55], which is based on optically selected AGNs in the local universe ($z < 0.1$).¹² In general, X-ray emission from XRBs (the dashed lines) is lower compared to that from AGNs, and it is less significant at high SFR. The stacked X-ray emission for individually undetected galaxies is consistent with being entirely due to XRBs.

¹⁰Without this constraint, we can only extend the SFR and M_* ranges by ≈ 0.5 dex (i.e., one bin; see Figs. 2.4 and 2.5). Such extended samples have very large uncertainties on \langle BHAR \rangle (~ 1 dex or only upper limit available) likely caused by statistical fluctuations, since each sample has only $\lesssim 20$ sources.

¹¹We employ the Python code, `scipy.optimize.curve_fit`, to performing the fitting. We use the median SFR of each bin when we perform the fitting. We adopt the mean values of 1σ upper and lower uncertainties on \langle BHAR \rangle in the fitting. We do not apply an error to the median SFR for simplicity, since the SFR distribution in each bin usually has a strong non-Gaussian shape. The code estimates the uncertainties on best-fit parameters from the covariance matrix. Median SFR and mean SFR are very close, since sources in each bin have similar SFR. Using the median or mean does not affect our results significantly.

¹²Starting from $\lambda_{\text{Edd}}/\text{sSFR} \approx 10^{-2.3}$ in their Fig. 18 (where λ_{Edd} is Eddington ratio and sSFR is specific SFR), we obtain $\text{BHAR}/\text{SFR} \sim 10^{-3.6}$ with the assumption of $\epsilon \sim 0.1$ (Sec. 2.2.3) and $M_*/M_{\text{BH}} \sim 500$ [4, 8].

Figure 2.4: Left panels: $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ as a function of SFR for different redshift ranges. The vertical and horizontal positions of the black points indicate $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ and median SFR, respectively; the horizontal error bars indicate the bin width. The blue upward-pointing and red downward-pointing triangles indicate $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ for two subsamples with $M_* > \text{med}(M_*)$ and $M_* \leq \text{med}(M_*)$, respectively, where $\text{med}(M_*)$ is the median M_* of sources in each bin (Sec. 2.3.3). The solid black line indicates our best-fit linear model with slope fixed at unity; the dotted black line indicates the model proposed by H14. The values of $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ are converted from $\langle L_X \rangle$, which is labelled on the right side of each panel. $\langle L_X \rangle$ is derived considering both X-ray detected and undetected (via stacking) sources, and contamination from galaxies is subtracted (see Sec. 2.2.3). All the errors are estimated via bootstrapping (1000 simulations). If the resulting 1σ lower limit of $\langle L_X \rangle$ is negative, we use the $\langle L_X \rangle$ expected from XRB emission as an upper limit. The dashed black line indicates the $\langle L_{X,\text{XRB}} \rangle$ that has been subtracted for each sample. The dash-dotted line indicates average X-ray luminosities for stacked sources (XRB contributions not subtracted), and it is generally comparable to $\langle L_{X,\text{XRB}} \rangle$. In the lower panel, the lowest-SFR bin has negative stacked $\langle L_X \rangle$ due to weak X-ray signals from the stacked sources and background fluctuations; thus, the dash-dotted line does not extend to the bin with the lowest SFR. Our results can be fitted acceptably by a linear relation between $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ and SFR, but more massive galaxies generally have higher $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ at a given SFR level. Right panels: the median M_* corresponding to each (sub)sample on the left. The numbers of X-ray detected sources and all sources in each (sub)sample are marked on the right side of the corresponding point.

2.3.2 BHAR Dependence on M_*

To investigate the relation between $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ and M_* , we bin our sources in M_* and calculate $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ for each bin. The total number of sources is 13114 (Tab. 2.1).¹³

¹³The sample size here is different from that in Sec. 2.3.1, because the sample here is defined as $10^8 \leq M_* < 10^{11} M_\odot$ while the sample in Sec. 2.3.1 is defined as $0.1 \leq \text{SFR} < 100 M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$.

The results are shown in Fig. 2.5. In general, $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ is higher in more massive galaxies, and the fraction of X-ray detected sources rises toward higher M_* , consistent with previous work (see Sec. 2.1). In the high- z bins, X-ray emission from AGNs is comparable with that expected from XRBs for galaxies with $M_* < 10^{10} M_\odot$, but AGN emission becomes dominant for more massive galaxies. The fact that more massive galaxies have higher $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ is also supported by Fig. 2.1 and Fig. 2.2, which demonstrates that most X-ray detections occur in galaxies with $M_* \gtrsim 10^{10} M_\odot$ despite the fact that those massive galaxies are only $\approx 10\%$ of the whole population. Similar to the behavior in Fig. 2.4 left, X-ray emission from stacked sources is generally comparable to that expected from XRBs. There are several bins ($M_* \lesssim 10^9 M_\odot$) with only a few X-ray-detected sources ($\lesssim 10$; see Fig. 2.5 right). In those bins, the $\langle L_X \rangle$ contribution from X-ray-detected sources does not dominate over that from stacked sources; thus, the small numbers of detected sources do not cause large statistical fluctuations.

As in Sec. 2.3.1, we perform a linear fitting to the $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ - M_* relation. If the slope is allowed to vary, we obtain

$$\log(\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle) = (1.10 \pm 0.08) \log(M_*) - (14.0 \pm 0.8) \quad (2.5)$$

with reduced $\chi^2 = 0.88$ (p -value = 54%); if the slope is fixed to unity, we obtain

$$\log(\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle) = \log(M_*) - (13.0 \pm 0.1) \quad (2.6)$$

with reduced $\chi^2 = 0.94$ (p -value = 50%). Therefore, as for the $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ -SFR relation, the $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ - M_* relation can also be described acceptably by a linear relation with a slope of unity. From Fig. 2.5 left, the $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ - M_* relation is similar in both redshift ranges. The weak redshift dependence is consistent with the behaviors of the AGN X-ray luminosity function (XLF) and stellar mass function (SMF). Both XLF and SMF of our studied regimes (i.e., $L_X \lesssim 10^{44} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$ and $10^8 \lesssim M_* \lesssim 10^{11} M_\odot$, respectively) drop slightly by ≈ 0.2 dex from $z = 0.8$ to 1.7, where these redshift values are the medians of the low- z and high- z samples, respectively (see, e.g., [13, 109]).

In the right panels of Fig. 2.5, the median SFR values for the bins with $M_* \lesssim 10^{10} M_\odot$ are close to those expected from the star-forming main sequence in the model of [31]. For massive galaxies with $M_* \gtrsim 10^{10} M_\odot$, our median SFRs are

systematically lower than the values expected from the star-forming main sequence. This is likely due to the existence of massive evolved systems in our sample. In fact, after removing the quiescent population, our median SFRs agree much better with the B13 model (see Sec. 2.6.1). For both the B13 model and our data, the SFR- M_* relation bends at $M_* \gtrsim 10^{10} M_\odot$ (Fig. 2.5 right), likely due to the depletion of cold gas commonly found in high- M_* systems [110].

Figure 2.5: Same format as Fig. 2.4, but the bins are based on different M_* (x -axis), and each sample is split into two subsamples based on SFR. $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ is positively correlated with M_* . The solid curves in the right panels indicate the star-forming main sequence (B13).

2.3.3 BHAR Dependence on Both SFR and M_*

As shown in Secs. 2.3.1 and 2.3.2, $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ has a positive dependence on both SFR and M_* . However, SFR and M_* are not independent properties for star-forming galaxies, which are the major population in our sample. These two properties are positively related to each other via the star-formation main sequence (e.g., [111]; also see Fig 2.2 and the right panels of Figs. 2.4 and 2.5). Therefore, it is possible that $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ is fundamentally correlated with one factor, and the observed relation with the other factor is only a secondary effect.

To investigate this possibility, we compare $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ for sources with different

M_* (SFR) but similar SFR (M_*). Specifically, we split each sample in Sec. 2.3.1 into two subsamples, i.e., with $M_* \leq \text{med}(M_*)$ and $M_* > \text{med}(M_*)$, respectively, where $\text{med}(M_*)$ is the median M_* in each sample. For completeness, we also split the samples with highest SFR, although the resulting subsamples have less than 100 sources (but more than 50). The high- M_* subsamples have similar typical redshifts compared to the corresponding low- M_* subsamples; the differences between their median redshifts are ≈ 0.1 . We then calculate $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ for both subsamples (red downward and blue upward triangles in Fig. 2.4). In general, the high- M_* subsample has significantly higher ($\approx 0.5 - 1.5$ dex) $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ than its low- M_* counterpart. The typical difference between the median M_* of the two subsamples is ≈ 0.5 dex.

Similarly, we also divide each sample in each M_* bin (Sec. 2.3.2) into two subsamples with $\text{SFR} \leq \text{med}(\text{SFR})$ and $\text{SFR} > \text{med}(\text{SFR})$ (Fig. 2.5). The high-SFR subsamples have slightly higher median redshifts than their low-SFR counterparts; the differences are ≈ 0.25 and 0.1 in the low- z and high- z ranges, respectively. This reflects the cosmic evolution of the star-forming main-sequence, i.e., galaxies tend to have higher specific SFR (sSFR, defined as SFR/M_*) at higher redshift.

As shown in Fig. 2.5, in the low- z range, the high-SFR subsample generally has higher $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$, but for galaxies in the high- z range, the $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ is similar for the two subsamples. Therefore, our results suggest that, at $1.3 \leq z < 2.0$, M_* is likely to be the main physical property correlated with $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$, and the observed $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ -SFR relation might be a secondary effect caused by the SFR- M_* correlation. This is also demonstrated by the comparison between different (sub)samples in Fig. 2.5 bottom panels. For example, the high-SFR subsample with $10^{9.5} < M_* < 10^{10} M_\odot$ has median SFR comparable to those of the two samples with highest M_* , but its $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ value is much lower than those of the latter. Nevertheless, we cannot rule out possible correlation between $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ and SFR in the high- z range. This is because for bins with $M_* < 10^{10} M_\odot$, the $\langle L_X \rangle$ from AGNs is low and comparable to $\langle L_{X,\text{XRB}} \rangle$. Considering the uncertainties associated with, e.g., stacking procedures and XRB modelling, our data are not sufficiently sensitive to differentiate possible $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ differences between high-SFR and low-SFR samples in the low $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ regime (when X-ray emission from AGNs is comparable to or weaker than that from XRBs). It is thus possible that SFR correlates more strongly with $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ at $M_* \gtrsim 10^{10.5} M_\odot$, especially in the low- z range (see the rightmost M_* bins in Fig. 2.5 left); the dependence of $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ on SFR in the high- M_* regime is also suggested

by some previous studies [55, 112, 113]. [42] suggest that among massive galaxies with $M_* \gtrsim 10^{10.5} M_\odot$, X-ray AGNs are more prevalent in high-SFR systems (see also, e.g., [16]). This is consistent with our observations. From the right panels of Fig. 2.5, in the bins with $10^{10.5} \leq M_* < 10^{11} M_\odot$, the high-SFR subsamples have $\approx 1.5 - 2$ times higher fractions of X-ray-detected sources than the low-SFR subsamples.

To clarify better whether SFR or M_* is more important in the low- z range, we bin our sources with $0.5 \leq z < 1.3$ over grids of SFR ($0.1 \leq \text{SFR} < 100 M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$) and M_* ($10^8 \leq M_* < 10^{11} M_\odot$) with the number of sources totaling 5224 (see Tab. 2.1). We enlarge the bin width to 1 dex to include more sources in each bin and reduce the uncertainties of $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ measurements (see Fig. 2.2). The larger bin width also makes our results less sensitive to the measurement errors on SFR and M_* . The results are shown in the upper panel of Fig. 2.6. As expected, both SFR and M_* display positive correlations with $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$.

We perform partial-correlation (PCOR) analyses on the results using “PCOR” in R.¹⁴ The PCOR analyses are deployed to measure the correlation between $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ and SFR (M_*) while controlling for the effects of M_* (SFR). There are three statistics available in `pcor` to perform the analyses: one parametric statistic (Pearson) and two non-parametric statistics (Spearman and Kendall). We perform the analyses with all three methods and list the p -values from each method in Tab. 2.2. All p -values for the $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ - M_* relation are significantly smaller than the corresponding p -values for the $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ -SFR relation, indicating that $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ correlates with M_* more strongly than SFR. The parametric method produces p -values generally smaller than the non-parametric methods. This is because the parametric method assumes linear relations (see Eqs. 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, and 2.6; see also Eqs. 2.7 and 2.8 below) and uses the input data quantitatively, while the non-parametric methods do not have such assumptions but only use ranks of the input data. Among the non-parametric methods, Spearman’s statistic leads to more significant relations than Kendall’s statistic. The reason is likely that the former uses the value of the difference between two ranks, while the latter is even more conservative, and only considers the sign of the difference (e.g., [115]). A

¹⁴The R code `PCOR` is available from <http://www.yilab.gatech.edu/pcor.html> [114]. In the analyses, we provide `PCOR` with $\log(\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle)$, $\log(\text{SFR})$, and $\log(M_*)$ for sources in each bin (as indicated by the black crosses in Fig. 2.6). Here, we use a logarithmic scale instead of a linear scale to reduce potential power-law relations to linear relations among the three quantities.

linear regression results in

$$\begin{aligned} \log(\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle) &= (0.26 \pm 0.11) \log(\text{SFR}) \\ &+ (1.24 \pm 0.11) \log(M_*) - (15.5 \pm 1.1) \end{aligned} \quad (2.7)$$

with reduced $\chi^2 = 0.51$ (model-rejection p -value = 77%; see Footnote 11 for the fitting method).

We also perform the same analyses for sources in both the low- z and high- z ranges together (11460 sources with $0.5 \leq z < 2.0$ as listed in Tab. 2.1).¹⁵ Fig. 2.6 (bottom) displays the results. The p -values from PCOR analyses are shown in Tab. 2.2. The $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ - M_* relation is still significant, in qualitative agreement with the results for the low- z range, but the $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ -SFR relation becomes insignificant. To visualize the PCOR analyses, we first fit $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ as a linear function of M_* (SFR) in logarithmic space, using the same data as in the PCOR analyses (see Fig. 2.6 bottom). Then we model the residuals as a linear function of SFR (M_*), and show the results in Fig. 2.7. The resulting residual-SFR relation is flat, and its slope is consistent with zero at a 3σ confidence level. However, the residual- M_* relation is steep. Therefore, $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ can largely be described via the relation with M_* rather than SFR. Similar analyses have also been performed for the low-redshift bin, and the conclusion is the same.

The linear-fitting ($\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ as a function of SFR and M_*) result is

$$\begin{aligned} \log(\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle) &= (0.22 \pm 0.08) \log(\text{SFR}) \\ &+ (1.16 \pm 0.09) \log(M_*) - (14.6 \pm 0.8), \end{aligned} \quad (2.8)$$

similar as in the low- z range. The best-fit reduced χ^2 is 2.0 which corresponds to a p -value = 9%. The p -value is much smaller than the previous value because the errors on $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ from $0.5 \leq z < 2.0$ (0.10 – 0.44 dex with median = 0.14 dex) are generally smaller than those from $0.5 \leq z < 1.3$ (0.15 – 0.48 dex with median = 0.22 dex) due to the increase of sample size in each bin (Fig. 2.6).

The above analyses are based on samples including both star-forming and quiescent galaxies, with star-forming galaxies being the major population ($\approx 80\%$).

¹⁵We do not analyze the high- z range independently, because this would lead to only three available bins having > 100 sources (see Sec. 2.3.1) and well-constrained L_X (positive 1σ lower limit); such a small number of bins is not suitable for PCOR analyses.

0.5 ≤ z < 1.3			
Relation	Pearson	Spearman	Kendall
BHAR-SFR	10 ⁻⁶ (4.8σ)	0.01 (2.6σ)	0.34 (0.9σ)
BHAR-M _*	10 ⁻¹⁰⁵ (22σ)	10 ⁻¹² (7.1σ)	0.01 (2.6σ)
0.5 ≤ z < 2.0			
Relation	Pearson	Spearman	Kendall
BHAR-SFR	0.30 (1.0σ)	0.23 (1.2σ)	0.68 (0.4σ)
BHAR-M _*	10 ⁻¹⁴ (7.5σ)	10 ⁻⁴ (3.5σ)	0.06 (1.9σ)

Table 2.2: p -values (Significances) of Partial Correlation Analyses

To test if our main conclusion ($\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ mainly relates to M_*) applies for star-forming galaxies alone, we repeat the above analyses with the sample of galaxies near the star-forming main sequence in Sec. 2.6.1. Our analyses there show $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ still correlates with M_* more strongly than SFR for star-forming galaxies.

2.3.4 BHAR/SFR Ratio as a Function of M_*

The ratio BHAR/SFR represents the relative growth between SMBHs and their host galaxies, and thus it has important implications for SMBH-galaxy coevolution. To study its dependence on M_* , we bin our sources based on M_* and derive $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle / \langle \text{SFR} \rangle$ for each bin. The results are displayed in Fig. 2.8. For both redshift ranges, massive galaxies with $M_* \gtrsim 10^{10} M_\odot$ generally have higher $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle / \langle \text{SFR} \rangle$. This is understandable considering that $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle / M_*$ is roughly a constant (Sec. 2.3.2), while sSFR generally drops for massive galaxies (Fig. 2.5 right; also see, e.g., [64, 117]).

However, the $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle / \langle \text{SFR} \rangle$ dependence on M_* is not observed by [11]. This difference is likely because their sample consists of only massive galaxies in a narrow range of M_* ($10^{10} \lesssim M_* \lesssim 10^{11} M_\odot$) and their uncertainties are relatively large. A recent study by [113], based on galaxies with $10^{10} \lesssim M_* \lesssim 10^{11.5} M_\odot$, found that a positive correlation still exists between $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle / \langle \text{SFR} \rangle$ and M_* , due to their small error bars on $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle / \langle \text{SFR} \rangle$. Our $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle / \langle \text{SFR} \rangle$ values for galaxies having similar M_* are slightly lower than those measured in the two studies, likely due to different sample selections and/or the missed accretion power from broad-line AGNs in our analyses (Secs. 2.2.1 and 2.3.5.1). Indeed, if we assume the luminous broad-line AGNs have $10^{10} \leq M_* < 10^{11} M_\odot$ and include them in our sample, our $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle / \langle \text{SFR} \rangle$ values would be consistent with those in previous studies (see

Sec. 2.3.5.1 for details). The M_* -dependent ratio of $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle / \langle \text{SFR} \rangle$ provides a possible explanation for the fact that our best-fit intercept of the $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ -SFR relation is lower than that expected from the H14 model (see Sec. 2.3.1). The data used by H14 to estimate the $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ -SFR relation are mainly for massive galaxies. Since massive galaxies have higher $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle / \langle \text{SFR} \rangle$ values, the resulting intercept of the $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ -SFR relation should be higher. For example, if we only use the high- M_* subsamples (blue points in Fig. 2.4) to derive the $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ -SFR relation with unity slope, we would obtain a higher intercept.

The $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle / \langle \text{SFR} \rangle$ ratio in the high- z range is generally lower than that in the low- z range (Fig. 2.8). This is consistent with global AGN activity and star formation studies. The emissivity of AGNs in our luminosity regime ($L_X \lesssim 10^{44} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$; see Fig. 2.1) slightly increases from $z \approx 2$ to $z \approx 1$ [13]; meanwhile, the emissivity of star formation drops (e.g., [118] and B13; see also Fig. 2.5 right). Physically, the redshift evolution might reflect that, at lower redshift, gas in galaxies is more concentrated in the vicinity of SMBHs.

2.3.5 Reliability Checks

2.3.5.1 Missed Accretion Power

Luminous X-ray emission is almost a universal tracer of SMBH accretion [107, 119]. Since this work is based on the deepest X-ray survey (the 7 Ms CDF-S) and includes individually undetected sources via stacking analyses (Sec. 2.2.3), we are unlikely to miss a large fraction of black-hole accretion power due to survey sensitivity [80]. Also, our stacked mean X-ray luminosities are similar to the predicted X-ray emission from XRBs (see Secs. 2.3.1 and 2.3.2), indicating that most of cosmic accretion power in our redshift range ($0.5 \leq z < 2.0$) is directly detected in the 7 Ms CDF-S. Due to the small size of GOODS-S (170 arcmin²), our sample will miss AGNs at the bright end of the XLF ($L_X \gtrsim 10^{44} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$; see Fig. 2.1). For the GOODS-S field (170 arcmin²), the fraction of missed accretion power is $\approx 37\%$ for $0.5 \leq z < 2.0$, estimated based on the XLF model of [9]. However, those luminous sources are likely to reside in massive systems ($M_* \gtrsim 10^{10} M_\odot$; e.g., [120–122]), and thus the bright-end correction is not likely to boost $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ for low- M_* galaxies and affect our main conclusions (i.e., massive galaxies have higher $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ and $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle / \langle \text{SFR} \rangle$ than less-massive ones). Moreover, a recent study of luminous

quasars also suggests their BHAR might be primarily related to M_* rather than SFR [123].

A large population of CTK AGNs might exist but show almost no X-ray signal, even in the unprecedentedly deep 7 Ms CDF-S (e.g., see Sec. 3.3 of [80]; [124]). Their accretion power would be largely missed in our analyses. We have stacked hard-band (observed-frame 2–7 keV) X-ray images and compared the results with the stacking of the soft band (observed-frame 0.5–2 keV). We do not find evidence of CTK populations. Nevertheless, it is possible to find signatures of CTK AGNs with more refined analyses (e.g., stacking of very hard narrower bands), and we will perform such analyses in a dedicated paper (B. Luo et al., in preparation). The prevalence of CTK AGNs is predicted by population-synthesis models of the cosmic X-ray background, although these models have significant uncertainties in the regime of very high N_{H} [13, 125]. The predicted total X-ray emission from CTK AGNs is usually less than that from other AGNs (e.g., [125, 126]; also see [127] for relevant spectral fitting), consistent with the very-hard X-ray ($\gtrsim 10$ keV) observations of the local universe [128, 129]. Even if these CTK AGNs predominantly reside in low- M_* systems, the total L_{X} from these galaxies will be at most the same as that from high- M_* galaxies; the average L_{X} in low- M_* galaxies should be still much lower than for massive galaxies, as the former has much larger number density. Their inclusion is unlikely to make qualitative changes to our main conclusion that $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ is a strong function of M_* . Nevertheless, the possible existence of the CTK AGN population could increase/decrease the dependence on other galaxy properties at given M_* . Some observations suggest that CTK AGNs are more prevalent in galaxies with high SFRs and/or that are experiencing major mergers [130, 131], while the dependence on redshift tends not to be strong [127].

Nineteen broad-line AGNs have been deliberately excluded from our sample (see Sec. 2.2.1). The majority of them (14/19) are X-ray luminous with $10^{43} < L_{\text{X}} \lesssim 10^{44}$ erg s $^{-1}$ (see Fig. 2.1 bottom). The rarity of broad-line AGNs with $L_{\text{X}} < 10^{43}$ erg s $^{-1}$ is consistent with, e.g., [132]. The 14 luminous broad-line AGNs make up of 25% of the total AGN population with $L_{\text{X}} > 10^{43}$ erg s $^{-1}$. This fraction agrees with Fig. 7 of [132], which shows the fraction of broad-line AGNs is ≈ 20 –40% for $10^{43} \lesssim L_{\text{X}} \lesssim 10^{44}$ erg s $^{-1}$. Therefore, we are not missing a significant fraction of broad-line AGNs due to, e.g., low-S/N spectra. Those luminous broad-line AGNs are likely to reside in massive galaxies [120, 122]. Indeed, $\approx 90\%$ of

our non-broad-line AGNs in the same luminosity regime are hosted by galaxies with $M_* > 10^{10} M_\odot$, and these should be physically similar systems as broad-line AGNs following the standard unified AGN model. Hence, including the broad-line AGNs would boost $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ for massive galaxies, and thus would make our main conclusions even stronger. This might also explain why our $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle / \langle \text{SFR} \rangle$ ratio for massive galaxies is lower than the values from previous studies (see Secs. 2.3.1 and 2.3.4). Quantitatively, if we include those 14 luminous broad-line AGNs assuming they reside in galaxies with $10^{10} \leq M_* < 10^{11} M_\odot$, the $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle / \langle \text{SFR} \rangle$ values for this M_* bin would be $10^{-3.3}$ and $10^{-3.7}$, respectively, in the low- z and high- z ranges. These values are consistent with previous studies (see Fig. 2.8). Considering the small population and relatively low luminosities ($L_X < 10^{43} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$) of the remaining 5 broad-line AGNs, excluding them is not likely to affect our results significantly.

2.3.5.2 Sample M_* and SFR Completeness

In the high- z range, our sample is not complete at $M_* \sim 10^7 M_\odot$ (Fig. 2.1 top), and this is the main reason why this study focuses on galaxies with $M_* \gtrsim 10^8 M_\odot$. To check quantitatively if our sample is complete down to $M_* \sim 10^8 M_\odot$ in the high- z range, we calculate the comoving number density for the bin with lowest M_* and compare it with the model of B13. There are 2550 sources in the bin (see Fig. 2.5); the comoving volume covered by the GOODS-S field (170 arcmin²; see [69]) is $3.8 \times 10^5 \text{ Mpc}^3$. Thus, the comoving number density for our galaxies having $10^8 \leq M_* < 10^{8.5} M_\odot$ is $1.3 \times 10^{-2} \text{ Mpc}^{-3} \text{ dex}^{-1}$. This value is roughly consistent with Fig. 3 of B13, indicating our sample is basically complete above $M_* \sim 10^8 M_\odot$.

A color-dependent completeness issue might exist in our flux-limited sample [58]. This is because for a given M_* , blue galaxies generally have higher optical-to-near-IR luminosities than red galaxies due to their relatively young stellar populations. Therefore, flux-limited optical/IR surveys like CANDELS might miss the red population in the low- M_* regimes. However, our sample is not likely to have this issue, since our SFR- M_* relation agrees well with the B13 model at the low- M_* end (see the right panels of Fig. 2.5). If our sample were biased to blue (high-SFR) galaxies at the low- M_* end, the measured SFR would be significantly above the model value.

The fact that our sample generally does not have color-dependent completeness is not surprising. At the low M_* ($\sim 10^8 M_\odot$) regime that we probe, the spread in rest-frame colors is relatively small, i.e., most low- M_* (thus low-luminosity) galaxies reside in the “blue cloud” rather than the “red sequence” in color-magnitude diagrams [117, 133, 134]. This is broadly consistent with the right panels of Fig. 2.5, assuming star-forming activity is generally traced by colors. The SFR dispersion is only $\lesssim 0.3$ dex in the bins whose $M_* \lesssim 10^{10} M_\odot$, i.e., most galaxies are located around the star-forming main sequence. In the high- M_* regime where the red sequence exists, our sample is also likely to be complete. This is because the comoving number density is $8.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ Mpc}^{-3} \text{ dex}^{-1}$ for the $10^{10.5} \leq M_* < 10^{11} M_\odot$ bin in the high- z range; this value is consistent with the stellar-mass function derived in a dedicated study ($9.3_{-1.7}^{+1.9} \times 10^{-4} \text{ Mpc}^{-3} \text{ dex}^{-1}$; see Tab. 1 of [109]), which includes both star-forming and quiescent galaxies.

On the other hand, our lowest-SFR regime (SFR $\sim 0.1 M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$) corresponds to $M_* \sim 10^8 M_\odot$ on the star-forming main sequence (see the right panels of Figs. 2.4 and 2.5). Since our sample is basically complete above $M_* \sim 10^8 M_\odot$, it should also be roughly complete above SFR $\sim 0.1 M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$. Moreover, our conclusions do not critically depend on the galaxies with SFR $\sim 0.1 M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$ and $M_* \sim 10^8 M_\odot$. Thus, even if there are minor completeness issues in our lowest-SFR and/or lowest- M_* bins, our results should not be affected materially.

2.4 Discussion

2.4.1 SMBH-Galaxy Coevolution

The linear relation between $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ and SFR was previously derived for observations of high-SFR galaxies (SFR $\gtrsim 10 M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$, e.g., [135]; C13). For the first time, our results show that this linear relation remains applicable to galaxies with SFRs down to $\sim 0.1 M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$ in the redshift range of $0.5 \leq z < 2.0$ (Sec. 2.3.1). The relation demonstrates that SMBH and galaxy growth broadly track each other over cosmic time. This is consistent with the observational fact that the evolutions of cosmic BHAR and SFR have broadly similar shapes. The normalization of cosmic SFR relative to cosmic BHAR is ~ 3.7 dex (see, e.g., [4, 9, 136]), similar to our best-fit intercept of the $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ -SFR relation.

The linear $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ -SFR relation suggests a simple scenario of coevolution. H14 assumed that, for any individual galaxy, the ratio between the amount of gas accreted by its SMBH and that used to form stars is a universal constant (when averaged over ~ 100 Myr). Under this assumption, the $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ for different samples of similar SFR should be similar. However, this assumption appears in contradiction with our observational results. For a given SFR level, the sources with larger M_* have significantly higher $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ (Sec. 2.3.3). In addition, $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ is also related to M_* linearly (Sec. 2.3.2), and $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ is correlated with M_* more strongly than SFR as indicated by our PCOR analyses in Sec. 2.3.3. Therefore, our results suggest that $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ might be intrinsically linked to M_* , and this $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ - M_* relation and the star-forming main sequence together might largely cause the observed $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ -SFR relation as a secondary effect.

In the analyses of Sec. 2.3.3, we find when controlling for M_* that the dependence of $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ on SFR is relatively weak. We have furthermore checked the $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ -sSFR relation for the whole sample, and do not find any significant trend.

2.4.2 The Physical Link between BHAR and M_*

It has been well established that X-ray-selected AGNs above a given L_X threshold are preferentially found in massive galaxies [58, 80]. This finding is consistent with our results that $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ depends strongly on M_* , even for SFR-controlled samples (Sec. 2.3.2 and 2.3.3). In fact, M_* , rather than SFR, appears to be the primary factor related to $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$.

Massive galaxies with $M_* \gtrsim 10^{10} M_\odot$ have lower sSFR (Sec. 2.3.4) than less-massive galaxies. If we assume SFR reflects the amount of cold gas available, the decrease of sSFR for massive galaxies indicates the mass fraction of cold gas drops toward high M_* [137]. The cold gas needed for star formation is also likely responsible for fueling black-hole accretion [138, 139], while hot-gas accretion could power low-luminosity AGNs that generally have little contribution to total black-hole growth (see, e.g., [140–142]). The M_* -dependent $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle / \langle \text{SFR} \rangle$ indicates the massive population is generally more efficient in feeding cold gas to their SMBHs (Fig. 2.8). This could be further broadly interpreted in two possible respects. First, the black-hole fueling efficiency of each galaxy might depend on M_* due to several physically plausible causes:

1. The potential wells in galactic centers are deeper for massive galaxies, making it easier for gas particles to fall into the galaxy center and fuel the SMBH. More specifically, supernova feedback might prevent gas from falling into the galaxy center when the potential well is not sufficiently deep [143, 144].
2. Compared to low- M_* systems, high- M_* ones are more likely to have bars and major mergers [145, 146] that could induce gas inflow effectively [138].
3. Massive galaxies often have more massive SMBHs than low- M_* galaxies [4]. Those SMBHs, having a stronger gravitational field, are more capable of accreting gas from their vicinity. In fact, some studies suggest long-term BHAR is proportional to M_{BH} , resulting from a universal Eddington-ratio distribution [59, 147].

Second, the SMBH occupation fraction might drop toward low M_* ($M_* \lesssim 10^{10} M_\odot$), and some low- M_* galaxies might only host intermediate-mass black holes (IMBHs) with $M_{\text{BH}} \lesssim 10^4 M_\odot$ [52, 54, 55]. Due to the Eddington limit, the X-ray emission from accretion onto IMBHs is likely to be much weaker than that from SMBHs. The $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ could thus be diminished for galaxies with lower M_* .

2.4.3 Implications for the $M_{\text{BH}}-M_*$ Relation in the Local Universe

Our results have implications for the $M_{\text{BH}}-M_*$ relation in the local universe, and we illustrate this with some basic arguments below. The M_{BH}/M_* ratio for a galaxy at $z = 0$ can be estimated as

$$\frac{M_{\text{BH}}(t_0)}{M_*(t_0)} \approx \frac{M_{\text{BH}}(t_2) + \int_{t_2}^{t_0} \text{BHAR}(t) dt}{M_*(t_2) + \int_{t_2}^{t_0} \text{SFR}(t) dt}, \quad (2.9)$$

where t is cosmic time and the subscripts of t indicate redshift. Assuming that the mass of SMBH seeds is small compared to that accreted over cosmic history [52] and most black-hole growth happens at $z \lesssim 2$,¹⁶ we have $M_{\text{BH}}(t_2) + \int_{t_2}^{t_0} \text{BHAR}(t) dt \approx$

¹⁶This is broadly supported by the Sołtan argument, such that $\approx 70\% - 80\%$ of total black-hole accretion (including the contribution from luminous quasars) happens at $z \lesssim 2$ [13, 80]. High-redshift luminous quasars mostly form SMBHs above $z \sim 2$ [148, 149], but they are rare objects and their discussion is beyond the scope of this study.

$\int_{t_2}^{t_0} \text{BHAR}(t)dt$, and Eq. 2.9 can be simplified as

$$\frac{M_{\text{BH}}(t_0)}{M_*(t_0)} \approx \frac{\int_{t_2}^{t_0} \text{BHAR}(t)dt}{M_*(t_2) + \int_{t_2}^{t_0} \text{SFR}(t)dt}. \quad (2.10)$$

For local giant ellipticals ($M_* \gtrsim 10^{11} M_\odot$), most of their stars are likely to have been formed at $z \gtrsim 2$ [150, 151]. Thus, M_* is roughly the same over $z \approx 0 - 2$, i.e., $M_* \equiv M_*(t_0) \approx M_*(t_2)$, and Eq. 2.10 is approximately¹⁷

$$\frac{M_{\text{BH}}(t_0)}{M_*} \approx \frac{\int_{t_2}^{t_0} \text{BHAR}(t)dt}{M_*} \quad (\text{elliptical}). \quad (2.11)$$

If we assume the BHAR- M_* linear relation extends to $M_* \gtrsim 10^{11} M_\odot$ and has not evolved significantly for $z \lesssim 2$ (Eq. 2.6 and Fig. 2.5), Eq. 2.11 leads to

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{M_{\text{BH}}(t_0)}{M_*} &\approx \frac{(t_2 - t_0)\text{BHAR}}{M_*} \quad (\text{elliptical}) \\ &\approx 10 \text{ Gyr} \times 10^{-13} \text{ yr}^{-1} \\ &\approx 10^{-3}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.12)$$

Therefore, the M_{BH}/M_* ratio for giant ellipticals should be approximately a constant (1/1000), similar to the value ($\approx 1/700$) observed by [8]. Considering that the existence of Compton-thick and broad-line AGNs could boost our observed $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ (see Sec. 2.3.5.1), the M_{BH}/M_* ratio might be several times larger and more consistent with the value ($\approx 1/300$) from ([4]; but also see [152]).

The above argument obviously depends on the assumption that giant ellipticals grow their M_{BH} mostly at $z \lesssim 2$. This assumption, although under debate, is supported by observations of submillimeter galaxies (SMGs; see, e.g., Sec. 8.6.7 of [4]). SMGs are likely the high-redshift ($z \sim 2$) progenitors of massive ellipticals [153, 154], and the growth of their SMBHs tends to lag that of the host galaxies [155, 156]. Nevertheless, it is also possible to reproduce the local M_{BH}/M_* ratio if both the growth of SMBHs and host galaxies take place at $z \gtrsim 2$ and have strong interplay. Simulations show that AGN feedback can keep a tight $M_{\text{BH}}-M_*$ relation when both SMBHs and host galaxies grow at high redshift [157].

¹⁷For galaxy mergers, Eq. 2.11 is still correct, providing mergers increase M_{BH} and M_* proportionally.

For local star-forming galaxies, most of their M_* is likely to be assembled at $z \lesssim 2$ (e.g., B13). Thus, we have $M_*(t_2) + \int_{t_2}^{t_0} \text{SFR}(t) dt \approx \int_{t_2}^{t_0} \text{SFR}(t) dt$, and Eq. 2.10 becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{M_{\text{BH}}(t_0)}{M_*(t_0)} &\approx \frac{\int_{t_2}^{t_0} \text{BHAR}(t) dt}{\int_{t_2}^{t_0} \text{SFR}(t) dt} \quad (\text{star-forming}) \\ &\sim \frac{\text{BHAR}}{\text{SFR}} \\ &\sim 10^{-5} - 10^{-3.5}, \end{aligned} \tag{2.13}$$

where we adopt the BHAR/SFR range from Figs. 2.8 and 2.11. Our results in Sec. 2.3.4 show that long-term average BHAR/SFR positively depends on M_* , and thus $M_{\text{BH}}(t_0)/M_*(t_0)$ is higher for massive galaxies than dwarf galaxies. This prediction is supported by some observations. [54] and [55] suggest that dwarf galaxies have a lower black-hole occupation fraction than massive galaxies, implying a generally lower M_{BH}/M_* for dwarfs. In addition, for some nearby galaxies (e.g., M 33, NGC 205, and NGC 404), studies of nuclear kinematics place tight upper limits on M_{BH} , indicating the absence of SMBHs [158–160].

Eqs. 2.12 and 2.13 suggest that ellipticals generally have higher M_{BH}/M_* ratios than star-forming galaxies, consistent with some recent studies [32, 56]. From the viewpoint of this study, it is understandable why the observed local M_{BH}/M_* values ($\sim 1/500$; e.g., [4, 8]) are much higher than cosmic BHAR/SFR ($\sim 1/5000$; e.g., [9, 136]). This is because local M_{BH}/M_* measurements are mainly based on observations of passive ellipticals (Eq. 2.12), and cosmic BHAR/SFR is generally linked to M_{BH}/M_* of star-forming galaxies (Eq. 2.13).

From Eq. 2.12, for massive ellipticals, the M_{BH}/M_* is expected to be lower in the early universe ($z \gtrsim 1$); for star-forming galaxies, it should depend on M_* and have relatively weak cosmic evolution according to Eq. 2.13. As discussed above, observations of SMGs support this scenario. Some studies of high-redshift quasars find higher M_{BH}/M_* ratios than the local values, not expected in our scheme (e.g., [161, 162]; but also see, e.g., [72, 163]). However, the M_{BH}/M_* measured from quasars might be biased and not representative for the majority of galaxies [164]. Also, large uncertainties often exist in the measurements of both M_{BH} and M_* for these quasars [60, 165].

2.5 Summary and Future Prospects

We have studied the dependence of SMBH growth on the SFR and M_* of host galaxies at $0.5 \leq z < 2.0$. Specifically, we compare $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ for samples with different SFR and/or M_* . Due to the deep multiwavelength data in the CDF-S, we are able to probe black-hole accretion in hosts down to $\text{SFR} \sim 0.1 M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$ and $M_* \sim 10^8 M_\odot$ with reasonable completeness. Our main results are summarized below:

1. $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ correlates with SFR linearly (Sec. 2.3.1). However, for SFR-controlled samples, galaxies with higher M_* have higher $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ (Sec. 2.3.3). Thus, SFR does not appear to be uniquely related to $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$. The scenario in which long-term average BHAR is only determined by host-galaxy SFR is over simplified (Sec. 2.4.1).
2. $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ is also proportional to M_* (Sec. 2.3.2). In fact, the correlation between $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ and M_* is stronger than that between $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ and SFR, suggesting M_* as the primary host-galaxy property related to SMBH growth. This result also holds for the star-forming population alone (Sec. 2.6.1). The observed $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ -SFR correlation might be largely a secondary effect due to the existence of the star-formation main sequence (Sec. 2.4.1).
3. Massive galaxies ($M_* \gtrsim 10^{10} M_\odot$) have higher $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle / \langle \text{SFR} \rangle$ ratios than their less-massive counterparts (Sec. 2.3.4), suggesting that they have higher black-hole fueling efficiency and/or SMBH occupation fraction (Sec. 2.4.2).
4. Our results can naturally explain the observed $M_{\text{BH}}-M_*$ relation for local giant ellipticals, and indicate that they have higher M_{BH}/M_* than their progenitors in the earlier universe (Sec. 2.4.3). Also, our results predict that M_{BH}/M_* for giant ellipticals is higher than that for star-forming galaxies in the nearby universe. Among local star-forming galaxies, the M_{BH}/M_* values for massive galaxies are likely to be higher than those for dwarfs.

In the future, this study could be extended to galaxies with larger M_* (SFR) by compiling a large number of luminous galaxies (Sec. 2.3.1). To perform this investigation, analyses based on multiwavelength surveys of wider fields, e.g., COSMOS, XMM-LSS, and Stripe 82, are needed. In addition, it is possible to

extend this study to higher redshift using the CDF-S field, but this approach will require SED fitting that can eliminate potential high-redshift biases for SFR and M_* measurements (Sec. 2.2.2). It would also be worthwhile to derive quantitative black-hole fueling efficiency and/or SMBH occupation-fraction estimates as a function of M_* , based on the M_* -dependent $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle / \langle \text{SFR} \rangle$ (Sec. 2.3.4). Future work could study the BHAR for giant ellipticals by including morphological information (Sec. 2.4.3) and the connection between BHAR and host-galaxy gas content by using ALMA observations.

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Disclaimer

The findings and conclusions do not necessarily reflect the view of the funding agencies.

2.6 Supplementary Materials

2.6.1 Analyses for Star-Forming Galaxies

Here we perform the same analyses as in Sec. 2.3 but for star-forming galaxies only, in order to check if our conclusions also apply for this population alone. We define star-forming galaxies as sources having sSFR within 5 times (i.e., 0.7 dex) of the median sSFR of the whole sample in the corresponding redshift range.¹⁸ The median sSFRs for the low- z and high- z samples are $10^{-8.94}$ and $10^{-8.72}$ yr^{-1} , respectively. The numbers of star-forming galaxies in the low and high redshift ranges are 8149 and 6604, respectively (see Tab. 2.3).

Similar to Sec. 2.3, we bin sources based on SFR (M_*), and split each sample based on M_* (SFR). For straightforward comparison with our results for all galaxies, we allow bins with numbers of sources less than 100 in our analyses. Figs. 2.9 and 2.10 show the results. Similar to the results in Sec. 2.3.1 and 2.3.2, sources with higher SFR (M_*) generally have higher $\langle\text{BHAR}\rangle$. However, due to the apparent non-linearity, the linear models in Sec. 2.3.1 and 2.3.2 result in unacceptable fitting quality, and thus we do not show the fitting results here. From Fig. 2.9 (Fig. 2.10), the non-linearity mainly arises from the apparent steep rise of $\langle\text{BHAR}\rangle$ above the threshold of $\text{SFR} \sim 10^{0.5} M_\odot \text{yr}^{-1}$ ($M_* \sim 10^{10} M_\odot \text{yr}^{-1}$). The steep change might be caused by statistical fluctuations atop a gradual rise, but it could also indicate an intrinsic threshold of SFR (M_*) above which AGN X-ray emission becomes dominant over that of XRBs for star-forming galaxies. Larger samples are needed to differentiate the two possibilities. The SFR- M_* relation for star-forming galaxies in Fig. 2.10 (right) is more similar to that of B13 compared to that in Fig. 2.5 at the high- M_* end (see Sec. 2.3.2).

From Fig. 2.9, the high- M_* subsamples generally have higher $\langle\text{BHAR}\rangle$ than the corresponding low- M_* subsamples. From Fig. 2.10, the two subsamples with different SFRs generally have similar $\langle\text{BHAR}\rangle$. These results qualitatively agree with our major conclusion that $\langle\text{BHAR}\rangle$ correlates with M_* more strongly than SFR

¹⁸Different studies often adopt different empirical definitions of star-forming galaxies. Here we adopt a similar definition as [111], i.e., the galaxies with sSFR around a typical value. We adopt a wider sSFR range than [111] when defining the main sequence, mostly because our SED-based SFR estimations have larger uncertainties than the FIR-based SFR estimations in [111] (see our Sec. 2.2.2).

Sample (1)	Low- z (2)	High- z (3)	Total (4)	Fig(s). (5)
All	8149	6604	14753	N/A
$0.1 \leq \text{SFR} < 100 M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$	5635	6185	11820	2.9
$10^8 \leq M_* < 10^{11} M_{\odot}$	5223	5800	11023	2.10 and 2.11

Table 2.3: Numbers of Sources in Different Samples of Star-Forming Galaxies. Same format as Tab. 2.1 but only for galaxies near the star-forming main sequence.

(see Sec. 2.3.3). In Fig. 2.10, the low-SFR subsamples of massive galaxies ($M_* \gtrsim 10^{10} M_{\odot}$) even appear to have higher $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ than their high-SFR counterparts. However, the difference is not statistically significant, and larger samples are needed to clarify this point. From PCOR analyses (see Sec. 2.3.3), the parametric method (Pearson) results in $\approx 2 - 3\sigma$ significances of the $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ - M_* relation in the two redshift ranges in Tab. 2.2, while the method shows the $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ -SFR relation is insignificant in both redshift ranges. However, this parametric method models correlations linearly, which is likely not appropriate considering the apparent non-linearity in Figs. 2.9 and 2.10. The non-parametric methods (Spearman and Kendall) do not assume linearity but have less statistical power (see Sec. 2.3.3). These methods cannot reveal high significances for either the $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ -SFR or $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ - M_* relations. The reasons are likely to be the reduced sample size (especially the reduced number of AGNs; see Fig. 2.2) and the reduced coverage of the SFR- M_* plane.

Fig. 2.11 shows the ratio between $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ and $\langle \text{SFR} \rangle$ for the star-forming galaxies. As in Fig. 2.8 for all galaxies, the ratio is higher for massive galaxies with $M_* \gtrsim 10^{10} M_{\odot}$. As expected from Fig. 2.10, there is a sudden “jump” of $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle / \langle \text{SFR} \rangle$ at $M_* \sim 10^{10} M_{\odot}$, probably indicating a physical M_* threshold above which AGN activity starts to become very strong. Compared to the corresponding bins in Fig. 2.8, $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle / \langle \text{SFR} \rangle$ values are slightly lower in general, although the trend is weak and within the error bars. This is expected, as the quiescent population has lower $\langle \text{SFR} \rangle$ but similar $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ (our main conclusion) compared to the star-forming population at given M_* .

Figure 2.6: Color-coded $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ as a function of SFR and M_* at $0.5 \leq z < 1.3$ (upper panel) and $0.5 \leq z < 2.0$ (lower panel). The text in the center of each square indicates the number of X-ray detected sources and all sources. The black cross indicates median values of SFR and M_* for sources in each bin, which are adopted in the analyses in Sec. 2.3.3. In both panels, the upper-left squares with white color include too few sources (fewer than 100; see Sec. 2.3.1), and their $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ values are not calculated. In the lower panel, the $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ of the bottom-left square has a negative 1σ lower limit; its value is not shown. The results for the two redshift bins are similar. Both M_* and SFR have positive correlations with $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$.

Figure 2.7: Top: the $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ residuals of the $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ - M_* fit as a function of SFR. The black solid line indicates the best fit for the residuals as a function of SFR. The shaded region indicates 3σ uncertainties derived from Markov chain Monte Carlo sampling utilizing “EMCEE” [116]. The residual-SFR relation is flat. Bottom: the $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ residual of the $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ -SFR fit as a function of M_* . The residual- M_* relation is steep.

Figure 2.8: The ratio of $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ to $\langle \text{SFR} \rangle$ as a function of M_* . The black points and red squares indicate sources in the low- z and high- z ranges, respectively. Their horizontal positions indicate median M_* in the bin, and the horizontal error bars (only shown for the low- z bin) indicate the bin width. The blue open symbols indicate results from [11]; the circles and squares indicate their $z \sim 1$ and $z \sim 2$ samples, respectively. The scale of $\langle L_X \rangle / \langle L_{\text{IR}} \rangle$ is shown on the right side, where we convert SFR to L_{IR} with a constant factor (C13). The gray solid and dash-dotted lines indicate the $\langle L_{\text{X,XRB}} \rangle / \langle L_{\text{IR}} \rangle$ ratios in the low- z and high- z ranges, respectively. These values are used as upper limits for $\langle L_X \rangle / \langle L_{\text{IR}} \rangle$ for AGNs, when 1σ lower limits of $\langle L_X \rangle$ for AGNs are negative. The solid horizontal line indicates the intercept of our best-fit $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle$ -SFR linear relation in Fig. 2.4; the dashed horizontal line indicates the H14 model. The $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle / \langle \text{SFR} \rangle$ ratio is strongly dependent on M_* . More massive galaxies generally have higher $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle / \langle \text{SFR} \rangle$, indicating that they are more efficient in growing their SMBHs. For high-mass galaxies ($M_* \gtrsim 10^{10} M_\odot$), our $\langle \text{BHAR} \rangle / \langle \text{SFR} \rangle$ values are systematically lower than those in [11]. This is likely caused by the exclusion of broad-line AGNs in our sample (see Secs. 2.2.1 and 2.3.5.1).

Figure 2.9: Same format as Fig. 2.4 but for star-forming galaxies. The black solid line indicates the fitting of all galaxies as in Fig. 2.4, rather than the fitting of star-forming galaxies.

Figure 2.10: Same format as Fig. 2.5 but for star-forming galaxies. The black solid line indicates the fitting of all galaxies as in Fig. 2.5, rather than the fitting of star-forming galaxies.

Figure 2.11: Same format as Fig. 2.8 but for star-forming galaxies. The solid horizontal line indicates the best-fit intercept in Fig. 2.4.

Chapter 3 | Does Black-Hole Growth Depend on the Cosmic Environment?

3.1 Introduction

The environments of galaxies play a crucial role in their evolution [167–169]. In the local universe, denser regions are preferentially populated by early-type quiescent galaxies, while less-dense regions are more likely to host late-type star-forming galaxies [170–172]. This environmental dependence of star-forming/quiescent types exists at $z \lesssim 1$, although it is less clear at higher redshifts [173–177].

Several possible environment-related mechanisms could affect galaxy evolution. Cold gas, the fuel of star formation, could flow into galaxies through cosmic filaments [178, 179]; frequent tidal interactions in denser regions could effectively deplete cold gas [180, 181]; the strong ram pressure in clusters can strip cold gas from galaxies and suppress subsequent star formation [182–184]; and mergers, which can fundamentally change galaxy properties, happen more frequently in high-density regions [185, 186]. These physical processes might also affect active galactic nucleus (AGN) activity, as the growth of supermassive black holes (SMBHs) also relies on the supply of cold gas [138, 139, 187].

Optical observations of low-redshift ($z \lesssim 1$) quasars disagree on whether they tend to reside in high-density or low-density regions compared to normal galaxies [188–190]. This disagreement might be caused if these works did not carefully

control for host-galaxy properties. [191] found quasars do not show a significant dependence on environment compared to normal galaxies with matched redshift and host-galaxy luminosities. At high redshift ($z \gtrsim 3$), optical observations are limited to rare luminous quasars, and deep spectroscopic observations are often needed to measure their environment. Therefore, these studies are often limited to small sample sizes and statistically significant conclusions cannot be obtained [192–194].

Optical selection is often biased to luminous broad-line (BL) quasars, especially at high redshift. These BL quasars are rare and not well representative of the whole AGN population. X-ray emission can trace AGN activity down to a modest level and is widely used to investigate SMBH growth over the majority of cosmic history [80, 195]. Studies of AGN activity vs. environment found that, at low redshift ($z \lesssim 1$), the X-ray AGN fraction in rare rich clusters is generally lower than that in the field (e.g. [196, 197]; but also see, e.g. [198]). At higher redshifts, relevant studies are often constrained to rare protoclusters with limited AGN/galaxy sample sizes. Their results suggest that AGN activity tends to be enhanced in these protoclusters (e.g. [199–204]; but also see [205]).

However, this apparent environmental dependence might only be a secondary effect, and SMBH growth might be more fundamentally related to host-galaxy properties which are themselves related to environment. For example, X-ray AGN activity is strongly related to host-galaxy stellar mass (M_\star) rather than color (e.g. [58]) or star-formation rate (SFR; e.g. [206]), and thus M_\star must be carefully controlled when assessing AGN dependence on other host-galaxy properties. On the other hand, massive galaxies tend to reside in high-density regions [207, 208]. Therefore, to avoid such M_\star -related biases, a large sample of AGNs and galaxies is needed to investigate the accretion-environment relation while controlling for host-galaxy M_\star .

In this paper, we study the dependence of sample-averaged SMBH accretion rate ($\overline{\text{BHAR}}$) on galaxy overdensity and cosmic-web environment while controlling for M_\star . The sample-averaged SMBH accretion is employed to approximate long-term average SMBH accretion for a galaxy sample [25, 26, 206, 209], because AGNs plausibly have strong variability on timescales of $\sim 10^2\text{--}10^7$ yr [23, 24, 49]. Here, we define the overdensity as the galaxy surface number density relative to the median value at a given redshift and cosmic-web environment as a galaxy’s association to the field, a filament, or a cluster. The overdensity and cosmic-web environment are assessed

on physical scales of sub-Mpc and $\approx 1\text{--}10$ Mpc, respectively. Hereafter, we refer to overdensity and cosmic-web environment as “local” and “global” environments, respectively.

Our aim is to probe a wide redshift range of $z = 0.3\text{--}3.0$ with large samples of X-ray AGNs ($\approx 2,000$) and galaxies ($\approx 170,000$). In particular, this range covers $z \approx 1.5\text{--}2.5$, the peak of cosmic AGN and star-formation activity, when various physical processes such as galaxy mergers and AGN feedback likely play an important role in shaping SMBH and galaxy coevolution [12, 80, 168, 210].

Our analyses are based on the Cosmic Evolution Survey (COSMOS; e.g. [211, 212]). COSMOS has been intensively covered by spectroscopic and multiwavelength imaging observations [213, 214]. Over 20,000 sources have secure spectroscopic redshifts (spec- z) while other sources have reliable photometric redshifts (photo- z) derived from high-quality UV-to-IR data (up to 32 bands; e.g. [214]). The UV-to-IR data also make it possible to assess host-galaxy properties such as M_\star and star-forming/quiescent type [215, 216]. Deep *Chandra* X-ray observations (≈ 160 ks exposure), which can be used to measure SMBH growth, are also available from the COSMOS-Legacy survey [217]. The excellent X-ray positions from *Chandra* ($\approx 0.5''$) enables reliable matching between X-ray and optical sources [218].

Thanks to its relatively large area (≈ 2 deg²) and deep panchromatic coverage, COSMOS is one of the major fields for environment studies. State-of-the-art techniques have been applied to COSMOS to derive reliable measurements of the surface-density field up to $z \approx 3$ [176, 219]. The statistical properties of the resulting density field such as mean densities and density ranges agree with the predictions from cosmological simulations [176]. Based on the density field, [220] utilized a new technique to construct a measurement of the cosmic web [221]. This method allows the mapping of sources to clusters, filaments, and the field.

This paper is structured as follows. In §3.2, we describe our data analyses. In §3.3, we present our results. We discuss our results in §3.4 and summarize our study in §3.5.

Throughout this paper, we assume a cosmology with $H_0 = 70$ km s⁻¹ Mpc⁻¹, $\Omega_M = 0.3$, and $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.7$, and a Chabrier initial mass function [68]. Quoted uncertainties are at the 1σ (68%) confidence level, unless otherwise stated. We express M_\star , M_{BH} , and M_{halo} (halo mass) in units of M_\odot and $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ in units of M_\odot yr⁻¹. L_X indicates AGN X-ray luminosity at rest-frame 2–10 keV and is in units

of erg s^{-1} . All lengths/distances are in physical (proper) scale, unless otherwise stated.

3.2 Data Analyses

3.2.1 Galaxy Sample Selection

Our data are based on the COSMOS2015 survey [214]. We only utilize sources within both the COSMOS and UltraVISTA regions, and remove objects in masked regions (e.g. bad pixels in detectors). These sources cover an area of $\approx 1.4 \text{ deg}^2$ (see Fig. 1 and Tab. 7 in [214]). The UltraVISTA region has deep NIR imaging data that are essential in estimating photo- z and M_* (§3.2.2). We restrict our study to the $\approx 170,000$ sources brighter than $K_S = 24$ (the 3σ limiting magnitude of the COSMOS2015 catalog) to avoid large uncertainties of photo- z for faint sources. The basic properties of our sample are listed in Tab. 3.1. Our analyses (§3.3) are performed for the three redshift bins ($z = 0.3\text{--}1.2$, $1.2\text{--}2$, and $2\text{--}3$) listed in Tab. 3.1. These redshift bins cover comoving volumes of $7 \times 10^6 \text{ Mpc}^3$, $1.2 \times 10^7 \text{ Mpc}^3$, and $1.7 \times 10^7 \text{ Mpc}^3$, respectively. Tab. 3.2 shows a portion of our source catalogs, and the full version is available as supplementary material.

We obtain spec- z for $\approx 20,000$ sources in our sample (see Tab. 3.1; [218, 222]; Salvato et al. in prep.).¹ For sources without spec- z , we adopt the photo- z measurements from the COSMOS2015 catalog. These measurements are derived from high-quality UV-to-NIR photometric data including 18 broad bands, 12 medium bands, and 2 narrow bands (see Tab. 1 in [214]). The medium bands can effectively improve the photo- z quality, enabling reliable environment studies in COSMOS [219, 220]. When compared to different spec- z catalogs, the photo- z have $\sigma_{\text{NMAD}} \approx 0.007\text{--}0.06$ and outlier ($|\Delta z|/(1 + z_{\text{spec}}) > 0.15$) fraction $\eta \approx 0.5\%\text{--}10\%$ (see Tab. 5 in [214]), where σ_{NMAD} is defined as $1.48 \times \text{median}(\frac{|\Delta z - \text{median}(\Delta z)|}{1 + z_{\text{spec}}})$ [224]. When compared with the recently released DEIMOS 10k spec- z catalog [223], the COSMOS2015 photo- z have $\sigma_{\text{NMAD}} = 0.015$ and $\eta = 8\%$, further demonstrating the high photo- z quality of the COSMOS2015 catalog. We consider all galaxies (including X-ray detected and undetected) when deriving $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ (see §3.2.4).

¹In the late stages of this work, a new spec- z data set, the DEIMOS 10k catalog, was released [223]. This catalog could increase our spec- z sample by $\approx 10\%$, unlikely to affect our qualitative results.

Redshift (1)	$N_{\text{gal}}/N_{\text{spec}}$ (2)	σ_{NMAD} (3)	η (4)	$\log M_{\star, \text{med}}$ (5)	Frac _Q (6)	N_{slice} (7)	$\log(1 + \delta)$ (8)	$N_{\text{field}}/N_{\text{fila}}/N_{\text{clu}}$ (9)	N_{X} (10)	E_{rest} (keV) (11)	$\log L_{\text{X}}$ (12)
0.3–1.2	94,152/18,099	0.011	2%	9.3	13%	180	(−0.16,0.18)	38,840/ 48,960/ 6,352	889	(0.9,12.5)	(42.6,43.3)
1.2–2.0	48,981/1,322	0.020	3%	9.8	7%	80	(−0.13,0.13)	20,365/ 28,616/ –	701	(1.3,17.7)	(43.3,43.9)
2.0–3.0	22,828/412	0.059	10%	9.9	2%	50	(−0.14,0.13)	14,265/ 8,563/ –	429	(1.7,23.6)	(43.7,44.2)

Table 3.1: Summary of sample properties. (1) Redshift bins. (2) Numbers of galaxies and spec- z sources in our sample ($K_{\text{S}} < 24$). (3) Photo- z uncertainty (compared to spec- z). (4) Photo- z outlier fraction. (5) Median stellar mass. (6) Fraction of quiescent galaxies. (7) Number of z -slices. (8) The overdensity (25%,75%) percentile range. (9) Number sources in the field/filament/cluster environments. We do not assign cluster environment at $z > 1.2$ due to its generally weak signals (see §3.2.3.2). (10) Number of X-ray detected sources. (11) Rest-frame X-ray energy sampled at median redshift. (12) The (25%,75%) percentile range of $\log L_{\text{X}}$ for X-ray detected sources.

RA (1)	DEC (2)	K_S (3)	z (4)	z_{lo} (5)	z_{up} (6)	$\log M_\star$ (7)	Type _{gal} (8)	$\log(1 + \delta)$ (9)	Web (10)	$\log L_X$ (11)
149.411496	2.712315	22.8	0.706	0.655	0.774	9.18	1	-0.343	2	-99.00
149.411504	2.765237	23.5	0.975	0.951	0.990	8.06	1	-0.256	2	-99.00
149.411576	2.336084	21.0	1.783	1.729	1.818	11.22	1	0.292	1	-99.00
149.411578	2.306681	21.3	1.359	1.241	1.433	10.71	0	-0.019	1	-99.00
149.411581	2.411649	21.5	0.389	0.381	0.398	9.28	1	0.149	1	-99.00
149.411603	2.243533	21.9	1.502	1.469	1.543	10.32	1	0.285	1	-99.00
149.411643	2.290855	23.6	1.185	1.171	1.198	9.07	1	0.128	1	-99.00
149.411643	2.592744	23.6	0.880	0.825	0.942	9.24	1	0.017	1	-99.00
149.411659	2.319370	23.6	1.022	0.812	1.148	9.23	1	-0.621	2	-99.00
149.411661	2.410365	22.5	1.063	1.063	1.063	9.11	1	-0.192	1	43.63

Table 3.2: Source catalog. Only a portion of this table is shown here, and the full version is available as online supplementary materials. The table is sorted in ascending order of RA. (1) & (2) Source J2000 coordinates. (3) K_S AB magnitude from the COSMOS2015 catalog [214]. (4), (5), & (6) Redshift and redshift 1σ lower and upper limits (§3.2.1). For spec- z sources, the lower and upper limits are set the same as the redshift value. (7) Stellar mass (§3.2.2). (8) Galaxy type (0: quiescent; 1: star-forming; §3.2.2). (9) Overdensity (§3.2.3.1). (10) Cosmic-web environment (0: cluster; 1: filament; 2: field; §3.2.3.2). We do not assign cluster environment at $z > 1.2$ due to its generally weak signals. (11) X-ray luminosity (rest-frame 2–10 keV; §3.2.4.1). For X-ray undetected sources, the values are set to “-99.00”.

3.2.2 Stellar Mass

To estimate M_* , we perform spectral energy distribution (SED) fitting with CIGALE [225, 226] at z_{spec} or z_{photo} (§3.2.1). The input photometry is from the COSMOS2015 catalog (§3.2.1). We do not adopt the M_* measurements from the COSMOS2015 catalog directly, mainly because the our redshifts are not exactly the same as those in the COSMOS2015 catalog (§3.2.1). We employ nebular and dust emission in CIGALE [225, 227]. We apply the extinction law from [77] with $E(B - V)$ ranging from 0 – 1. Following [209], we use a τ model of the star formation history (SFH) with $\log(\tau/\text{yr})$ ranging from 8 to 10.5. We allow stellar metallicity values of $Z = 0.0001, 0.0004, 0.004, 0.008, 0.02, 0.05$, where Z is the mass fraction of metals. Our M_* measurements have a systematic of 0.002 dex and a scatter of 0.11 dex compared to those in the COSMOS2015 catalog. For the 239 BL AGNs (identified by [218]), we also adopt an additional BL AGN component following the settings in Tab. 1 of [81]. The resulting M_* values are typically ≈ 0.3 dex different from those obtained with only galaxy templates (see § 2.1.3 of [209]). Fig. 3.1 displays M_* vs. redshift for our sample. We also show the M_* completeness limit corresponding to $K_S = 24$ from [214] in Fig. 3.1. The completeness limit is estimated based on an empirical method which does not assume a specific galaxy template. The limiting $\log M_*$ at $z = 1.2, 2, \text{ and } 3$ are 9.3, 10.0, and 10.3, respectively. In §3.3, we perform analyses for M_* above these limits in three redshift bins of $z = 0.3\text{--}1.2, 1.2\text{--}2, \text{ and } 2\text{--}3$, respectively.

We classify a source as a quiescent galaxy if its rest-frame colors satisfy $\text{NUV} - r > 3(r - J) + 1$ and $\text{NUV} - r > 3.1$, otherwise we classify it as a star-forming galaxy [228, 229].² Here, the rest-frame colors are obtained from our SED fitting. This color-based selection helps to avoid misclassifying dust-reddened star-forming galaxies as quiescent galaxies [215, 229]. The fractions of quiescent galaxies in different redshift ranges are listed in Tab. 3.1. This classification is used to estimate X-ray emission from X-ray binaries (XRBs; see §3.2.4.3). Our color-color scheme is not appropriate for galaxies hosting BL AGNs due to the strong AGN UV-to-NIR emission. Following [206], we set the hosts of BL AGNs as star-forming galaxies. Setting them as either star-forming or quiescent galaxies has negligible effects to our results, as BL AGNs are only a small population compared to the entire galaxy

²Here, the NUV specifically refers to the *GALEX* band centered at 2300 Å.

Figure 3.1: M_* , overdensity, and L_X as a function of redshift. The contours encircle 68%, 90%, and 95% of all sources (§3.2.1), respectively. The red points represent X-ray detected sources. In the top panel, the dashed curve indicates the M_* completeness limit from [214]. In the bottom panel, the solid curve represents the limiting L_X .

sample ($\approx 0.1\%$).

3.2.3 Environment

We build the surface-density field and cosmic-web estimates in this section. The technical details are presented in [219, 220], and we briefly describe the procedures in §3.2.3.1 and §3.2.3.2. In §3.6.1, we explain our environment measurements in a straightforward way, especially for readers who are not familiar with environmental studies. As demonstrated in §3.4.1, the physical environment-SFR relation clearly exists in our sample, supporting the robustness of our environment measurements.

Some studies suggest that there might be different environmental effects for “central” vs. “satellite” galaxies in a dark-matter halo [230,231]. We do not label our sources as central or satellite galaxies, because most galaxies ($\approx 80\%$ – 90%) at low redshift ($z \lesssim 0.6$) are observed to be isolated or reside in small groups (galaxy members $\lesssim 5$) and their central/satellite classification is challenging due to factors like photo- z uncertainties and survey sensitivity [232,233]. At higher redshift, the fraction of isolated or small-group galaxies is even higher as the large-scale structure is still in development [193,234]. Considering that our sources cover a wide redshift range of $z = 0.3$ – 3 , a detailed unbiased central/satellite classification is beyond the scope of this work.

3.2.3.1 Density Field (Local Environment)

We adopt the “weighted adaptive kernel smoothing” method to construct the surface-density field that probes sub-Mpc physical scales. As demonstrated by intensive simulations, the performance of this method is excellent (see §5 and §6 of [219]). The density field is calculated for all sources, including normal galaxies and X-ray detected sources.

We first calculate $\sigma_{|\Delta z|/(1+z)}$ as a function of redshift. $\sigma_{|\Delta z|/(1+z)}$ is derived within $z \pm 0.2$ at each redshift. $\sigma_{|\Delta z|/(1+z)}$ is ≈ 0.01 at low redshift ($z \lesssim 1$) and rises to ≈ 0.04 toward high redshift ($z \gtrsim 2$). This level of photo- z accuracy is sufficient for reliable cosmic-environment characterization [176,219]. We then define a series of redshift slices (z -slices) with widths of $\pm 1.5(1+z)\sigma_{|\Delta z|/(1+z)}$. This width is suggested by [235]. The z -slices are designed in a way that $\gtrsim 90\%$ of each z -slice is overlapping with its next z -slice. Such dense design is to appropriately consider the photo- z distribution of galaxies close to the boundaries of each z -slice (see §3.1 of [219]). The numbers of z -slices in different redshift ranges are listed in Tab. 3.1. For each z -slice, we calculate the weight for each source, defined as the percentage of the redshift probability distribution function within this z -slice. We assign a weight of 100% to sources with available spectroscopic redshifts. To reduce computational time, at each redshift, we only include sources with weight at least 10%. To derive the surface-density field for each z -slice, we utilize a 2D Gaussian kernel whose width adaptively decreases in denser regions, ranging from ≈ 0.2 Mpc (1% percentile) to ≈ 0.9 Mpc (99% percentile). The algorithm requires an input “global smoothing width”. We adopt the value of 0.5 Mpc which is the typical virial radius of X-ray

clusters in COSMOS ($\log M_{\text{halo}} \approx 13\text{--}14$; e.g. [236, 237]).³ Following [220], we filter out sources near (< 1 Mpc) the edge of the field and/or large masked regions in the COSMOS2015 survey [214], because density measurements for these sources are unreliable. The procedures above yield measurements of surface number density (Σ , in units of Mpc^{-2}) for each source.

We quantify the local environment for each source via the dimensionless overdensity parameter, defined as

$$1 + \delta = \frac{\Sigma}{\Sigma_{\text{median}}}, \quad (3.1)$$

where Σ_{median} is the median Σ at each redshift. To minimize the effects of cosmic variance, Σ_{median} is calculated within $z \pm 0.2$ at redshift z . Figs. 3.2 and 3.3 show the overdensity maps for two z -slices centered at $z = 1.0$ and 2.0 , respectively. The above overdensity measurements are based on sources with $K_s < 24$ (see §3.2.1).

Figs. 3.1 and 3.4 show overdensity as a function of redshift and M_* , respectively (see Tab.3.1 for typical overdensity ranges of our sample). There are positive trends between overdensity and M_* at $z \lesssim 2$, consistent with previous work [220].

In our overdensity estimation above, we have appropriately weighted sources according to their photo- z uncertainties (see §3.2.3). However, this weighting technique does not account for catastrophic photo- z outliers. The outlier fractions are $\approx 0.5\%$ – 10% , when compared with different spec- z catalogs (see §3.2.1 and Tab. 3.1). The photo- z outliers increase the noise level in the derivation of density field. [219] assessed the effects of outliers via simulations (see their §5.1). They concluded that an outlier fraction of 10% has little effect on the derived density field. Therefore, our results should not be qualitatively affected by the photo- z outliers.

The typical stellar mass of our sample is relatively small ($\log M_* \lesssim 10$; see Tab. 3.1). We have also tested using only a subsample of $\log M_* > 10$ galaxies when estimating the density field. Our results (§3.3) do not change qualitatively. The total stellar mass included in this subsample is $\approx 80\%$ of that included in the entire sample. However, the subsample consists of only $\approx 30\%$ of our sources, inevitably leading to stronger Poisson noise in the density-field estimation.

³ [219] tested global smoothing widths from 0.1 to 2.0 Mpc and did not find a significant change in the resulting density field.

Figure 3.2: The maps of overdensity (top) and cosmic web (bottom) for the z -slice at $z = 1.00 \pm 0.04$ derived from our galaxy sample (see §3.2.3). A physical scale of 3 Mpc is marked at the lower left corner in each panel. From the field to cluster environment, the overdensity tends to be higher. However, this is only a statistical trend. For example, high overdensity (top) does not necessarily correspond to cluster (bottom), and vice versa (see §3.2.3.2). The clusters identified in COSMOS are relatively low-mass systems ($\log M_{\text{halo}} \lesssim 14$; see §3.2.3.1). The white patches at the lower left corner are masked regions where NIR imaging data are not available [212].

Figure 3.3: Same format as Fig. 3.2 but for the z -slice centered at $z = 2.00 \pm 0.22$. Unlike in Fig. 3.2, we do not assign cluster environment due to its generally weak signals (see §3.2.3.2).

3.2.3.2 Cosmic Web (Global Environment)

Based on the density field derived in §3.2.3.1, we extract a cosmic-web estimate with the multi-scale morphology filter (MMF) algorithm [220, 221, 238]. The basic idea is to measure the geometry of the density field around each point in the z -slice. If the geometry is similar to that of a typical cluster/filament, then the point's

Figure 3.4: Overdensity vs. M_* for different redshift ranges. The contours include 68%, 90%, and 95% of all galaxies, respectively. The red points represent X-ray detected sources. The blue squares and orange circles indicate the median overdensity in each M_* bin (§3.3.1.1) for all galaxies and X-ray detected sources, respectively. We only calculate the medians for bins with more than 20 sources to avoid large uncertainties. The vertical dashed lines represent the M_* completeness limits at $z = 1.2, 2,$ and $3,$ respectively (§3.2.2). The X-ray detected sources tend to have high M_* but do not show an obvious dependence on overdensity.

environment is classified as cluster/filament; otherwise it is classified as the field.

Specifically, we first derive the Hessian matrix (second-order partial derivatives) of the density field for each point in a z -slice (see §3.4.1 of [220] for details). We then calculate two eigenvalues for each Hessian matrix. The eigenvalues describe the density-field geometry around the point. Based on the signs, ratios, and normalizations of the two eigenvalues, a cluster signal (S_c) and a filament signal (S_f) are obtained for the point. Here, the signals are two numbers within 0–1, where larger values indicate higher chances of lying in a cluster/filament. To account for the multi-scale nature of clusters and filaments, the above procedures are repeated but each time the density field is smoothed with a Gaussian kernel of different physical scales (0.25, 0.50, 0.75, 1.00, 1.50, 2.00 Mpc). The final cluster/filament signal for each point is assigned as the largest value among those obtained with different smoothing scales.

After obtaining the signal maps for each z -slice, we need to apply appropriate signal thresholds to identify clusters and filaments. A higher signal threshold generally increases reliability but decreases completeness in structure selection. We adopt the redshift-dependent thresholds from §3.4.2 of [220], which are designed to balance between reliability and completeness. These thresholds are $T_c = 0.0639z + 0.1142$ (cluster) and $T_f = 0.0253z + 0.0035$ (filament). Following [220], we assign

a cluster environment to a point if it has $S_c \geq S_f$ and $S_c \geq T_c$. If a point is not assigned as a cluster environment but has $S_f \geq T_f$, we assign it as a filament environment. If an object is not assigned as cluster or filament environment, we assign it as the field environment.

The above criterion has been successfully applied to $z \lesssim 1.2$ sources [220]. Fig. 3.2 shows the cosmic-web map for the z -slice centered at $z = 1.0$. The clusters are roughly round with typical physical sizes of ~ 1 Mpc. The filaments are elongated, with a typical length of ~ 10 Mpc. However, we find, at $z \gtrsim 1.2$, the clusters are often dominated by noise. This is understandable as clusters are still forming at high redshifts and they exist in the form of protoclusters [193, 239]. The protoclusters have weaker signals and are generally beyond our detection sensitivity. Therefore, we do not assign cluster environments for redshift ranges of $z = 1.2\text{--}2.0$ and $z = 2.0\text{--}3.0$. Specifically, if an object at $z = 1.2\text{--}3.0$ has $S_f \geq T_f$, we assign it as a filament environment; otherwise, we assign it as a field environment. Fig. 3.3 displays the cosmic-web map for the z -slice centered at $z = 2.0$. The numbers of sources associated with different cosmic-web environments are summarized in Tab. 3.1.

Fig. 3.5 shows the overdensity as a function of redshift for different cosmic-web environments. Although the overdensity generally rises from the field to clusters, there are substantial overlapping areas in the overdensity-redshift parameter space. This overlap is understandable as the overdensity and cosmic-web measurements describe cosmic environment on different scales (sub-Mpc vs. $\approx 1\text{--}10$ Mpc). The overlap highlights the importance of our MMF algorithm in the construction of the cosmic web, and a simple overdensity-based algorithm would not be feasible for cosmic-web association. Readers might worry that the overlap might smear out potentially weak trends between $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ and environment. However, this is not an issue in our analyses, because we assess $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ dependence on both overdensity and cosmic-web environment individually and reach consistent results (see §3.3).

[237] have associated galaxies with X-ray selected clusters at $z < 1$ using a probabilistic method. We match their cluster-member candidates (member probability above 70%) to our sample with a $0.5''$ matching radius. As expected, the 1,851 matched galaxies generally have high overdensity values of $\log(1 + \delta) = 0.34\text{--}0.66$ (25%–75% percentile) compared to our overall sample (see Tab. 3.1). For these 1,851 galaxies, 44% and 50% are assigned as cluster and filament, respectively,

Figure 3.5: Overdensity vs. redshift for 2,000 randomly selected sources in our sample. Different colors indicate sources with different cosmic-web environments. The clusters identified in COSMOS are relatively low-mass systems ($\log M_{\text{halo}} \lesssim 14$; see §3.2.3.1). We do not assign cluster environment at redshifts above $z = 1.2$ due to its generally weak signals (§3.2.3.2). Although the overdensity tends to increase moving from the field to clusters, there are significant overlaps between different cosmic-web environments.

in our catalog. The 44% filament objects tend to lie in the boundary between clusters and filaments in our z -slices, where the cluster/filament classification is sensitive to the methodology. The other 6% of galaxies are assigned as the field environment in our catalog. This disagreement is likely caused by the differences in adopted redshift measurements, as these galaxies' redshift values in the two catalogs differ by $\approx 3\%$. In comparison, the other 94% of galaxies ([237] cluster candidates assigned as cluster/filament galaxies) have redshift differences of only $\approx 0.7\%$. Our adopted photo- z values should have improved quality compared to those adopted in [237], who used photo- z from an earlier COSMOS catalog [240]. Note that it is natural that most of our cluster galaxies are not identified by [237], because their X-ray selected clusters are not complete.

3.2.4 Black Hole Accretion Rate

We derive $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ for samples of sources broadly following the procedures in §2.3 of [206]. Briefly, we first calculate the total sample-averaged L_X ($\overline{L_X}$) considering both X-ray detected sources (§3.2.4.1) and undetected sources (§3.2.4.2). The undetected sources are considered with an X-ray stacking technique. The stacking procedure is necessary to avoid biases due to the limited X-ray survey sensitivity, as faint AGNs become undetected toward high redshift. We obtain the AGN $\overline{L_X}$ by subtracting the $\overline{L_X}$ component contributed by XRBs (§3.2.4.3). Finally, we convert AGN $\overline{L_X}$ to $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ in units of $M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$.

3.2.4.1 X-ray Detected Sources

We select all X-ray detected sources using the COSMOS-Legacy X-ray survey [217]. The COSMOS-Legacy survey, conducted by *Chandra*, is the deepest X-ray survey available for COSMOS, and can sample most of cosmic accretion power. For instance, at $z \approx 1.5$ – 2.5 , the peak of cosmic AGN activity, it covers L_X ranging from ≈ 10 times below the knee luminosity of the X-ray luminosity function to ≈ 3 times above the knee luminosity, corresponding to $\approx 80\%$ of the total L_X (integrated from the X-ray luminosity function).

There are $\approx 2,020$ X-ray sources matched to the optical/NIR COSMOS2015 catalog based on a likelihood-ratio technique by [218]. Most ($\gtrsim 90\%$) of these X-ray sources should be AGNs considering their relatively high X-ray luminosity ($\log L_X > 42.5$; e.g. [67, 241]). Besides the ≈ 240 BL AGNs, there are ≈ 730 X-ray sources with spec- z measurements (see §3.2.1). We use these ≈ 730 non-BL X-ray sources to assess the photo- z quality for the $\approx 1,050$ X-ray sources with only photo- z measurements, because [209] estimated most ($\approx 80\%$) of the photo- z sources should be non-BL AGNs. The photo- z have $\sigma_{\text{NMAD}} = 0.018$ and $\eta = 7.5\%$ (see 3.2.1), comparable to the AGN photo- z quality in the literature [79, 224, 242].

A source might be detected in multiple X-ray bands. In this case, we choose, in order of priority, hard-band (2–7 keV), full-band (0.5–7 keV), and soft-band (0.5–2 keV) fluxes, for the L_X calculation below. This order of detection bands is to minimize the effects of X-ray obscuration. The fractions of X-ray sources with fluxes from the hard, full, and soft bands are 63%, 34%, and 3%, respectively.

The X-ray fluxes in the COSMOS-Legacy catalog are only corrected for Galactic

absorption. [218] have estimated intrinsic absorption column densities (N_{H}) based on hardness ratios. We do not apply these absorption corrections, because the majority ($\approx 70\%$) of sources have poorly constrained N_{H} values (consistent with zero at a 90% confidence level) mainly due to limited numbers of counts. Instead, we evaluate the level of absorption corrections for COSMOS-like sources using the ultradeep 7 Ms catalog of the *Chandra* Deep Field-South (CDF-S; [67]). Such sources have ≈ 44 times more counts in CDF-S than COSMOS and absorption corrections have been estimated individually [48, 67, 243]. These COSMOS-like sources are selected via applying the COSMOS flux limits [217] to CDF-S. We find that these COSMOS-like sources have a median absorption correction factor (intrinsic flux divided by observed flux) of ≈ 1.2 . The corresponding uncertainty caused by absorption correction is generally smaller than the statistical uncertainties of $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ (§3.2.4.3), and thus absorption should not bias our conclusions. The relatively low level of absorption corrections is mainly due to our choice of bands. Another reason is that we can sample ultra-hard ($\approx 10\text{--}20$ keV, rest-frame) penetrating X-rays for most sources (see Tab. 3.1).

We convert the X-ray fluxes to L_{X} assuming a power-law model with a photon index of $\Gamma = 1.7$, which is the typical intrinsic slope of distant AGNs [48, 243, 244]. Our conclusions do not change if we adopt a slightly different Γ value (e.g. $\Gamma = 1.4$). The resulting L_{X} values as a function of redshift are displayed in Fig. 3.1 (also see Tab. 3.1 for typical L_{X} ranges). Fig. 3.1 also shows the estimated L_{X} limit, assuming a 0.5–10 keV flux threshold of 8.9×10^{-16} erg cm $^{-2}$ s $^{-1}$ [217].

3.2.4.2 X-ray Undetected Sources

We perform X-ray stacking to calculate $\overline{L_{\text{X}}}$ for X-ray undetected sources in our samples. We use the full-band X-ray data. The full band is the most sensitive in the sense that it detects the largest number of X-ray sources [217], while the hard band is the least sensitive. Also, compared to the soft band, the full band is less affected by X-ray obscuration. Tab. 3.1 shows the rest-frame energy ranges corresponding to the full band. Using the soft band or hard band for stacking does not change our conclusions qualitatively.

Based on the full-band X-ray image and exposure map, we broadly follow the procedures in §2 of [96]. First, we mask the X-ray image for both detected extended and point-like sources. Since the extended-source catalog for the COSMOS-Legacy

survey is not available, we use the X-ray cluster catalog from *XMM-Newton* observations of COSMOS [236]. For point-like sources, we use the catalog from [217]. Since the X-ray clusters are masked, we cannot perform stacking analyses for some of the densest environments, and this could potentially bias our results for $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ dependence on environment. However, most of the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ in our sample is contributed by the X-ray detected sources (see §3.3.1.1). Indeed, our qualitative results do not change even if we only consider $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ contributed from X-ray detected sources. Therefore, we argue that the masking of X-ray clusters, and other technical details of the stacking, should not be critical to our analyses (see §3.3).

For each detected source (including extended and point-like sources), we mask its surrounding area with a radius of R_{msk} . We adopt $R_{\text{msk}} = r_{500}$ for extended sources, where r_{500} , in the range of $\approx 0.5' - 3'$, is the estimated cluster radius provided by [236]. We adopt $R_{\text{msk}} = 20''$ for point-like sources, as [96] show such a radius is large enough to include nearly all X-ray flux even for the brightest sources (thousands of counts) at the largest off-axis angles. We do not adopt a masking radius that depends on off-axis angle, because one source is often observed by multiple pointings and has different off-axis angles in different pointings. The masked regions (including those for extended and point-like sources) cover a total of $\approx 20\%$ of the survey area. We fill each masked region with the background randomly sampled from the corresponding background region, defined as the annulus with inner and outer radii of R_{msk} and $2R_{\text{msk}}$, respectively. This is performed with the “dmfilth” command in the *Chandra* data-analysis package CIAO. In the analyses below, we treat the masked regions as background.

We then derive net count rates for X-ray undetected galaxies (§3.2.1) utilizing the masked X-ray image and exposure map. We only calculate the net count rates for each source that is not within or close to the masked regions, i.e., its distance (d) to every masked source should satisfy $d > R_{\text{msk}} + R_{\text{phot}}$, where R_{phot} is the radius used to perform X-ray photometry. About 30% of sources are discarded in this step, and we account for X-ray emission from these sources in §3.2.4.3.

For each object, we obtain its total X-ray counts enclosed within a radius of $R_{\text{phot}} = 4''$ and the average exposure time for this area. The value $R_{\text{phot}} = 4''$ is chosen because the signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) of stacking becomes substantially lower for larger R_{phot} values. We calculate the total count rate by dividing the total counts by the average exposure time in the R_{phot} circle. The total count rate

includes not only the X-ray emission from the source but also the background. Therefore, we need to subtract the background properly. We choose the background region as an annulus with inner and outer radii of $10''$ and $20''$, respectively, and calculate the background count rate. We obtain the net count rates by subtracting the background count rates from the total count rates.

Since we are performing aperture photometry with a limited aperture size ($R_{\text{phot}} = 4''$), there is a fraction of X-ray emission falling outside of our photometric aperture. To estimate this effect, we re-calculate net counts but with a very large photometric radius of $R_{\text{phot}} = 10''$. We find that the final stacked count rates for $R_{\text{phot}} = 10''$ are systematically higher than those for $R_{\text{phot}} = 4''$ by a factor of ≈ 1.4 . Thus, $R_{\text{phot}} = 4''$ corresponds to a radius for $1/1.4 \approx 70\%$ encircled-energy fraction (EEF) on average. The 70% EEF is reasonable considering that the typical 50% EEF radius is 3–4'' for the detected sources (see Fig. 2 of [217]). We correct the net count rate ($R_{\text{phot}} = 4''$) for each source by multiplying by 1.4 to obtain the final net count rate.

Following [206], we obtain the average count rate for samples of sources and convert it to full-band X-ray flux with a constant factor ($9.5 \times 10^{-12} \text{ erg cm}^{-2} \text{ counts}^{-1}$). The factor is calculated with PIMMS assuming $\Gamma = 1.7$ (§3.2.4.1). We derive the average X-ray luminosity ($\overline{L_{X,\text{stack}}}$) from the average flux and the average redshift of the stacked sample. Our conclusions do not change if we adopt $\Gamma = 1.4$ for X-ray undetected sources (resulting in a $\approx 10\%$ change of $\overline{L_{X,\text{stack}}}$ at $z = 1$), as expected from the fact that total X-ray emission is dominated by X-ray detected sources in general.

3.2.4.3 Calculation of $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$

We calculate $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ for samples of sources following the recipe in §2.3 of [206]. We first calculate the average AGN X-ray luminosity for the sample as

$$\overline{L_X} = \frac{(\Sigma_{\text{det}} L_X) + N_{\text{non}} \overline{L_{X,\text{stack}}} - \Sigma_{\text{all}} L_{X,\text{XRB}}}{N_{\text{det}} + N_{\text{non}}}, \quad (3.2)$$

where N_{det} and N_{non} are numbers of X-ray detected and undetected sources, respectively; $L_{X,\text{XRB}}$ is the luminosity from XRBs.

In the numerator of Eq. 5.2, the first term ($\Sigma_{\text{det}} L_X$) is the total luminosity of X-ray detected sources (§3.2.4.1). The second term ($N_{\text{non}} \overline{L_{X,\text{stack}}}$) accounts for the

total luminosity of X-ray undetected sources. Stacked sources are only a subsample of the undetected sources as some undetected sources (within or close to the masked regions) are discarded in the stacking procedure (see §3.2.4.2). The formula ($N_{\text{non}}\overline{L_{X,\text{stack}}}$) assumes these discarded sources have the same average luminosity as the stacked sources.

The third term ($\Sigma_{\text{all}}L_{X,\text{XRB}}$ in Eq. 5.2) is to subtract the XRB component from the total luminosity. For star-forming galaxies (see §3.2.2 for the classification), we use $L_{X,\text{XRB}} = \alpha M_{\star} + \beta \text{SFR}$. The coefficients (α and β) are functions of redshift from model 269 of [98]; model 269 is a theoretical XRB model which is preferred by observations of galaxies at $z \approx 0\text{--}2$ ([97]; typical uncertainties $\lesssim 0.3$ dex). The M_{\star} value is from our SED fitting (§3.2.2). We approximate SFR by using the value from the star-forming main sequence in Eq. 6 of [101]. For quiescent galaxies, we neglect the SFR term and estimate their XRB emission as $L_{X,\text{XRB}} = \alpha M_{\star}$, since this term dominates. The sample-averaged XRB emission is $\approx 0.6\text{--}1.3$ dex lower than the average AGN emission. It is even ≈ 0.3 dex lower than the stacked X-ray emission. Therefore, the details of subtracting the XRB component are not critical to our analyses.

Following [206], we convert $\overline{L_X}$ to $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ as

$$\overline{\text{BHAR}} = \frac{3.53\overline{L_X}}{10^{45} \text{ erg s}^{-1}} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}. \quad (3.3)$$

This conversion assumes a constant bolometric correction factor ($k_{\text{bol}} = 22.4$; [104]) and a constant radiation efficiency ($\epsilon = 0.1$). We calculate the uncertainties of $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ with a bootstrapping technique (see §2.3 of [206]). The bootstrapping $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ errors are statistical uncertainties resulting from finite sampling.

A radiation efficiency of $\epsilon = 0.1$ is a typical value for the overall AGN population and is supported by observations [80, 105, 106]. Studies have found k_{bol} depends on AGN luminosity [108, 245, 246]. We do not adopt a L_X -dependent k_{bol} , because it cannot be applied to our stacking procedure. Also, a L_X -dependent k_{bol} requires careful subtraction of non-negligible XRB contributions for individual low-luminosity AGNs, and this task is challenging and beyond our work. Therefore, we adopt the constant k_{bol} for simplicity and consistency. However, we have tested applying a L_X -dependent k_{bol} [108] for AGN-dominated X-ray sources with $\log L_X > 43$ and our results do not change qualitatively. This is as expected, because our main

conclusions only depend on the relative values of $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ in different environments which are not significantly affected by different k_{bol} schemes. Admittedly, there might be systematics up to a factor of a few in our absolute values of $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ due to the uncertainties of k_{bol} and ϵ . We have also marked $\overline{L_X}$ values in the relevant figures below, allowing readers to consider either $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ or $\overline{L_X}$ when viewing these.

3.3 Results

3.3.1 $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ vs. Overdensity

3.3.1.1 Qualitative Tests

To probe the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ dependence on overdensity at different redshifts, we first bin sources into redshift ranges of 0.3–1.2, 1.2–2.0, and 2.0–3.0, respectively. We restrict our analyses to sources above the M_* completeness limits, $\log M_* = 9.3, 10,$ and 10.3 , for redshift ranges of 0.3–1.2, 1.2–2.0, and 2.0–3.0, respectively (see Figs. 3.1 and 3.4). Applying these M_* cuts is crucial, because incomplete M_* samples could lead to biased $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ values. For example, the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ at $\log M_* \approx 8$ in the bin of $z = 0.3\text{--}1.2$ would be strongly biased to $z \lesssim 0.5$, above which $\log M_* \approx 8$ galaxies remain largely undetected (see Fig. 3.1 top). Therefore, such a $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ value would not be representative of the entire redshift range of $z = 0.3\text{--}1.2$. Tab. 3.3 lists the sizes of these refined samples in different redshift ranges. Hereafter, this rule applies to all the analyses, unless otherwise stated. The fractions of our X-ray detected sources lying above the M_* cuts are 96%, 90%, and 77% for redshift ranges of 0.3–1.2, 1.2–2.0, and 2.0–3.0, respectively (see Fig. 3.4). Therefore, we are still capturing most accretion power after applying the M_* cuts. For each redshift bin, we further divide the sources into overdensity bins of $\log(1+\delta) < -0.3$, $\log(1+\delta) = -(0.3-0.1)$, $\log(1+\delta) = -0.1-0$, $\log(1+\delta) = 0-0.1$, $\log(1+\delta) = 0.1-0.3$, and $\log(1+\delta) > 0.3$. These bin boundaries ($-0.3, -0.1, 0, 0.1,$ and 0.3) roughly correspond to $\approx 10\%$, 30% , 50% , 70% , and 90% percentiles of the $\log(1+\delta)$ distribution of all objects.

We calculate $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ with the methods in §3.2.4.3 for all the bins and show the results in Fig. 3.6. $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ tends to be slightly higher toward high overdensity (black points), likely due to the positive dependence between M_* and overdensity and the intrinsic $\overline{\text{BHAR}}\text{-}M_*$ correlation (see Fig. 3.4; e.g. [58, 206, 209, 247, 248]). To show the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ dependence on M_* , we divide each overdensity sample into high- M_*

and low- M_* subsamples. In Fig. 3.6-left, the high- M_* and low- M_* subsamples have M_* above and below the median M_* of the overdensity sample, respectively; in Fig. 3.6-right, the high- M_* and low- M_* subsamples include sources with the highest 20% M_* and the lowest 20% M_* of the overdensity sample, respectively. In both the left and right panels, the high- M_* subsamples have significantly higher $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ than their corresponding low- M_* subsamples, indicating the previously known strong $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_*$ correlation. The $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ differences between the high- M_* and low- M_* subsamples are generally larger in the right panels than in the corresponding left panels, as expected from the positive $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_*$ correlation.

To investigate the potential $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -overdensity correlation for the M_* controlled sample, we divide the sources into bins of $\log M_* = 9.3-9.7, 9.7-10, 10-10.3, 10.3-10.6, 10.6-11, \text{ and } 11-11.5$ for each redshift range. The bin widths are ≈ 0.4 dex and the M_* limits at $z = 1.2, 2.0, \text{ and } 3.0$ (§3.2.2) are chosen as the boundaries of the M_* bins. We then split each M_* sample into high-overdensity and low-overdensity subsamples in a similar way as in Fig. 3.6.

We calculate $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ for all the M_* samples and overdensity subsamples. The results are shown in Fig. 3.7 (left). The high-overdensity and low-overdensity subsamples do not appear to have significantly different $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$, indicating that SMBH growth does not have a strong dependence on local environment at a given M_* . Any small apparent $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ differences between the high-overdensity and low-overdensity subsamples are likely just due to statistical fluctuations, as some blue points in Fig. 3.7 (left) are slightly above the corresponding red points while other blue points are below. The subsamples' median $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ 1σ uncertainty is 0.09 dex. Therefore, if the high-overdensity and low-overdensity subsamples had $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ differing by $\gtrsim 0.09$ dex systematically, the blue and red points would be significantly separated in Fig. 3.7 (left). In all redshift bins, $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ rises toward the high M_* regime. [209] have modeled the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_*$ relations at different redshifts in detail, and our data points are consistent with their results (see Fig. 3.7). The $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ contributed from stacking is generally ≈ 0.5 dex lower than the total $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$. Therefore, most X-ray emission is from the X-ray detected sources.

The two-subsample split (Fig. 3.7 left) guarantees that both subsamples have half the number of sources in each M_* bin, and thus the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ uncertainties are relatively small (median uncertainty = 0.09 dex) for the subsamples. We also probe more extreme overdensity regimes by comparing $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ of subsamples with the

highest 20% of overdensities and the lowest 20% of overdensities (see Fig. 3.7 right). The high-overdensity and low-overdensity subsamples also have similar $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ in general, although the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ uncertainties become larger (median uncertainty = 0.13 dex) compared to those in Fig. 3.7 (left) due to reduced subsample sizes. In Fig. 3.7, there are 2 pairs of high-overdensity and low-overdensity points that are separated above a 2σ confidence level. These deviations are likely due to statistical fluctuations. There are a total of 26 pairs of points in Fig. 3.7 (i.e., 26 trials), and we expect to find $\lesssim 4$ such deviations (99% confidence level, calculated with a binomial distribution). Also, our detailed quantitative analyses in §3.3.1.2 do not find statistically significant $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -overdensity relation when M_\star is controlled.

3.3.1.2 Partial Correlation Analyses

In §3.3.1.1, we qualitatively showed that the high-overdensity subsamples have similar $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ as the corresponding low-overdensity subsamples when controlling for M_\star . This result indicates that SMBH growth, at a given M_\star , does not significantly depend on local environment. We further quantitatively verify this point via partial-correlation (PCOR) analysis [114].

Following [206], we utilize PCOR.R in the R statistical package to perform PCOR analyses [249]. We bin sources in the overdensity- M_\star plane and derive $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ for each bin. The bin boundaries of overdensity and M_\star are the same as in §3.3.1.1. Fig. 3.8 shows the resulting $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ on overdensity- M_\star grids. Similar to [206], we input the $\log \overline{\text{BHAR}}$, $\log(1 + \delta)$, and $\log M_\star$ values into PCOR.R, where the $\log(1 + \delta)$ and $\log M_\star$ are the medians in each bin. We study the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -overdensity ($\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ - M_\star) correlation while controlling for the effects of M_\star (overdensity) via all three statistics available in PCOR.R (Pearson, Spearman, and Kendall). The Pearson statistic assumes log-linear relations, while the Spearman and Kendall non-parametric statistics are rank-based and do not have such assumptions.

The results are listed in Tab. 3.3. The $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ - M_\star correlation is statistically significant for all statistical techniques and across all redshift ranges. In contrast, the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -overdensity correlation is not significant ($< 3\sigma$) under any statistic in any redshift range. To visualize the PCOR results, we perform a least- χ^2 log-linear fit of the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ - M_\star ($\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -overdensity) relation. We then fit the residual $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ as a function of overdensity (M_\star). This procedure is similar to the Pearson statistic in PCOR analyses. The uncertainties of the best fit are estimated based on Markov

Figure 3.6: $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ as a function of overdensity for different redshift ranges. In the left panels, each overdensity bin is split into two subsamples with M_* above and below the median value, respectively. In the right panels, the subsamples include sources with the highest 20% of M_* and the lowest 20% of M_* , respectively. $\overline{L_X}$ is marked on the right-hand side of each panel. The red upward and blue downward triangles indicate the subsamples with M_* above and below the median value, respectively. The error bars are derived from a bootstrapping technique (see §3.2.4.3). The dashed curves indicate $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ contributed from X-ray stacking (see §3.2.4.2). The high- M_* subsamples have significantly higher BHAR than the corresponding low- M_* subsamples.

chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) sampling with EMCEE [250]. Fig. 3.9 displays the fitting results for $z = 0.3\text{--}1.2$. The best fit of the residual $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -overdensity relation is consistent with a flat model at a 3σ confidence level, while the residual $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ - M_* relation is step. The conclusion also holds for the other two redshift ranges. In Fig. 3.9-bottom, the data points at $\log M_* \approx 10.75$ tend to be above the fit. This perhaps indicates a log-linear model (assumed in the Pearson statistic) is not enough to describe fully the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ - M_* relation, consistent with previous works [209, 247, 248]. The Spearman and Kendall statistics do not assume a log-

Figure 3.7: Same format as Fig. 3.6 but for $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ vs. M_* . In both panels, the shaded regions show the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_*$ relations from [209]. The lower and upper boundaries of the [209] relations correspond to the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ at the low and high limits of the redshift bin, respectively, except for the redshift bin of $z = 0.3-1.2$. For $z = 0.3-1.2$, the lower boundary of the shaded region represents $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ at $z = 0.4$, which is the lowest redshift probed in [209]. The $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ for high-overdensity and low-overdensity subsamples are similar in general.

linear model, and they lead to qualitatively similar results as the Pearson statistic (see Tab. 3.3). Also, we note that since there are a total of such 12 trials in Fig. 3.9 (considering both the top and bottom panels), it is not surprising that one such deviation happens by chance (see §3.3.1.1).

Therefore, we conclude that the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ significantly depends on M_* but not overdensity. The conclusion is qualitatively supported by Figs. 3.1, 3.4, and 3.8. In Figs. 3.1 and 3.4, the X-ray detected sources preferentially appear in the high- M_* regime but do not show much dependence on overdensity. In Fig. 3.4, X-ray sources have median overdensity values similar to those of all galaxies. In Fig. 3.8, the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ gradient is strong in the x (M_*) direction but weak in the y (overdensity)

direction.

Our analyses above are based on the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ technique to assess SMBH growth. Another common technique in the literature is to consider AGN fractions above a given L_X threshold [58, 251]. Compared to our $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ approach, the AGN-fraction approach is less informative and less physical, because it needs a pre-defined L_X threshold which depends on X-ray survey sensitivity, and it does not consider X-ray emission from undetected sources. Also, unlike the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ approach, the AGN-fraction method weights low- L_X and high- L_X AGNs equally, as long as they are above the L_X threshold, thereby sacrificing information. However, the AGN-fraction method still serves as a common alternative way to assess SMBH accretion [201, 202]. For a consistency check, we also present the AGN fractions in different M_* bins for different local environments in Tab. 3.4 and Fig. 3.10. The AGN fractions are calculated as the fractions of X-ray detected sources above $\log L_X = 42.6$ ($z = 0.3\text{--}1.2$), $\log L_X = 43.1$ ($z = 1.2\text{--}2.0$), and $\log L_X = 43.5$ ($z = 2.0\text{--}3.0$), respectively. For each redshift range, the threshold is chosen as the $\log L_X$ completeness limit at the redshift upper boundary (see Fig. 3.1). Due to the differences in L_X thresholds, the AGN fractions (Tab. 3.4) at different redshift ranges are not directly comparable. The AGN-fraction errors are derived as 1σ binomial uncertainties using the ASTROPY module “BINOM_CONF_INTERVAL” [252]. From Tab. 3.6 and Fig. 3.10, at given M_* and redshift, the AGN fractions are generally similar in different overdensity bins, consistent with our PCOR analyses. This consistency indicates that our conclusions are not affected by the X-ray stacking procedures (especially the masking of X-ray extended sources; see §3.2.4.2), since the AGN fractions are based on X-ray detected sources only. Also, the AGN fraction rises toward massive galaxies, as expected from the strong $\overline{\text{BHAR}}\text{--}M_*$ relation (Fig. 3.7). In Fig. 3.10 (both top and middle panels), the lowest overdensity bin appears to have lower AGN fraction than other overdensity bins at $\log M_* \approx 11.1$. However, the differences are not significant at a 2σ confidence level. Also, considering there are many (78) points in Fig. 3.10, it is natural that a few deviations happen considering the “number of trials” effect detailed in §3.3.1.1. Therefore, we consider the apparent differences are likely due to statistical fluctuations.

$z = 0.3\text{--}1.2$ (48,581 galaxies)			
Relation	Pearson	Spearman	Kendall
$\overline{\text{BHAR-overdensity}}$	0.9 (0.1 σ)	0.2 (1.2 σ)	0.6 (0.6 σ)
$\overline{\text{BHAR-}M_\star}$	10^{-48} (14.7 σ)	10^{-45} (14.1 σ)	10^{-10} (6.3 σ)
$z = 1.2\text{--}2.0$ (18,944 galaxies)			
Relation	Pearson	Spearman	Kendall
$\overline{\text{BHAR-overdensity}}$	0.08 (1.7 σ)	0.4 (0.8 σ)	0.4 (0.8 σ)
$\overline{\text{BHAR-}M_\star}$	10^{-33} (12.0 σ)	10^{-21} (9.5 σ)	10^{-7} (5.0 σ)
$z = 2.0\text{--}3.0$ (5,932 galaxies)			
Relation	Pearson	Spearman	Kendall
$\overline{\text{BHAR-overdensity}}$	0.08 (1.8 σ)	0.1 (1.6 σ)	0.4 (0.9 σ)
$\overline{\text{BHAR-}M_\star}$	10^{-19} (8.9 σ)	10^{-19} (9.0 σ)	10^{-5} (4.3 σ)

Table 3.3: p -values (Significances) of Partial Correlation Analyses (see 3.3.1.2). Here, the numbers of galaxies are different from Tab. 3.1, because only sources above the limiting M_\star are used in the analyses of the $\overline{\text{BHAR-}M_\star}$ -environment relation (see §3.3.1.1).

$z = 0.3\text{--}1.2$ ($\log L_X > 42.6$)						
$\log M_\star$	9.3–9.7	9.7–10.0	10.0–10.3	10.3–10.6	10.6–11.0	11.0–11.5
$\log(1 + \delta) < -0.3$	$0.1^{+0.13}_{-0.07}$	$0.6^{+0.38}_{-0.24}$	$0.4^{+0.37}_{-0.19}$	$3.1^{+0.97}_{-0.75}$	$4.0^{+1.28}_{-0.98}$	$1.4^{+2.13}_{-0.83}$
$-0.3 \leq \log(1 + \delta) < -0.1$	$0.3^{+0.10}_{-0.07}$	$0.5^{+0.20}_{-0.14}$	$1.0^{+0.29}_{-0.22}$	$2.1^{+0.44}_{-0.37}$	$3.8^{+0.63}_{-0.54}$	$4.9^{+1.73}_{-1.29}$
$-0.1 \leq \log(1 + \delta) < 0.0$	$0.1^{+0.09}_{-0.05}$	$0.4^{+0.21}_{-0.14}$	$0.7^{+0.27}_{-0.19}$	$1.5^{+0.43}_{-0.33}$	$4.9^{+0.77}_{-0.67}$	$6.2^{+1.89}_{-1.47}$
$0.0 \leq \log(1 + \delta) < 0.1$	$0.1^{+0.09}_{-0.05}$	$0.3^{+0.17}_{-0.10}$	$0.7^{+0.29}_{-0.20}$	$2.4^{+0.53}_{-0.43}$	$4.6^{+0.71}_{-0.62}$	$6.3^{+1.65}_{-1.33}$
$0.1 \leq \log(1 + \delta) < 0.3$	$0.2^{+0.09}_{-0.07}$	$0.3^{+0.13}_{-0.09}$	$1.0^{+0.25}_{-0.20}$	$2.3^{+0.38}_{-0.33}$	$4.3^{+0.50}_{-0.45}$	$6.5^{+1.16}_{-1.00}$
$\log(1 + \delta) \geq 0.3$	$0.0^{+0.08}_{-0.03}$	$0.6^{+0.25}_{-0.18}$	$1.0^{+0.32}_{-0.24}$	$1.7^{+0.39}_{-0.32}$	$3.7^{+0.54}_{-0.47}$	$5.5^{+1.04}_{-0.88}$
All	$0.2^{+0.04}_{-0.03}$	$0.4^{+0.07}_{-0.06}$	$0.9^{+0.11}_{-0.10}$	$2.1^{+0.18}_{-0.17}$	$4.2^{+0.26}_{-0.24}$	$5.7^{+0.57}_{-0.52}$
$z = 1.2\text{--}2.0$ ($\log L_X > 43.1$)						
$\log M_\star$	–	–	10.0–10.3	10.3–10.6	10.6–11.0	11.0–11.5
$\log(1 + \delta) < -0.3$	–	–	$1.1^{+0.81}_{-0.46}$	$2.2^{+1.10}_{-0.74}$	$4.2^{+1.60}_{-1.17}$	$3.3^{+3.14}_{-1.63}$
$-0.3 \leq \log(1 + \delta) < -0.1$	–	–	$1.0^{+0.31}_{-0.24}$	$2.5^{+0.48}_{-0.41}$	$3.9^{+0.63}_{-0.54}$	$6.8^{+1.61}_{-1.32}$
$-0.1 \leq \log(1 + \delta) < 0.0$	–	–	$0.9^{+0.31}_{-0.23}$	$2.3^{+0.52}_{-0.43}$	$4.1^{+0.68}_{-0.59}$	$10.1^{+1.81}_{-1.56}$
$0.0 \leq \log(1 + \delta) < 0.1$	–	–	$1.1^{+0.33}_{-0.25}$	$3.2^{+0.57}_{-0.48}$	$4.2^{+0.65}_{-0.57}$	$6.2^{+1.34}_{-1.12}$
$0.1 \leq \log(1 + \delta) < 0.3$	–	–	$1.4^{+0.33}_{-0.27}$	$2.6^{+0.45}_{-0.39}$	$4.5^{+0.56}_{-0.50}$	$6.1^{+1.06}_{-0.91}$
$\log(1 + \delta) \geq 0.3$	–	–	$0.5^{+0.48}_{-0.24}$	$2.9^{+1.00}_{-0.75}$	$3.3^{+0.94}_{-0.73}$	$7.6^{+2.03}_{-1.63}$
All	–	–	$1.1^{+0.14}_{-0.12}$	$2.7^{+0.23}_{-0.21}$	$4.1^{+0.28}_{-0.26}$	$7.0^{+0.61}_{-0.57}$
$z = 2.0\text{--}3.0$ ($\log L_X > 43.5$)						
$\log M_\star$	–	–	–	10.3–10.6	10.6–11.0	11.0–11.5
$\log(1 + \delta) < -0.3$	–	–	–	$1.5^{+0.96}_{-0.59}$	$2.4^{+1.47}_{-0.91}$	$10.8^{+6.17}_{-4.11}$
$-0.3 \leq \log(1 + \delta) < -0.1$	–	–	–	$2.7^{+0.74}_{-0.58}$	$5.6^{+1.10}_{-0.93}$	$10.8^{+2.92}_{-2.36}$
$-0.1 \leq \log(1 + \delta) < 0.0$	–	–	–	$2.4^{+0.75}_{-0.57}$	$6.2^{+1.29}_{-1.08}$	$8.6^{+2.69}_{-2.10}$
$0.0 \leq \log(1 + \delta) < 0.1$	–	–	–	$2.9^{+0.79}_{-0.62}$	$7.8^{+1.36}_{-1.17}$	$9.7^{+2.75}_{-2.20}$
$0.1 \leq \log(1 + \delta) < 0.3$	–	–	–	$3.3^{+0.75}_{-0.62}$	$5.5^{+1.05}_{-0.89}$	$10.8^{+2.50}_{-2.08}$
$\log(1 + \delta) \geq 0.3$	–	–	–	$4.6^{+1.64}_{-1.23}$	$7.8^{+2.15}_{-1.72}$	$16.4^{+5.01}_{-4.03}$
All	–	–	–	$2.8^{+0.33}_{-0.29}$	$6.1^{+0.52}_{-0.48}$	$10.7^{+1.21}_{-1.10}$

Table 3.4: AGN fractions (%) in different overdensity bins

Figure 3.8: $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ as a function of overdensity and M_* for different redshift ranges. Darker color indicates higher $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ as labeled. White color indicates $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ is not available, because of large uncertainties on $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ or M_* lying below the completeness limits. The $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ in each bin has an uncertainty of $\lesssim 0.3$ dex.

3.3.2 $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ vs. Cosmic-Web Environment

In §3.3.1, we show that the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ is not related to overdensity (on sub-Mpc scales) at given M_* . In this section, we investigate the dependence of $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ on cosmic-web environment ($\sim 1\text{--}10$ Mpc scales). Following §3.3.1.1, we derive the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ for galaxies in field, filament, and cluster environments, respectively. The cosmic web describes global environment on $\approx 1\text{--}10$ Mpc scales (§3.2.3.2). The results are displayed in Fig. 3.11. The $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ does not show a significant trend as a function of cosmic-web environment. For each environment bin, we further divide the sources into high- M_* and low- M_* subsamples, respectively, and calculate $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ for each subsample. Similar to Fig. 3.6, the high- M_* subsamples have significantly higher $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ than the corresponding low- M_* subsamples, consistent with the dominant $\overline{\text{BHAR}}\text{--}M_*$ relation (§3.3.1).

We also bin our samples based on M_* , and further divide each bin into subsamples for different parts of the cosmic web. We calculate $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ for each subsample and show the results in Fig. 3.12. The $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ values are not systematically different for different cosmic-web environments. Now we test the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ dependence on cosmic-web environment quantitatively. Unlike in §3.3.1.2, we do not perform a PCOR analysis, because the cosmic-web environment (field, filament, and cluster) is not a continuous quantity. Instead, we employ another statistical analysis based on the Akaike information criterion (AIC; [253]). The AIC is designed for model selection and defined as $\text{AIC} = C + 2k$, where C is the fitting statistic (χ^2 for

Figure 3.9: $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ residuals (of the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_\star$ fit) vs. overdensity (top) and $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ residuals (of the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -overdensity fit) vs. M_\star (bottom) for $z = 0.3-1.2$. The black lines represent the best fit of the data points; the shaded regions indicate the 3σ uncertainties. In the top panel, the residual $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ is relatively flat as a function of overdensity; in the bottom panel, the residual $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ rises steeply toward high M_\star . Results are found similar at $z = 1.2-2.0$ and $z = 2.0-3.0$.

Figure 3.10: AGN fraction as a function M_\star for different overdensity bins. The data are from Tab. 3.4. At a given M_\star , different overdensity bins have similar AGN fractions. Some of the data points are overlapping due to this similarity.

least squares fitting) and k is the number of free parameters in the model. If one model has an AIC value much smaller than another model ($\Delta\text{AIC} < \Delta\text{AIC}_{\text{thresh}}$), then the former is considered superior to the latter (see, e.g. §2.6 of [254]). In our analyses, we choose $\Delta\text{AIC}_{\text{thresh}} = -7$, corresponding to a 3σ confidence level under the situation where the model parameter uncertainties are Gaussian (e.g. [255]).

We apply the AIC technique to our data points in Fig. 3.12. For each redshift range, we perform a least- χ^2 fit to all the data points with a log-linear model, $\log \overline{\text{BHAR}} = A \times \log M_\star + B$, where A and B are free model parameters.⁴ We calculate the AIC value (AIC_1) for this fitting. The best-fit models are displayed in Fig. 3.12. We then create a set of three independent log-linear models, i.e., $\log \overline{\text{BHAR}} = A_{\text{field}} \times \log M_\star + B_{\text{field}}$, $\log \overline{\text{BHAR}} = A_{\text{filament}} \times \log M_\star + B_{\text{filament}}$, and $\log \overline{\text{BHAR}} = A_{\text{cluster}} \times \log M_\star + B_{\text{cluster}}$, to fit the data.⁵ As the subscripts indicate, each model is used to fit the data points of the corresponding cosmic-web environment in Fig. 3.12. We derive the AIC value (AIC_2) for this multi-model fitting. If $\Delta\text{AIC} = \text{AIC}_2 - \text{AIC}_1 < -7$, then the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_\star$ relations might be different for different cosmic-web environments. The resulting AIC values are listed in Tab. 3.5. For all three redshift ranges, the ΔAIC values are above -7 . Therefore, the differences among the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_\star$ relations for different cosmic-web environments are not statistically significant. However, the non-detection of a $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -environment correlation might be, in principle, due to the limited sensitivity of our data. [196] found that the AGN fraction in rich clusters is ≈ 0.7 dex below that in the field at $z \lesssim 1$. A natural question is whether our data are sensitive enough to detect such $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ differences, i.e., $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ drops by 0.7 dex from the field to cluster environments. To answer this question, we perform a test. For our $z = 0.3\text{--}1.2$ bin, we systematically shift our cluster (field) $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ by -0.35 dex ($+0.35$ dex) and re-calculate ΔAIC . We find $\Delta\text{AIC} = -114$, much lower than our threshold (-7). Therefore, if our $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ dropped by 0.7 dex from the field to cluster environments, we would definitely detect the environmental dependence of $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$. In fact, we find that our data are sensitive at a $\approx 3\sigma$ level to a ≈ 0.2 dex difference of $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ from the field to cluster environments at $z = 0.3\text{--}1.2$. This difference between our work and [196] might be due to the lack of rich clusters in our sample (see §3.4.1 for more discussion).

⁴The single upper limit point in Fig. 3.12 is not used in the fitting.

⁵For $z > 1.2$, we only create the field and filament models, as we do not assign cluster environment (see §3.2.3.2).

Figure 3.11: Same format as Fig. 3.6 but for $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ vs. cosmic-web environment. We do not assign cluster environment at redshifts above $z = 1.2$ due to its generally weak signals (see §3.2.3.2). The high- M_* subsamples have BHAR significantly higher than their corresponding low- M_* subsamples.

In Fig. 3.13, we also compare $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ for cluster and field environments at $z = 0.3-1.2$. Here, we limit the cluster (field) galaxies to those with the highest (lowest) 20% overdensity in each M_* bin.⁶ In this way, we probe the most-extreme environments. We perform AIC analyses and obtain $\Delta\text{AIC} = 3.9$, above the threshold (-7). Therefore, the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_*$ relations for these two extreme environments are also not statistically different. At higher redshift, we have also performed similar analyses for filament vs. field environments and reached the same conclusion.

⁶Here, we do not limit cluster galaxies to those also identified by [237], because this would lead to too few sources (only < 10 AGNs) for our analyses, as the cluster-member catalog in [237] is not complete (see §3.2.3.2).

Figure 3.12: $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ as a function of M_* for different cosmic-web environments. $\overline{L_X}$ is marked on the right-hand side of each panel. The black line represents the best-fit log-linear model using all the data points. At a given M_* , the BHAR values are similar for different cosmic-web environments.

Figure 3.13: Same format as Fig. 3.12 (top) but for cluster vs. field environments. Here, we limit the cluster (field) galaxies to those with the highest (lowest) 20% overdensity in each M_* bin. At a given M_* , the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ values are similar for cluster and field environments.

Redshift	AIC ₁	AIC ₂	ΔAIC
0.3–1.2	32.48	33.35	0.9
1.2–2.0	12.34	14.38	2.0
2.0–3.0	9.82	9.75	−0.1

Table 3.5: Best-fit AIC values of the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_*$ relation (see 3.3.2)

3.3.3 Tests in Narrower Redshift Bins

Our analyses above adopt relatively wide redshift bins, i.e., $z = 0.3\text{--}1.2$, $1.2\text{--}2.0$, and $2.0\text{--}3.0$, to retain relatively large sample size in each bin. Considering that both galaxy and AGN properties as well as cosmic environment evolve with redshift, the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -environment relation might also have redshift dependence. To test for possible redshift dependence, we repeat our analyses in §3.3.1 and §3.3.2 using narrower redshift bins, i.e., $z = 0.3\text{--}0.8$, $0.8\text{--}1.2$, $1.2\text{--}1.6$, $1.6\text{--}2.0$, $2.0\text{--}2.5$, and $2.5\text{--}3.0$. This procedure reduces the sample size in each bin and thus increases the uncertainties on $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ in general. In the new analyses with narrower redshift

Figure 3.14: AGN fraction as a function M_\star for different cosmic-web environments. The data are from Tab. 3.6. At a given M_\star , AGN fractions are similar for different cosmic-web environments.

$z = 0.3-1.2$ ($\log L_X > 42.6$)						
$\log M_\star$	9.3-9.7	9.7-10.0	10.0-10.3	10.3-10.6	10.6-11.0	11.0-11.5
Field	$0.2^{+0.07}_{-0.05}$	$0.5^{+0.14}_{-0.11}$	$0.7^{+0.17}_{-0.14}$	$2.6^{+0.34}_{-0.30}$	$4.4^{+0.46}_{-0.42}$	$5.0^{+1.05}_{-0.88}$
Filament	$0.1^{+0.05}_{-0.03}$	$0.4^{+0.10}_{-0.08}$	$1.0^{+0.17}_{-0.14}$	$1.7^{+0.23}_{-0.20}$	$4.2^{+0.34}_{-0.32}$	$6.0^{+0.77}_{-0.69}$
Cluster	$0.1^{+0.15}_{-0.06}$	$0.1^{+0.22}_{-0.09}$	$0.8^{+0.42}_{-0.27}$	$2.2^{+0.65}_{-0.51}$	$3.5^{+0.81}_{-0.66}$	$5.9^{+1.66}_{-1.31}$
All	$0.2^{+0.04}_{-0.03}$	$0.4^{+0.07}_{-0.06}$	$0.9^{+0.11}_{-0.10}$	$2.1^{+0.18}_{-0.17}$	$4.2^{+0.26}_{-0.24}$	$5.7^{+0.57}_{-0.52}$
$z = 1.2-2.0$ ($\log L_X > 43.1$)						
$\log M_\star$	–	–	10.0-10.3	10.3-10.6	10.6-11.0	11.0-11.5
Field	–	–	$0.8^{+0.20}_{-0.16}$	$2.7^{+0.38}_{-0.33}$	$4.0^{+0.46}_{-0.42}$	$6.9^{+1.11}_{-0.96}$
Filament	–	–	$1.3^{+0.20}_{-0.17}$	$2.6^{+0.29}_{-0.26}$	$4.2^{+0.36}_{-0.33}$	$7.0^{+0.75}_{-0.68}$
All	–	–	$1.1^{+0.14}_{-0.12}$	$2.7^{+0.23}_{-0.21}$	$4.1^{+0.28}_{-0.26}$	$7.0^{+0.61}_{-0.57}$
$z = 2.0-3.0$ ($\log L_X > 43.5$)						
$\log M_\star$	–	–	–	10.3-10.6	10.6-11.0	11.0-11.5
Field	–	–	–	$2.6^{+0.40}_{-0.35}$	$6.4^{+0.69}_{-0.63}$	$11.1^{+1.66}_{-1.47}$
Filament	–	–	–	$3.3^{+0.60}_{-0.51}$	$5.5^{+0.80}_{-0.70}$	$10.1^{+1.86}_{-1.60}$
All	–	–	–	$2.8^{+0.33}_{-0.29}$	$6.1^{+0.52}_{-0.48}$	$10.7^{+1.21}_{-1.10}$

Table 3.6: AGN fractions (%) for different cosmic-web environments

bins, we still do not find any significant $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ dependence on either overdensity or cosmic-web environment, consistent with the results in §3.3.1 and §3.3.2. Fig. 3.15 shows some example figures for $z = 0.8-1.2$, and the figures for other narrower redshift bins are qualitatively similar. Therefore, our main conclusions are unlikely to be affected by our choice of relatively wide redshift bins.

3.4 Discussion

We discuss the physical implications of our results in §3.4.1. We compare our results with previous observations of BHAR-environment relations in §3.4.2.

3.4.1 Physical Implications

Our results indicate that SMBH accretion is fundamentally related to M_\star . At a given M_\star , our $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ does not show significant dependence on host-galaxy environment. Since galaxy environment is largely determined by dark matter, which generally dominates the gravitational field on \gtrsim subMpc scales, our conclusions suggest SMBH growth is primarily related to baryons rather than dark matter [4, 209]. The broad physical picture is likely that dark-matter density fluctuations lead to the formation of halos, allowing baryons to condense into the halo centers and form

Figure 3.15: The top and bottom panels follow the same formats as Figs. 3.7 and Fig. 3.12 but for the narrower redshift bin of $z = 0.8 - 1.2$. Still, we do not find significant $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ dependence on environment. This conclusion also applies for other narrower redshift bins in §3.3.3.

galaxies. The galaxies feed their SMBHs with cold gas via baryonic physics, e.g. disk instabilities and galaxy bars (e.g. [138] and references therein). This scenario indicates that, in future studies of SMBH-galaxy coevolution, it is critical to focus on relations between BHAR and host-galaxy intrinsic properties (e.g. M_* , SFR, and morphology) rather than the environment. Small but deep surveys such as the *Chandra* Deep Fields [67, 241] and CANDELS [65, 66] are ideal for studying SMBH-galaxy coevolution.

It is well established that environment affects galaxy evolution. At a given M_* and at $z \lesssim 1$, the quiescent-galaxy fraction (as defined in §3.2.2) rises toward high-density regions, and this effect is often termed “environmental quenching” [175–177, 219, 220, 256]. Fig. 3.16 shows the quiescent-galaxy fraction in our sample as a function of M_* for different cosmic-web environments (see §3.2.2 for star-forming/quiescent classifications). At $z = 0.3$ – 1.2 and a given M_* , the quiescent galaxy fraction significantly rises from the field to cluster environments; at higher redshifts this environmental dependence seems to disappear. Therefore, environmental quenching at $z = 0.3$ – 1.2 is significantly observed in our sample. For a given cosmic-web environment, the quiescent-galaxy fraction also rises toward high M_* at all redshifts. This M_* dependence is expected from previous studies [216, 257].

In contrast, our $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ does not show a significant dependence on environment, if M_* is controlled (see §3.3). These different behaviors of SMBH accretion and star formation suggest that SMBH and galaxy stellar-mass growth are not strongly coupled in general [206, 209], although we cannot rule out a weak secondary $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -SFR relation (see §3.4.2). The potential physical mechanisms responsible for environmental quenching such as tidal interaction and ram-pressure stripping (§3.1) might only have limited effects on SMBH accretion.

Since galaxy evolution has significant dependence on environment at low redshift ($z \lesssim 1$), the host-galaxy types of AGNs might also depend on environment. In Tab. 3.7, we list the quiescent-galaxy fractions for AGNs (as defined in §3.3.1.2) in different cosmic-web environments. At $z = 0.3$ – 1.2 , the quiescent-galaxy fraction of AGN hosts appears to rise from the field to clusters, similar to the trend for normal galaxies (see Fig. 3.16). At higher redshift, if anything, the trend seems to be the opposite going from the field to filament environments. However, these trends are not statistically significant at a 3σ confidence level due to our limited AGN sample size. Future work with much larger AGN samples can determine these trends more

Redshift	Field	Filament	Cluster	All
0.3–1.2	18.8 ^{+2.66} _{-2.40}	26.5 ^{+2.38} _{-2.25}	29.3 ^{+6.29} _{-5.59}	24.0 ^{+1.70} _{-1.62}
1.2–2.0	13.9 ^{+2.62} _{-2.26}	10.0 ^{+1.67} _{-1.45}	–	11.4 ^{+1.40} _{-1.26}
2.0–3.0	7.6 ^{+2.19} _{-1.73}	6.6 ^{+2.63} _{-1.92}	–	7.2 ^{+1.63} _{-1.35}

Table 3.7: Quiescent-galaxy fractions (%) for AGN host galaxies

accurately.

3.4.2 Previous Works on BHAR vs. Environment

Based on sources at $z \lesssim 1$, observations have found that cluster ($M_{\text{halo}} \lesssim 10^{14} M_{\odot}$) and field environments have similar X-ray AGN fractions among massive galaxies, consistent with our results [251, 258, 259]. However, these analyses are often restricted to low-redshift relatively bright galaxies. Thanks to the reliable photo- z measurements and our improved methodology for assessing SMBH accretion, our work is able to investigate $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -environment relations for all galaxies above the M_{\star} completeness limits up to $z = 3$. Importantly, our study covers $z \approx 1.5$ – 2.5 where cosmic AGN activity peaks.

Some studies find that, at $z \lesssim 1$, the X-ray AGN fractions in rich clusters ($M_{\text{halo}} \sim 10^{15} M_{\odot}$) are generally lower than those in the field [196, 197]. Due to the lack of excellent multiwavelength coverage for M_{\star} calculation, these studies often adopt a simple R -band magnitude cut to approximate an M_{\star} cut of the galaxy population [260]. However, we note that consensus has not been widely reached on whether rich clusters have lower AGN fractions than the field. For example, [198] found that rich clusters and the field have similar AGN fractions at $z = 0.05$ – 0.31 , when the same magnitude and L_X cuts are applied to the cluster and field populations. If AGN activity is indeed suppressed in rich clusters at a given M_{\star} , the physical reason might be different galaxy types in cluster and field environments. Rich clusters, especially in their central regions, are dominated by the quiescent galaxy population, which tends to have lower AGN fractions than the star-forming population at a given M_{\star} [209, 248, 261]. We cannot study such rich clusters in our work, because they are rare and generally absent in COSMOS, where the clusters typically have $M_{\text{halo}} \lesssim 10^{14} M_{\odot}$ [232, 237]. However, only a small fraction of the galaxy population ($\lesssim 1\%$) lives in rare rich clusters with

Figure 3.16: Quiescent-galaxy fraction vs. stellar mass for different cosmic-web environments. The star-forming/quiescent classifications are based on a standard color-color scheme (see §3.2.2). At $z = 0.3-1.2$ and a given M_\star , the quiescent-galaxy fraction rises from the field to cluster environments (environmental quenching). At $z > 1.2$, galaxies associated with the field and filament environments have similar quiescent-galaxy fractions.

$M_{\text{halo}} \sim 10^{15} M_{\odot}$ (e.g. Tab. 1 of [262]). Our work covers a large comoving volume ($\approx 10^7 \text{ Mpc}^3$ for each redshift bin; §3.2.1), and thus we probe the main range of cosmic environments in the overall Universe with $M_{\text{halo}} \approx 10^{11}\text{--}10^{14} M_{\odot}$. We do not find significant $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -environment relations when controlling for M_{\star} , even at the extremes of the environments we sample (e.g. Figs. 3.7 and 3.13). Therefore, we conclude that, for the overall galaxy population, $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ generally does not depend on cosmic environment once M_{\star} is controlled, although this conclusion might not hold for galaxies living in rare rich clusters.

At high redshift ($z \gtrsim 2$), observations suggest that some massive protoclusters might have elevated AGN activity (see §3.1; but also see [205]). For example, SSA 22 is a prominent protocluster at $z \approx 3.1$, and it is likely a progenitor of local rich clusters with $M_{\text{halo}} \sim 10^{15} M_{\odot}$ [263]. [199] estimated that its X-ray AGN fraction is $\approx 5\%$ – 10% among Lyman Break Galaxies (LBGs) and Ly α Emitters (LAEs), considerably higher than the AGN fraction ($\approx 1\%$ – 2%) among LBGs and LAEs in the field at similar redshifts. However, the LBGs and LAEs in SSA 22 might have different M_{\star} compared to the LBGs and LAEs in the field, and the difference in M_{\star} could drive the apparent differences in AGN fraction (see Tab. 3.6). Also, the SSA 22 AGN sample size is limited (≈ 10) and suffers from significant statistical uncertainty. SSA 22 has $\gtrsim 150$ galaxies in its central region of $\approx 10 \text{ Mpc}^2$ [264], translating to an overdensity value of $\log(1 + \delta) \gtrsim 1.3$ (§3.2.3.1). We do not have such prominent structures in our sample at $z \gtrsim 2.5$ (Fig. 3.1) and thus cannot probe their AGN activity using COSMOS. Note that the estimated overdensity value of SSA 22 is for high redshifts ($z \gtrsim 2.5$). It is not directly comparable to our structures at low redshift, since the normalization factors Σ_{median} are different at different redshifts (see Eq. 3.1).

AGN-clustering studies also make use of source spatial distributions to probe SMBH-galaxy coevolution. Early observations found that X-ray AGNs and normal galaxies appear to have different clustering properties (especially on $\lesssim 1 \text{ Mpc } h^{-1}$ comoving scales), suggesting different environmental effects for central vs. satellite galaxies [231,265,266]. However, galaxy properties (especially M_{\star}) were not carefully controlled among these studies. Considering the strong $\overline{\text{BHAR}}\text{--}M_{\star}$ correlation [206, 209] and the well-established relation between galaxy clustering and M_{\star} [207, 208], it is critical to match M_{\star} in AGN vs. galaxy clustering analyses. More recent observations show that the clustering properties of AGNs and galaxies are

similar over a wide range of comoving scale ($\approx 0.1\text{--}30 \text{ Mpc } h^{-1}$) when M_\star is carefully matched, indicating that M_\star (rather than a central/satellite effect) mainly drives the observed clustering properties of AGNs [27–30]. Also, our analyses do not support different environmental effects for central vs. satellite galaxies, although we do not perform a central/satellite classification (§3.2.3). If, for example, environment only affects AGN activity in central galaxies, we would witness an increasingly strong $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -environment relation in more massive galaxies which have a higher chance of being central [267]. However, we do not find any significant $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -environment correlation over a wide range of stellar mass ($\log M_\star \approx 9.5\text{--}11.5$; §3.3). Clustering analyses infer that AGNs typically have $\log M_{\text{halo}} \approx 13$ [268–271] This is as expected, since low-mass halos ($\log M_{\text{halo}} \lesssim 12$) only host low-mass galaxies with weak $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ and high-mass halos ($\log M_{\text{halo}} \gtrsim 14$) are rare.

3.5 Summary and Future Work

We have studied the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ dependence on M_\star and environment in redshift bins of $z = 0.3\text{--}1.2$, $z = 1.2\text{--}2.0$, and $z = 2.0\text{--}3.0$, based on sources in the COSMOS field. Our main procedures and results are summarized below:

1. We have compiled a large galaxy sample in the COSMOS field ($\approx 170,000$ sources; §3.2.1) and estimated their M_\star via SED fitting (§3.2.2). We have measured surface overdensity (sub-Mpc scales) and cosmic-web environment ($\approx 1\text{--}10 \text{ Mpc}$ scales) for our sources (§3.2.3).
2. We have derived $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ for different samples, considering both X-ray detected and undetected sources (§3.2.4). For X-ray detected sources, we adopt, in order of priority, hard-band, full-band, and soft-band fluxes, in our calculations (§3.2.4.1). This choice is to minimize the effects of X-ray obscuration. We include the X-ray emission from X-ray undetected sources via stacking (§3.2.4.2).
3. We do not find a statistically significant $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ dependence on overdensity or cosmic-web environment ($\approx 1\text{--}10 \text{ Mpc}$) for M_\star controlled samples (§3.3). Instead, $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ is always strongly related to M_\star , regardless of environment. These results suggest that $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ might be primarily related to the host

galaxies rather than cosmic environment on scales of $\approx 0.1\text{--}10$ Mpc, which is determined by dark matter (§3.4.1). Thanks to the large comoving volume sampled ($\approx 10^7$ Mpc³ for each redshift bin), we can probe the main range of cosmic environments in the overall Universe (§3.4.2). Therefore, we conclude that, for the overall galaxy population, $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ generally does not depend on cosmic environment once M_\star is controlled, although this conclusion might not hold for the $\lesssim 1\%$ of galaxies living in rare rich clusters with $M_{\text{halo}} \sim 10^{15} M_\odot$.

4. In contrast to SMBH accretion, star formation activity significantly depends on environment at $z \lesssim 1$ (§3.4.1). For our sample, the quiescent-galaxy fraction rises from the field to cluster environment for M_\star -controlled samples at $z = 0.3\text{--}1.2$, consistent with previous observations. The different behaviors of SMBH accretion and star formation suggest that SMBH and galaxy growth are not strongly coupled in general. Environment-related mechanisms such as tidal interaction and ram-pressure stripping that could shape galaxy evolution do not appear to strongly affect SMBH growth.

Future work can probe the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ dependence on environment for larger physical scales ($\approx 10\text{--}100$ Mpc). Since COSMOS alone cannot sample the full range of cosmic environments on these scales [272, 273], these studies will need several COSMOS-like fields, e.g. XMM-LSS [274], Wide-CDF-S, and ELAIS-S1, or much larger fields such as Stripe 82 [275] and XMM-XXL [276]. Such larger fields can also be used to probe SMBH growth in rare rich clusters/protoclusters (see §3.4.2) while controlling for host-galaxy properties, especially M_\star . In addition, future work may study $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ in galaxy close pairs on $\approx 10\text{--}100$ kpc scales [277].

The upcoming *eROSITA* all-sky X-ray survey will yield a sample of $\sim 10^6$ AGNs at $z \lesssim 1$ [278], allowing studies of $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -environment relations at low-to-moderate redshift with overwhelming source statistics. In this work, we do not find significant environmental dependence of average BHAR. It is still possible that the full distribution of BHAR depends on environment, although this would require “finely tuned” BHAR distributions in different environments to maintain constant $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$. A full characterization of the BHAR distribution as a function of M_\star , environment, and redshift [209, 247, 248] requires future X-ray observatories like *Athena* and *Lynx*, which are necessary to sample the faint end of the BHAR distribution in COSMOS-like (or larger) fields [279].

With the advance of environment-measurement methodology, new environmental metrics other than overdensity (and the consequent field/filament/cluster classification) may be developed. Future work can study the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ dependence on these new environmental metrics (e.g. mass density instead of number density as used in this work). Future spectroscopic observations with Extremely Large Telescopes (ELTs) should improve the spec- z completeness for COSMOS and other fields by a large factor, allowing environmental measurements with superior accuracy (e.g. reducing the projection distance from ≈ 100 Mpc to ≈ 10 Mpc; §3.6.1). Based on such new spec- z data, studies can revisit the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -environment- M_* connection, even for central/satellite galaxies separately.

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Disclaimer

The findings and conclusions do not necessarily reflect the view of the funding agencies.

3.6 Supplementary Materials

3.6.1 Explanation of Environment Measurements

Our environment estimation in §3.2.3 is two-dimensional in nature (2D; projected over $\approx 80\text{--}200$ Mpc along the line-of-sight (LOS); see Fig. 3.17). Admittedly, the 2D environment measurements have limitations and cannot fully recover the entire 3D environment. However, through intensive tests on simulated data, studies have found that the 2D environment estimates can reliably trace the intrinsic 3D environments. For example, [176] found that the projected 2D densities are monotonically related to the true 3D volume densities with a power-law slope of ≈ 0.67 . [256] found that the 2D measured filaments robustly match their 3D counterparts. These strong 2D-3D correlations result from the fact that, in the projection, the chance for different structures to overlap is low. The low overlapping probability is caused by the facts that most ($\gtrsim 80\%$) of the 3D space is the field environment in Λ CDM simulations [281, 282] and that low-mass halos might not host galaxies and are thus unobservable (e.g. [283] and references therein). Assuming Poisson fluctuations, we estimate the chance for two (or more) overlapping filaments along a LOS is $\lesssim 3\%$, based on the fact that the filament environment covers $\lesssim 30\%$ of the total area (see Figs. 3.2 and 3.3). Although a rigorous quantitative demonstration on simulated data is beyond the scope of this work, we qualitatively explain our 2D environment measurements in a straightforward way below.

Taking our z -slice at $z = 1$ as an example (Fig. 3.2), we show the scheme of our environment measurements in Fig. 3.17.⁷ Our surface-density field is measured within a 2D circle with a radius of ≈ 0.5 Mpc, projected from a 3D cylinder of length ≈ 100 Mpc (Fig. 3.17 left). Fig. 3.17 (right) shows typical field, filament, and cluster environments. The numbers of galaxies plotted reflect the typical galaxy numbers in our measurements for different environments at $z \approx 1$. For the field environment, our surface density is averaged over the whole cylinder with a volume of $\pi \times 0.5^2 \times 100$ Mpc³. This relatively large volume is necessary to include $\gtrsim 1$ galaxies. For the filament environment, the density enhancement is mainly due to the 3D dense region with scale similar to the filament “thickness” ($\lesssim 1$ Mpc scales;

⁷Technically, the measurements are more complicated (see §3.2.3), the schematic plot here is just for demonstration purposes.

see Figs. 3.2 and 3.3). The situation for the cluster environment is similar to that for filament environment.

Admittedly, environment mis-classification might happen in some cases. For example, a filament, when it aligns with the LOS, might be mis-classified as a cluster. However, this situation should be rare because filaments are often not straight and have curved shapes (see Figs. 3.2 and 3.3). Also, galaxies in the cluster environment generally have significantly lower SFR than those in the filament environment at $z \lesssim 1$ (e.g. [220]; Fig. 3.16). This physical phenomenon would not be observed if our classified cluster population is heavily polluted by an intrinsic filament population.

Due the existence of various projection effects, any quantitative correlation with 2D environment should not be literally interpreted as a quantitative correlation with the intrinsic 3D environment. For example, a quantity “ A ” is found to be positively correlated with 2D overdensity with a power-law index of α . We can only conclude qualitatively that A is positively related to 3D overdensity, but not quantitatively that the relation between A and 3D overdensity is also a power law with an index of α .

Figure 3.17: Schematic plot for overdensity measurements (not drawn to scale). The left panel shows the redshift slice at $z = 1$. The z -slice contains galaxies projected along the LOS over $\approx 100 \text{ Mpc}$. Our surface density is measured in cylinders with radii $\approx 0.5 \text{ Mpc}$ as marked. The right panel illustrates three typical cylinders for the field, filament, and cluster environments, respectively. The dashed circles denote galaxies inside the cylinders. Blue, green, and red colors indicate galaxies associated with 3D field, filament, and cluster environments, respectively. The numbers of galaxies plotted reflect the typical galaxy numbers in our measurements at $z \approx 1$.

Chapter 4 | Linking Black-Hole Growth with Host Galaxies: the Accretion- Stellar Mass Relation and its Cosmic Evolution

4.1 Introduction

The connection between supermassive black holes (SMBHs) and host galaxies is a central topic in extragalactic studies. Observations of the local universe reveal that black-hole mass (M_{BH}) is tightly related to host-galaxy bulge mass (M_{bulge}) and bulge velocity dispersion (σ) [4, 6–8]. This $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\text{bulge}}$ relation suggests that SMBHs and host galaxies evolve in a coordinated way over cosmic history, i.e., the so-called “SMBH-galaxy coevolution” scenario.

The black-hole accretion rate (BHAR) can be inferred from X-ray emission, thanks to the near-universality and penetrating nature of X-rays generated by the SMBH accretion process [80, 195]. However, since orders-of-magnitude variability is likely common among active galactic nuclei (AGNs) on timescales of $\approx 10^2 - 10^7$ yr (e.g., [23]; [26] and references therein), the instantaneous X-ray luminosity (L_{X}) cannot be used to study the long-term behavior of black-hole accretion. The sample-mean BHAR of a galaxy population is often adopted as a proxy for the long-term average BHAR ($\overline{\text{BHAR}}$, i.e., $\overline{dM_{\text{BH}}/dt}$).

Much work has focused on relations between $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ (i.e., the activity of AGNs)

and host-galaxy properties such as star formation rate (SFR) and stellar mass (M_*) in the distant universe. Some studies have found a positive correlation between sample-mean BHAR and SFR, and interpret this result as a reflection of an intrinsic $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -SFR relation for individual galaxies [11,25,26,112]. In addition, observations have demonstrated that the AGN fraction above a given L_X threshold rises steeply toward high M_* , suggesting a connection between $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ and M_* [58,261,284].

The apparent $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -SFR and $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ - M_* relations might not both be fundamental, because SFR and M_* are positively correlated through the “star-formation main sequence” for star-forming galaxies. To address this SFR- M_* degeneracy, [206] studied the sample-mean BHAR dependence on both SFR and M_* , and concluded via partial-correlation analyses that $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ is primarily related to M_* rather than SFR in general. This result is consistent with some observations suggesting AGN host galaxies have similar SFR as normal galaxies at a given M_* [15,19,123,285]. Therefore, the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ - M_* relation might be a key to addressing questions about SMBH-galaxy coevolution.

[206] fitted the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ - M_* relation with a log-linear model and found that the slope is consistent with unity (see their Fig. 5). They did not find significantly different $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ - M_* relations for the two redshift ranges ($0.5 \leq z < 1.3$ and $1.3 \leq z < 2.0$) used in their analyses. However, the constraints on cosmic evolution were not tight due to the limited sample sizes and large redshift bin widths. Strong cosmic evolution could plausibly exist, since the cosmic BHAR density (ρ_{BHAR}) significantly depends on redshift [10,13]. [206] only probed the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ - M_* relation for galaxies with low and intermediate M_* [$\log(M_*/M_\odot) \lesssim 10.5$]. However, massive galaxies may have a very different BHAR- M_* correlation, due to stronger AGN feedback governing SMBH growth [286,287].

In this paper, we investigate the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ - M_* relation and its cosmic evolution [$\overline{\text{BHAR}}(M_*, z)$] over ranges of $\log(M_*/M_\odot) = 9.5\text{--}12$ and $z = 0.4\text{--}4$. We do not discuss the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ - M_{BH} relation. The $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ - M_{BH} relation might be more physically relevant than the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ - M_* relation, as high- M_{BH} SMBHs should be more capable of accreting surrounding material. It is even possible that the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ - M_* relation ultimately originates from a $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ - M_{BH} relation (or other similar relations), since massive galaxies tend to host high- M_{BH} SMBHs. However, unlike M_* , M_{BH} is not a property of host galaxies, and thus the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ - M_{BH} relation does not directly provide clues about SMBH-galaxy coevolution. Also,

M_{BH} measurements are often limited to rare luminous broad-line (BL) quasars and subject to large uncertainties [165]. On the other hand, M_* is an observable for most systems and its measurement techniques are mature [71, 216].

Our $\overline{\text{BHAR}}(M_*, z)$ is derived from the probability distribution of specific X-ray luminosity [$P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$, where $L_{\text{SX}} = L_{\text{X}}/M_*$]. The definition of L_{SX} allows it to serve as a rough proxy for the Eddington ratio, i.e., $\lambda_{\text{Edd}} = L_{\text{bol}}/L_{\text{Edd}}$, where $L_{\text{Edd}} = 1.26 \times 10^{38} (M_{\text{BH}}/M_{\odot}) \text{ erg s}^{-1}$ is the Eddington luminosity and L_{bol} is the bolometric luminosity, as L_{bol} and M_{BH} are broadly correlated with L_{X} and M_* , respectively [4, 246]. For our purpose, choosing the mathematical format of L_{SX} is only to follow the convention of previous work [59, 60], and the choice of whether to derive $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ or $P(L_{\text{X}}|M_*, z)$ does not affect the final $\overline{\text{BHAR}}(M_*, z)$. Previous work on $P(L_{\text{X}}|M_*, z)$ [247, 248] focuses on interpreting the physical cause of $P(L_{\text{X}}|M_*, z)$ itself (e.g., its shape and normalization). Our work utilizes $P(L_{\text{X}}|M_*, z)$ as a method to derive $\overline{\text{BHAR}}(M_*, z)$, and study SMBH-galaxy coevolution based on $\overline{\text{BHAR}}(M_*, z)$. Therefore, our scientific goals are different from those works.

At low and moderate L_{SX} ($\lesssim 1 L_{\odot} M_{\odot}^{-1}$), $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ has a power-law shape with a slope of $\approx 0.4 - 0.6$ [59, 60, 147, 261]. Some recent work identified a sharp drop toward high L_{SX} ($\gtrsim 1 L_{\odot} M_{\odot}^{-1}$; e.g., [247, 248, 288]). The break at high L_{SX} is physically expected, because otherwise the average X-ray luminosity ($\overline{L_{\text{X}}}$), which is the integral of $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z) \times M_* \times L_{\text{SX}}$, would diverge.

In this work, we derive $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ utilizing the data from CANDELS survey [65, 66], in particular the GOODS-South and GOODS-North fields (hereafter GOODS-S and GOODS-N), as well as the data from COSMOS survey [211], in particular the UltraVISTA field [212]. All these fields have superb multiwavelength coverage. The UV-to-mid-IR (MIR) data allow accurate photometric redshift and M_* measurements [71, 214]. All fields have *Chandra* X-ray observations, allowing us to derive L_{X} for the AGNs. Thanks to the excellent positional accuracy of *Chandra* ($\approx 0.5''$), the matching between X-ray sources and optical/near-IR (NIR) sources is highly reliable, with typical false matching rate less than a few percent [67, 241]. GOODS-S and GOODS-N are small fields ($\approx 170 \text{ arcmin}^2$) but are covered by the deepest X-ray surveys, the 7 Ms *Chandra* Deep Field-South and 2 Ms *Chandra* Deep Field-North (CDF-S and CDF-N; [67, 241, 289]). These two fields provide constraints on $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ at low L_{SX} . COSMOS, covered by the COSMOS-

Legacy survey, is a much larger field ($\approx 1.4 \text{ deg}^2$ for the utilized UltraVISTA region) than GOODS-S and GOODS-N, although the X-ray data are much shallower ($\approx 160 \text{ ks}$; see [217]). COSMOS generally constrains $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ at higher L_{SX} than GOODS-S and GOODS-N. Following [288], we also constrain $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ utilizing the X-ray luminosity function (XLF) and stellar mass function (SMF) from the literature. This technique can constrain $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ for rare high- L_X AGNs which are included in the XLF.

We do not calculate $\overline{\text{BHAR}}(M_*, z)$ via averaging the instantaneous BHAR from samples of galaxies in surveys [206]. Survey data often have small-area effects; e.g., accretion power from rare luminous AGNs is not included due to the limited size of the survey area, and this effect is difficult to determine when performing sample averaging of BHAR. Also, it is challenging to combine different surveys when directly averaging the instantaneous BHAR, because different X-ray data have large differences in sensitivity. However, these issues can be properly considered when modeling $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ [59, 288].

This paper is structured as follows. In §4.2, we describe the survey data, SMF, and XLF. We detail our analyses and results in §4.3. In §4.4, we discuss the implications of our measurements, and summarize our work in §4.5.

Throughout this paper, we assume a cosmology with $H_0 = 70 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$, $\Omega_M = 0.3$, and $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.7$, and a Chabrier initial mass function [68]. Quoted uncertainties are at the 1σ (68%) confidence level, unless otherwise stated. We express L_{SX} in units of $L_\odot M_\odot^{-1}$, and M_* (M_{BH}) in units of M_\odot , unless otherwise stated. L_X indicates AGN intrinsic X-ray luminosity at rest-frame 2–10 keV and is in units of erg s^{-1} .

4.2 Data and Sample

4.2.1 Multiwavelength Surveys

In this work, we compile observational data from the GOODS-S, GOODS-N, and COSMOS surveys.

4.2.1.1 GOODS-S and GOODS-N

We include all 34,779 and 34,651 galaxies in the GOODS-S and GOODS-N catalogs, respectively [65, 66, 69]. In the catalogs, 4,314 and 4,660 sources have $\log M_\star > 9.5$ (our $\log M_\star$ threshold; see §4.3.2.2). The basic information for these two fields is summarized in Tab. 4.1. These two catalogs are based on H -band detections with 3σ limiting magnitude of $H \approx 28$. The solid angle is ≈ 170 arcmin² for both the GOODS-S and GOODS-N surveys. We utilize both fields to minimize the effects of cosmic variance.

We adopt the galaxies' M_\star and redshift from [71] and Barro et al. (in prep.), respectively, for GOODS-S and GOODS-N sources. The M_\star and redshift measurements in both fields are based on spectral energy distribution (SED) fitting of broad-band photometry ranging from the U band to *Spitzer*/IRAC bands (i.e., 3.6, 4.5, 5.8, 8.0 μm). In both surveys, the M_\star estimations were performed by several independent teams, some of whom used galaxy templates with nebular emission. The nebular emission is important at high redshift ($z \gtrsim 2$), where some strong emission lines enter the wavelength ranges of the NIR bands. Since this work includes redshifts up to $z = 4$, we adopt the median M_\star of teams using templates with nebular emission; these median M_\star values are available in the catalogs of [71] and Barro et al. (in prep.). The SED-based M_\star measurements have typical uncertainties of $\lesssim 0.3$ dex [71]. The redshifts are taken from spectroscopic measurements when available; otherwise, they are high-quality photometric redshifts. These photometric redshifts in GOODS-S and GOODS-N have median uncertainties $[|z_{\text{phot}} - z_{\text{spec}}|/(1 + z_{\text{spec}})]$ of 0.02 and 0.004, respectively, and outlier fractions $[|z_{\text{phot}} - z_{\text{spec}}|/(1 + z_{\text{spec}}) > 0.15]$ of 9% and 5%, respectively. The M_\star as a function of redshift is shown in Fig. 4.1 (top and middle).

We also obtain the SED-based SFR values from [71] and Barro et al. (in prep.) to classify galaxies as star-forming or quiescent. The SFRs from SED fitting have typical uncertainties of ≈ 0.5 dex (see, e.g., §2.2 of [206]). Although the errors are relatively large, they are sufficient for our purpose (star-forming vs. quiescent classification; [248]). We adopt a SFR threshold that is 1.3 dex below the star-forming main sequence (Eq. 1 in [248]). If a galaxy has SFR above (below) this threshold, we classify it as star-forming (quiescent). We do not classify galaxies hosting a BL AGN, as the total UV flux of these galaxies might have a significant contribution from the AGN thereby biasing the SED-based SFRs.

Name	Area (deg ²)	Galaxies	X-ray Depth	AGNs
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
GOODS-S	0.05	4,314	7 Ms	264
GOODS-N	0.05	4,660	2 Ms	195
COSMOS	1.38	141,004	160 ks	1,448

Table 4.1: Summary of Survey Data. (1) Field name. (2) Area of the field in units of deg². (3) Number of galaxies above $\log M_\star = 9.5$. (4) *Chandra* effective exposure time. (5) Number of AGNs with $\log L_{\text{SX}} > -2$.

We cross-correlate these galaxies with the X-ray sources in the CDF-S [67] and CDF-N [241] surveys using the method described in [206]. CDF-S and CDF-N fully cover GOODS-S and GOODS-N, respectively. They are the deepest X-ray surveys with 7 Ms and 2 Ms *Chandra* observations, respectively. We only use hard-band (observed-frame 2–7 keV) detected sources, taking advantage of the fact that the hard band is less affected by obscuration than the soft band (observed-frame 0.5–2 keV). Soft-band detections are biased to less-obscured sources, and it is difficult to account for this bias with our methodology (see §4.3.1.1). Also, for a source detected in the soft band but not in the hard band, it is not feasible to obtain their absorption-corrected L_X which is necessary in our analyses (§4.3.1.1).

We obtain hard-band fluxes from [67, 241] and convert them to L_X assuming a power-law spectral shape with a photon index of $\Gamma = 1.6$ and that absorption only has minor effects on the observed hard-band flux [206, 243]. We justify these assumptions in §4.3.5.1 and discuss the contamination from X-ray binaries (XRBs) in §4.3.5.2. We adopt $\Gamma = 1.6$ instead of $\Gamma = 1.8$ – 1.9 , mainly because the former can produce L_X values that agree better with those from X-ray spectral fitting (see §4.3.5.1 for more details). Although the observed-frame soft band corresponds to rest-frame energies above 2 keV at $z > 3$, we do not use the soft-band data for high- z sources, as obscuration generally becomes stronger toward high redshift, and the soft band can still be affected by obscuration at high redshift [243, 290]. Fig. 4.2 displays the sky coverages as a function of hard-band flux for GOODS-S and GOODS-N, and Fig. 4.3 shows L_X and L_{SX} as functions of redshift for X-ray detected sources in these two fields. There are 264 and 195 X-ray AGNs with $\log L_{\text{SX}} > -2$ (our L_{SX} cut; see §4.3.2.3) in GOODS-S and GOODS-N, respectively.

Figure 4.1: M_{\star} as a function of redshift for GOODS-S (top), GOODS-N (middle), and COSMOS (bottom). The total numbers of galaxies in these three fields are 34,779, 34,651, and 520,778, respectively. The small blue points indicate galaxies; the larger points indicate X-ray-detected sources. The dashed horizontal line indicates our M_{\star} threshold (see §4.3.2.2).

Figure 4.2: GOODS-S, GOODS-N, and COSMOS sky coverages as functions of hard-band (2–7 keV) X-ray flux. Different colors indicate different surveys. GOODS-S and GOODS-N are quite deep but cover small areas; COSMOS covers a larger area but is shallower than GOODS-S and GOODS-N.

4.2.1.2 COSMOS

We adopt the COSMOS2015 galaxy catalog for the COSMOS field [214]; the basic information for this field is summarized in Tab. 4.1. We only use sources within both the COSMOS and UltraVISTA regions, after removing the masked objects (1.38 deg²; see Fig. 1 and Tab. 7 in [214]). The UltraVISTA region has deep NIR observations that are critical in SED fitting. The COSMOS2015 catalog includes sources detected in a χ^2 sum of $zYJHK_s$ images (see [291] for this detection technique). The 3σ limiting magnitude is $K_S \approx 24$. We note that this limiting magnitude is only a rough estimation of the depth of the K_S imaging data. The COSMOS2015 catalog is actually deeper than $K_S \approx 24$ due to the multiwavelength-based detection method used. In fact, $\approx 50\%$ of sources are fainter than $K_S \approx 24$. The multiwavelength photometric data in the COSMOS2015 catalog include 18 broad bands from *GALEX* NUV to *Spitzer*/IRAC, 12 medium optical bands, and

Figure 4.3: Top panel: L_X vs. z for the X-ray-detected sources in our sample. Different colors indicate sources from different surveys. The black solid curve indicates the XLF knee luminosity from [10], who derived the knee luminosities for obscured and unobscured populations, respectively. Here, we adopt the values for the obscured AGNs, which are the majority population. The GOODS-S and GOODS-N sources are generally less luminous than COSMOS sources at a given redshift. Bottom panel: L_{SX} vs. z . The black solid curve represents the L_{SX} for X-ray binaries of galaxies on the star-forming main sequence (see §4.3.5.2). The black dashed horizontal line indicates our L_{SX} cut, i.e., $10^{-2} L_\odot M_\odot^{-1}$ (see 4.3.2.3).

2 narrow optical bands (see Tab. 1 in [214]).

The refined catalog consists of 520,778 galaxies with M_\star and photometric-redshift measurements, among which 141,004 sources have $\log M_\star > 9.5$. Compared with the spectroscopic redshifts available [213], the photometric redshifts have a median uncertainty of 0.006 and an outlier fraction of 3%, thanks to the good

coverage of the multiwavelength observations.¹ Fig. 4.1 (bottom) shows M_\star vs. z for these sources. We also adopt the SED-based SFR measurements and perform star-forming vs. quiescent classifications as in §4.2.1.1.

[218] have matched these sources with the COSMOS-Legacy X-ray survey, which has 160 ks *Chandra* effective exposure time [217]. We utilize hard-band flux to derive L_X for hard-band detected sources as in §4.2.1.1. The sky coverage as a function of hard-band flux is shown in Fig. 4.2. COSMOS covers an area ≈ 30 times larger than GOODS-S/GOODS-N but is substantially shallower. The L_X and L_{SX} as functions of redshift are presented in Fig. 4.3. There are 1,448 X-ray AGNs with $\log L_{SX} > -2$ (see §4.3.2.3).

The ultra-deep fields of GOODS-S and GOODS-N and the medium-deep field COSMOS are complementary in sampling a wide range of L_X . At a given redshift, the most luminous COSMOS sources often have L_X a few times higher than the knee luminosity; the faintest GOODS sources have $L_X \approx 2$ decades below the knee luminosity. This wide range of sampled L_X typically includes $\gtrsim 70\%$ of the total L_X from the integral of the XLF. In this sense, our survey data sample contains most of cosmic accretion power.

4.2.1.3 Broad-Line AGNs

The photometric redshifts and M_\star in the survey catalogs (§4.2.1) are obtained from SED fitting with galaxy templates. This is appropriate for normal galaxies and non-BL AGNs where rest-frame UV to NIR SEDs are dominated by stellar light (see, e.g., [79, 80]; §2.2 of [206]). However, BL AGNs can be responsible for a large fraction of the total UV-to-NIR SED. When they are present, AGN components should be considered properly in SED fitting, and thus the redshift and M_\star measurements in the survey catalogs may not be reliable. There are 359 BL AGNs in our survey data identified from spectroscopic observations (GOODS-S: 22 sources from [75]; GOODS-N: 15 sources from [292]; COSMOS: 322 sources from [218]). These observations provide reliable spectroscopic redshifts for these BL AGNs.

¹ [214] derived M_\star using the photometric redshifts. Thus, we do not adopt the spectroscopic redshifts for these objects even when these are available. Since their photometric redshifts agree well with the spectroscopic redshifts, the adoption of the former instead of the latter should not affect our conclusions materially.

Additional BL AGNs might be missed due to the lack of full spectroscopic coverage. Most of the missed BL AGNs should be in COSMOS due to its relatively large area. Now we estimate the number of possibly missed BL AGNs for COSMOS. For the ≈ 710 X-ray AGNs with high-quality spectra [218], we find that BL AGNs are generally brighter and bluer than non-BL AGNs, and these two populations are separated in the color-magnitude diagram by $B - r = 0.8$ and $r = 24$ (observed AB magnitude; from [214]). Applying this criterion ($B - r < 0.8$ and $r < 24$) to the ≈ 740 X-ray sources without high-quality spectra, we estimate that the missed BL AGN number in COSMOS is ≈ 70 , significantly smaller than the number of spectroscopically identified BL AGNs (322). We caution that there might be additional BL AGNs not satisfying the empirical criterion. However, those sources are faint ($r \geq 24$) and/or red ($B - r \geq 0.8$), and their AGN SED components are less likely to dominate over the host-galaxy components. Therefore, the missed BL AGNs in our sample should not affect our analyses significantly.

To obtain reliable M_\star for BL AGNs, we perform SED decomposition utilizing a minimum- χ^2 method implemented in CIGALE [225,226].² CIGALE can perform SED fitting for a source based on a set of photometric data at a given redshift, and output physical parameters like M_\star and SFR. We use the photometric data from the survey catalogs (§4.2.1) and redshifts from spectroscopic observations. The AGN model in [293] is implemented in CIGALE, and we follow the settings for the typical BL AGN template in Tab. 1 of [81]. We allow $frac_{AGN} = 0-1$ with a step of 0.05, where $frac_{AGN}$ is the AGN fractional contribution to the total IR luminosity. For galaxy components, we assume a Chabrier initial mass function (IMF; [68]), which is also adopted to measure M_\star for galaxies in the survey data. We adopt a τ model of star formation history (SFH) and allow values for $\log(\tau/\text{yr})$ ranging from 8 to 10.5 with a step size of 0.5 dex. The stellar templates are from the model of [76]. We allow several possible values of metallicity ($Z = 0.0001, 0.0004, 0.004, 0.008, 0.02, 0.05$, where Z is the mass fraction of metals). We adopt the Calzetti extinction law [77] allowing $E(B - V)$ to vary from 0.0–1.0 with a step of 0.1. CIGALE also includes nebular and dust emission [225,227]. The above settings for galaxy SED is similar to those used to derive photometric redshifts and M_\star in the survey catalogs ([71,214]; Barro et al. in prep.).

Fig. 4.4 displays the SED fitting for two typical BL AGNs. Although the AGN

²<http://cigale.lam.fr/>

component can be dominant over the galaxy component at rest-frame UV-to-optical wavelengths, the galaxy component often contributes significantly to the total SED at NIR wavelengths ($\approx 1 \mu\text{m}$, rest-frame). This effect arises because emission from the AGN accretion disk and the torus are both relatively weak in the NIR, but starlight often peaks in the NIR (see, e.g., Fig. 1 of [294]). The relatively high contrast of galaxy/AGN at NIR wavelengths ensures reliable M_\star measurements, since NIR flux is critical in assessing M_\star [81, 294].

We compare our updated M_\star values with those from the survey catalogs in Fig. 4.5. Here, we only compare BL AGNs having spectroscopic redshifts consistent with the redshifts from the catalogs [$|\Delta z|/(1 + z_{\text{spec}}) < 0.15$; see Footnote 1]. The systematics between these two measurements are low with the median of $\Delta \log M_\star$ being 0.01 dex. The scatter (median of $|\Delta \log M_\star|$) is 0.26. The two measurements agree within 0.5 dex for the majority (73%) of sources. From Fig. 4.5, there is a group of sources with our M_\star values being significantly lower than the corresponding catalog M_\star values. These sources tend to be X-ray luminous ($\log L_X \gtrsim 44$; see Fig. 4.5), and their AGN SED components are comparable to or even dominant over their galaxy components in the NIR. Thus, the catalog measurements, which only utilize galaxy templates, significantly overestimate their M_\star . There are also some sources for which our M_\star measurements are ≈ 0.5 dex higher than the catalog measurements. The reason is likely that the catalog measurements underestimate the stellar age, resulting in small mass-to-light ratio. This is because when using galaxy templates only, the photometric data require young stellar age to account for the UV flux generated by the BL AGN.

Throughout the paper, for BL AGNs, we adopt the M_\star values derived from our AGN-galaxy SED decomposition rather than the catalog values.

We do not recalculate M_\star for non-BL AGNs. However, these sources might have strong AGN emission in the rest-frame mid-IR, contributing significantly to the observed SED, especially in the IRAC bands. To evaluate this effect, we compare our adopted M_\star values for non-BL AGNs in COSMOS with those from [285], who included AGN components in SED fitting. The two sets of M_\star agree well: the offset and scatter are 0.08 dex and 0.11 dex, respectively. We thus conclude that the presence of non-BL AGNs does not bias our adopted M_\star measurements.

Figure 4.4: Two examples of our SED decomposition for BL AGNs. The black data points are observed photometry, and the black line indicates our best-fit SED model. The blue and orange lines represent the AGN and galaxy components, respectively. At rest-frame $\approx 1 \mu\text{m}$, the galaxy component often contributes significantly to the total SED.

4.2.2 Stellar Mass Function and X-ray Luminosity Function

Our methodology also utilizes the SMF and XLF as inputs, which provide additional constraints to $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ besides the GOODS-S/GOODS-N/COSMOS data set (see §4.3.1.2), especially for luminous AGNs (see §4.3.1.2). We adopt the SMF from [31]. Their SMF is based on a galaxy evolution model that considers both star formation and mergers and is constrained by the observed SMF, specific SFRs

Figure 4.5: Comparison between the M_\star measurements from our SED fitting (with both BL AGN and galaxy templates) and those from the catalogs (with only galaxy templates; see §4.2.1). Different colors indicate AGNs in different L_X regimes. The black solid line indicates the 1:1 relation between the two M_\star measurements; the dashed lines indicate 0.5 dex offsets. A group of sources have our M_\star measurements significantly lower than the catalog values. These sources tend to be luminous AGNs with $\log L_X \gtrsim 44$.

($\text{sSFR} = \text{SFR}/M_\star$), and ρ_{SFR} . The SMF model covers ranges of $\log M_\star = 7\text{--}12$ and $z = 0\text{--}8$. To evaluate the quality of this SMF, we compare it with the observational results of [216] (see Fig. 3 in [31] for comparison with some previous observations). Fig. 4.6 displays the results. The SMF from the [31] model agrees well with the observed SMF values even at high redshift ($z \approx 4$).

We adopt the binned soft-band XLF values of [13] (see their Fig. 10). Fig. 4.7 compares the binned rest-frame 2–10 keV XLF derived from soft-band and hard-band observations.³ We choose the soft-band XLF instead of the hard-band XLF because the former extends to extremely high luminosity ($\log L_X \gtrsim 46$), largely due to the wide-field surveys of *ROSAT*. The soft-band XLF is already corrected for

³In [13], the hard-band data include various survey results above 2 keV (see their Tab. 1 for details).

Figure 4.6: Stellar mass function. The solid curves indicate the SMF model from [31]. The data points are the observational results of [216]. Different colors indicate different redshifts. For display purposes only, the SMF (both the curve and data points) for a given redshift bin is shifted downward by 0.2 dex relative to the next lower redshift bin; the SMF for the lowest redshift bin is not shifted. The SMF model agrees well with the observations.

obscuration and is thus consistent with the hard-band XLF when available (see Fig. 4.7). In practice, adopting the hard-band XLF would only have minor effects on our results (§4.3.4). We have also compared the XLFs from [13] with those from [10], and found they agree well. Since [13] extend to higher L_X than [10], we adopt the XLF results from [13]. The XLF data points in [13] are derived from all X-ray detected sources with $\log L_X \gtrsim 42$, and thus components of XRBs might become important at the low-luminosity end. To avoid this XRB contamination, we only adopt the XLF at $\log L_X > 43$. Also, we do not probe the low- L_{SX} regime

Figure 4.7: X-ray luminosity function. The circles and squares indicate the binned XLF values derived from the soft band and hard band, respectively, in [13]. The hard-band data are shifted slightly toward the right for display purposes only. The solid curves are the best-fit XLF model in [13]. The soft-band XLF agrees well with the hard-band XLF. Different colors indicate different redshifts. For display purposes only, the XLF (both the curve and data points) for a given redshift bin is shifted upward by 0.3 dex relative to the next lower redshift bin; the XLF for the lowest redshift bin is not shifted. The vertical dashed solid line indicates our L_X cut ($\log L_X = 43$) for the XLF.

($\log L_{SX} < -2$; see §4.3.2.3) that could significantly contribute to the XLF at $\log L_X < 43$. For example, at $\log L_X = 42-42.5$, 32% of the X-ray sources in our sample have $\log L_{SX} < -2$. At $\log L_X < 43$, our $P(L_{SX}|M_*, z)$ are constrained by the survey data (see §4.2.1) which have ≈ 420 X-ray AGNs with $\log L_X < 43$.

4.2.3 Bolometric Correction

To obtain $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ from the $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$, we require a bolometric correction ($k_{\text{bol}} = L_{\text{bol}}/L_X$) which is a function of AGN luminosity (e.g. [108, 245, 246]; see §4.3.4 for $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ calculation). Our k_{bol} is based on the results of [246], which are derived from the multiwavelength observations of X-ray selected AGNs. We did not adopt the k_{bol} from [108], because they included the dust-reprocessed IR emission that is not directly produced by AGN accretion power. This inclusion results in a fraction of the accretion-powered radiation being accounted for twice. Thus, their k_{bol} serves as an empirical bolometric correction but is an overestimation for our purpose, i.e., to infer the accretion power of the SMBH.

[246] modeled k_{bol} as polynomials of AGN L_{bol} for BL ($k_{\text{bol, BL}}$) and non-BL AGNs ($k_{\text{bol, nBL}}$), respectively (see their Tab. 2). We present their $k_{\text{bol, BL}}$ and $k_{\text{bol, nBL}}$ as a function of L_X in Fig. 4.8 (dashed curves). Both $k_{\text{bol, BL}}$ and $k_{\text{bol, nBL}}$ are positively dependent on L_X . The differences between $k_{\text{bol, BL}}$ and $k_{\text{bol, nBL}}$ are small ($\lesssim 0.1$ dex), consistent with the standard unified AGN model. The BL AGNs are generally more luminous than the non-BL AGNs in [246]. Denoting the overlapping L_X range of the BL and non-BL as $L_{X,1} - L_{X,2}$, we adopt $k_{\text{bol, nBL}}$ if $L_X < L_{X,1}$ and $k_{\text{bol, BL}}$ if $L_X > L_{X,2}$. For $L_{X,1} \leq L_X \leq L_{X,2}$, we adopt k_{bol} as

$$k_{\text{bol}} = k_{\text{bol, BL}} \frac{L_X - L_{X,1}}{L_{X,2} - L_{X,1}} + k_{\text{bol, nBL}} \frac{L_{X,2} - L_X}{L_{X,2} - L_{X,1}}. \quad (4.1)$$

This linear interpolation produces a smooth k_{bol} as a function of L_X (see Fig. 4.8). $k_{\text{bol, BL}}$ diverges quickly toward high L_X due to the polynomial functional form of k_{bol} that [246] assumed. To avoid this divergence, we set an upper limit of 100 for the adopted k_{bol} , which is about the maximum value of k_{bol} reported in the literature [105, 108].

Some studies suggest that k_{bol} might also be related to λ_{Edd} (e.g., [104]; but also see [295]). While it is still under investigation whether k_{bol} is more fundamentally related to AGN luminosity or λ_{Edd} , we adopt the $k_{\text{bol}} - L_X$ relation because we are not able to obtain λ_{Edd} accurately. We discuss the effects of a $k_{\text{bol}} - \lambda_{\text{Edd}}$ relation in §4.3.4.1.

Figure 4.8: Bolometric correction as a function of X-ray luminosity. The black solid line indicates the k_{bol} adopted in this work. The blue and orange dashed lines indicate k_{bol} for BL and non-BL AGNs, respectively, in [246]. k_{bol} generally increases toward high L_X .

4.3 Data Analyses

We derive $\overline{\text{BHAR}}(M_*, z)$ from $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ (§4.3.4), which is constrained utilizing maximum-likelihood fitting (§4.3.3). The fitting requires likelihood functions, and our likelihood functions are based on the survey data (§4.3.1.1) as well as the SMF and XLF (§4.3.1.2). The survey data mostly constrain $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ for low-to-moderate luminosity AGNs, while the SMF and XLF constrain $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ for luminous AGNs.

4.3.1 Likelihood Functions

4.3.1.1 The Likelihood Function of Survey Data

With the survey data providing L_X , M_* , and z for individual sources (§4.2), we can derive the corresponding likelihood function, which quantifies how well the input

$P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ model matches the survey data. The methodology is detailed in §6.1 of [59]; below we briefly summarize this technique.

For each survey in §4.2.1, we denote the number of detected X-ray AGNs as N_{AGN} , where we only consider X-ray sources with $\log L_{\text{SX}} > -2$ as AGNs (see §4.3.2.3). The log-likelihood function for this survey can be derived from the unbinned Poisson probability [296] as

$$\ln L = -N_{\text{mdl}} + \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{AGN}}} \ln P(L_{\text{SX},i}|M_{*,i}, z_i), \quad (4.2)$$

where N_{mdl} is the expected number of X-ray detected AGNs from the input $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ model. In the survey area, there are N_{gal} galaxies within the redshift range, each with M_* and redshift measurements. The quantity N_{mdl} can be calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} N_{\text{mdl}} &= \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{gal}}} \int_{-2}^{\infty} P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_{*,i}, z_i) p_{\text{det}}(L_X, z_i) d \log L_{\text{SX}} \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{gal}}} \int_{-2}^{\infty} P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_{*,i}, z_i) p_{\text{det}}(L_{\text{SX}} M_{*,i}, z_i) d \log L_{\text{SX}}, \end{aligned} \quad (4.3)$$

where p_{det} , as a function of L_X and z , is the correction factor for survey sensitivity. The integral lower limit (-2) is the lowest L_{SX} probed in this work, and we discuss the effects of this L_{SX} cut in §4.3.2.3. $p_{\text{det}}(L_X, z)$ is defined as

$$p_{\text{det}}(L_X, z) = \frac{A[f(L_X, z)]}{A_{\text{tot}}}, \quad (4.4)$$

where $f(L_X, z)$ is the expected X-ray flux in the detection band for a source with L_X at redshift z ; $A[f(L_X, z)]$ is the sky coverage of the survey sensitive to the flux $f(L_X, z)$ (Fig. 4.2); A_{tot} is the total survey area.

We calculate the log-likelihood for each survey (GOODS-S, GOODS-N, and COSMOS; see §4.2.1) independently according to Eq. 4.2, and combine them as

$$\ln L_{\text{surv}} = \ln L_{\text{GOODS-S}} + \ln L_{\text{GOODS-N}} + \ln L_{\text{COSMOS}}. \quad (4.5)$$

Since our data only include 0.05–1.4 deg² surveys, most of our X-ray selected

sources are low-to-moderate luminosity AGNs ($\log L_X \lesssim 44.5$; see Fig. 4.3), and the number of luminous AGNs is limited. However, this small-area effect does not introduce biases for these luminous AGNs, because the sizes of the survey areas are already properly considered in the likelihood function through the term “ N_{mdl} ” (see Eq. 4.3). Moreover, $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_\star, z)$ for luminous AGNs is constrained by our SMF-XLF methodology in §4.3.1.2.

4.3.1.2 The Likelihood Function of SMF and XLF

Besides the constraints from the survey data, we can also constrain $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_\star, z)$ utilizing the SMF and XLF. By definition, the SMF provides the comoving number density of galaxies at given M_\star and z . Thus, we can convolve the SMF with $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_\star, z)$ at a given redshift to obtain the comoving number density of AGNs at given L_X and z (i.e., the XLF),

$$\begin{aligned}\phi_L(L_X|z) &= \int_{9.5}^{12} P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_\star, z)\phi_M(M_\star|z)d\log M_\star \\ &= \int_{9.5}^{12} P(L_X/M_\star|M_\star, z)\phi_M(M_\star|z)d\log M_\star,\end{aligned}\tag{4.6}$$

where ϕ_L and ϕ_M are the XLF and SMF, respectively. Both ϕ_L and ϕ_M are in units of $\text{Mpc}^{-3} \text{dex}^{-1}$. The integral range ($\log M_\star = 9.5\text{--}12$) corresponds to the M_\star regime probed in our analyses, and we discuss the effects of this M_\star cut in §4.3.2.2.

To evaluate quantitatively how well a model $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_\star, z)$ meets the constraints from the SMF and XLF (§4.2.2), we compare N_{mdl} and the observed numbers of X-ray sources (N_{obs}) for each ϕ_L bin in [13]. For any given model of $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_\star, z)$, we can obtain the corresponding model XLF ($\phi_{L,\text{mdl}}$) via Eq. 4.6. We can convert $\phi_{L,\text{mdl}}$ to N_{mdl} as

$$N_{\text{mdl}} = \phi_{L,\text{mdl}} \frac{N_{\text{obs}}}{\phi_{L,\text{obs}}},\tag{4.7}$$

where $N_{\text{obs}}/\phi_{L,\text{obs}}$ is the conversion factor between the number of sampled X-ray sources and the XLF in [13]. $N_{\text{obs}}/\phi_{L,\text{obs}}$ considers many factors such as X-ray survey area and sensitivity and is provided by Y. Ueda (2017, private communication).

We can then obtain the log-likelihood function for the SMF and XLF as

$$\ln L_{\text{XLF}} = \sum_{i=1}^n \ln P(N_{\text{obs},i} | \lambda = N_{\text{mdl},i}), \quad (4.8)$$

where n is the total number of L_X and redshift bins available for the XLF, and $P(N_{\text{obs},i} | \lambda = N_{\text{mdl},i})$ is the Poisson probability of $N_{\text{obs},i}$ events for the rate parameter $\lambda = N_{\text{mdl},i}$.

Since we apply an L_X cut to the XLF ($\log L_X > 43$; see §4.2.2), the SMF-XLF method does not constrain $P(L_{\text{SX}} | M_*, z)$ for low-luminosity AGNs. In fact, this method is also not very effective when assessing moderate-luminosity AGNs with $43 < \log L_X \lesssim 44$. For example, for an AGN with $\log L_X \approx 43.5$, its host galaxy can be either a moderate- M_* galaxy with relatively high L_{SX} (e.g., $\log M_* \approx 10$ and $\log L_{\text{SX}} \approx 0$) or a high- M_* galaxy with low L_{SX} (e.g., $\log M_* \approx 11$ and $\log L_{\text{SX}} \approx -1$). The SMF-XLF method cannot determine which case is more probable, although it does require that the sum of the contributions from all galaxies must match the AGN number density. However, this degeneracy is weak in the high- L_X regime. For example, for an AGN with $\log L_X \approx 45$, its host galaxy is likely massive ($\log M_* \gtrsim 11$) with moderate-to-high L_{SX} ($-0.5 \lesssim \log L_{\text{SX}} \lesssim 0.5$); otherwise, the corresponding L_{SX} would be too high and far beyond the high- L_{SX} cutoff ($\log L_{\text{SX}} \approx 0$; see, e.g. [247, 248, 288]). This is the reason why the SMF-XLF method is most effective for luminous AGNs.

4.3.2 Cuts in Parameter Space

4.3.2.1 Redshift Cuts

We limit our study to the redshift range of $z = 0.4$ – 4 . The primary reason for this is that we have a limited number of X-ray AGNs outside this redshift range. Quantitatively, the number of AGNs with $z < 0.4$ or $z > 4$ is 89 which accounts for only $\approx 5\%$ of the whole AGN sample.

4.3.2.2 M_* Cuts

In this work, we only study galaxies having $\log M_* = 9.5$ – 12 . The reason for the lower cut of M_* is that X-ray AGNs are rarely detected in low- M_* galaxies (see

Fig. 4.1); in our sample (§4.2.1), only $\approx 5\%$ of X-ray AGNs are detected with $\log M_\star < 9.5$. The low detection rate of X-ray AGNs for the low- M_\star systems makes it challenging to constrain effectively $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_\star, z)$ for these sources. We investigate galaxies with M_\star up to $\log M_\star = 12$. In our sample, there are ≈ 190 galaxies with $\log M_\star = 11.5\text{--}12$ but only 7 galaxies above $\log M_\star = 12$.

These M_\star cuts have little effect on our methods in §4.3.1.2, because the XLF is dominated by AGNs hosted in galaxies with $\log M_\star = 9.5\text{--}12$. At $\log L_X = 43\text{--}43.5$ (the lowest-luminosity bin we adopt for the XLF; see §4.2.2), almost all (98%) AGN-host galaxies have $\log M_\star = 9.5\text{--}12$ in our sample, and the fraction is even larger toward higher luminosities.

4.3.2.3 L_{SX} Cut

We cannot probe low L_{SX} values at high redshift due to survey sensitivity. For example, we only have two sources with $\log L_{\text{SX}} < -2$ at $z > 2$. Also, at low L_{SX} , it is difficult to disentangle X-ray emission from AGNs and XRBs (see §4.3.5.2). We thus limit our investigation to $\log L_{\text{SX}} \geq -2$.

This L_{SX} cut has little effect on our SMF-XLF method (§4.3.1.2), since galaxies with $\log L_{\text{SX}} < -2$ have almost no contribution to the XLF above $\log L_X = 43$ (the lowest L_X we adopt for the XLF; see §4.2.2). For example, among the $\approx 1,500$ AGNs with $\log L_X \geq 43$ in our sample, only one source has $\log L_{\text{SX}} < -2$.

Now we demonstrate that SMBH accretion below $\log L_{\text{SX}} = -2$ does not contribute significantly to the growth of SMBHs over cosmic history. The Eddington ratio is defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \lambda_{\text{Edd}} &= \frac{L_{\text{bol}}}{L_{\text{Edd}}} \\
 &= \frac{\epsilon \text{BHAR} c^2}{1.3 \times 10^{38} \text{ erg s}^{-1} M_{\text{BH}} M_\odot^{-1}} \\
 &= \frac{M_\odot c^2}{1.3 \times 10^{39} \text{ erg s}^{-1}} \frac{\text{BHAR} \epsilon_{0.1}}{M_{\text{BH}}} \\
 &= 0.044 \text{ Gyr} \frac{\text{BHAR} \epsilon_{0.1}}{M_{\text{BH}}},
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.9}$$

where c is the speed of light, ϵ is radiation efficiency, and $\epsilon_{0.1} = \epsilon/0.1$. λ_{Edd} can

also be related to L_{SX} as

$$\begin{aligned}
\lambda_{\text{Edd}} &= \frac{L_{\text{bol}}}{L_{\text{Edd}}} \\
&= \frac{k_{\text{bol}} L_{\text{X}}}{3.2 \times 10^4 L_{\odot} M_{\text{BH}} M_{\odot}^{-1}} \\
&= \frac{10 \times 5000}{3.2 \times 10^4} \frac{L_{\text{X}} L_{\odot}^{-1}}{M_{\star} M_{\odot}^{-1}} \frac{k_{\text{bol}}}{10} \frac{M_{\star}}{5000 M_{\text{BH}}} \\
&= 1.6 L_{\text{SX}} k_{10} m_5,
\end{aligned} \tag{4.10}$$

where $k_{10} = k_{\text{bol}}/10$ and $m_5 = M_{\star}/(5000 M_{\text{BH}})$. From Eqs. 4.9 and 4.10, we can obtain the e -folding timescale of SMBH growth as

$$t_e = \frac{M_{\text{BH}}}{\text{BHAR}} = 0.028 \text{ Gyr} \frac{\epsilon_{0.1}}{L_{\text{SX}} k_{10} m_5}. \tag{4.11}$$

$\log L_{\text{SX}} < -2$ corresponds to $\log L_{\text{X}} \lesssim 43.5$ with $k_{10} \approx 1$ (see Fig. 4.8). Assuming the average L_{SX} for this low- L_{SX} ($\log L_{\text{SX}} < -2$) accretion is $\approx 10^{-2.5}$ and $\epsilon_{0.1} \approx 1$, then $t_e \approx 9 m_5^{-1}$ Gyr. From our results in Sec. 4.4.3, m_5 ranges from ≈ 0.1 to 1 up to at least $z \approx 2$. Thus, the growth time for low- L_{SX} accretion should be $t_e \approx 9\text{--}90$ Gyr comparable to or longer than the Hubble time. Therefore, the accretion with $\log L_{\text{SX}} < -2$ is unlikely important in our overall understanding of SMBH growth.

The above argument assumes $\epsilon \approx 0.1$, which is typical for a cold accretion disk [297, 298]. For hot accretion flows, ϵ can be much lower ($\epsilon \lesssim 0.01$). However, such low ϵ only arises when the accretion rate is low, i.e.,

$$\frac{0.1 \text{BHAR} c^2}{L_{\text{Edd}}} \lesssim 10^{-3}, \tag{4.12}$$

(see Fig. 2 of [142]). Under this condition, the SMBH growth timescale is

$$\begin{aligned}
t_e &= \frac{M_{\text{BH}}}{\overline{\text{BHAR}}} \\
&= \frac{L_{\text{Edd}}}{1.3 \times 10^{38} \overline{\text{BHAR}} \text{ erg s}^{-1} M_{\odot}^{-1}} \\
&= \frac{M_{\odot} c^2}{1.3 \times 10^{39} \text{ erg s}^{-1}} \frac{L_{\text{Edd}}}{0.1 \overline{\text{BHAR}} c^2} \\
&\gtrsim \frac{M_{\odot} c^2}{1.3 \times 10^{39} \text{ erg s}^{-1}} \times 10^3 \\
&\approx 44 \text{ Gyr},
\end{aligned} \tag{4.13}$$

which is also longer than Hubble time. Therefore, low- ϵ accretion states should not contribute significantly to the overall SMBH growth across cosmic history.

Our argument above shows that low- L_{SX} accretion cannot increase M_{BH} effectively over cosmic history. However, low- L_{SX} accretion might still contribute more significantly to $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ than high- L_{SX} accretion in specific limited ranges of redshift and M_{\star} . In such regimes, our $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ calculation, which does not account for low- L_{SX} accretion, will be inaccurate. We discuss this possibility in §4.3.5.4.

4.3.3 Maximum-Likelihood Fitting of $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_{\star}, z)$

The likelihood functions from survey data and the SMF-XLF data are the most effective in constraining $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_{\star}, z)$ for AGNs in different L_{X} regimes (see §4.3.1). Thus, they need to be combined to identify the best model for $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_{\star}, z)$. We obtain the final log-likelihood function as

$$\ln L = \ln L_{\text{SURV}} + \ln L_{\text{XLF}}, \tag{4.14}$$

where $\ln L_{\text{SURV}}$ and $\ln L_{\text{XLF}}$ are the log-likelihood functions in Eqs. 4.5 and 4.8, respectively. For a given model, we search for best-fit model parameters via maximum-likelihood fitting with IMINUIT v1.2.⁴

Following [288], we model $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_{\star}, z)$ as a smoothed double power law. We do not adopt a single power-law model or a Schechter model [299] of $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_{\star}, z)$. A single power law would lead to an unphysical divergent $\overline{L_{\text{X}}}$ (see §4.1). A Schechter

⁴See <https://pypi.python.org/pypi/iminuit> for IMINUIT.

model results in an exponential decline toward high L_X in the predicted XLF (see Eq. 4.6), inconsistent with the observed power-law decline [10, 13]. However, a smoothed double power law can produce a power-law decline in the XLF. The smoothed double power law at given M_* and z is written as

$$P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z) = A \left[\left(\frac{L_{\text{SX}}}{L_c} \right)^{\gamma_1} + \left(\frac{L_{\text{SX}}}{L_c} \right)^{\gamma_2} \right]^{-1}. \quad (4.15)$$

We define $\gamma_1 \leq \gamma_2$, and thus they are the slopes in the low and high L_{SX} regimes, respectively. All of $\log A$, $\log L_c$, γ_1 , and γ_2 are modeled in the general form of polynomial functions of $\log M_*$ and $\log(1+z)$, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} X &= X_0 + \alpha_0^X \log(1+z) + \alpha_1^X \log M_{10} \\ &+ \beta_0^X [\log(1+z)]^2 + \beta_1^X \log(1+z) \log M_{10} + \beta_2^X (\log M_{10})^2 \\ &+ \dots \end{aligned} \quad (4.16)$$

where $M_{10} = M_*/10^{10}M_\odot$, and X indicates $\log A$, $\log L_c$, γ_1 , or γ_2 .

To determine the highest order of polynomial necessary for each X , we perform a detailed model selection presented in §4.6.1. We find that $\log A$, $\log L_c$, and γ_2 are consistent with 2nd-order, 2nd-order, and 1st-order polynomials, respectively; γ_1 is consistent with a constant value (0th-order polynomial). The best-fit parameter values and their errors are listed in Tab. 4.2; these errors are estimated from MCMC sampling (see §4.6.1). Our conclusions (§4.4) are robust under $> 3\sigma$ confidence levels. The fitting quality and comparison with previous work are presented in §4.6.2.

We are aware that there is an issue of “double-counting” when combining the likelihood functions in Eq. 4.14, since there are some AGNs being included in both survey and XLF data. This could lead to underestimation of our model uncertainties. However, we expect that this issue only has minor effects on our results. For COSMOS AGNs, this issue does not exist because the XLF measurements do not include them (see Tab. 1 of [13]). For CDF-S and CDF-N, only AGNs above $\log L_X = 43$ (our L_X cut for XLF; see §4.2.2) are counted doubly, and these objects account for only $\approx 50\%$ of the whole AGN population in these two fields.

	X_0	α_0^X	α_1^X	β_0^X	β_1^X	β_2^X
$\log A$	$-2.68^{+0.18}_{-0.19}$	$0.81^{+0.68}_{-0.85}$	$1.33^{+0.26}_{-0.20}$	$-0.20^{+1.04}_{-0.90}$	$1.00^{+0.43}_{-0.46}$	$-0.76^{+0.09}_{-0.11}$
$\log L_c$	$-0.57^{+0.19}_{-0.21}$	$4.66^{+0.90}_{-0.62}$	$-1.61^{+0.30}_{-0.39}$	$-4.24^{+0.82}_{-1.07}$	$0.90^{+0.62}_{-0.57}$	$0.46^{+0.16}_{-0.12}$
γ_1	$0.43^{+0.04}_{-0.02}$	—	—	—	—	—
γ_2	$2.45^{+0.27}_{-0.16}$	$-0.88^{+0.72}_{-0.52}$	$0.56^{+0.19}_{-0.36}$	—	—	—

Table 4.2: Best-Fit Model Parameters and 1σ Errors. The parameters are the polynomial coefficients in Eq. 4.16. The symbol “—” indicates the corresponding parameter is not required, and hence fixed to zero in our modeling (see §4.6.1).

4.3.4 The Results for $\overline{\text{BHAR}}(M_*, z)$

The main goal of this paper is to characterize the overall SMBH growth for the majority galaxy population at $z = 0.4\text{--}4$. Therefore, we derive the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ for all galaxies, including both star-forming and quiescent populations, in §4.3.4.1. We also study the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ for star-forming galaxies in §4.3.4.2. We do not investigate the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ for quiescent galaxies, as explained in §4.3.4.3.

4.3.4.1 All Galaxies

Due to the existence of strong AGN variability, ensemble-averaged BHAR is often adopted as an approximation of long-term average BHAR (see §4.1). From our derived L_{SX} distribution, we can obtain this $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ as a function of M_* and redshift, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned}
& \overline{\text{BHAR}}(M_*, z) \\
&= \int_{-2}^{\infty} P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z) \frac{(1-\epsilon)k_{\text{bol}}(L_X)L_X}{\epsilon c^2} d \log L_{\text{SX}} \\
&= \int_{-2}^{\infty} P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z) \frac{(1-\epsilon)k_{\text{bol}}(M_*L_{\text{SX}})M_*L_{\text{SX}}}{\epsilon c^2} d \log L_{\text{SX}}.
\end{aligned} \tag{4.17}$$

We use the $k_{\text{bol}}(L_X)$ function presented in §4.2.3. Although theoretical studies suggest that ϵ depends on factors like SMBH spin and the state of accretion flow [142, 297, 298], it is not feasible to determine ϵ accurately for individual AGNs from observations. The adopted $\epsilon = 0.1$ is likely a typical value for the overall AGN population [105, 106], and has been widely adopted in previous work [11, 25, 206]. We caution that there might be uncertainties up to a factor of a few for this typical ϵ .

The results are displayed in Fig. 4.9. As explained in §4.6.2 and §4.3.5.5, the model uncertainties at $z \lesssim 1$ and $\log M_\star \gtrsim 11.5$ might be underestimated due to limited AGN sample sizes and k_{bol} uncertainties. Therefore, we mark $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ in these ranges as dotted curves in Fig. 4.9. Our derived $\overline{\text{BHAR}}(M_\star, z)$ shows that, at a given redshift, $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ generally increases toward high M_\star , although the M_\star dependence is weaker toward the local universe. This positive $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_\star$ relation is also reported by [206]. Their data are consistent with a linear $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_\star$ (in logarithmic space) relation with a slope of unity for sources at $z = 0.5-2$ (the dashed line in Fig. 4.9).

$\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ has stronger redshift evolution at higher M_\star . For instance, for $\log M_\star = 9.5$, $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ at $z = 4$ is 0.7 ± 0.4 dex higher than at $z = 0.5$; for $\log M_\star = 11.5$, $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ rises by 3.0 ± 0.3 dex from $z = 0.5$ to $z = 4$. This strong redshift dependence for massive galaxies is also found by recent works [247, 248]. [206] compared the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_\star$ relations for two broad redshift bins, $z = 0.5-1.3$ and $z = 1.3-2.0$, but did not find significant differences, possibly due to the limited sample size of the GOODS-S field in their study (§4.2.1.1). Their relatively small sample lacks luminous AGNs (see Fig. 4.3), and could lead to a generally underestimated $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$. This underestimation should be stronger at higher redshifts, where luminous AGNs contribute more significantly to ρ_{BHAR} than less-luminous AGNs [13]. In this work, we included the COSMOS field that probes more luminous AGNs than GOODS-S at a given redshift (§4.2.1.2). Also, our methodology based on SMF and XLF provides further constraints on the luminous AGNs’ contribution to $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ (see §4.3.1.2).

Since $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ has a positive dependence on M_\star in general, we expect more massive galaxies to have higher M_{BH} in the local universe. However, the final M_{BH} not only depends on M_\star at $z = 0$, but also on the stellar mass history $[M_\star(z)]$.⁵ Galaxy evolution is complex, e.g., high- M_\star galaxies tend to form earlier in cosmic history than low- M_\star galaxies (“galaxy downsizing”; e.g., [300]). In §4.4.3 and §4.4.4, we consider all these effects and predict typical $M_{\text{BH}}-M_\star$ relations at different redshifts.

⁵For example, consider two galaxies (dubbed “A” and “B”) that both have $\log M_\star(z = 0) = 11.5$, but A forms earlier than B. Assume at $z = 2$, A and B have $\log M_\star = 11$ and 10, respectively. Then A has much higher $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ than B at $z = 2$, according to Fig. 4.9. Therefore, the final $M_{\text{BH}}(z = 0)$ of A will be higher than that of B.

Figure 4.9: Top panel: $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ for all galaxies, derived from our best-fit $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_\star, z)$ model, as a function of M_\star and redshift. Different colors indicate different redshifts as labeled. The shaded regions indicate 1σ uncertainties derived from our MCMC sampling (see §4.6.1). The dotted curves indicate the redshift and M_\star regimes ($z \lesssim 1$ and $\log M_\star \gtrsim 11.5$) where $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ might have larger uncertainties than estimated (see §4.3.5.5 and §4.6.2). The dashed black line indicates the best-fit relation from Eq. 6 of [206] based on GOODS-S sources at $z = 0.5-2.0$. Bottom panel: Same format as the top panel but for $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ vs. M_{halo} . $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ is positively dependent on M_{halo} for $\log M_{\text{halo}} \lesssim 12-13$, but the dependence becomes much weaker toward higher M_{halo} . There are no corresponding dotted curves (large $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ uncertainties) in the bottom panel. This is because, at $z \lesssim 1$, even for the highest M_{halo} shown, the corresponding $\log M_\star$ is below 11.5.

4.3.4.2 Star-forming Galaxies

The $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_*$ slope in §4.3.4.1 becomes shallower toward low redshift. This could be due to the fact that the quiescent galaxy population becomes increasingly significant at low redshifts in massive galaxies [109, 257], and that quiescent galaxies generally have weaker AGN activity compared to star-forming galaxies [42, 248, 261]. To test this scenario, we derive $\overline{\text{BHAR}}(M_*, z)$ for star-forming galaxies. We only use the survey-data constraints (§4.3.1.1), as the SMF-XLF constraints (§4.3.1.2) are for the whole galaxy population rather than the star-forming subset.

We select star-forming galaxies using the classifications in §4.2.1, which are not applied to BL AGNs. We now discuss the star-forming/quiescent types for BL AGNs. The star-forming population is dominant over the quiescent population for $\log M_* \lesssim 10.5$ or $z \gtrsim 2$. Therefore, we assign a BL AGN to be star-forming if it satisfies $\log M_* \lesssim 10.5$ or $z \gtrsim 2$, and this accounts for the majority population ($\approx 70\%$) of the BL AGNs. For the other 30% of BL AGNs, we include them in our $\overline{\text{BHAR}}(M_*, z)$ derivation considering two extreme scenarios. The first scenario is that these 30% of BL AGNs are all star-forming [301]; the second is that they are all quiescent. The resulting $\overline{\text{BHAR}}(M_*, z)$ for the two scenarios are similar at $\log M_* \lesssim 11.5$ ($\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ differences $\lesssim 0.3$ dex). We thus only discuss the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}(M_*, z)$ for star-forming galaxies at $\log M_* \lesssim 11.5$. The results for the first scenario are displayed in Fig. 4.10.

The $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ dependence on M_* does not become significantly weaker toward low redshift. Therefore, it is likely that the shallow slope of the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_*$ relation for all galaxies in §4.3.4.1 is due to the increasing fraction of quiescent galaxies toward low redshifts and high M_* . However, one caveat is that our star-forming vs. quiescent classification scheme is largely empirical (§4.2.1). Previous studies adopt various criteria for identifying star-forming galaxies [111, 214], while the physical meanings of these bimodal classification schemes are still under debate [302]. Different classification methods can yield different $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_*$ relations in Fig. 4.10.

4.3.4.3 Quiescent Galaxies

We have tested deriving $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ for quiescent galaxies. However, the uncertainties are generally large, and thus we do not show the results. The large uncertainties are due to the limited sample size of quiescent galaxies, especially in the high- z

Figure 4.10: Same format as Fig. 4.9 (top) but for star-forming galaxies only. We do not show $\log M_{\star} > 11.5$ due to large uncertainties. The $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ dependence on M_{\star} does not become significantly weaker toward low redshift.

and low- M_{\star} regime ($z \gtrsim 2$ and $\log M_{\star} \lesssim 10.5$; see §4.3.4.2). At low redshifts and high M_{\star} , $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ is also significantly affected by whether to include BL AGNs as quiescent galaxies (see §4.3.4.2).

4.3.5 Reliability Checks

4.3.5.1 Effects of X-ray Obscuration

In §4.2.1, we derived L_X from observed-frame hard-band fluxes. However, even these measurements might suffer from obscuration, and thus the inferred L_X might be underestimated. Also, we assume a photon index of 1.6 when deriving L_X , and this choice could introduce additional uncertainties.

To evaluate the accuracy of our L_X estimations, we compare them with those derived from XSPEC spectral fitting [89]. This exercise is performed for GOODS-S sources for which we have L_X from X-ray spectral fitting (see §2.3 in [206] for details of the spectral fitting). The intrinsic obscuration column density and photon index are free parameters in the fitting. The L_X values derived from fluxes agree well with those derived from spectral fitting: the systematic offset is 0.01 dex, and the typical offset (the median of $|\Delta \log L_X|$) is 0.09 dex. We do not find significant redshift or luminosity dependence of the systematic offset, indicating that our adopted L_X values should also be reliable for COSMOS AGNs which are generally more luminous than GOODS-S AGNs.

At $z > 2$, assuming $\Gamma = 1.8$ instead of $\Gamma = 1.6$ leads to a systematic overestimation (≈ 0.1 dex) of L_X compared to that derived from spectral fitting, likely because Γ appears generally lower at high redshift [244]. At low redshift where the k correction is smaller, the flux-based L_X is only weakly dependent on Γ ; for example, at $z = 1$, the difference between L_X produced by $\Gamma = 1.6$ and $\Gamma = 1.8$ is only 0.04 dex. The relatively low apparent value of Γ (1.6) at high redshift might result from Compton reflection. At $z \gtrsim 2$, the X-ray observations can cover energies above 20 keV where the Compton reflection component is strong. The reflection component is hard, and thus may cause the “apparent” Γ value to be lower than the “intrinsic” value. However, due to the limited number of counts, it is not feasible to model properly the reflection component and obtain the “intrinsic” Γ . Our adopted $\Gamma = 1.6$ is thus a practical approximation for the total X-ray spectra rather than necessarily the intrinsic photon index for the transmission component.

Most of the distant AGNs detected in X-ray surveys are likely Compton-thin (CTN; $N_H < 10^{24} \text{ cm}^{-2}$; e.g., [243]), and the XLF we adopt does not include Compton-thick (CTK) AGNs. Therefore, our derived $\overline{\text{BHAR}}(M_*, z)$ does not account for accretion contributed by CTK AGNs. Previous studies indicate that the

CTK population is unlikely to be dominant over other AGNs and there is no evidence that the CTK fraction strongly depends on M_\star and/or z . [125, 127, 128, 303–305]. Thus, our $\overline{\text{BHAR}}(M_\star, z)$ should not be significantly affected by CTK AGNs.

4.3.5.2 Contamination from X-ray Binaries

In the low- L_{SX} regime, the X-ray sources have a significant contribution of X-ray emission from XRBs rather than AGNs. X-ray emission from XRBs can be modeled as $L_{\text{X,XRB}} = \alpha M_\star + \beta \text{SFR}$, where α and β are functions of redshift. We adopt α and β from model 269 of [98] which is preferred by the observations of [97]. Therefore, the L_{SX} for XRBs can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} L_{\text{SX,XRB}} &= \frac{L_{\text{X,XRB}}}{M_\star} \\ &= \frac{\alpha M_\star + \beta \text{SFR}}{M_\star} \\ &= \alpha + \beta \text{sSFR}. \end{aligned} \tag{4.18}$$

Since most star-forming galaxies have similar sSFR at a given redshift (i.e., the star-forming “main sequence”), the right-hand side of Eq. 4.18 only depends on redshift for star-forming galaxies. For quiescent galaxies, the $L_{\text{SX,XRB}}$ is even lower than that of star-forming galaxies. We display the $L_{\text{SX,XRB}}$ for the main-sequence galaxies as a function of redshift in Fig. 4.3 (bottom). The sSFR is from Eq. 13 of [111]. The $L_{\text{SX,XRB}}$ increases toward higher redshift. Above our L_{SX} threshold ($\log L_{\text{SX}} = -2$; see §4.3.2.3), all the sources have L_{SX} larger than $L_{\text{SX,XRB}}$. Even for the GOODS-S data (the deepest), the typical L_{SX} of our X-ray AGNs is higher than $L_{\text{SX,XRB}}$ by an order of magnitude at any redshift. Also, almost all of our X-ray sources above $\log L_{\text{SX}} = -2$ in GOODS-S (98%) and GOODS-N (99%) are classified as “AGN” instead of “galaxy” by [67] and [241], respectively. Therefore, our analyses should not be significantly affected by X-ray emission from XRBs.

4.3.5.3 Sample M_\star Completeness

To evaluate potential issues of M_\star completeness, we derive the galaxy comoving number density as a function of M_\star for each field and compare with the SMF from ([31]; see §4.2.2). The number density is calculated as the observed number of galaxies divided by the corresponding comoving volume. Fig. 4.11 displays the

Figure 4.11: Galaxy comoving number density as a function of M_\star at $z = 3.0\text{--}4.0$. The data points indicate values derived from our sample of different fields. We do not plot bins where only one source is available due to large uncertainties. The black solid curve represents the SMF from [31]. The vertical black dashed line indicates our M_\star cut (see 4.3.2.2). Our sources in all of the three fields are complete above our M_\star cut.

results for $z = 3\text{--}4$ (the highest redshift range probed in this work). The number densities for all the three fields agree with the SMF above $\log M_\star = 9.5$ (our M_\star cut; see §4.3.2.2), indicating our sample is complete for the M_\star regime probed in this work. The number density for COSMOS deviates from the SMF below $\log M_\star \approx 9$. The number densities for GOODS-S and GOODS-N both deviate from the SMF below $\log M_\star \approx 8.5$, as expected from their deeper imaging data than those of COSMOS.

4.3.5.4 Contribution to $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ from Low- L_{SX} Accretion

Our derivation of $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ does not include the contribution from $\log L_{\text{SX}} < -2$ (see §4.3.2.3 and §4.3.4.1). Although we have shown that this low- L_{SX} accretion cannot contribute significantly to the overall SMBH growth (see §4.3.2.3), it can still affect the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}\text{--}M_\star$ relation, especially at low redshifts when the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ from high- L_{SX}

accretion is low.

We here consider one extreme case in which $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ is a narrow lognormal distribution centered at $\log L_{\text{SX}} = -2.2$ with a width of ± 0.1 dex; then the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ contribution from $\log L_{\text{SX}} < -2$ will be dominant over that from $\log L_{\text{SX}} \geq -2$. This extreme case can be used to estimate the upper limit on $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ contributed by $\log L_{\text{SX}} < -2$. Quantitatively, we can estimate this upper limit as

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{\text{BHAR}} &= \frac{L_X k_{\text{bol}}(1 - \epsilon)}{\epsilon c^2} \\ &= \frac{L_{\text{SX}} k_{\text{bol}}(1 - \epsilon)}{\epsilon c^2} M_* \\ &\approx 10^{-3.5} \frac{M_*}{10^{10} M_\odot}, \end{aligned} \tag{4.19}$$

where we adopt $\epsilon = 0.1$ and $k_{\text{bol}} = 10$ (see §4.3.2.3). Only at low redshifts ($z \lesssim 0.8$), can our $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ (see Fig. 4.9) be below this upper limit. Therefore, low- L_{SX} accretion can only be important at low redshifts.

To examine whether low- L_{SX} accretion is actually dominant over high- L_{SX} accretion at low redshifts, we utilize GOODS-S where the deepest X-ray observations and stacking data are available to probe low- L_{SX} accretion [96, 206]. We study sources in three M_* bins ($\log M_* = 9.5\text{--}10$, $10\text{--}10.5$, and $10.5\text{--}11$) at $z = 0.4\text{--}0.7$. We do not probe higher M_* due to the limited number of galaxies (only 14 available). We use total L_X to approximate total BHAR for each M_* bin. For each M_* bin, we obtain the total L_X for all sources in this bin, including both X-ray detected and undetected sources (via stacking); we also derive the contributions to total L_X from $\log L_{\text{SX}} \geq -2$ sources by summing the L_X of detected X-ray sources above $\log L_{\text{SX}} = -2$. We find that, for all of the three M_* bins, the contributions from $\log L_{\text{SX}} \geq -2$ sources account for $\gtrsim 80\text{--}90\%$ of the total L_X . If we only consider the L_X from AGNs by subtracting the expected XRB component (see Eq. 1 of [206]), almost all ($\gtrsim 99\%$) of the total L_X from AGNs is from $\log L_{\text{SX}} \geq -2$ sources. The dominance of accretion at $\log L_{\text{SX}} \geq -2$ indicates that the extreme lognormal $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ distribution above is unlikely to be physical, which is also suggested by some other studies [247, 248].

Therefore, we conclude that accretion from sources with $\log L_{\text{SX}} < -2$, which is not included in our $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ calculation, should not significantly affect our $\overline{\text{BHAR}}(M_*, z)$ at all redshifts probed (i.e., $z = 0.4\text{--}4$).

4.3.5.5 Bolometric Correction

The analyses in §4.3.4 assume k_{bol} is a function of L_X . This luminosity-dependent k_{bol} is generally larger for more massive galaxies, as they typically host AGNs with higher L_X [206, 248]. However, k_{bol} might be related to λ_{Edd} (see §4.2.3).

If we assume a $k_{\text{bol}}-\lambda_{\text{Edd}}$ relation instead, then the k_{bol} dependence on M_* will be weaker, because, compared to L_X , λ_{Edd} is likely much less dependent on M_* [59, 246, 248]. We test an extreme case such that k_{bol} is a constant value of 22.4 (the median of k_{bol} values in the local AGN sample of [104]). The resulting $\overline{\text{BHAR}}(M_*, z)$ is broadly similar to that in Fig. 4.9. $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ generally has positive dependence on M_* and redshift, and the redshift dependence is stronger in more massive systems. However, we find that the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_*$ relation becomes flat at $z \lesssim 1.0$ and $\log M_* \gtrsim 11.5$. This redshift and M_* regime is marked in Fig. 4.9 (see also §4.6.2).

4.4 Discussion

4.4.1 Physical Causes of the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_*$ Relation and its Cosmic Evolution

At a given M_* , $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ is positively correlated with redshift out to $z \approx 4$ (see Fig. 4.9). The physical reason could be that cold gas which fuels SMBH growth becomes more abundant toward high redshift [11, 139, 306]. At a given redshift, $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ is generally higher in massive galaxies. As discussed in §4.2 of [206], this positive dependence of $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ on M_* might be due to, e.g., deeper potential wells [143] and/or higher SMBH occupation fractions at high M_* [52].

The positive dependence of $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ on M_* becomes significantly weaker at low redshift, i.e., the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_*$ slope becomes shallower. One possible cause of the shallower $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_*$ slope at low redshifts is that the fraction of star-forming galaxies, which have generally stronger AGN activity than quiescent galaxies, decreases toward low redshift and high- M_* . We show that when only including star-forming galaxies, the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_*$ slope does not become significantly shallower at low redshifts (see §4.3.4.2).

The low $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ of massive galaxies at low redshift is understandable considering

the cosmic evolution of the SMF and XLF. Luminous quasars ($\log L_X \gtrsim 44$), which are likely responsible for most of the SMBH growth in massive galaxies [105], become much rarer toward the local universe [13, 307]. The number density of massive galaxies, however, becomes higher toward low redshift (see, e.g., Fig. 15 of [216]). Therefore, the average SMBH accretion power for the massive galaxy population decreases sharply toward low redshift. The strong redshift dependence of $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ for massive galaxies is also evident in our survey data. The detected AGN fraction ($\log L_{\text{SX}} > -2$) is $\approx 9\%$ among massive galaxies ($\log M_\star > 11$) at $z > 2$, while the fraction is $\approx 5\%$ at $z < 2$. Considering the larger incompleteness at higher redshift, the intrinsic AGN fractions for $z > 2$ and $z < 2$ should have even larger differences.

The physical cause of this strong $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ redshift evolution might be AGN feedback that could regulate the growth of SMBHs in massive galaxies. At high redshift, effective quasar-mode accretion could launch powerful winds that expel the cold gas in host galaxies [210]. Due to the lack of cold gas, SMBH growth drops significantly toward low redshift and hot-gas accretion occurs. The hot accretion flow could produce jets that prevent the gas from cooling and thereby maintain a low accretion rate [140, 142].

The positive dependence of $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ on redshift (especially at $z \gtrsim 2$) does not contradict the observational fact that ρ_{BHAR} peaks at $z \approx 2$ [80]. We calculate ρ_{BHAR} by convolving $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ with the SMF, i.e.,

$$\rho_{\text{BHAR}}(z) = \int_{9.5}^{12} \overline{\text{BHAR}}(M_\star, z) \phi_M(M_\star|z) d \log M_\star. \quad (4.20)$$

Fig. 4.12 (top) displays the results. The $z \approx 2$ peak is successfully reproduced. $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ describes the accretion power *per galaxy* while ρ_{BHAR} characterizes the accretion power per comoving volume. Their different redshift evolution indicates that the drop of ρ_{BHAR} toward high redshift is driven by the evolution of the SMF: the number density of galaxies with $\log M_\star \approx 9.5\text{--}12$ decreases toward high redshift [216]. A similar conclusion is also found by [308] who studied X-ray AGNs at $z = 3\text{--}6$. Our ρ_{BHAR} curve has a similar shape as that of [13], but it is a factor of ≈ 3 lower than theirs. The difference is primarily caused by the different k_{bol} adopted: our k_{bol} (from [246]; §4.2.3) is ≈ 3 times lower than their k_{bol} (from [108]) at $\log L_X \approx 44$ (the XLF break luminosity). For the reasons explained in §4.2.3, we

believe our adopted k_{bol} is more reliable than that from [108].

Some studies suggest that M_{BH} might be fundamentally related to the mass of the dark matter halo (M_{halo} ; e.g., [309]; but also see [4]). We thus change the variable M_{\star} to M_{halo} utilizing the typical redshift-dependent $M_{\text{halo}}-M_{\star}$ relation from [31], and convert $\overline{\text{BHAR}}(M_{\star}, z)$ to $\overline{\text{BHAR}}(M_{\text{halo}}, z)$. Fig. 4.9 (bottom) displays the results.⁶ At $\log M_{\text{halo}} \lesssim 12-13$, $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ is positively dependent on M_{halo} and strongly so at high redshifts. At higher M_{halo} , $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ becomes relatively flat as a function of M_{halo} , indicating M_{halo} is not a good tracer of $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ in massive systems [4].

To clarify the cause of this flatness, we express the slope of the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_{\text{halo}}$ relation as

$$\frac{d \log \overline{\text{BHAR}}}{d \log M_{\text{halo}}} = \frac{d \log \overline{\text{BHAR}}}{d \log M_{\star}} \frac{d \log M_{\star}}{d \log M_{\text{halo}}}. \quad (4.21)$$

The slope of the $M_{\star}-M_{\text{halo}}$ relation ($d \log M_{\star}/d \log M_{\text{halo}}$) is small ($\lesssim 0.3$) above $\log M_{\text{halo}} \approx 12-13$ (see Fig. 7 of [31]), and this results in a small slope of the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_{\text{halo}}$ relation ($d \log \overline{\text{BHAR}}/d \log M_{\text{halo}}$), even though the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_{\star}$ relation can be steep (e.g., $d \log \overline{\text{BHAR}}/d \log M_{\star} \gtrsim 1$ at $z \gtrsim 1$; see Fig. 4.9 top). The physical cause of the flat $M_{\star}-M_{\text{halo}}$ relation in massive systems is likely that gas cannot efficiently cool and collapse to form stars. This inefficient cooling might be due to AGN feedback and/or deep gravitational potential wells in massive halos (e.g., [310]; §8.4 of [4]).

4.4.2 BHAR vs. SFR

The redshift-evolution curves of ρ_{BHAR} and ρ_{SFR} are similar at least up to $z \approx 2$ (e.g., [4, 10]; Fig. 4.12, which we will discuss in detail below). This similarity is considered a supporting point of the straightforward scenario that the long-term growth of SMBHs and their host galaxies are in lockstep. However, ρ_{BHAR} and ρ_{SFR} are quantities averaged over the whole galaxy population from low M_{\star} to high M_{\star} , and their evolutionary similarity might not hold for galaxies with different M_{\star} .

To investigate this possibility, we compare the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_{\star}$ relation with the $\overline{\text{SFR}}-M_{\star}$ relation from [31] in Fig. 4.13 (top). The $\overline{\text{SFR}}-M_{\star}$ relation is truncated

⁶Due to the complicated evolution history of massive systems (e.g., frequent mergers), [31] do not provide relations such as $M_{\text{halo}}-M_{\star}$ and $\overline{\text{SFR}}-M_{\star}$ at very high M_{\star} (P. Behroozi 2017, private communication).

Figure 4.12: Top panel: ρ_{BHAR} and ρ_{SFR} as a function of redshift. The black solid curve indicates ρ_{BHAR} derived from our best-fit model using Eq. 4.20; the blue data points indicate ρ_{SFR} scaled by a factor of 10^{-4} [31]. Bottom panel: the $\rho_{\text{BHAR}}/\rho_{\text{SFR}}$ ratio as a function of redshift. The black horizontal dashed line represents a constant ratio of 10^{-4} . $\rho_{\text{BHAR}}/\rho_{\text{SFR}}$ depends on redshift weakly.

at high M_{\star} due to the reason in Footnote 6. We note that the $\overline{\text{SFR}}-M_{\star}$ relation represents an ensemble-averaged property (the same as for the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_{\star}$ relation), and thus it is not affected by the SFR variability of individual galaxies. We normalize the $\overline{\text{SFR}}$ values by a factor of 10^{-4} so that they become comparable with $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$. Fig. 4.13 (bottom) presents the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}/\overline{\text{SFR}}$ ratio as a function of M_{\star} .

At a given M_{\star} , both $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ and $\overline{\text{SFR}}$ rise toward high redshifts in general. However, $\overline{\text{BHAR}}/\overline{\text{SFR}}$ has relatively weak redshift evolution, especially at $z \gtrsim 0.8$.

At a given redshift, $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ rises more strongly as a function of M_* than $\overline{\text{SFR}}$. As a result, the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}/\overline{\text{SFR}}$ ratio is positively correlated with M_* at a given redshift, broadly consistent with the findings of [206]. This positive dependence disfavors the straightforward coevolution model where SMBH and galaxy growth are in lockstep and $\overline{\text{BHAR}}/\overline{\text{SFR}}$ is a universal constant [26]. As explained in §4.2 of [206], the larger $\overline{\text{BHAR}}/\overline{\text{SFR}}$ toward high M_* may indicate that massive systems are more effective in feeding cold gas to their central SMBHs due to, e.g., their deep potential wells. Another possibility is that the SMBH occupation fraction increases toward high M_* . Our $\overline{\text{BHAR}}/\overline{\text{SFR}}$ agrees with the sample of [206] at $0.5 \leq z < 1.3$ (the red points in Fig. 4.13). We do not compare with their high-redshift ($1.3 \leq z < 2.0$) sample, because luminous AGNs ($\log L_X \gtrsim 44$) are dominant at high redshift but almost absent in their sample. This rarity of luminous AGNs is due to the small area of GOODS-S used in [206] and the removal of BL AGNs from their sample.

Fig. 4.12 compares our ρ_{BHAR} (§4.4.1) with ρ_{SFR} from the observational data compiled by [31]. The ρ_{BHAR} and ρ_{SFR} curves have similar shapes consistent with previous work [4, 10]. The $\rho_{\text{BHAR}}/\rho_{\text{SFR}}$ ratio only rises slightly (≈ 0.3 dex) from $z = 0$ to $z \gtrsim 3$. We note that this weak redshift dependence does not contradict our conclusion that $\overline{\text{BHAR}}/\overline{\text{SFR}}$ for massive galaxies ($\log M_* \gtrsim 11$) rises strongly toward high redshift (see Fig. 4.13). This is because massive galaxies are relatively rare and their weight in $\rho_{\text{BHAR}}/\rho_{\text{SFR}}$ is not dominant over that of less-massive galaxies.

Fig. 4.14 compares the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_*$ and $\overline{\text{SFR}}-M_*$ relations for star-forming galaxies. The $\overline{\text{SFR}}$ vs. M_* are from the star-forming main-sequence relations (Eq. 6 of [311]). We do not compare these relations above $z = 3$, as the uncertainties of the main-sequence relations are large at $z \gtrsim 3$. At a given redshift, the $\overline{\text{SFR}}-M_*$ relation generally has a slope shallower than the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_*$ relation. This leads to $\overline{\text{BHAR}}/\overline{\text{SFR}}$ rising toward high M_* (Fig. 4.14 bottom), similarly to the trend in Fig. 4.13 (bottom). Also similarly to Fig. 4.13 (bottom), the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}/\overline{\text{SFR}}$ has weak redshift evolution at a given M_* above $z \gtrsim 0.8$. The $\overline{\text{BHAR}}/\overline{\text{SFR}}$ curve in Fig. 4.14 is concave down while that in Fig. 4.13 is concave up.

Fig. 4.14 also shows the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}/\overline{\text{SFR}}$ measurements from the literature. The $\overline{\text{BHAR}}/\overline{\text{SFR}}$ values from [11] are higher than ours, possibly due to their large uncertainties. However, the observations of [113] at $z \sim 2$ have much smaller uncertainties and agree with our $\overline{\text{BHAR}}/\overline{\text{SFR}}$. Since these measurements are for

star-forming galaxies, they are not displayed in Fig. 4.13, which is for all galaxies.

4.4.3 Evolution of The $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\star}$ Relation

Our $\overline{\text{BHAR}}(M_{\star}, z)$ describes the long-term average BHAR for a galaxy at given M_{\star} and z . Based on $\overline{\text{BHAR}}(M_{\star}, z)$, we can calculate the cumulative accreted SMBH mass for galaxies with given stellar mass history $[M_{\star}(z)]$, i.e.,

$$M_{\text{BH}}(z) = \int_4^z \overline{\text{BHAR}}(M_{\star}(z'), z') \frac{dt}{dz'} dz' + M_{\text{BH}}|_{z=4}, \quad (4.22)$$

where t is the cosmic time; the prime superscript in z' is to differentiate the redshift z as the integral upper boundary. We adopt the stellar mass history of [31] who derived the average $M_{\star}(z)$ for galaxies as a function of $M_{\star}(z=0)$ up to $\log M_{\star}(z=0) \approx 11.4$ (see their Fig. 9). To obtain the initial condition $M_{\text{BH}}|_{z=4}$, we test different $M_{\text{BH}}/M_{\star}|_{z=4}$ values and multiply them with $M_{\star}(z=4)$ from [31].

When $M_{\star}(z)$ lies below our limit of $\log M_{\star} = 9.5$ in Eq. 4.22 (i.e., our M_{\star} cut; see §4.3.2.2), we assume their $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ as $\overline{\text{BHAR}}(\log M_{\star} = 9.5, z) \times (M_{\star}/10^{9.5})^{\zeta}$. We set the power-law index $\zeta = 1$, i.e., assuming $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ at $\log M_{\star} \leq 9.5$ is proportional to $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ at $\log M_{\star} = 9.5$ [206]. To reduce the uncertainties of this approximation, we do not discuss the $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\star}$ relation for $\log M_{\star} < 10$ at all redshifts.⁷ In fact, we find that setting ζ to 0.5 or 2 does not affect our conclusions. For redshifts below our cut ($z = 0.4$; §4.3.2.1), we use $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ from model extrapolation. This should not bring noticeable uncertainties given that $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ is low at $z < 0.4$. In fact, we have tested two extreme scenarios: $\overline{\text{BHAR}}(M_{\star}, z < 0.4) = \overline{\text{BHAR}}(M_{\star}, z = 0.4)$ (no redshift evolution at $z < 0.4$) and $\overline{\text{BHAR}} = 0$ (no SMBH growth at $z < 0.4$), respectively. Both of these cases produce almost the same $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\star}$ relation as that from model extrapolation.

In Eq. 4.22, we assume long-term BHAR can be inferred from M_{\star} and redshift. This assumption will not be strictly correct, if, for example, $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ also depends on SFR at given M_{\star} and redshift. However, this SFR dependence is likely weak based on previous work [19, 206], and significantly different $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ might only be found between galaxies with extremely different SFRs, e.g., star-forming vs. quiescent

⁷We still need to assume $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ for $\log M_{\star} \leq 9.5$, even though we do not probe $\log M_{\star} < 10$. For example, a galaxy with $\log M_{\star}(z=0) = 10.5$ has $\log M_{\star} < 9.5$ in the early universe ($z > 2$), and we need to account for its SMBH accretion at $z = 2-4$.

Figure 4.13: Top panel: Comparison between $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ and $\overline{\text{SFR}}$ as functions of M_{\star} . The solid lines indicate $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$; the dashed lines indicate $\overline{\text{SFR}}$ scaled by a factor of 10^{-4} . Different colors indicate different redshifts as labeled. Bottom panel: The ratio between $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ and $\overline{\text{SFR}}$ as functions of M_{\star} at different redshifts. The purple data points indicate the measured $\overline{\text{BHAR}}/\overline{\text{SFR}}$ values from [206]. At $z \gtrsim 0.5$, $\overline{\text{BHAR}}/\overline{\text{SFR}}$ rises toward high M_{\star} ; it is flat as a function of M_{\star} at lower redshift.

Figure 4.14: Same format as Fig. 4.13 but for star-forming galaxies only. The data points in the bottom panel indicate measurements from [11, 113].

galaxies [248, 261]. In the case of weak SFR dependence, our ensemble analyses are still valid in characterizing the typical $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\star}$ relation for the entire galaxy population.

We show the resulting M_{BH} as a function of M_{\star} at different redshifts in Fig. 4.15. The $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\star}$ curves are truncated at the highest $M_{\star}(z)$ values in ([31]; see Footnote 6). As expected, the effects of the $M_{\text{BH}}/M_{\star}|_{z=4}$ assumption generally become weaker toward low redshift. At $z \lesssim 2$, the $M_{\text{BH}}/M_{\star}|_{z=4} = 1/100$ (black dashed) and $M_{\text{BH}}/M_{\star}|_{z=4} = 1/10^4$ (black dash-dotted) curves only differ from the $M_{\text{BH}}/M_{\star}|_{z=4} = 1/500$ (black solid) curve by $\lesssim 0.3$ dex in vertical direction. Thus, below we only discuss the $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\star}$ relations at $z \leq 2$.

From Fig. 4.15, the $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\star}$ relation only has weak redshift evolution since $z \approx 2$ (solid black vs. red curves). This result does not contradict Fig. 4.13 which shows that $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ and $\overline{\text{SFR}}$ have strong redshift dependence. This is because $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ and $\overline{\text{SFR}}$ are both low at $z \lesssim 0.8$ compared to at higher redshift. For example, at a given M_{\star} , the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ ($\overline{\text{SFR}}$) at $z = 0.5$ is lower than $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ ($\overline{\text{SFR}}$) at $z = 3$ by a factor of ≈ 10 . Therefore, the SMBH and galaxy growth at $z \lesssim 0.8$ are not important, and the $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\star}$ relation is thus primarily determined by $\overline{\text{BHAR}}/\overline{\text{SFR}}$ at higher redshift. At $z \gtrsim 0.8$, the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}/\overline{\text{SFR}}$ does not have strong redshift dependence at a given M_{\star} . The weak redshift dependence of the $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\star}$ relation is consistent with the observations of [312] which show that the ratio between SMBH and stellar mass densities is flat as a function of redshift since $z \approx 5$. Based on observations of BL AGNs, [72] also found a redshift-independent $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\star}$ relation (but also see [162]).

Since massive galaxies tend to form at high redshifts (§4.3.4), our result suggests that their SMBHs should follow a similar trend. The massive galaxies ($\log M_{\star} \gtrsim 11$) at $z \approx 2$ are likely the progenitors of local giant ellipticals for which $M_{\star} = M_{\text{bulge}}$. Their M_{BH} values are already at the level expected from the local $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\text{bulge}}$ relation [4, 8]. This conclusion disfavors the scenario that the local $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\text{bulge}}$ relation for giant ellipticals mostly formed at low redshift, as proposed in §4.3 of [206]. Their scenario assumes their $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_{\star}$ relation (see Fig. 4.9) extends to $\log M_{\star} \gtrsim 11$ and has weak redshift evolution at $z \lesssim 2$, which is inconsistent with our results.

The $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\star}$ relations at $z \lesssim 2$ differ significantly from those expected from a constant M_{BH}/M_{\star} ratio (the brown lines in Fig. 4.15). The M_{BH}/M_{\star} ratio is

positively related to M_* : it is $\sim 1/5000$ at $\log M_* \lesssim 10.5$ and rises to $\sim 1/500$ at $\log M_* \gtrsim 11.2$. This positive dependence is predicted by [206] based on the fact that $\overline{\text{BHAR}}/\overline{\text{SFR}}$ is generally higher toward high M_* (see Fig. 4.13).

Fig. 4.15 also compares our $M_{\text{BH}}-M_*$ relation with the observations of BL AGNs at $z \gtrsim 0.5$ [72, 162, 163, 313–315]. At $\log M_* \gtrsim 11$, these observations agree well with our $M_{\text{BH}}-M_*$ relation. However, at lower M_* , the M_{BH} values for BL AGNs are significantly higher than those predicted by our $M_{\text{BH}}-M_*$ relation. The discrepancies might be caused by selection biases and/or M_{BH} measurement uncertainties. Due to observational sensitivity, the BL AGNs with M_{BH} measured tend to have massive SMBHs, and thus do not well represent the whole galaxy population at given M_* [164]. The measurements of M_{BH} are based on single-epoch spectra, and large uncertainties (both scatter and biases) exist in these measurements [165]. In fact, in the local universe where M_{BH} can be measured for BL AGNs with lower luminosities and normal galaxies, the observations agree better with our $M_{\text{BH}}-M_*$ relation (see §4.4.4).

We do not calculate M_{BH} vs. M_* for star-forming galaxies due to the lack of their average stellar mass history (i.e., the needed $M_*(z)$ is not provided by [31] or other works to our knowledge), and we only make qualitative arguments below. Since the cosmic evolution of $\overline{\text{BHAR}}/\overline{\text{SFR}}$ for star-forming galaxies is weak at $z \gtrsim 0.8$ (see §4.4.2), their $M_{\text{BH}}-M_*$ relation should also have weak dependence on redshift (as explained above for all galaxies). The M_{BH}/M_* likely rises in more massive galaxies where $\overline{\text{BHAR}}/\overline{\text{SFR}}$ is higher. These qualitative conclusions for star-forming galaxies are similar to those for all galaxies (Fig. 4.15).

4.4.4 The $M_{\text{BH}}-M_*$ Relation at $z = 0$

Fig. 4.16 compares our $M_{\text{BH}}-M_*$ relation at $z = 0$ with observations. At $\log M_* \gtrsim 11$ where $M_* \approx M_{\text{bulge}}$, our derived M_{BH} is similar to that expected from the $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\text{bulge}}$ relations in [8] and [4]. However, at lower M_* , our M_{BH} is significantly lower compared to that expected from the $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\text{bulge}}$ relations. This result is expected, because the bulge components become less dominant and M_{bulge}/M_* drops toward low M_* [316].

SMBH growth can occur via both accretion and mergers. Some studies propose that mergers could be the main channel of SMBH growth for local giant ellipticals,

Figure 4.15: SMBH mass vs. stellar mass at different redshifts. The black solid, dot-dashed, and dashed lines indicate our best-fit model assuming $M_{\text{BH}}/M_{\star}|_{z=4} = 1/500$, $1/100$, and $1/10^4$, respectively. The MCMC 1σ uncertainties are small ($\lesssim 0.1$ dex) and thus are not shown. The red solid line represents our $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\star}$ relation at $z = 0$ assuming $M_{\text{BH}}/M_{\star}|_{z=4} = 1/500$. The brown dashed and dot-dashed lines are $M_{\text{BH}}/M_{\star} = 1/500$ and $M_{\text{BH}}/M_{\star} = 1/5000$, respectively; the blue and orange lines indicate the $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\text{bulge}}$ relations in the local universe from [8] and [4], respectively. The pink stars identify BL AGNs from the literature (see §4.4.3). Our $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\star}$ relation is not strongly affected by the assumptions about $M_{\text{BH}}/M_{\star}|_{z=4}$ at $z \lesssim 2$. The $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\star}$ relation has weak redshift evolution since $z \approx 2$, and it is similar to the local $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\text{bulge}}$ relations at high M_{\star} where $M_{\star} \approx M_{\text{bulge}}$. At low M_{\star} , our $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\star}$ relation deviates from the $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\text{bulge}}$ relations likely because the bulge is less dominant toward low M_{\star} .

and their $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\star}$ relation might be a natural result of merger averaging (e.g., [33, 34]; §8.5 of [4]). However, the similarity between our $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\star}$ relation and the $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\text{bulge}}$ relations at high M_{\star} suggests that accretion is sufficient to produce the observed $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\star}$ relation in local giant ellipticals, since merger growth is not included in our M_{BH} calculation (Eq. 4.22).⁸ Also, merger averaging of low- M_{\star}

⁸Our scheme of M_{BH} calculation in Eq. 4.22 is different from the Soltan argument [317]. The Soltan argument considers M_{BH} density which is not affected by mergers. However, our M_{BH}

galaxies can only lead to the final M_{BH}/M_{\star} ratio being farther from that observed in giant ellipticals, because M_{BH}/M_{\star} is lower toward low M_{\star} . This argument can also apply to the giant ellipticals beyond our probed M_{\star} limit ($\log M_{\star} \approx 11.4$). Therefore, merger growth might not dominate over accretion growth for giant ellipticals in general. We caution that our scheme describes the ensemble-averaged growth history for SMBHs and galaxies, and it is possible that mergers are dominant in some individual systems.

Fig. 4.16 displays M_{BH} and M_{\star} values for individual normal galaxies (cyan and red data points). The M_{BH} values are measured via reliable stellar dynamics or megamasers. These data points are mainly based on Tabs. 2 (elliptical galaxies) and 3 (disk galaxies) of [4] where M_{bulge} values are provided, and the unreliable M_{BH} measurements (the purple rows in these two tables) are discarded. For elliptical galaxies, M_{bulge} equals M_{\star} ; for disk galaxies, we divide M_{bulge} by the K_s -band bulge-to-total luminosity ratio (B/T ; also provided in [4]) to approximate M_{\star} . The data points also include the recent M_{BH} measurements based on megamasers for three galaxies (Mrk 1029, J0437+2456, and UGC 6093; [56]). These data broadly agree with our $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\star}$ relation: the typical M_{BH}/M_{\star} is low (one over several thousand) at $\log M_{\star} \lesssim 10.5$ and becomes high (one over several hundred) at $\log M_{\star} \gtrsim 11$. At $10.5 \lesssim \log M_{\star} \lesssim 11$, the observed M_{BH} scatters around that expected from our $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\star}$ relation, although the scatter of M_{BH} is large at a given M_{\star} .

Fig. 4.16 also compares our $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\star}$ relation with measurements for local BL AGNs based on single-epoch spectra or reverberation mapping [32]. At $\log M_{\star} \lesssim 10.5$, these measurements broadly agree with our $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\star}$ relation and the measurements for normal galaxies. However, at higher M_{\star} , the M_{BH} for BL AGNs is systematically lower than the M_{BH} for normal galaxies at given M_{\star} . This discrepancy could result from large uncertainties in the M_{BH} measurements for BL AGNs (§4.4.3). For example, these M_{BH} measurements assume a single virial coefficient “ f ” for all sources, which might have systematic errors up to a factor of a few [165]. Another possibility is that the normal galaxies with M_{BH} measurements may not be representative of the entire galaxy population due to selection bias. [152] proposed that observations tend to select massive SMBHs for

calculation aims to characterize the average behavior for individual galaxies. Both accretion and mergers can contribute to the M_{BH} for individual galaxies, although we only consider the accretion component in Eq. 4.22.

Figure 4.16: Same format as the bottom-right panel in Fig. 4.15, but plotted against data points of local systems. The red points and blue squares indicate elliptical and disk galaxies, respectively, with M_{BH} measurements from stellar dynamics or megamasers. The disk galaxies include S0 and spiral galaxies. The data point representing the Milky Way is labeled as “MW” at its lower right. The pink and purple stars represent local BL AGNs based on M_{BH} measurements of single-epoch spectra and reverberation mapping, respectively. The blue and orange lines indicate the $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\text{bulge}}$ relations from [8] and [4], respectively; the green solid line represents the local “unbiased” $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\star}$ relation from [152].

which M_{BH} measurements are achievable. They argued that this selection effect might strongly bias the observed $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\star}$ relation in the local universe, and they presented an intrinsic $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\star}$ relation (the green curve in Fig. 4.16). However, our model M_{BH} does not suffer from this selection bias but is generally higher than that of [152] at any given M_{\star} . This discrepancy suggests that the selection bias might not be as strong as they proposed.

Fig. 4.17 shows the $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\text{halo}}$ relation converted from our $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\star}$ relation (see §4.4.1 for the method). The relation is steep ($M_{\text{BH}} \propto M_{\text{halo}}$; the green dashed line) at $\log M_{\text{halo}} \lesssim 13$, but flattens at higher M_{halo} ($M_{\text{BH}} \propto M_{\text{halo}}^{0.4}$; the red dash-dotted line). This behavior qualitatively agrees with [4] who assumed $M_{\text{bulge}} \approx M_{\star}$. The flattening is expected from the weak $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ dependence on M_{halo} in massive systems (see Fig. 4.9).

Figure 4.17: The local $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\text{halo}}$ relation. The black solid curve indicates our best-fit model assuming $M_{\text{BH}}/M_{\star}|_{z=4} = 1/500$. The curve flattens toward high M_{halo} . The green dashed and red dash-dotted lines indicate $M_{\text{BH}} \propto M_{\text{halo}}$ and $M_{\text{BH}} \propto M_{\text{halo}}^{0.4}$, respectively; they are normalized at $\log M_{\text{halo}} = 12$ and 15 , respectively. These two lines are not from fitting but are just to guide the eye.

4.5 Summary and Future Prospects

We have derived $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ as a function of M_{\star} and redshift for galaxies with $\log M_{\star} = 9.5-12$ and $z = 0.4-4$. Our method is based on survey data from GOODS-S, GOODS-N, and COSMOS, as well as the SMF and XLF from the literature. Our main results are summarized below:

1. $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ generally increases toward high M_{\star} at a given redshift (see §4.3.4.1 and 4.4.1). This M_{\star} dependence becomes weaker toward the local universe. For example, from $\log M_{\star} = 9.5$ to $\log M_{\star} = 11.5$, $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ increases by a factor of $\sim 10^3$ at $z \approx 4$ while the factor is only ~ 10 at $z \approx 0.5$. This is probably due to the increasing fraction of quiescent galaxies at low redshift and high M_{\star} , as the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_{\star}$ slope does not become much shallower toward low

redshift for star-forming galaxies (see §4.3.4.2). At a given M_* , $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ is higher toward high redshift, and this redshift dependence is stronger for more massive systems, e.g., for $\log M_* \approx 11.5$, $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ is \approx three decades higher at $z = 4$ than at $z = 0.5$. This strong redshift evolution for massive galaxies is plausibly explained by AGN feedback.

2. At a given M_* , $\overline{\text{BHAR}}/\overline{\text{SFR}}$ has weak redshift evolution at $z \gtrsim 0.8$. At a given redshift, $\overline{\text{BHAR}}/\overline{\text{SFR}}$ depends positively on M_* . These features also exist when limiting the sample to star-forming galaxies. This positive dependence is inconsistent with the scenario that SMBH and galaxy growth are in lockstep. We have converted the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_*$ relation to the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_{\text{halo}}$ relation based on the recipe of [31]. $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ positively depends on M_{halo} at $\log M_{\text{halo}} \lesssim 12\text{--}13$ but becomes flat at higher M_{halo} , indicating SMBH growth is not well traced by M_{halo} in massive systems.
3. Based on our $\overline{\text{BHAR}}(M_*, z)$, $M_*(z)$ from [31], and the assumption of $M_{\text{BH}}/M_*|_{z=4}$, we have derived the $M_{\text{BH}}-M_*$ relation at different redshifts (see §4.4.3). At $z \lesssim 2$, our $M_{\text{BH}}-M_*$ relation does not strongly depend on the $M_{\text{BH}}/M_*|_{z=4}$ assumption. The M_{BH}/M_* ratio is higher toward massive galaxies: it rises from $\approx 1/5000$ at $\log M_* \lesssim 10.5$ to $\approx 1/500$ at $\log M_* \gtrsim 11.2$. Our results suggest the $M_{\text{BH}}-M_*$ relation is already largely in place at $z \approx 2$. However, the M_{BH} expected from our $M_{\text{BH}}-M_*$ relation at $\log M_* \lesssim 11$ is significantly lower than that from the observations of BL AGNs at $z \gtrsim 0.5$. This discrepancy might be due to selection biases and/or inaccuracy of direct M_{BH} measurements of distant BL AGNs.
4. Our predicted $M_{\text{BH}}-M_*$ relation (at $z = 0$) is similar to the local $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\text{bulge}}$ relation at $\log M_* \gtrsim 11$, suggesting that mergers do not dominate over accretion in the SMBH growth of giant ellipticals. At $\log M_* \lesssim 10.5$, our $M_{\text{BH}}-M_*$ relation broadly agrees with the observations of local normal galaxies and BL AGNs. At higher M_* , our predicted M_{BH} are broadly consistent with those of normal galaxies but are systematically higher than those of BL AGNs. We have also derived the $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\text{halo}}$ relation at $z = 0$ using the M_*-M_{halo} relation from [31]. Similar to the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_{\text{halo}}$ relation, $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\text{halo}}$ relation is steep ($M_{\text{BH}} \propto M_{\text{halo}}$) at $\log M_{\text{halo}} \lesssim 13$ but becomes relatively flat ($M_{\text{BH}} \propto M_{\text{halo}}^{0.4}$) at higher M_{halo} .

In this work, we do not study SMBH growth at $z < 0.4$ due to the limited sample size at low redshifts. Although SMBH accretion in the low- z epoch should not affect the $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\star}$ relation significantly (see §4.4.3), it is critical for understanding how SMBH-galaxy coevolution develops from high redshifts to the local universe. Future work could combine wide-field optical/NIR (e.g., SDSS, UKIDSS, and 2MASS) and X-ray (e.g., *Swift*/BAT, *Chandra* Source Catalog, and 3XMM) surveys to investigate the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_{\star}$ relation at low redshift [198, 318, 319]. We also do not investigate SMBH growth for quiescent galaxies (see §4.3.4.3); future studies could derive their $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_{\star}$ relation.

The scatter of the observed local $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\star}$ relation is large (Fig. 4.16). At least one origin of this scatter is related to $M_{\star}(z)$ (see Footnote 5 and Eq. 4.22). We use average $M_{\star}(z)$ in this work while individual galaxies have different stellar mass histories. This aspect can be investigated based on the $M_{\star}(z)$ for individual systems from numerical simulations such as Illustris [320]. Another origin of the large scatter may be that $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ is dependent on other galaxy properties such as SFR, morphology, and cosmic environment in addition to M_{\star} (see, e.g., §4.3.4.2 and [196, 248, 321]). The detailed $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ dependence on SFR and morphology can be investigated using the CANDELS survey fields where deep *Chandra*, *Herschel*, and *HST* observations are available. The $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ dependence on environment can be studied using surveys of several deg^2 such as COSMOS and X-SERVS (Chen et al. in prep.), where reliable environmental measurements can be performed [220].

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Disclaimer

The findings and conclusions do not necessarily reflect the view of the funding agencies.

4.6 Supplementary Materials

4.6.1 Modeling of $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_{\star}, z)$

We describe $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_{\star}, z)$ at given M_{\star} and redshift with a smoothed double power law, and each parameter in this function ($\log A$, $\log L_{\text{c}}$, γ_1 , and γ_2) is modeled as a polynomial function of $\log M_{\star}$ and $\log(1+z)$ (see §4.3.3). To decide the orders of the polynomial functions, we utilize the Akaike information criterion (AIC; e.g. [254]). The AIC technique is applicable to any log-likelihood function, and it does not assume a specific distribution of parameter uncertainties. For a given polynomial model, the AIC value is calculated as $\text{AIC} = -2 \ln L_{\text{max}} + 2k$, where k is the number of free model parameters and $\ln L_{\text{max}}$ is the maximum value of the likelihood function in Eq. 4.14. $\ln L_{\text{max}}$ is calculated with the maximum-likelihood fitting method in §4.3.3. The AIC balances the complexity of the model and its efficiency in describing the data. In general, models with smaller AIC values are considered as more probable.

Assuming the currently favored model has an AIC value of AIC_{F} and a proposed

model has an AIC value of AIC_P , we accept the proposed model as the new favored model if $\Delta\text{AIC} = \text{AIC}_P - \text{AIC}_F < \Delta\text{AIC}_T$. We choose the AIC threshold as $\Delta\text{AIC}_T = -7$ (e.g., Chapter 2.6 of [254]). This value corresponds to a 3σ confidence level in the case when parameter uncertainties are Gaussian [255].

We first use a model of constant $\log A$, $\log L_c$, γ_1 , and γ_2 (i.e., 0th-order polynomials), and obtain $\text{AIC}_F = 24998.7$. We then test the 1st-order polynomial models of $\log A$, i.e.,

$$\log A = \log A_0 + \alpha_0^A \log(1+z) + \alpha_1^A \log M_{10}. \quad (4.23)$$

The fitting of the 1st-order polynomial model produces $\text{AIC}_P = 18164.2$, and thus the change of AIC is $\Delta\text{AIC} = \text{AIC}_P - \text{AIC}_F = -6834.5 < \Delta\text{AIC}_T$. Therefore, we accept the 1st-order polynomial model of $\log A$, and with this model, we further test the 1st-order models of $\log L_c$, γ_1 , and γ_2 . We find that the 1st-order models of $\log L_c$ and γ_2 significantly reduces the AIC value (< -7). Thus, γ_1 is consistent with a model that has no redshift or M_\star dependence.

We further test higher-order polynomial models of $\log A$, $\log L_c$, and γ_2 . The required polynomial orders for $\log A$, $\log L_c$, and γ_2 are 2nd, 2nd, and 1st, respectively. After determining the orders of the polynomials and obtaining the best-fit model parameters, we estimate the parameter uncertainties utilizing Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) sampling with EMCEE [250].⁹ The 2D contours and 1D histograms of the sampling results are shown in Fig. 4.18. The 1σ confidence range of a parameter is calculated as the 16%–84% percentile range of the corresponding 1D histogram (shown as the vertical dashed lines in Fig. 4.18). We use the same method to derive uncertainties shown in Fig. 4.9. The best-fit parameters and the MCMC uncertainties are presented in Tab. 4.2. From Fig. 4.18, the contours can be highly tilted and/or irregular (e.g., β_0^L vs. α_0^L), and thus the parametric uncertainties in Tab. 4.2 can be strongly correlated.

4.6.2 $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_\star, z)$ Fitting Quality

In Fig. 4.19, we compare the observed XLFs (§4.2.2) and the XLFs derived from our best-fit model (Eq. 4.6). The model XLFs generally agree well with the observed

⁹<http://dan.iel.fm/emcee/current/>

Figure 4.18: 2D contours and 1D histograms for our MCMC sampling results. The vertical dashed lines in the histograms indicate the 1σ confidence intervals. The contour confidence levels are 1σ (68.3%) and 2σ (95.5%), respectively. The grayscale pixels inside the 1σ contour denote probability with darken color indicating higher probability. The points outside the 2σ contour represent individual MCMC sampling. This figure is plotted using CORNOR.PY [322]. Some contours are highly irregular/tilted, indicating strongly correlated parametric uncertainties.

values. Fig. 4.19 also shows the observed XLFs that are not used to constrain $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ ($\log L_X < 43$; open symbols). At $z \gtrsim 0.8$, our model XLFs are consistent with the observed values at $\log L_X < 43$. At lower redshifts, our model underestimates the XLFs at $\log L_X \approx 42.5$. This underestimation might be due to the fact that our model XLFs do not include low- L_{SX} AGNs and XRBs (see 4.2.2).

In Fig. 4.20, we compare the best-fit $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ with the binned values from our sample, utilizing the $N_{\text{obs}}/N_{\text{mdl}}$ method, where N_{obs} and N_{mdl} are the observed and model-expected numbers of sources in the bin, respectively [59]. Specifically, we derive the N_{mdl} from the best-fit $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ using Eq. 4.3. The binned $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ value is calculated as the model $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ value scaled by a factor of $N_{\text{obs}}/N_{\text{mdl}}$, while the corresponding uncertainty is the 1σ Poisson error of N_{obs} scaled by the same factor. In the bin of $z = 0.4\text{--}0.7$ and $\log M_* = 11.5\text{--}12$ where no AGNs are detected, we derive the 1σ Poisson upper limits using the approach in [323]. The model $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ is generally consistent with the observed values. However, we note that at $z \lesssim 1$ and $\log M_* \gtrsim 11.5$, the constraints on $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ are weak. In this case, the $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ is largely based on model extrapolation and the uncertainties are likely underestimated.

We also compare our best-fit $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ with those derived in some previous studies in Fig. 4.20.¹⁰ [59], [60], and [261] adopted simple power-law models, and the slopes are (almost) independent of M_* and redshift, similar to our results (see Tab. 4.2). [59] and [261] probed $\log(L_{\text{SX}}) \lesssim -0.5$; their slopes are ≈ 0.4 and ≈ 0.6 , respectively, similar to the low- L_{SX} slope in our model. Their normalizations are dependent on redshift but not M_* , while our normalization depends on both factors. Therefore, their normalizations should be considered as averaged over the M_* range of their samples. The relatively flat power-law shape at low-to-moderate L_{SX} is also confirmed by two recent studies [247, 248] that adopt non-parametric modeling for $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$.¹¹ These two studies also identified a sharp drop of $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ above $\log L_{\text{SX}} \approx 0$, similar to our results. [60] obtained a steeper slope (≈ 1.0); the reason could be that they probed L_{SX} above the break L_{SX} , where the slope is steep L_{SX} above the break L_{SX} , where the slope is steep (≈ 2.5 in our model; see Tab. 4.2). Thus, it is understandable that their slope is between our low- L_{SX} and high- L_{SX} slopes. [288] modeled the bivariate distribution function of M_* and redshift, i.e., $\Psi(L_{\text{SX}}, M_*, z)$, and we convert it to $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ by dividing it by our adopted SMF (§4.2.2). The resulting $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ shape is also a double power law. Their low- L_{SX} slope depends on redshift and is steeper than our low- L_{SX} slope at $z \lesssim 1.5$. From our data, it appears [288] overestimated the low- L_{SX} slope. A

¹⁰We do not compare with the studies that investigate λ_{Edd} distributions [324, 325], since it is not feasible to convert their λ_{Edd} distribution to $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$.

¹¹The results of $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ in [248] and [247] are not publicly available. Therefore, their $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ curves are not shown in Fig. 4.20.

Figure 4.19: The XLFs in redshift bins from $z = 0.4-4$. The solid curves are the XLFs derived from our best-fit $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ model. The data points indicate the soft-band XLFs from [13]. The solid symbols represent the XLFs used in this work; the open symbols represent the XLFs below our L_X threshold (see §4.2.2). The XLFs from our model fit the observed data acceptably in general.

possible reason for this difference might be that they did not include the ultra-deep fields (GOODS-S and GOODS-N) that are critical in constraining the low- L_{SX} slope.

Figure 4.20: $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ for different M_* and redshift ranges. The solid curves with blue, orange, green, red, and purple colors indicate our best-fit $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ model, and the shaded regions indicate the 1σ confidence intervals. For each of the seven redshift ranges, the first five panels display the probability distributions for five M_* ranges; the last panel compares our best-fit $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ for these M_* ranges. The data points indicate the binned $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ values from our sample. The error bars (upper limit) indicate the Poisson 1σ confidence level. The brown curves represent $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ from the literature. Our best-fit model is in agreement with the data. The brown lines indicate $P(L_{\text{SX}}|M_*, z)$ from different studies. Here, we only present the figures for $z = 0.4-0.7$ and $z = 1.0-1.5$ for display purposes; the entire set of 6 figures for the other redshift ranges is available in the online version of the journal.

Figure 4.20

Chapter 5 | Evident Black Hole-Bulge Co- evolution in the Distant Uni- verse

5.1 Introduction

One of the essential challenges of extragalactic astronomy is to understand the connection between supermassive black holes (SMBHs) and their host galaxies. It is well established that the masses of SMBHs (M_{BH}) are tightly correlated with the stellar masses of host-galaxy classical bulges (M_{bulge}) in the local universe (the Magorrian relation; e.g. [4–8]). The intrinsic scatter of the $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\text{bulge}}$ correlation is only ≈ 0.3 dex [4]. This tight correlation is surprising considering that M_{BH} is only a tiny fraction (a few thousandths) of M_{bulge} . Therefore, some fundamental connections between the growth of SMBHs and host-galaxy bulges likely exist over cosmic history. These physical connections are often termed as “SMBH-bulge coevolution”.

Tremendous observational efforts have been made to identify these mysterious connections. It has been found that the cosmic evolution of SMBH accretion rate (BHAR) density and star formation rate (SFR) density are broadly similar, both peaking at $z \sim 2$ [9–13]. However, from observations of active galactic nuclei (AGNs), the SFR is a relatively flat function of the observed BHAR at a given redshift [14–20]. This apparent lack of a strong SFR-BHAR connection might be caused by AGN variability. While star formation activity is stable on time scales

longer than ~ 100 Myr, SMBH accretion could vary strongly on much shorter time scales ($\approx 10^2\text{--}10^7$ yr; e.g. [21–24]). An intrinsic connection between SFR and long-term average BHAR might be hidden by this strong AGN variability.

To obtain long-term average BHAR, the ideal way is to observe a galaxy for at least millions of years, which is presently infeasible. Practically, it has been proposed to adopt sample-averaged BHAR ($\overline{\text{BHAR}}$) as a proxy of long-term average BHAR [25, 26]. Indeed, a positive $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -SFR connection has been observed [18, 25, 26, 206]. However, [206] show, via partial correlation analyses (PCOR), that $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ is actually more strongly related to host-galaxy total stellar mass (M_\star) than SFR (also see [326] for a similar conclusion). Their results suggest that the apparent $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -SFR relation is only a secondary effect resulting from a primary $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ - M_\star relation and the star-formation main sequence. [327] further show that once M_\star is carefully controlled, SMBH accretion is largely independent of the cosmic environment of the host galaxies, consistent with previous AGN clustering studies (e.g. [27]; [28]; [29]; [30]). Motivated by the important role of M_\star in connecting SMBHs and host galaxies, [209] quantitatively derived the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ - M_\star relation at different redshifts up to $z = 4$. Aided by the stellar-mass history from [31], [209] predicted the typical M_{BH} - M_\star relation in the local universe. At the massive end ($M_\star \gtrsim 10^{11.2} M_\odot$) of their M_{BH} - M_\star relation, their M_{BH}/M_\star ratio is $\approx 1/500$, similar to observed $M_{\text{BH}}/M_{\text{bulge}}$ values (e.g. [8]; [4]). This agreement is expected, as the bulge becomes dominant and $M_{\text{bulge}} \approx M_\star$ for massive galaxies.

Despite the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ - M_\star relation being generally supported by observations, it cannot straightforwardly explain the tightness of the M_{BH} - M_{bulge} correlation. The key to the origin of the tight M_{BH} - M_{bulge} correlation might be related to the morphology of host galaxies, since M_{BH} is only correlated with the masses of classical bulges rather than other galactic components such as pseudo-bulges or disks (e.g. [4] and references therein). Therefore, SMBH growth might be related to star formation activity of the bulge only. To investigate this potential SMBH-bulge coevolution, one should ideally study the relation between $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ and bulge SFR in the distant universe. However, with current facilities, it is infeasible to separate the bulge SFR from total SFR when disks are present. In this work, we focus on a sample of bulge-dominated galaxies for which bulge SFR \approx total SFR. If SMBHs indeed coevolve with host-galaxy bulges, we expect a strong correlation between $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ and SFR for these bulge-dominated galaxies over cosmic history.

Our bulge-dominated sample is selected from the Cosmic Assembly Near-Infrared Deep Extragalactic Legacy Survey (CANDELS) where deep *HST* *H*-band observations are available [65, 66]. X-ray emission is a robust tracer of SMBH accretion (e.g. [80] and references therein). The CANDELS fields also have deep *Chandra* X-ray observations, allowing us to estimate reliable $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ for any given sample of galaxies (e.g. [206, 327]).

This paper is structured as follows. In §5.2, we describe the data used in this work and define our samples. In §5.3, we perform data analyses and present the results. We discuss our results in §5.4. We summarize our work and discuss future prospects in §5.5.

Throughout this paper, we assume a cosmology with $H_0 = 70 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$, $\Omega_M = 0.3$, and $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.7$. We adopt a Chabrier initial mass function (IMF; [68]). Quoted uncertainties are at the 1σ (68%) confidence level. We express M_{bulge} , M_\star , and M_{BH} in units of M_\odot , SFR and $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ in units of $M_\odot \text{ yr}^{-1}$. L_X indicates AGN X-ray luminosity at rest-frame 2–10 keV and is in units of erg s^{-1} .

5.2 Data and Sample

Our analyses are based on the five CANDELS fields, i.e., GOODS-S, GOODS-N, EGS, UDS, and COSMOS [65, 66]. All these fields have multiwavelength observations from *HST*, *Spitzer*, and ground-based telescopes such as Subaru and VLT. These high-quality data sets allow for measurements of galaxy morphology (§5.2.1), stellar mass (M_\star ; §5.2.2), and star-formation rate (SFR; §5.2.2). FIR observations from *Herschel* are also available in these fields, enabling robust SFR estimation based on cold-dust emission (§5.2.2). All of the five CANDELS fields have *Chandra* X-ray observations from which we derive $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ (§5.2.4). We define our sample in §5.2.3 and the sample properties are summarized in Tab. 5.1.

Field (1)	Area (2)	Gal. # (3)	Spec./Photo. # (4)	Galaxy Ref. (5)	B.-D. (X) (6)	Comp. (X) (7)	X. Dep. (8)	X-ray Ref. (9)
GOODS-S	170	1,504	727/777	[71]	398 (100)	1,106 (241)	7 Ms	[67]
GOODS-N	170	1,855	391/1,464	Barro et al., in prep.	483 (71)	1,372 (168)	2 Ms	[241]
EGS	200	2,446	219/2,227	[328]	591 (48)	1,855 (105)	800 ks	[329]
UDS	200	2,128	254/1,874	[71]	549 (42)	1,579 (75)	600 ks	[330]
COSMOS	220	2,369	10*/2,359	[331]	603 (22)	1,766 (39)	160 ks	[217]
Total	960	10,302	1,601/8,701	–	2,624 (283)	7,678 (628)	–	–

Table 5.1: Summary of sample properties (1) CANDELS field name. (2) Field area in arcmin². (3) Number of galaxies in our M_* -complete sample (§5.2.3). (4) Number of spec- z /photo- z sources (§5.2.2). (5) Reference for CANDELS galaxy catalog. (6) & (7) Sample size of bulge-dominated and comparison galaxies (§5.2.3). The number in parentheses means the sample size of X-ray detected sources. (8) X-ray depth in terms of exposure time (§5.2.4). (9) Reference for X-ray catalog.

* Although there are more than 500 spec- z available in COSMOS, the latest version of the COSMOS catalog is mostly based on photo- z . Future releases of the COSMOS catalog will adopt spec- z when available (H. Nayyeri 2018, private communication).

5.2.1 Morphology

Rest-frame optical/NIR light is essential for morphological measurements [168]. The *HST* *H* band, centered at $\approx 1.6 \mu\text{m}$, can cover rest-frame optical/NIR wavelengths up to $z \approx 3$. We adopt the *H*-band morphological measurements in [35] that are based on machine learning for CANDELS galaxies with $H < 24.5$. The machine-learning technique is chosen to approximate visual morphologies from humans, and is trained with a galaxy sample that has morphological measurements performed by human classifiers [332]. This training sample has the same magnitude cut ($H < 24.5$) as reliable visual morphological measurements are difficult at fainter magnitudes. For each galaxy, the [35] catalog provides five fractional numbers, i.e., f_{sph} , f_{disk} , f_{irr} , f_{pt} , and f_{unc} . These fractions represent the probabilities that a hypothetical classifier would have voted for a galaxy having a spheroid, a disk, and some irregularities, being point-like and unclassifiable, respectively. Note that the sum of the fractions might exceed unity, because, for example, a galaxy might have both spheroidal and disk features simultaneously.

A high f_{unc} value indicates that the source might be a spurious detection, e.g. the spikes of a bright star being falsely detected as a source (see, e.g. Fig. 13 of [35]). Sources with high f_{pt} value might be stars or broad-line (BL) AGNs. Due to strong light from the AGN central engine, morphology measurements of host galaxies are unreliable for luminous BL AGNs (e.g. §5.3 of [80]). We exclude the $\approx 8\%$ of sources that have f_{unc} or f_{pt} greater than any of f_{sph} , f_{disk} , and f_{irr} . Upon visual inspection, the excluded sources are indeed spurious detections or point-like. Morphological measurements are challenging at high redshift and our work probes up to $z = 3$. We discuss some possible redshift-related effects on our results in §5.3.4.

5.2.2 Redshift, Stellar Mass, and Star Formation Rate

We obtain redshift measurements from the CANDELS catalogs (see Tab. 5.1). These measurements are spectroscopic redshifts (spec- z) or photometric redshifts (photo- z). The photo- z measurements are based on dedicated photometry extracted with careful consideration of PSF sizes and source shapes (e.g. [69]; [333]). Compared to the available spec- z , the photo- z shows high quality, with $\sigma_{\text{NMAD}} = 0.018$ and

an outlier fraction of 2%.¹ As in §5.2.1, we discard the 79 spectroscopic BL AGNs reported in the literature ([75, 218, 292, 334, 335]; Suh et al., in prep.).

The CANDELS catalogs also provide stellar mass (M_*) and star formation rate (SFR) measurements from independent teams. Following [206], we adopt the median M_* and SFR values from the five available teams (2a $_{\tau}$, 6a $_{\tau}$, 11a $_{\tau}$, 13a $_{\tau}$, and 14a).² Fig. 5.1 (top) shows M_* as a function of redshift for $H < 24.5$ galaxies that have morphological measurements (§5.2.1). We limit our analyses to a M_* -complete (corresponding to $H < 24.5$) sample (§5.2.3). The limiting M_* (M_{lim}) for $H < 24.5$ is also displayed in Fig. 5.1. The M_{lim} -redshift curve is derived based on an empirical method (e.g. [215]). We first divide our sources into narrow redshift bins with width of $\Delta z = 0.2$. For each redshift bin, we calculate $\log M_{\text{lim}}^{\text{ind}} = \log M_* + 0.4 \times (H - 24.5)$ for individual galaxies in the bin. We then adopt M_{lim} as the 90th percentile of the $M_{\text{lim}}^{\text{ind}}$ distribution for the redshift bin.

The CANDELS M_* and SFR are based on SED fitting of rest-frame UV-to-NIR photometry using galaxy templates. As demonstrated by previous works [79, 206, 330], the rest-frame UV-to-NIR light is often predominantly contributed by galaxy component rather than the AGN component for X-ray AGNs in the CANDELS fields. Also, we have removed BL AGNs that might have strong AGN components in their UV-to-NIR SED. Therefore, the AGN SED contribution should not qualitatively affect our results (see §5.3.4 for other evidence).

The SED-based SFR estimation, which is physically based on obscuration-corrected UV light, is reliable for low-to-moderate levels ($\text{SFR} \lesssim 100 M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$) of star-formation activity. However, it tends to underestimate SFR in the high-SFR regime, possibly due to strong dust obscuration [70, 206, 336]. To alleviate this issue, we adopt SFR from FIR photometry of *Herschel* when available ([82]; [337]; [83]). The FIR-based SFR is more robust than the SED-based SFR, especially in the high-SFR regime [25, 206]. Due to limited sensitivity, *Herschel* can only detect sources with the highest SFR at a given redshift. There are five *Herschel* bands available for the CANDELS fields, i.e., 100 μm , 160 μm , 250 μm , 350 μm , and 500 μm . We only utilize robust detections with $\text{S/N} > 3$. We discard the 100 μm band at redshifts above $z = 1.5$, because the observed 100 μm corresponds

¹Here, σ_{NMAD} is defined as $1.48 \times \text{median}(\frac{|\Delta z - \text{median}(\Delta z)|}{1 + z_{\text{spec}}})$, and outliers are defined as sources having $|\Delta z| / (1 + z_{\text{spec}}) > 0.15$.

²For GOODS-N, only three teams are available (2a $_{\tau}$, 6a $_{\tau}$, and 14a) for now.

to rest-frame $< 40 \mu\text{m}$ which might be contaminated by hot-dust emission powered by AGN activity. We adopt the reddest available *Herschel* band to estimate SFR, since longer wavelengths are “freer” from possible AGN emission. We calculate SFR from FIR flux following the procedure in [25] and [206]. We first derive galaxy total IR luminosity (L_{IR}) from FIR flux based on the star-forming galaxy templates of [84]. We adopt the $z \sim 1$ and $z \sim 2$ templates for $z < 1.5$ and $z \geq 1.5$ sources, respectively. We then obtain SFR as

$$\frac{\text{SFR}}{M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}} = 1.09 \times 10^{-10} \frac{L_{\text{IR}}}{L_{\odot}}. \quad (5.1)$$

Fig. 5.1 (middle) shows SFR (based on SED or FIR) as a function of redshift for all $H < 24.5$ galaxies. The FIR-based SFR is reliable in the high-SFR regime. In the low-to-moderate SFR regime, where dust extinction is not strong, the SED-based SFR should be reliable as obscuration corrections are relatively mild [70, 206, 336]. The comparison sample has a higher fraction of FIR-based SFR measurements than the bulge-dominated sample (32% vs. 9%), because the former generally has stronger star-formation activity than the latter. To investigate whether this difference in SFR measurements could bias our results, we have tested cutting our $z = 0.5\text{--}1.5$ ($z = 1.5\text{--}3$) sample at $\text{SFR} < 10 M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ ($\text{SFR} < 10^{1.5} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$), below which the SFR measurements are mostly SED-based (see Fig. 5.1). Under these cuts, our results do not change qualitatively.³ We have also tested using SED-based SFR for the entire sample and our conclusions still hold. Therefore, our main conclusions are unlikely to depend on the technical details of SFR measurements.

5.2.3 The Bulge-Dominated and Comparison Samples

Our analyses are based on a bulge-dominated sample and a comparison sample. In this Section, we detail the selections of these two samples. We first select all $H < 24.5$ galaxies for which morphology measurements are available (§5.2.1). As in §5.2.1 and §5.2.2, we exclude BL AGNs, stars, and false detections. We then divide these galaxies into two redshift bins, i.e., $z = 0.5\text{--}1.5$ and $z = 1.5\text{--}3.0$ for our analyses. The relatively broad redshift bins are necessary to guarantee sufficiently large samples for our statistical analyses (§5.3). We have also tested on

³We cannot perform a similar test for high-SFR galaxies with *Herschel* detections, because the sample size of *Herschel*-detected sources is too small.

Figure 5.1: M_* , SFR, and L_X as a function of redshift for the bulge-dominated (left) and comparison (right) samples. The contours encircle 68%, 90%, and 95% of all $H < 24.5$ galaxies, respectively. The red points represent X-ray detected sources. In the top panels, the dashed curve indicates the M_* completeness limit (§5.2.2). In the middle panels, the dashed curve indicates the SFR values above which 70% of sources have FIR-based SFR (§5.2.2).

narrower redshift bins and found our qualitative results do not change, although the statistical scatter becomes larger due to reduced sample sizes. Therefore, the two wide redshift bins ($z = 0.5\text{--}1.5$ and $z = 1.5\text{--}3.0$) should not bias our results, and we adopt them throughout this paper.

We select M_* -complete samples for the two redshift bins. The limiting M_* at $z = 1.5$ and $z = 3.0$ are $\log M_* \approx 9.7$ and $\log M_* \approx 10.2$, respectively (see Fig. 5.1). Therefore, we limit our analyses to $\log M_* > 9.7$ and $\log M_* > 10.2$ galaxies for the low and high redshift bins, respectively. These M_* thresholds are

below the characteristic M_\star of the stellar-mass function (SMF), i.e., $\log M_\star \approx 10.6$ at $z \approx 0.5\text{--}3$ [109, 216]. The stellar-mass density above these M_\star cuts is $\approx 90\%$ and $\approx 70\%$ of the total for the low and high redshift bins, respectively (calculated with the SMF in [31]). After applying the M_\star cuts, our sample does not include dwarf galaxies ($\log M_\star \lesssim 9.5$). Aside from technical constraints, the exclusion of dwarf galaxies is also motivated by our major science goal, i.e. investigating the origin of the $M_{\text{BH}}\text{--}M_{\text{bulge}}$ relation. Since the $M_{\text{BH}}\text{--}M_{\text{bulge}}$ relation is mostly established for $\log M_{\text{bulge}} \gtrsim 10$ [4], we should also focus on relatively massive galaxies rather than dwarf galaxies.

The basic properties of the M_\star -complete sample are summarized in Tab. 5.1. In the M_\star -complete sample, we classify a source as bulge-dominated if it satisfies $f_{\text{sph}} \geq 2/3$, $f_{\text{disk}} < 2/3$, and $f_{\text{irr}} < 1/10$. These empirical criteria are suggested by several previous studies (e.g. [36, 37, 332].) If it does not meet these criteria, we include it in our comparison sample, i.e., galaxies that are not bulge-dominated. The bulge-dominated and comparison samples have $\approx 2,600$ and $7,700$ galaxies, respectively (see Tab. 5.1). Our analyses in §5.3 are based on these two samples.

In Fig. 5.2, we show some random H -band cutouts for the bulge-dominated and comparison samples, respectively. The fractions of bulge-dominated galaxies are both $\approx 25\%$ for the low and high redshift bins. Fig. 5.3 shows the fraction of bulge-dominated galaxies as a function of M_\star and SFR, respectively. At the high- M_\star end ($\log M_\star \gtrsim 11$), the bulge-dominated fraction in the low-redshift bin is much higher than that in the high-redshift bin ($\approx 50\%$ vs. $\approx 20\%$). This is probably due to the fact that galaxy mergers/interactions for massive galaxies are increasingly prevalent toward high redshift, and thus galaxy irregularities are much stronger toward the early universe [168, 338]. The bulge-dominated fraction drops significantly toward high SFR, indicating that bulge-dominated galaxies tend to have low SFR. Similar trends have also been found in previous studies (e.g. [36, 37]). The underlying physical reason might be “morphological quenching”, such that bulges can effectively suppress star formation [339]. Fig. 5.4 displays the source distribution on the SFR- M_\star plane for the bulge-dominated and comparison samples, respectively. The bulge-dominated sample tends to lie below the star-formation main sequence, while the majority of the comparison sample appears to be on the main sequence. However, we note that our morphological classification is essentially different from a star-forming vs. quiescent classification. For example, the quiescent

Figure 5.2: Example H -band $3'' \times 3''$ cutouts for the bulge-dominated (left) and comparison (right) samples, and the X-ray undetected (top) and detected (bottom) samples. The galaxy of interest is placed at the center of each cutout. These galaxies are randomly selected from our sample in §5.2.3. Note that galaxies can simultaneously have high f_{sph} and f_{disk} values; these galaxies are not selected as bulge-dominated and are included in the comparison sample (see §5.2.3).

population in our sample is made up of $\approx 55\%$ bulge-dominated galaxies and $\approx 45\%$ comparison galaxies.

Figure 5.3: The fraction of bulge-dominated galaxies as a function of M_\star (left) and SFR (right). The error bars represent binomial uncertainties. The vertical dashed lines indicate the limiting M_\star corresponding to $H < 24.5$ (§5.2.2).

5.2.4 Black Hole Accretion Rate

All five CANDELS fields have deep X-ray observations from *Chandra*. Tab. 5.1 lists the X-ray depth and number of X-ray detected sources for each CANDELS field. We calculate $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ contributed by both X-ray detected and undetected sources, and thus the resulting $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ should cover essentially all SMBH accretion. This procedure allows us to seamlessly analyze all sources in different CANDELS fields which have different X-ray depths. We have also repeated our analyses but without sources in COSMOS, which has X-ray depth much shallower than other fields (see Tab. 5.1), and our results do not change qualitatively. For each X-ray detected source, we calculate L_X from the X-ray flux from the corresponding X-ray catalog assuming a photon index of $\Gamma = 1.7$ (e.g. [48]; [243]). Following [327], we choose, in order of priority, hard-band (observed-frame 2–7 keV), full-band (observed-

Figure 5.4: The SFR- M_* distribution for the bulge-dominated (top) and comparison (bottom) samples for $z = 0.5-1.5$ (left) and $z = 1.5-3.0$ (right). The contours encircle 68%, 90%, and 95% of sources, respectively. The red points represent X-ray detected sources. The dashed lines indicate the star-formation main sequence at $z = 0.98$ (left) and $z = 1.97$ (right), respectively [64]. $z = 0.98$ and $z = 1.97$ are the median redshifts for our sources at $z = 0.5-1.5$ and $z = 1.5-3.0$, respectively. The bulge-dominated sample tends to have lower SFR than the comparison sample.

frame 0.5–7 keV), or soft-band (observed-frame 0.5–2 keV) flux to minimize X-ray obscuration effects. Indeed, [327] estimated that, under this scheme of band choice, the X-ray flux decrease due to obscuration is typically small ($\approx 20\%$) for bright sources in CDF-S, for which there are enough photons to assess obscuration. We increase the X-ray fluxes of our X-ray sources by 20% to account for the average

systematic effect from obscuration.

For X-ray undetected sources, we employ a stacking technique to include their X-ray emission. We perform this process on full-band X-ray images.⁴ We generally follow the steps in [96], and we briefly summarize this procedure below. First, we mask X-ray detected sources in the X-ray images. We choose masking radii (R_{msk}) of $2 \times R_{90}$, $2.25 \times R_{90}$, and $2.5 \times R_{90}$ for sources with net counts < 100 , 100–1000, and > 1000 , respectively. Here, R_{90} means the radius for a 90% encircled-energy fraction (EEF), and it is a function of off-axis angle (see Appendix A of [96]). After source masking, we derive the net count rate for X-ray undetected sources. To enhance signal-to-noise, we adopt an aperture radius $R_{\text{aper}} = R_{80}$, R_{75} , R_{60} , and R_{40} for sources with off-axis angle $< 3.5'$, $3.5'–4.25'$, $4.25'–5.5'$, and $5.5'–7.8'$, respectively. We discard sources whose off-axis angle is $> 7.8'$ and/or whose apertures overlap with masked regions. The counts in the apertures include contributions from both sources and background, and we need to subtract the background counts. We estimate the background counts in an annulus with inner and outer radii of $1.1R_{90}$ and $1.1R_{90} + 10''$, respectively. Due to the limited aperture size, the net counts encircled in the aperture only represent a fraction of the total net counts. We perform an aperture correction for each source, depending on the aperture size adopted. For example, if $R_{\text{aper}} = R_{80}$ for a source, we divide the aperture net counts by 80% to recover the total net counts. We then obtain the count rate by dividing the total net counts by the exposure time at the position of the source. For sources in each field, we derive fluxes by multiplying the count rates by a constant factor, which is the median flux/count-rate ratio of X-ray detected sources in the field. Finally, for a group of X-ray undetected sources, we can obtain their average X-ray luminosity ($\overline{L_{X,\text{stack}}}$) from the average X-ray flux and redshift, assuming $\Gamma = 1.7$. Our derived SMBH accretion power is mostly contributed by the X-ray detected sources, and the stacking procedure typically accounts for less than 20% of the accretion power.

For X-ray detected objects, we have L_X for individual sources; for X-ray undetected sources, we have $\overline{L_{X,\text{stack}}}$ for any group of sources. We can then calculate

⁴For the EGS field, we use the X-ray image from [340], since [329] did not produce the X-ray image for the entire EGS field.

average AGN bolometric luminosity for any sample of sources as

$$\overline{L_{\text{bol}}} = \frac{\Sigma_{\text{det}}(L_X - L_{X,\text{XRB}})k_{\text{bol}} + (\overline{L_{X,\text{stack}}} - \overline{L_{X,\text{XRB}}})N_{\text{non}}\overline{k_{\text{bol}}}}{N_{\text{det}} + N_{\text{non}}} \quad (5.2)$$

Here, N_{det} and N_{non} are the numbers of X-ray detected and undetected sources in the sample. $L_{X,\text{XRB}}$ is the expected luminosity from X-ray binaries (XRBs) and $\overline{L_{X,\text{XRB}}}$ is the average XRB luminosity for the stacked sources. To obtain $L_{X,\text{XRB}}$ and $\overline{L_{X,\text{XRB}}}$, we adopt model 269 of [98] which describes XRB X-ray luminosity as a linear function of M_* and SFR. Model 269 is a theoretical model favored by the observations of galaxies at $z = 0-2$ [97]. The expected X-ray emission from XRBs only accounts for $\approx 15\%$ of the total X-ray power, and thus the uncertainties related to the XRB modelling should not affect our analyses significantly. k_{bol} and $\overline{k_{\text{bol}}}$ are the L_X -dependent bolometric corrections at $(L_X - L_{X,\text{XRB}})$ and $(\overline{L_{X,\text{stack}}} - \overline{L_{X,\text{XRB}}})$, respectively. We adopt the bolometric-correction model from [108].⁵ Assuming a constant radiative efficiency of $\epsilon = 0.1$, we can convert $\overline{L_{\text{bol}}}$ to $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ as

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{\text{BHAR}} &= \frac{(1 - \epsilon)\overline{L_{\text{bol}}}}{\epsilon c^2} \\ &= \frac{1.58\overline{L_{\text{bol}}}}{10^{46} \text{ erg s}^{-1}} M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}, \end{aligned} \quad (5.3)$$

where c is the speed of light. The adopted $\epsilon = 0.1$ is motivated by observations (see, e.g. §3.4 of [80]). We obtain the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ uncertainties with a bootstrapping technique (e.g. §2.3 of [206]).

As explained in §5.1, the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ quantity is designed to approximate long-term average SMBH accretion rate, and has been widely adopted in the studies of AGN-galaxy relations (e.g. [25, 26, 206, 209, 326, 327]). Some works proposed to recover the full distribution of BHAR as a function of galaxy properties (e.g. [57, 247, 248, 311]), and quantities such as $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ and duty cycle can then be derived. However, detailed modelling of the BHAR distribution at given M_* , SFR, and morphological type is beyond the scope of this work, and we leave it to future studies.

⁵As pointed out in Footnote 4 of [341], the k_{bol} in [108] appears to be overestimated due to the double counting of IR reprocessed emission. Following [341], we multiply the k_{bol} in [108] by a factor of 0.7 to address this issue.

5.3 Analyses and Results

In this Section, we study $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ as a function of SFR and M_\star (§5.3.1). We address the question of whether $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ is mainly related to SFR or M_\star in §5.3.2. All these analyses are performed for the bulge-dominated and comparison samples, respectively. In Appendix 5.6.1, we perform the same analyses for all galaxies. In §5.3.3, we quantify the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -SFR relation for the bulge-dominated sample.

5.3.1 BHAR as a Function of SFR and M_\star

We plot the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ as a function of SFR for our bulge-dominated and comparison samples, respectively, in Fig. 5.5 (black points). In each panel, the bins are chosen to include approximately the same number of sources, and this approach is to reach similar $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ signal-to-noise (S/N) ratios for the bins. Adjusting the bins does not change our conclusions qualitatively, although the statistical scatter of $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ measurements increases.

For the bulge-dominated sample, $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ rises strongly from low to high SFR by a factor of ≈ 400 ($z = 0.5\text{--}1.5$) and ≈ 100 ($z = 1.5\text{--}3.0$). In contrast, for the comparison sample, $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ only increases by a factor of ≈ 10 ($z = 0.5\text{--}1.5$) and ≈ 2 ($z = 1.5\text{--}3.0$) from low to high SFR. We show $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ vs. M_\star in Fig. 5.6 (black points). For the bulge-dominated sample, there is no strong correlation between $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ and M_\star . For the comparison sample, $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ appears to rise toward high M_\star in general. We note that, due to our limited sample size, statistical fluctuations can be strong sometimes. For example, for the black point at $\log M_\star \approx 9.8$ in Fig. 5.6 (right), the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ is mostly contributed by a single source. These fluctuations inevitably cause some scatter in Figs. 5.5 and 5.6.

5.3.2 Is $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ Mainly Related to SFR or M_\star ?

In this Section, we address the question of whether $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ is mainly related to SFR or M_\star for the bulge-dominated and comparison samples, respectively. The analysis methods here are similar to those in [206]. We compare our results with [206] in Appendix 5.6.1.

In Fig. 5.5, we divide each SFR bin into two bins with M_\star above and below the median M_\star of the SFR bin, respectively. In general, the high- M_\star and low- M_\star

Figure 5.5: $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ vs. SFR for bulge-dominated (left) and comparison (right) samples. The horizontal position of each data point indicates the median SFR of the sources in the bin. Each SFR sample is further divided into two subsamples, i.e., M_{\star} above (blue points) and below (red points) the median M_{\star} of the SFR sample, respectively. The black lines are the best-fit log-linear model to the black data points. The error bars represent a 1σ confidence level.

bins have similar $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ for the bulge-dominated sample. However, the high- M_{\star} bins have significantly higher $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ than the corresponding low- M_{\star} bins for the comparison sample. Similarly, in Fig. 5.6, we also divide each M_{\star} bin into high-SFR and low-SFR bins. The high-SFR bins have much higher $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ than the corresponding low-SFR bins for the bulge-dominated sample. In contrast, the high-SFR and low-SFR bins have similar $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ for the comparison sample. [342] found that, for compact galaxies, the star-forming population has elevated AGN activity compared to the quiescent population with matched M_{\star} at $z \approx 2$. However, for extended galaxies, the star-forming and quiescent populations have similar AGN activity. Since our bulge-dominated population is morphologically more compact than other galaxy populations in general [35], our results in Fig. 5.6 are broadly consistent with the findings of [342].

Figure 5.6: Same format as Fig. 5.5 but for $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ vs. M_{\star} .

The results above qualitatively indicate that $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ might primarily depend on SFR rather than M_{\star} for the bulge-dominated sample and that the situation is the opposite for the comparison sample. To further test this point, we perform partial-correlation (PCOR) analyses with PCOR.R in the R statistical package [249]. We first bin sources based on both SFR and M_{\star} and calculate $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ for each bin, and Fig. 5.7 shows the results. Following Fig. 5.5, the bins for the x -axis (y -axis) include similar numbers of sources. Adjusting the bins does not affect our results qualitatively. We input the median $\log M_{\star}$, median $\log \text{SFR}$, and $\log \overline{\text{BHAR}}$ in each bin to PCOR.R and calculate the significance levels for the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_{\star}$ and $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-\text{SFR}$ relations, respectively. The PCOR tests are performed with the Pearson and Spearman statistics, respectively, and the results are summarized in Tab. 5.2. These results show that, for the bulge-dominated sample, the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-\text{SFR}$ correlation is significant ($> 3\sigma$) while the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_{\star}$ correlation is not ($< 3\sigma$). For the comparison sample, the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_{\star}$ correlation is significant while the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-\text{SFR}$ correlation is not. These conclusions are also supported by Figs. 5.5 and

Figure 5.7: Color-coded $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ at different M_{\star} and SFR for bulge-dominated (left) and comparison (right) samples. The black plus sign indicates the median SFR and M_{\star} of the sources in each bin. The $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$, median M_{\star} , and median SFR are the input in our PCOR analyses (§5.3.2).

5.6.

Fig. 5.5 (left) is the key plot in this paper. It displays the strong $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -SFR connection and qualitatively demonstrates that the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -SFR relation cannot be significantly split by M_{\star} . We have also tested dividing each SFR bin by other galaxy properties (instead of M_{\star}) such as f_{disk} (§5.2.1) and rest-frame $U - V$ color, and none of these parameters can significantly split the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -SFR relation. Therefore, the strong $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -SFR correlation is likely fundamental.

Bulge-Dominated; $z = 0.5-1.5$		
Relation	Pearson	Spearman
$\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_\star$	0.03 (2.2σ)	0.02 (2.3σ)
$\overline{\text{BHAR}}-\text{SFR}$	$10^{-18.8}$ (9.0σ)	$10^{-13.3}$ (7.5σ)
Bulge-Dominated; $z = 1.5-3$		
Relation	Pearson	Spearman
$\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_\star$	0.26 (1.1σ)	0.44 (0.8σ)
$\overline{\text{BHAR}}-\text{SFR}$	$10^{-28.5}$ (11.2σ)	$10^{-5.2}$ (4.5σ)
Comparison; $z = 0.5-1.5$		
Relation	Pearson	Spearman
$\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_\star$	$10^{-7.7}$ (5.6σ)	$10^{-8.4}$ (5.9σ)
$\overline{\text{BHAR}}-\text{SFR}$	0.01 (2.5σ)	0.02 (2.3σ)
Comparison; $z = 1.5-3$		
Relation	Pearson	Spearman
$\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_\star$	$10^{-14.3}$ (7.8σ)	$10^{-4.5}$ (4.2σ)
$\overline{\text{BHAR}}-\text{SFR}$	0.20 (1.3σ)	0.97 (0.0σ)

Table 5.2: p -values (significances) of partial-correlation analyses for the bulge-dominated (top) and comparison (bottom) samples.

5.3.3 Quantification of the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-\text{SFR}$ Relation

In §5.3.2, we find that $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ is mainly correlated with SFR rather than M_\star for the bulge-dominated sample. To quantify this $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-\text{SFR}$ relation, we fit the data points in Fig. 5.5 (left; black points) with a log-linear model. For convenience, we list the sample properties of each data point in Tab. 5.3. We adopt a standard least- χ^2 fitting method implemented by a PYTHON package `SCIPY.OPTIMIZE.CURVE_FIT`. We first fit the data points in the two redshift bins independently, and the results are

$$\log \overline{\text{BHAR}} = \begin{cases} (0.88 \pm 0.07) \log \text{SFR} - (2.56 \pm 0.08), & z = 0.5-1.5 \\ (0.89 \pm 0.08) \log \text{SFR} - (2.38 \pm 0.09), & z = 1.5-3 \end{cases} \quad (5.4)$$

Considering the best-fit parameters are similar for the two redshift bins, we fit all the data points in both redshift bins simultaneously. The best-fit model is

$$\log \overline{\text{BHAR}} = (0.92 \pm 0.04) \log \text{SFR} - (2.47 \pm 0.05), \quad (5.5)$$

where the errors are calculated under a 68% confidence level. The reduced χ^2 of the fit is 0.8 (p -value = 53%), showing that the fit quality is acceptable. Considering

that the slope of the best-fit model is close to unity, we also fit the data with slope fixed to unity. This procedure results in

$$\log \overline{\text{BHAR}} = \log \text{SFR} - (2.48 \pm 0.05). \quad (5.6)$$

The fit quality is also acceptable, with reduced χ^2 of 1.2 (p -value = 32%). This best-fit model is displayed in Fig. 5.5 (left). The best-fit $\overline{\text{BHAR}}/\text{SFR}$ ratio in this model is $10^{-2.48}$.

Our $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ does not include the accretion from BL AGNs (§5.2). Here, we consider this missed accretion power statistically. We first construct a non-BL AGN sample with L_X and redshift matched with the spectroscopic BL AGN sample (§5.2.2): for each BL AGN, we randomly select a “nearby” non-BL AGN in the L_X - z plane (within $\log L_X \pm 0.15$ and $z \pm 0.2$). We find that $\approx 35\%$ of these non-BL AGNs reside in bulge-dominated galaxies. Assuming, following the unified model, that a similar fraction of BL AGNs have bulge-dominated hosts, we find that the missed accretion power (contributed by BL AGNs) is $\approx 40\%$ of the observed accretion power for bulge-dominated galaxies. Therefore, after including the accretion power of BL AGNs, the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}/\text{SFR}$ ratio might be slightly higher (≈ 0.15 dex) than the best-fit value. We note that errors resulting from radiative-efficiency and IMF uncertainties likely exist, and thus the best-fit value of $\overline{\text{BHAR}}/\text{SFR}$ inevitably suffers from systematic uncertainty up to a factor of a few. However, the systematic uncertainties should not affect our main qualitative conclusion, i.e. $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ primarily depends on SFR among bulge-dominated galaxies.

Considering the importance of SMBH-galaxy growth among bulge-dominated galaxies, we also plot AGN fraction as a function of SFR in Fig. 5.8. Here, we count an X-ray source as an “AGN” if it has $\log L_X > 42.8$ ($z = 0.5$ – 1.5) or $\log L_X > 43.5$ ($z = 1.5$ – 3). These thresholds are the L_X limits at $z = 1.5$ and $z = 3$, respectively, for a 0.5–10 keV flux limit of 8.9×10^{-16} erg cm $^{-2}$ s $^{-1}$. This flux limit is the detection limit of the COSMOS survey [217], which is the shallowest CANDELS X-ray survey (Tab. 5.1). $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ is mainly driven by duty cycle and average accretion rate of AGNs. From Fig. 5.8, AGN fraction increases toward high SFR for both redshift bins. This result indicates that the positive $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -SFR relation is, at least partially, due to the rise of AGN duty cycle toward high SFR. Detailed quantitative analyses of AGN duty cycle and average accretion rate require the full distribution

Bulge-Dominated; $z = 0.5\text{--}1.5$					
log SFR	log M_*	log BHAR	Gal. #	X. #	AGN #
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
-1.97	10.24	$-4.35^{+0.17}_{-0.17}$	360	14	0
-1.24	10.44	$-3.67^{+0.14}_{-0.16}$	360	20	1
-0.71	10.48	$-2.82^{+0.20}_{-0.39}$	360	29	6
0.14	10.25	$-2.41^{+0.12}_{-0.15}$	360	46	15
1.05	10.19	$-1.69^{+0.12}_{-0.17}$	361	69	36
Bulge-Dominated; $z = 1.5\text{--}3$					
log SFR	log M_*	log BHAR	Gal. #	X. #	AGN #
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
-0.90	10.62	$-3.27^{+0.15}_{-0.21}$	274	7	0
-0.01	10.64	$-2.28^{+0.13}_{-0.18}$	274	21	4
1.47	10.59	$-1.08^{+0.09}_{-0.11}$	275	77	41

Table 5.3: Properties of each bin in Fig. 5.5 (left; black points). (1) & (2) Median log SFR and log M_* . (3) log BHAR and its uncertainties. (4) Number of galaxies. (5) Number of X-ray sources. (6) Number of AGNs as defined in Fig. 5.8.

of BHAR (see §5.2.4), for which we leave to future studies.

5.3.4 Reliability Checks

Our M_* and SFR measurements are mostly based on SED fitting of rest-frame UV-to-NIR photometry, and we have removed BL AGNs from our sample to avoid strong AGN SED components that might affect our results (§5.2.2 and §5.3.3). Also, from Fig. 5.2, the X-ray detected sources do not appear to have strong central point-like emission, indicating that the presence of AGNs should not significantly affect the M_* , SFR, and morphology measurements. Also, if potential AGN SED contamination significantly biased our analyses, we would expect to reach a similar conclusion for bulge-dominated and comparison samples, which is not the case (§5.3.2). Therefore, we consider that our conclusions are not biased by AGN SED contamination.

Our bulge-dominated galaxies at $z = 0.5\text{--}3$ are selected utilizing machine-learning morphological measurements based on *HST* *H*-band imaging (§5.2.1 and §5.2.3). Morphological measurements at high redshift are challenging due to effects such as redshifting of photons and image degradation (e.g. [168] and references therein). Detailed assessment of these redshift effects on our results requires careful simulations of *HST* imaging and repetition of the machine-learning measurements

on the simulated data. These procedures are beyond the scope of this work. Here, we qualitatively discuss the robustness of our results against such redshift effects.

Due to the redshifting of photons, the same observed-frame wavelength covers different rest-frame wavelengths at different redshifts. The correction for this redshifting effect is named the “morphological k -correction”. From multiwavelength observations of local galaxies, [343] found that the morphological k -correction is weak in the optical/NIR wavelength range (≈ 0.36 – $0.85 \mu\text{m}$, where $0.36 \mu\text{m}$ corresponds to the Balmer break and $0.85 \mu\text{m}$ is the longest wavelength available in their work), especially for elliptical/S0 galaxies. For our work, the observed-frame H band (used for morphological measurements; §5.2.1) does not reach out to rest-frame UV photons below the Balmer break at $z = 0.5$ – 3 , and it corresponds to the rest-frame NIR ($\approx 1 \mu\text{m}$) and optical ($\approx 0.4 \mu\text{m}$) light at $z = 0.5$ and $z = 3$, respectively. Also, considering that we only utilize the morphological information for a basic selection of bulge-dominated galaxies rather than, e.g. a quantitative measurement of galaxy size, we conclude that the morphological k -correction should not affect our results qualitatively. Another point of support for this conclusion is that, although the H band is sampling different wavelengths for $z = 0.5$ – 1.5 and $z = 1.5$ – 3 , we have obtained qualitatively the same results for the two redshift bins (§5.3.2).

At low redshift, the H band samples rest-frame red optical/NIR photons. Since galactic-disk components are generally bluer than bulge components, one might worry that H -band imaging could miss disk components. This issue mainly happens for low- M_* faint disk galaxies. Considering that our main focus is relatively massive galaxies (§5.2.3) and that CANDELS H -band data are deep, this issue might not be problematic for our study. However, we still check this issue in the following ways. First, we visually check *HST* I -band cutouts of ≈ 100 random galaxies in our bulge-dominated samples at $z = 0.5$ – 1 . We do not find significant disk components for these sources. Indeed, the average I -band Sérsic index of our low-redshift bulge-dominated sample is ≈ 3.5 (using the measurements of [344]), which is typical for bulge-dominated galaxies [168, 345]. On the other hand, we visually check the low-redshift disk ($f_{\text{disk}} \geq 2/3$; §5.2.3) galaxies in our sample. We find their disk components do not appear to be significantly weaker in H band than in I band, and we attribute this result to the deep exposure and relatively low extinction of H band. Therefore, we consider that the H band-based morphological classification is

robust at low redshift.

The imaging quality generally becomes worse toward higher redshift. Some fine galactic structures (e.g. spiral arms and clumps) might be smoothed out, and thus some disk and irregular galaxies might be classified as the smooth bulge-dominated type [346]. Therefore, our bulge-dominated sample might be “contaminated”. However, this issue is, at least to some extent, mitigated by the H mag cut ($H < 24.5$) applied to our sample (§5.2.1). This cut guarantees a minimum signal-to-noise ratio ($S/N \approx 80$) of the imaging, with the penalty of a smaller sample size. Also, if our bulge-dominated sample were strongly contaminated, we would observe a similar $\overline{\text{BHAR}}\text{-SFR-}M_\star$ relation for both the bulge-dominated and comparison samples. However, the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ dependences on SFR and M_\star are qualitatively different for these two samples (§5.3.2). We thus consider that image degradation should not be a significant issue for our conclusions.

5.4 Discussion

5.4.1 Physical Implications

We emphasize that the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}\text{-SFR}$ correlation only exists for our bulge-dominated sample, while $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ appears to be primarily correlated with M_\star for the comparison sample. This difference indicates that SMBHs only coevolve with bulges rather than entire galaxies, consistent with the observations of local systems [4, 347]. Such SMBH-bulge coevolution might be driven by the amount of cold gas available in the bulge, since both SMBH and bulge growth require cold gas. From the SMBH-bulge coevolution scenario, we expect that $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ is also fundamentally correlated with bulge SFR even when a galactic disk is present. Due to the constraints of current observational facilities, it is not feasible to separate bulge SFR from the total SFR cleanly (see §5.1). However, this might be achievable with the upcoming *JWST* that has excellent angular resolution at IR wavelengths.

Earlier studies speculated an intrinsic $\overline{\text{BHAR}}\text{-SFR}$ relation for the overall galaxy population (see §5.1). However, the scenario of SMBH vs. entire galaxy coevolution leads to M_{BH} being strongly related to M_\star rather than M_{bulge} in the local universe, contradicting observations [4]. To reconcile this contradiction, an *ad hoc* galaxy evolution model was invoked where all stellar mass formed in the distant universe

($z \gtrsim 0.5$) is transformed to bulge mass at $z = 0$ [11, 163]. In contrast, the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -bulge SFR correlation, as revealed by our work, can naturally result in the $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\text{bulge}}$ relation observed in the local universe, without invoking any unphysical galaxy evolution models. Our findings highlight the critical role of morphological measurements when observationally studying the connections between distant SMBHs and their host galaxies, as the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -SFR correlation only exists among bulge-dominated galaxies. Without deep *HST* observations of CANDELS, our discovery would not be possible (see Appendix 5.6.1).

Some papers attribute the local $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\text{bulge}}$ relation entirely to a non-causal statistical origin (e.g. [33]; [34]). If galaxy/SMBH mergers happen frequently enough, the scatter of the $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\text{bulge}}$ relation could be averaged out. Our results show that there is indeed an intrinsic $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -SFR connection at high redshift that can lead to the $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\text{bulge}}$ correlation among nearby galaxies (§5.4.2). Therefore, the non-causal scenarios of merger averaging are not necessary to explain the $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\text{bulge}}$ relation. Also, recent observations of [209] show that frequent mergers will lead to a $M_{\text{BH}}/M_{\text{bulge}}$ ratio much smaller than the observed values in the local universe.

5.4.2 Implications for the $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\text{bulge}}$ Relation

From the best-fit results in §5.3.3, we have $\overline{\text{BHAR}}/\text{SFR} = 10^{-2.48}$. This value is similar to the typical observed $M_{\text{BH}}/M_{\text{bulge}}$ values in the local universe ($\approx 10^{-2.5}-10^{-2.2}$; [4]). Also, similar to the observed $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\text{bulge}}$ relation in the local universe, our $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -SFR relation for bulge-dominated galaxies has slope close to unity. These similarities indicate that the observed $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\text{bulge}}$ relation originates from SMBH-bulge coevolution as revealed by our work, and the $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\text{bulge}}$ relation is not heavily biased by the possibility that observations tend to select massive SMBHs for M_{BH} measurements [152].

The strong $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -SFR relation among bulge-dominated galaxies indicates that SMBH and bulge growth are in lockstep. A natural consequence from this lockstep growth is that the $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\text{bulge}}$ relation should not have strong redshift dependence. Some observations suggest that the $M_{\text{BH}}/M_{\text{bulge}}$ ratio appears to be higher toward higher redshifts [161, 348], contradicting the scenario of lockstep growth. However, this apparent redshift dependence of $M_{\text{BH}}/M_{\text{bulge}}$ might result

from observational biases [164], because M_{BH} measurements in the distant universe are generally limited to luminous quasars. These luminous quasars are likely the most massive SMBHs accreting at high Eddington ratios, and thus the observed $M_{\text{BH}}/M_{\text{bulge}}$ should be systematically higher than the typical $M_{\text{BH}}/M_{\text{bulge}}$ among the entire galaxy population.

5.5 Summary and Future Work

We have studied the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ dependence on SFR and M_{\star} for a bulge-dominated sample and a comparison sample of galaxies, respectively, based on multiwavelength observations of the CANDELS fields. Our main analysis procedures and conclusions are summarized below:

1. We have compiled redshift, M_{\star} , and SFR for galaxies brighter than $H = 24.5$ from the CANDELS catalogs (§5.2.2). The CANDELS M_{\star} and SFR measurements are based on SED fitting. For sources detected by *Herschel*, we estimate their SFR from FIR photometry. We have applied M_{\star} cuts of $\log M_{\star} > 9.7$ ($z = 0.5\text{--}1.5$) and $\log M_{\star} > 10.2$ ($z = 0.5\text{--}1.5$) to our sample to ensure M_{\star} completeness (§5.2.3). Based on machine-learning morphological measurements (§5.2.1), we have selected a sample of bulge-dominated galaxies and included the other galaxies in a comparison sample (§5.2.3). The bulge-dominated galaxies consist of $\approx 25\%$ of the entire galaxy population.
2. We have measured sample-averaged BHAR for different samples of galaxies based on the deep X-ray observations from *Chandra* (§5.2.4). We first measure the L_{X} for each X-ray detected source as well as average X-ray luminosity for undetected sources via a stacking process. From these measurements, we calculate average AGN bolometric luminosity adopting an L_{X} -dependent bolometric correction. Finally, we estimate $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ from $\overline{L_{\text{bol}}}$ assuming a constant radiation efficiency.
3. For the bulge-dominated sample, we have shown, with both qualitative and quantitative (PCOR) analyses, that $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ primarily depends on SFR rather than M_{\star} (§5.3.1 and §5.3.2). For the comparison sample, the situation is the opposite. The tight $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -SFR connection for bulge-dominated galaxies

indicates that SMBHs only coevolve with bulges rather than entire host galaxies (§5.4.1). The non-causal scenarios of merger averaging are unlikely the origin of the $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\text{bulge}}$ relation in the local universe.

4. Our best-fit $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -SFR relation for the bulge-dominated sample is $\log \overline{\text{BHAR}} = \log \text{SFR} - (2.48 \pm 0.05)$ where the slope is fixed to unity (§5.3.3). Our best-fit $\overline{\text{BHAR}}/\text{SFR}$ ratio is similar to the observed $M_{\text{BH}}/M_{\text{bulge}}$ ratio in the local universe (§5.4.2). This agreement indicates that our observed $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -SFR relation is indeed responsible for the well-known tight $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\text{bulge}}$ correlation among local galaxies. On the other hand, our findings support that the observed local $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\text{bulge}}$ relation is not heavily biased. The strong $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ -SFR relation among bulge-dominated galaxies indicate lockstep growth of SMBHs and bulges, predicting that the $M_{\text{BH}}-M_{\text{bulge}}$ relation should not have strong redshift dependence.

Future work can derive the full BHAR distribution as a function of SFR and M_{\star} for bulge-dominated and comparison galaxies, respectively (§5.2.4). Future ALMA observations can target the AGNs in bulge-dominated galaxies and study their gas contents. This paper probes the redshift range of $z = 0.5-3$. Future studies can extend our work to the local universe based on wide/all-sky surveys, e.g. Sloan Digital Sky Survey [349], *Chandra* Source Catalog [350], 3XMM [351], and Swift/BAT [352].

5.6 Supplementary Materials

5.6.1 Results for All Galaxies

In this appendix, we perform analyses like those in §5.3 for all galaxies with $H < 24.5$, including both the bulge-dominated and comparison samples grouped together. The results are presented in Figs. 5.9, 5.10, and 5.11, and Tab. 5.4. In Fig. 5.10, we also compare the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_{\star}$ relation with that derived in [209]. The $\overline{\text{BHAR}}-M_{\star}$ relation in this work agrees with the results of [209].

From Tab. 5.4, $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ is more strongly related to M_{\star} than SFR. This is expected, because the comparison sample is the numerically dominant galaxy population (see §5.2.3) and $\overline{\text{BHAR}}$ is mainly related to M_{\star} for the comparison

All; $z = 0.5\text{--}1.5$		
Relation	Pearson	Spearman
$\overline{\text{BHAR}}\text{-}M_\star$	$10^{-5.3}$ (4.6σ)	$10^{-2.8}$ (3.1σ)
$\overline{\text{BHAR}}\text{-SFR}$	$10^{-2.5}$ (2.9σ)	0.03 (2.2σ)
All; $z = 1.5\text{--}3.0$		
Relation	Pearson	Spearman
$\overline{\text{BHAR}}\text{-}M_\star$	$10^{-4.4}$ (4.1σ)	$10^{-3.0}$ (3.3σ)
$\overline{\text{BHAR}}\text{-SFR}$	$10^{-2.0}$ (2.6σ)	0.04 (2.1σ)

Table 5.4: p -values (significances) of partial-correlation analyses for all galaxies.

sample, especially at $z = 1.5\text{--}3.0$. This conclusion is also qualitatively consistent with [206], although their statistical significances of the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}\text{-}M_\star$ relation are higher than those in Tab. 5.4. We attribute this difference to the fact that the dynamic range of M_\star probed in [206] is much wider than that in this work ($\log M_\star \approx 8\text{--}11$ vs. $\log M_\star \approx 10\text{--}11$), since here we require $H < 24.5$ to ensure high-quality morphological information for all galaxies. The narrower dynamic range also results in smaller sample sizes, leading to the relatively large statistical scatter in Figs. 5.9 and 5.10 (compared to Figs. 4 and 5 in [206]).

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Disclaimer

The findings and conclusions do not necessarily reflect the view of the funding agencies.

Figure 5.8: AGN fraction as a function of SFR for bulge-dominated galaxies. The upper and lower panels are for $z = 0.5-1.5$ and $z = 1.5-3$, respectively. As labelled, the AGN fractions are calculated based on different L_X thresholds for different redshift bins, and the thresholds are derived from the X-ray flux limit of the COSMOS survey (§5.3.3). The AGN fraction rises toward high SFR.

Figure 5.9: Same format as Fig. 5.5 but for all galaxies in our sample.

Figure 5.10: Same format as Fig. 5.6 but for all galaxies in our sample. The shaded regions indicate the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}\text{-}M_\star$ relation derived in [209]. The upper and lower boundaries of the shaded regions indicate the $\overline{\text{BHAR}}\text{-}M_\star$ relations at the upper and lower redshift limits, respectively.

Figure 5.11: Same format as Fig. 5.7 but for all galaxies in our sample.

Appendix A | Photometric Redshifts in the Hawaii-Hubble Deep Field-North (H-HDF-N)

A.1 Introduction

Redshifts and consequent results (e.g., luminosity distance, look-back time, and angular distance) are the basis of nearly all observational astronomical studies of extragalactic objects (e.g., luminosity function, mass function, large-scale structures, and galaxy evolution), progress on which would be greatly hampered by the lack of redshift information. The most reliable way to obtain secure redshifts is by taking spectra and identifying emission (or absorption) lines. However, this approach of obtaining spectroscopic redshifts (z_{spec}) is observation time demanding, and proves to be quite challenging especially for very faint objects, e.g., the Caltech Faint Galaxy Redshift Survey is 92% complete down to $R=24$ mag in the Hubble Deep Field-North and to $R=23$ mag in the flanking fields [353]; however, when targeting slightly fainter objects over a larger area, the Team Keck Treasury Redshift Survey obtained secure spectroscopic redshifts for only 53% of their targets that are brighter than $R = 24.4$ mag in the GOODS-N field [354].

Therefore another approach, obtaining photometric redshifts (z_{phot}) of good quality, is of great value. Determining photometric redshifts with broad-band and/or medium-band imaging observations is able to capture very faint objects in a time-efficient manner, e.g., [355] reached a 5σ detection limit of (*HST*/ACS F850LP)

$z = 28.1$ mag in their z_{phot} catalog in the GOODS-S field. Generally speaking, there are two classes of methods for calculating photometric redshifts: empirical and template spectral energy distribution (SED) fitting. The former make use of a large set of spectroscopic objects to calibrate some empirical relations between redshifts and photometry (i.e., photometric magnitudes and/or colors), e.g., [356] simply fit z_{spec} as a linear or quadratic function of magnitudes; [357] developed their code ANNz based on an artificial neural network method. The empirical methods prove to be accurate; however they need a large number of training spectroscopic samples and potentially have large uncertainties for faint sources for which z_{spec} is sparsely sampled [358]. To evaluate the quality of z_{phot} derived by empirical methods more accurately and realistically, the authors often need to perform blind tests, i.e., randomly picking out a subsample of the z_{spec} sources for training and the rest for z_{phot} quality evaluation. The template SED fitting methods utilize library template sets and fit photometry at a series of redshift grid points to estimate z_{phot} . Typically, no apparent training procedures are involved, the results are thus believed to be largely unbiased, but the choice of templates is essential in determining quality z_{phot} estimates.

There are additional factors such as resolution of photometric SED (depending on the number and bandwidths of filters) and wavelength coverage of filters that affect z_{phot} quality. A high-resolution photometric SED might capture some detailed spectroscopic features such as emission or absorption lines, thereby narrowing the possible redshift range. Wide wavelength coverage could eliminate the degeneracy of SEDs, thus reducing the probability of catastrophic failures. The largest uncertainty in z_{phot} estimation lies in photometric errors, especially for faint sources where the signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) is low [355, 359]. Furthermore, images of different bands are often obtained with different instruments and their point spread functions (PSFs) might differ significantly. Therefore the challenge is to measure the same fraction of light (i.e., accurate colors) for a source in images with different PSFs. The method of PSF matching has proven to be effective in obtaining uniform photometry across different instruments and filters, with large variations in PSFs and pixel scales taken into account [355, 360]. Another issue in photometry is blending. When two sources are close to each other (due to projection effects), photometry of one source might be contaminated by the light from the other source [355]; on some occasions two such sources might even be detected as one single source if their angular separation

is sufficiently small (i.e., comparable to the angular resolution of the observations).

In this paper, we perform PSF-matched photometry and determine photometric redshifts for over one hundred thousand objects in the Hawaii-Hubble Deep Field-North (H-HDF-N; [361]; C04 hereafter) that is an intensively-observed field. Centered at $\alpha_{J2000.0} = 12^{\text{h}}37^{\text{m}}$ and $\delta_{J2000.0} = +62^{\circ}10'$, the 0.4-deg² H-HDF-N contains the GOODS-N [362] and CDF-N ([363]; [289], A03 hereafter) fields. [364] calculated z_{phot} for the 48,858 sources in the C04 catalog, using photometry that is not PSF-matched and was collected from several origins. The recent 3D-*HST* project [365] derived z_{phot} based on deep *HST* data and some ground-based observations in the GOODS-N field, which covers a much smaller area than the H-HDF-N. Given the fact that the H-HDF-N is a premium field with an enormous investment of multi-wavelength observations (in particular the recent addition of deep infrared data), it is imperative to produce a catalog that presents both PSF-matched photometry and photometric redshifts for the *entire* H-HDF-N field. Therefore, we collect images in 17 broad bands from ultraviolet (*U* band, $\sim 0.3 \mu\text{m}$) to mid-infrared (IRAC 8.0 μm) and derive z_{phot} using the EAzy code (i.e., a SED fitting code developed by [366], B08 hereafter) based on 15 bands (excluding IRAC 5.8 μm and 8.0 μm ; see Section A.6.2) in this field. Our main procedures are outlined in Figure A.1.

This paper is structured as follows. We describe the imaging and spectroscopic data in Section A.2, astrometry correction in Section A.3, PSF-matching procedures in Section A.4, and photometry extraction in Section A.5, respectively. In Section A.6, we present the procedures used to derive z_{phot} and evaluate our z_{phot} quality. We describe the corrections to obtain absolute photometry and astrometry, source classification, special treatment for z_{phot} of X-ray sources, advice on using our catalog, and catalog details in Section A.7. In Section A.8, we give a brief summary of this work. Throughout this paper, all apparent magnitudes are quoted in the AB system unless otherwise stated, where AB magnitude is defined as $\text{mag} = 23.9 - 2.5\log(\text{flux}(\mu\text{Jy}))$. We assume a cosmology of $\Omega_M = 0.3$, $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.7$, and $H_0 = 70 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$.

Figure A.1: The flow chart of our main procedures for z_{phot} estimation. For brevity we adopt the flowing abbreviations: Img.=Images, Astrom.=Astrometry, Off.=Offsets, Cor.=Correction, Estim.=Estimation, Build.=Building, Photo.=Photometry, Err.=Error, S.E.=SExtractor, Cat.=Catalog, ZP.=Zero Point, Crit.=Criterion, Abs.=Absolute, Gal.=Galaxy, Class.=Classification, Improv.=Improvement, and Sec.=Section.

A.2 data

A.2.1 Imaging Data

We collect the U -, B -, V -, R -, I -, z' -, and HK' -band images from C04, the J - and H -band images from [367], and the K_s -band image from [368] (W10 hereafter), respectively. We also make use of an independently observed z' -band image from [369]. The IRAC 3.6, 4.5, 5.8, and 8.0 μm images were obtained from the Spitzer Heritage Archive processed via Super-Mosaic pipeline version 2.0, calibration pipeline version S18.25.0, and MOPEX (for mosaic processing) version 18.5.4 (for 3.6, 4.5, and 5.8 μm) and 18.5.6a (for 8.0 μm), while another set of IRAC 3.6 and 4.5 μm images were taken from the Spitzer Extended Deep Survey (SEDS) presented in [370]. The image information is listed in Table A.1 and the filter transmission curves are plotted in Figure A.2. We show the R -band image overlaid with various coverages in the H-HDF-N in Figure A.3. The GOODS-N, CDF-N, and K_s -band coverages are encircled by the blue, cyan, and red rectangles, respectively. The yellow rectangle indicates the region (i.e., the central H-HDF-N field) where C04 derived their catalogs. We find that, different from other images, all IRAC images have some residual background, which could bias the PSF model building (see Section A.4); therefore, we run SExtractor to subtract the background before further analyses.

Figure A.2: Normalized filter transmission curves. From left to right (except HK' that is indicated as a black curve), the curves are for the U , B , V , R , I , $zc(z_0)$, J , H , K_s , $S1(A1)$, $S2(A2)$, $S3$, and $S4$ bands, respectively.

Band	Depth	PSF Size	Zero Point	Solid Angle	Group	Galactic Extinction	Epoch	Reference
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)
<i>U</i>	26.3	1.63''	31.369	0.42	II	-0.048	2002	[361]
<i>B</i>	26.3	1.13''	31.136	0.31	I	-0.042	2001	[361]
<i>V</i>	25.8	1.56''	34.707	0.39	II	-0.031	2001	[361]
<i>R</i>	26.0	1.60''	34.676	0.39	II	-0.025	2001	[361]
<i>I</i>	25.1	1.08''	33.481	0.39	I	-0.018	2001-2002	[361]
<i>z'</i> (<i>zc</i>)	24.9	1.08''	33.946	0.39	I	-0.014	2000-2001	[361]
<i>z'</i> (<i>zo</i>)	25.7	1.20''	33.020	0.33	I	-0.014	2001-2007	[369]
<i>J</i>	24.5	1.11''	23.900	0.22	I	-0.008	2006	[367]
<i>H</i>	22.9	1.32''	23.900	0.36	I	-0.005	2008	[367]
<i>K_s</i>	23.7	1.08''	23.900	0.36	I	-0.004	2006-2008	[368]
<i>HK'</i>	22.3	1.20''	30.132	0.11	I	-0.005	1999-2002	[361]
3.6 μ m (<i>A1</i>)	25.1	2.53''	21.581	0.33	III	-0.002	2004-2011	[370]
3.6 μ m (<i>S1</i>)	24.5	2.40''	21.581	0.33	III	-0.002	2004-2006	Spitzer Archive
4.5 μ m (<i>A2</i>)	24.6	2.53''	21.581	0.33	III	-0.002	2004-2011	[370]
4.5 μ m (<i>S2</i>)	24.2	2.43''	21.581	0.31	III	-0.002	2004-2006	Spitzer Archive
5.8 μ m (<i>S3</i>)	22.6	2.96''	21.581	0.33	III	-0.002	2004-2006	Spitzer Archive
8.0 μ m (<i>S4</i>)	22.7	3.24''	21.581	0.28	III	-0.002	2004-2006	Spitzer Archive

Table A.1: Imaging Data. Col. (1): Band name. Col. (2): 5σ limiting AB magnitude estimated with a 2.1''-diameter (7 pixels) aperture, based on background noise estimation detailed in Section A.5.4. Col. (3): PSF size that is calculated based on the PSF models built in Section A.4.1, which is defined as the aperture diameter that encircles half of the total flux. Col. (4): Zero point in units of AB magnitude. Col. (5): Solid-angle coverage in units of deg². We only consider the areas located in the H-HDF-N field. Col. (6): Group name that is classified based on the PSF size of a band (see Section A.5.1). Col. (7): Galactic extinction in units of AB magnitude (see Section A.5.6). Col. (8): Observational epoch. Col. (9): Reference of imaging data.

For convenience in describing the PSF-matching technique (see Section A.4), we denote PSF size as the aperture diameter that encircles half of the total flux. Hereafter, we refer to Ouchi’s z' band as zo band, and Capak’s z' band as zc band. The filters of zo and zc are identical, but the images were taken during different observational epochs (C04; [369]). The $3.6\ \mu\text{m}$ and $4.5\ \mu\text{m}$ bands in [370] are referred to as $A1$ and $A2$ bands respectively, while the 3.6 , 4.5 , 5.8 , and $8.0\ \mu\text{m}$ bands from the Spitzer Heritage Archive are referred to as $S1$, $S2$, $S3$, and $S4$ bands respectively. Filters of $A1$ and $S1$, $A2$ and $S2$ are identical, and the observational epochs of $S1$ and $S2$ were also used to derive the $A1$ and $A2$ images ([370]; also see Table A.1). Although the $S1$ and $S2$ images are shallower, we still incorporate them in our z_{phot} estimation, because the deeper $A1$ and $A2$ images were obtained by stacking more observations and thus were potentially more blurred (see Table A.1 for a comparison between PSF sizes). Indeed, we find that the inclusion of the $S1$ and $S2$ bands improves slightly the z_{phot} quality (see Section A.2.2 for the indicators of z_{phot} quality). The application of the rest-frame template error function by EAZY gives much lower weights to mid-IR than optical bands, therefore the use of duplicate $3.6\ \mu\text{m}$ and $4.5\ \mu\text{m}$ bands should not affect the z_{phot} estimation significantly (see Section A.6), as found above. We do not make use of the Hubble Space Telescope (*HST*) data in our z_{phot} estimation for the following reasons. First, the *HST* images are restricted in the GOODS-N region, the area of which is only $\lesssim 20\%$ of that of the H-HDF-N (see Figure A.3). Second, the *HST* images have much smaller PSF sizes than our images, but this great advantage would be compromised if we apply the same PSF-matched photometry-extraction procedures (see Section A.5) to them. Finally, the 3D-HST team has derived photometry and photometric redshifts [365] for the GOODS-N region to greater depths utilizing the *HST* data, and their z_{phot} catalog is available now and complements our catalog effectively.

A.2.2 z_{spec} Data

The z_{spec} data are collected from a number of references, with relevant information listed in Table A.2. We only adopt secure z_{spec} data that include at least two spectral features. Note that the z_{spec} data mainly come from [371], which is due to the fact that a significant fraction of their data were compiled from previous

Figure A.3: R -band image overlaid with rectangles indicating the K_s coverage (red), the field in C04 (i.e., the central H-HDF-N field; yellow), the CDF-N (cyan), and the GOODS-N region (blue), respectively. The z_c band covers nearly the same region as the R band.

works, e.g., [354]. To remove duplicate z_{spec} entries, z_{spec} sources from different references are matched with each other using a $0.5''$ matching radius, except for those from [292] that have already been matched by the authors to the 2 Ms *Chandra* Deep Field-North (CDF-N) main X-ray catalog (A03; see Section A.7.4). If one source has multiple z_{spec} values and any two of those values are inconsistent (i.e. $|z_{\text{spec}1} - z_{\text{spec}2}|/(1 + z_{\text{spec}1}) > 0.01$), we then discard all z_{spec} values of that source (less than 2% of the z_{spec} values are discarded this way). If a source has

Index	Reference	Non-X-ray	X-ray	Stars
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
1	[371]	2557	217	197
2	[372]	64	2	17
3	[373]	23	0	0
4	[354]	82	1	5
5	[374]	111	3	2
6	[353]	5	0	1
7	[375]	3	1	0
8	[292]	0	57	7
Total		2845	281	229

Table A.2: z_{spec} references. Col. (1): Index of reference. If a source has consistent z_{spec} values in different references, then we attribute it to the reference with the lowest index. Col. (2): z_{spec} reference. Cols. (3–5): Numbers of additional unique z_{spec} sources that are non-X-ray detected, X-ray detected, and spectroscopic stars from each reference, respectively. The X-ray source classification is based on matching with the A03 main X-ray catalog (see Section A.7.4). If a source is classified as a star, then we do not classify it as an X-ray or non-X-ray source.

only one z_{spec} value, we simply keep that z_{spec} for the source. Most of the z_{spec} sources ($\sim 80\%$) are in the GOODS-N region. In Figure A.4, we plot in the top panel the R -band magnitude (derived from this work; see Section A.5; upper limits not included) distribution of all non-stellar z_{spec} sources, which peaks around $R=23.5$ mag and declines rapidly beyond that; and we plot in the bottom panel the z_{spec} distribution of all non-stellar z_{spec} sources, the vast majority of which have $z_{\text{spec}} \lesssim 1.6$.

We adopt the widely-used normalized median absolute deviation σ_{NMAD} (e.g., B08) to evaluate our z_{phot} quality (see Section A.6.4), defined as

$$\sigma_{\text{NMAD}} = 1.48 \times \text{median}\left(\left|\frac{\Delta z - \text{median}(\Delta z)}{1 + z_{\text{spec}}}\right|\right), \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where $\Delta z = z_{\text{phot}} - z_{\text{spec}}$. Additionally, we also examine outlier fractions of z_{phot} results, with outliers being defined as sources having $|\Delta z|/(1 + z_{\text{spec}}) > 0.15$.

A.3 Astrometry Correction

The above images are of various origins and thus have inconsistent astrometry, i.e., a source might have slightly different coordinates in different images. The systematic offsets among different images can be up to the order of $\approx 0.3''$ in some

areas. Given that Capak’s 7 images (see Table A.1) are well aligned with each other (C04), we adopt these images as standard, and align other images with them using GEOMAP and GEOTRAN (IRAF¹ tasks). Specifically, we first run SExtractor (version 2.8.6; [376]) on the *zc* image, whose wavelength is closer to the infrared bands than the other Capak bands, to locate standard objects, which are bright, not blended, unsaturated, and far from image borders. We then run SExtractor on the X (standing for *J*, *H*, *K_s*, *zo*, *A1*, *S1*, *A2*, *S2*, *S3*, and *S4*) band, and match the detected sources with those standard objects (typically there are $\sim 10,000$ sources matched). GEOMAP uses these results to find an image manipulation solution (4th-order polynomial correction in our case, including linear manipulation such as rotation, shift, and rescaling as well as higher-order corrections), and GEOTRAN executes the solution. We stress that we do not use stars exclusively as standard objects, because a fraction of registered stars are saturated in our deep images. Moreover, they are relatively sparse in our field, and thus the exclusive use of them might potentially compromise the astrometry in regions where no stars are present. Subsequently, we use *hastrom.pro*² (an IDL procedure) to transform all other images (i.e., *J*, *H*, *K_s*, *zo*, *A1*, *S1*, *A2*, *S2*, *S3*, and *S4*) to the same format as Capak’s images, which are 8485×8375 arrays with a pixel size of $0.3''$. This procedure enables performing photometry in the dual-image mode of SExtractor (see Section A.5.2).

Figure A.5 plots the source density maps of coordinate offsets between the *K_s* and *R* bands before and after astrometry correction, which demonstrates the effectiveness of our procedures of astrometry correction. In the construction of our final catalog (see Section A.7.2), we lock the absolute astrometry of our sources to the astrometry frame of the VLA data [377], in order to facilitate cross matching between our catalog and other catalogs. The reason why we adopt the astrometry frame of Capak’s images, rather than that of the VLA data in the first place, is that we only care about relative astrometry when extracting photometry and want to make best use of the merit of the highly consistent astrometry among Capak’s images.

¹See <http://iraf.noao.edu/>

²See <http://idlastro.gsfc.nasa.gov/>

A.4 Point Spread Function

As shown in Table A.1, the image PSF sizes differ significantly, ranging from $1.08''$ (I , z_c , and K_s bands) to $\sim 3''$ (IRAC bands). If a single-sized aperture were used to measure fluxes, it would encircle different fractions of light for images with different PSF sizes. Therefore it would be impossible to obtain accurate colors, which holds the key to obtaining accurate z_{phot} measurements. One may propose to use different aperture sizes on different images, so that the same fraction of light could be captured. Indeed, this proposal may work for point-like sources whose profiles are simply PSFs of the images, given that we know the relation between the fraction of light encircled and the aperture size. However, for extended sources we do not know such relation due to the uncertainty in their shapes, thus this method is not practical. A common routine for consistent photometry is to smooth different images to the same PSF level before photometry extraction [360]. In this way, two processed images could have identical PSFs theoretically, and apertures of same size will capture the same fraction of light. Below we describe our techniques to smooth one image to the PSF level of another.

A.4.1 PSF Models

For each image, we match the detected sources with the stars in the GSC 2.3 catalog [378], and use SExtractor’s output flags to discard saturated, blended, and/or near-border ones. We then check source profiles, morphology, and contamination from nearby sources to further filter out surviving galaxies and saturated stars, and find that the profiles of the remaining stars resemble each other. About twenty stars in each image are selected this way to build the PSF models. We create a fixed-size thumbnail image centered on each star and normalize its flux to unity. We then construct the PSF model in the form of an image of the same size, whose pixel values are assigned as the median values of the corresponding pixels of those standard stars. Thus the PSF models represent the typical PSFs of corresponding images, with one single PSF model for each image.

A.4.2 PSF Smoothing

We make use of Lucy’s procedure (IRAF task; [379]) to build the kernel to smooth one PSF to another PSF. Assuming there are two PSF thumbnail images, i.e., PSF A and PSF B as inputs (the corresponding images are denoted as image A and image B), Lucy’s procedure will approximate the solution iteratively, which can then be used as the kernel to smooth image A to the PSF level of image B. The merit of Lucy’s procedure is that it does not require that the PSFs are of specific modeled shapes such as Gaussian. It performs well when the target PSF size is much larger. In Figure A.6, we demonstrate the effectiveness of Lucy’s procedure when smoothing the J -band PSF (having the size of $1.11''$) to the U -band PSF (having a larger size of $1.63''$).

A.5 Photometry Extraction

To conform with Capak’s and Wang’s catalogs (C04; W10), we construct three catalogs, i.e., R -selected, z_c -selected, and K_s -selected catalogs, respectively. The first two bands were used by C04 to detect sources, while the K_s band was used by W10. We perform aperture photometry via the dual-image mode in SExtractor (see Section A.5.2). An appropriate choice of aperture size is critical in obtaining high-quality photometry: if the aperture is too big, then the S/N might be low leading to large contributions from noise; if it is too small, the uncertainty of astrometry might affect photometry significantly. We find that a choice of 1.5 times the PSF size as aperture diameter appears optimal for photometry extraction in terms of achieving good z_{phot} quality, which captures about 70% of the light for a point-like source in each image.

A.5.1 PSF Solutions

The PSF sizes can be divided into three groups (see Table A.1):

- I. The B -, I -, z_c -, z_o -, J -, H -, K_s -, and HK' -band images have the smallest PSF sizes, i.e., $\lesssim 1.3''$;

II. The U -, V -, and R -band images have moderate PSF sizes, i.e., $\approx 1.6''$;

III. The $A1$ -, $A2$ -, $S1$ -, $S2$ -, $S3$ -, and $S4$ -band images have the largest PSF sizes, i.e., $\gtrsim 2.4''$.

If we smooth all images to the largest PSF, then the quality of the images with small PSF sizes, such as group I bands, will drop significantly, leading to much larger photometry errors. Therefore, we adopt the following approach to obtain accurate colors, and preserve the quality of the images maximally at the same time, which yields three catalogs (i.e., R -, z_c -, and K_s -selected) that are finally merged into one based on the Q_z criterion (see Section A.6.3).

A.5.1.1 z_c and K_s Catalogs

Here we describe how we perform PSF matching in order to obtain the z_c - and K_s -selected catalogs. For group I images, we smooth the B -, I -, z_c -, z_o -, J -, K_s -, and HK' -band images to the PSF level of the H -band image (the largest PSF size in group I); therefore the smoothed images are consistent with the H -band image, and we extract the photometry of the detected sources. For the images in groups II and III, we adopt the strategy of aperture correction [360], which we describe below. First, we smooth image M (M stands for the detection band, i.e., z_c or K_s ; see Section A.6.3) to image N (N stands for any band in groups II and III), and perform our photometry procedures on image N and the smoothed image M. Then we define an aperture correction factor, cor_{aper} , for each detected source, as

$$\text{cor}_{\text{aper}} = \frac{\text{flux}(\text{M at PSF level of } H)}{\text{flux}(\text{M at PSF level of N})}, \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where flux is the total ADUs (Analog-to-Digital Units, i.e. the values of pixels in the image matrix) encircled by the aperture whose diameter equals 1.5 times the corresponding PSF sizes. Finally we obtain the flux of N at the PSF level of the H -band image for a source as

$$\text{flux}(\text{N}) = \text{flux}(\text{N not smoothed}) \times \text{cor}_{\text{aper}}. \quad (\text{A.3})$$

A.5.1.2 *R* Catalog

The difference of the *R* band from the *zc* and K_s bands is that the *R* band belongs to group II. Therefore, to obtain the *R*-band selected catalog, we cannot smooth the *R*-band image to the PSF levels of group I images, which have smaller PSF sizes. Thus we smooth all group I and II images to the PSF level of *U* band (the largest PSF size in group II), and apply aperture corrections to group III images, following the procedure described in Section A.5.1.1.

A.5.2 SExtractor

We use SExtractor to detect sources and extract photometry. At first, we detect many more sources in the K_s -band image ($>200,000$ sources in total) than those in the *zc*- and *R*-band images (each having $<100,000$ sources) when using the same SExtractor parameters, but find that many of the K_s -band sources are false detections through visual inspection. The reason is that, during the SExtractor runs, the *zc*- and *R*-band images are supplied with corresponding RMS maps, while the K_s -band image with a weight map. Internally, SExtractor treats RMS maps as absolute noise levels, while weight maps are treated as relative noise levels; it then scales weight maps to absolute RMS maps via an internal algorithm. However, this algorithm tends to underestimate the noise level. To avoid the vast majority of false detections, W10 adopted the most stringent cleaning procedure, i.e., setting `CLEAN_PARAM = 0.1`.³ This configuration reduces effectively the number of K_s -band detected sources to $\approx 90,000$. Visual inspection shows that false detections are rare in this case. The other parameters in W10 were also chosen carefully and are therefore reliable, and, consequently, we adopt most of their parameters and run SExtractor on the dual-image mode. Table A.3 lists the main SExtractor parameters adopted for the K_s -band image. There are only minor changes in SExtractor parameters for other images. Specifically, we lower the detection thresholds by setting `DETECT_MINAREA=2` and `CLEAN_PARAM=1` for the *zc* and *R* bands due to the difference between using their RMS maps and using the K_s -band weight map as stated above. Generally these detection thresholds

³To avoid false detections due to bright objects, SExtractor assumes Moffat profiles for bright sources, and subtracts these profiles in the image to see if their faint neighbors could have been detected. This is the so-called ‘clean’ procedure, and `CLEAN_PARAM` controls the shape of the Moffat profile.

DETECT_MINAREA	4
THRESH_TYPE	relative
DETECT_THRESH	1.25
FILTER	Y
FILTER_NAME	gauss_1.5_3x3.conv
DEBLEND_NTHRESH	64
DEBLEND_MINCONT	0.00001
CLEAN	Y
CLEAN_PARAM	0.1
MASK_TYPE	correct
PHOTO_APERTUES	6.62, 8.16, 7.79, 8.02, 12.66, 12.01, 12.15, 14.79, 16.18
PHOTO_AUTOPARAMS	2.5, 3.5
GAIN	0 ^a
PIXEL_SCALE	0.3
BACK_TYPE	auto
BACK_SIZE	32
BACK_FILTERSIZE	6
BACKPHOTO_TYPE	local
BACKPHOTO_THICK	24
BACK_FILTTHRESH	0.0

Table A.3: Main Parameters of SExtractor. ^a In SExtractor, gain is only used in calculating flux uncertainty. Setting gain=0 means gain=Infinity, i.e., not including Poisson errors. There are two reasons for this: 1. Many images do not contain the gain values in their headers, and we do not find the information in related papers either. 2. Poisson errors are often small compared to background noise and can be neglected. W10 also set the gain to 0.

are sufficiently low to detect very faint sources. However, this might potentially lead to some false detections. Users of our catalog should be aware of this issue (see Section A.7.5).

A.5.3 Completeness

Our source-detection approach recovers 46,914 sources out of a total of 48,858 sources with $\geq 5\sigma$ significance in the C04 catalog using a 0.5" matching radius after removing any systematic astrometry offsets (46914/48858=96%). For the K_s -band selected catalog of W10, the recovered number of sources is 53,544 out of a total of 56,967 sources with $\geq 5\sigma$ significance (53544/56967=94%). Through visual inspection, we find that nearly all the unmatched sources are very faint or blended with other sources, and thus source detection and position determination are more uncertain.

To estimate the completeness level of our catalog, we compare our magnitude-dependent source density with that of the GOODS-N catalog [362], and plot the source density histograms for our z_c band and the *HST* $z(\text{F850lp})$ band of the GOODS-N catalog in Figure A.7. For both catalogs, we only count sources with $\geq 3\sigma$ significance. Assuming that the GOODS-N $z(\text{F850lp})$ catalog is complete at least down to $z \approx 25.5$ mag, our catalog is then $\approx 100\%$ and $\approx 80\%$ complete down to $z \approx 24.5$ mag and 25.5 mag, respectively. Note in some magnitude bins, our number densities are slightly higher than those of *HST*. And this might be the result of filter differences.

A.5.4 Photometric Errors

SExtractor assumes pixel-uncorrelated errors, and neglects background noise contributed by faint sources below the detection threshold. Therefore its derived photometric errors are underestimated. As pointed out by, e.g., [359], accurate photometric errors are crucial in deriving accurate z_{phot} . To obtain a more accurate background noise estimate for each source, we place around the source 100 apertures of the same size used for photometry extraction. These apertures are placed avoiding sources shown in the SExtractor-provided segmentation checkimage, and do not overlap with each other. Then we calculate the standard deviation of the flux in those apertures, and use it to replace the error given by SExtractor. The new errors, typically being several times larger than those provided by SExtractor, result in much better z_{phot} quality. Furthermore we also consider additional errors introduced by our PSF-matching procedure. We thus introduce err_{psf} : if we smooth band P to the PSF level of band Q, then err_{psf} is defined as

$$\text{err}_{\text{psf}} = \frac{|\text{FL}(\text{smoothed P}) - \text{FL}(\text{Q})|}{\text{FL}(\text{Q})}, \quad (\text{A.4})$$

where FL means the fraction of light encircled by the photometry aperture in the PSF image. err_{psf} is a relative quantity, and is multiplied by the flux before being added quadratically to the aforementioned new error. For most bands, err_{psf} is $\lesssim 4\%$. Typically, the background error dominates the err_{psf} . For those objects whose flux in one band is less than the corresponding error, an upper limit is assigned by setting the flux to the value of the error and is included in the z_{phot} derivation (see

Section A.6).

A.5.5 Photometric Consistency

We note that one photometric band might have two images (e.g., zc and zo bands). If large photometric differences exist between the two images, it will be impossible to fit both sets of photometry well with templates in the z_{phot} estimation. We find that even a single inconsistent band could often ruin z_{phot} quality, regardless of how perfect the other bands are. To reduce inconsistency, we first eliminate the systematic offset ($\lesssim 0.03$ mag) between the two fluxes by adjusting the zero point of either band in order to meet the condition of $\text{median}(\text{mag1} - \text{mag2}) = 0$. This adjustment is adopted only to facilitate discarding inconsistent photometry and is not applied to the photometry for z_{phot} estimation. Then, for each source, if

$$|\text{mag1} - \text{mag2}| > 3 \times \max(\text{err_mag1}, \text{err_mag2}), \quad (\text{A.5})$$

both sets of photometry will be discarded ($\lesssim 5\%$ of sources have inconsistent fluxes in at least one band). The main reasons for inconsistent photometry are blending effects in crowded fields and contamination from nearby bright sources.

A.5.6 Galactic Extinction Correction

The H-HDF-N field, located at high Galactic latitude, was initially chosen to be subject to minimal Galactic extinction. We apply Galactic extinction corrections obtained from an online utility provided through the NASA/IPAC Infrared Science Archive.⁴ As shown in Table A.1, the corrections, as expected, are small, ranging from 0.002 mag for the $A1$, $A2$, $S1$, $S2$, $S3$, and $S4$ bands to 0.048 mag for the U band.

A.5.7 Zero-point Correction

The above procedures such as PSF matching and aperture correction are all likely to introduce systematic errors into the photometry. We account for this factor by fitting the photometry for spectroscopic stars (see Section A.2.2) to derive

⁴See <http://irsa.ipac.caltech.edu/applications/DUST/> for details.

	K_s	zc	R
U	0.227	0.190	0.193
B	-0.024	-0.011	-0.015
V	-0.102	-0.125	-0.119
R	0.026	0.014	0.009
I	0.023	0.035	0.016
zc	-0.043	-0.029	-0.022
zo	0.114	0.110	0.113
J	-0.025	-0.032	-0.036
H	0.039	0.045	0.044
K_s	0.025	0.018	0.032
HK'	-0.181	-0.154	-0.056

Table A.4: Zero-point Correction (unit: mag). Row names indicate photometry bands, and column names indicate source-detection bands. The zero points of IRAC bands are not corrected because of the wavelength coverage of our stellar templates (see Section A.7.3)

zero-point correction. We only do this for the bands bluer than IRAC ones due to the wavelength coverage of our stellar templates (see Section A.7.3). There are ~ 130 stars that are not saturated or blended after visual check.

We obtain the new zero points as follows, ⁵

$$\text{new_zp} = \text{old_zp} - 2.5 \times \log\left(\frac{\text{fitting_flux}}{\text{observed_flux}}\right). \quad (\text{A.6})$$

. The results are listed in Table A.4. Note that for the three detection bands (i.e., K_s , zc and R), the corrections are not exactly the same. This might be because photometry from different catalogs are derived from different sets of images (see Section A.5.1), and there are some uncertainties (e.g. the kernels used in smoothing, see Section A.5.4) when obtaining those images.

We plot the $VRzc$ color-color plots in Figure A.8 to show the effect of zero-point correction. For the first case (i.e., the left panel of Figure A.8) overall, our star colors do not agree well with template star colors; however, for the second case (i.e., the right panel of Figure A.8), our star colors are in good agreement with template star colors. Therefore, we conclude that zero-point correction is effective in eliminating systematic errors and adopt the new zero points in the final catalog.

⁵We do not calculate the zero points iteratively, because of the small sample. And in fact, the results do not converge even after more than 10 times of iteration.

A.5.8 Blending

When detecting sources, SExtractor might fail to separate two very close sources. To estimate the importance of this effect in our catalog, we make use of the GOODS-N catalog [362] that is based on *HST* observations with superb angular resolutions of $\approx 0.05''$. We only estimate the effect for our *R* band, the one with the largest PSF size among the three detection bands, to assess an approximate upper limit of this effect. We then only consider sources with $R \lesssim 26$ mag (i.e., 5σ detection limit of our *R* band; see Table A.1). Through visual inspection of both our *R*-band and the *HST F606W*-band images (the *HST F606W* band is similar to our *R* band and both bands are centered at $\approx 6000 \text{ \AA}$), we find that the detection generally fails if the angular separation of two sources is less than $1.2''$. We also find that $\approx 10.8\%$ of the *HST F606W* $\lesssim 26$ mag sources in the GOODS-N catalog have neighboring sources within a radius of $1.2''$. We therefore conclude that about $10.8\%/2 = 5.4\%$ of our *R*-band sources might be in fact two sources that can only be separated distinctly in images with higher angular resolution.

Another issue caused by blending is photometry contamination by nearby sources. We assume that photometry of one source is subject to contamination if another source is present within a radius of $1.5 \times \text{PSF}$ size. For non-IRAC bands, we estimate the effect for our *U* band, the one with the largest PSF size of $1.63''$, to assess an approximate upper limit of this effect. We find that $\approx 28\%$ of the *U*-band sources might suffer from such photometry contamination. However, the actual contamination effect should be much less severe and could be totally negligible in many cases. For example, bright sources are minimally affected (if at all) by their faint neighbors. Furthermore, SExtractor can reduce this contamination effect when computing photometry (see Page 40 of the SExtractor manual for version 2.13). For IRAC bands, the photometry contamination is expected to be worse considering their large PSF sizes. However, this situation is largely alleviated given that IRAC data have much lower weights than optical and near-infrared data in z_{phot} estimation (see Section A.2.1).

Sources that suffer from the above blending issues would generally have inaccurate photometry and thus z_{phot} of poor quality. Such sources typically have large Q_z (the redshift quality parameter defined in Section A.6.3) values, e.g., for sources with $\geq 5\sigma$ significance, $\approx 56\%$ of the (likely) blended sources have $Q_z > 1$, in

contrast to $\approx 23\%$ of the non-blended sources having $Q_z > 1$. In such cases, their z_{phot} are generally not recommended for use (see Sections A.6.3 and A.7.5).

A.6 Photometric Redshifts

A.6.1 EAzy

We use the EAzy code (B08) to estimate photometric redshifts. EAzy (version 1.00) can fit with linear combinations of template SEDs. There are two novel features of EAzy. First, the default template set (see Figure A.9) is based on semi-analytical models rather than spectroscopic samples (usually these are highly biased). B08 used the “non-negative matrix factorization” algorithm to extract a template set from the library of ~ 3000 PÉGASE models [380] with ages ranging from 1 Myr to 20 Gyr and having a variety of star formation histories. Second, B08 designed a rest-frame template error function to estimate template uncertainty. This function assigns different wavelength regimes different weights (being largest, moderate, smallest for the rest-frame optical, ultraviolet, and near-infrared bands, respectively), and ensures that the formal redshift uncertainties are realistic (B08).

A.6.1.1 Templates

We find that the default template set of EAzy does not represent young galaxies well, leading to large z_{phot} uncertainties for such galaxies. To obtain more accurate z_{phot} for this population, we introduce two additional representative young galaxy templates (see Figure A.9 for a total of eight galaxy templates adopted). The first one is a lightly dust-reddened young galaxy taken from [381], and is designed to describe the most massive subset of the Lyman break galaxy population. This template improves the overall quality of z_{phot} . The other template is a 50-Myr-old single-burst model with metallicity $Z = Z_{\odot}$ generated by GALAXEV [76]. This model improves the z_{phot} quality of objects at $z \gtrsim 2$.

To examine the effect of degeneracy introduced by adding these two young galaxy templates, we compare z_{phot} results obtained for the sources detected in the R band with $> 5\sigma$ significance, using the default template set of EAzy and using all eight galaxy templates shown in Figure A.9, respectively. We find that the best-fit templates and thus z_{phot} values do not change at all for the majority

of the sources when these two new templates are introduced, thereby resulting in a nominal $\sigma_{\text{NMAD}} = 0.000$; and we obtain a nominal outlier fraction of 2.6%. Therefore, the effect of this degeneracy is negligible.

A.6.1.2 Other Parameters

We adopt the default mode of linear combination of templates and the featured template error function when fitting the photometry. The estimation of intergalactic medium (IGM) absorption is based on the default IGM absorption law [382] in EAZY. We do not apply apparent magnitude priors when using EAZY, because we find this configuration tends to underestimate redshifts especially for high-redshift galaxies. We set the redshift grid from 0.01 to 8.0 with a logarithmic step size of $\Delta \ln(1+z) = 0.01$. For each source, we adopt the z grid value that minimizes the fitting χ^2 as our z_{phot} value.

A.6.2 Zero-point Offsets

In Section A.5.7, we correct our photometry based on SED fitting of spectroscopic stars. However, the corrected photometry might still have systematic differences compared to those from galaxy templates used in z_{phot} calculation. And eliminating the differences is helpful in improving z_{phot} quality. We do this by fitting the photometry at z_{spec} with the eight adopted templates (see Figure A.9) to derive zero-point offsets.

We first tentatively match our sources with the z_{spec} catalogs (see Section A.2.2 and Figure A.4) using a 0.5'' matching radius and then remove the systematic astrometry difference ($\approx 0.08''$) before matching them again. The false-matching rate is estimated to be $\lesssim 3\%$ by systematically shifting source coordinates and then re-correlating them. We calculate the zero point offsets by,

$$\text{zp_offset} = -2.5 \times \log\left(\text{median}\left(\frac{\text{fitting_flux}}{\text{observed_flux}}\right)\right). \quad (\text{A.7})$$

. After three iterations, the zero-point offsets converge (vary by $\lesssim 0.01$ mag). The zero-point offsets are listed in Table A.5.

The zero-point offsets for the $S3$ and $S4$ bands indicate that our photometry has fluxes higher than template fluxes at $> 5\mu\text{m}$ wavelengths. However, the $S3 - S4$

	K_s	zc	R
U	-0.147	-0.135	-0.130
B	-0.007	-0.001	0.009
V	0.029	0.022	0.028
R	0.048	0.034	0.035
I	-0.034	-0.027	-0.021
zc	-0.022	-0.017	-0.009
zo	-0.005	0.002	-0.001
J	0.020	0.031	0.016
H	0.009	0.017	-0.012
K_s	0.104	0.123	0.101
HK'	0.074	0.082	0.043
$A1$	-0.033	-0.055	-0.042
$S1$	-0.045	-0.064	-0.048
$A2$	-0.035	-0.056	-0.037
$S2$	-0.028	-0.042	-0.025
$S3$	0.096	0.075	0.101
$S4$	0.367	0.351	0.378

Table A.5: Zero-point Offsets (unit: mag). Row names indicate photometry bands, and column names indicate source-detection bands.

color of stars without zero-point offsets applied appears more consistent with that of [383]. Furthermore, the inclusion of these two offset bands in our z_{phot} calculation yields a worse z_{phot} quality (see Section A.6.4). Therefore we conclude that the zero-point offsets for the $S3$ and $S4$ bands are unreliable, likely due to the absence of PAH emission features in our templates. We thus discard zero-point offsets for these two bands and do not use their photometry for z_{phot} estimation; however, for completeness, we still provide their photometry in the final catalog (see Section A.7).

We find that stellar photometry become generally inconsistent with spectroscopic stars after applying the offsets. Therefore, we conclude that zero-point offsets are template-dependent; we thus adopt the zero-point offsets only in z_{phot} estimation, but do not apply them to the photometry presented in the final catalog (see Section A.7.6).

A.6.3 K_s , zc , or R Catalog?

As described above, we have three catalogs derived from detections in the K_s -, zc -, and R -band images, respectively. When merging the K_s -, zc -, and R -band catalogs, we use a matching radius of $1.0''$ because the positions of a same source in different detection images could sometimes have shifts exceeding $0.5''$ even after

astrometry correction, due to the fact that such sources (a total of ≈ 5000 , i.e., $\lesssim 4\%$ of the final catalog; see the latter part of this section) are typically very faint and/or blended to some degree in certain bands and thus have inaccurate positions therein. About 60% of the sources are detected in more than one band; their z_{phot} values derived from different catalogs are generally very similar even though we use different approaches to produce the three catalogs. However, in some cases these sources do have apparently different z_{phot} values from different catalogs because the z_{phot} qualities for given same source present in all three catalogs might be different: (1) if a source appears faint in one detection image, then its position and aperture correction factor (see Section A.5.1) are likely to be determined relatively poorly in that image, which might further lead to large uncertainties in photometry; and (2) different catalogs are in fact obtained from differently processed image sets (see Section A.5.1), and technically speaking, noise levels and blending conditions differ among those image sets. Therefore, proper choices among the three catalogs should enhance the overall z_{phot} quality.

Here we adopt the following criterion for source selection. First we calculate the redshift quality parameter Q_z (see Equation 8 of B08) for each source in multiple catalogs as

$$Q_z = \frac{\chi^2}{N_{\text{fit}} - 3} \frac{z_{\text{up}}^{99} - z_{\text{lo}}^{99}}{P_{\delta z=0.2}}, \quad (\text{A.8})$$

where χ^2 is obtained from template fitting; $N_{\text{fit}} - 3$ is the degrees of freedom; $z_{\text{up}}^{99} - z_{\text{lo}}^{99}$ is the 99% confidence level interval that represents the z_{phot} scatter [384]; and $P_{\delta z}$ is the fraction of the total integrated probability that lies within $\pm\delta z$ of the z_{phot} estimate, designed to identify sources that have broad and/or multi-modal probability distributions [385]. Then if a source appears in more than one catalog (i.e., multiple detections), we regard the detection with the lowest Q_z value as the most reliable one and adopt its corresponding photometry and z_{phot} . The relation between Q_z and $|\Delta z|/(1 + z_{\text{spec}})$ (where $\Delta z = z_{\text{phot}} - z_{\text{spec}}$) is plotted in the top-left panel of Figure A.10. In Figure A.10, we also plot Q_z histograms for spectroscopic and all sources, respectively, in the top-right panel (as expected, the spectroscopic sources typically have smaller Q_z values indicating better z_{phot} quality than average), and present two typical SED fitting results that correspond to two Q_z values in the two bottom panels. The first SED is fitted well by the template with $Q_z = \mathbf{0.09}$, and its z_{phot} probability distribution shows a single peak. In

contrast, the second SED is fitted relatively poorly by the template with $Q_z = \mathbf{3.31}$, and its z_{phot} probability distribution shows double peaks.

Following the above source-selection criterion, we obtain a total of 131,678 distinct sources, among which 46447, 25478, and 59753 sources are selected from the K_s , z_c , and R catalogs, respectively. Typically, a value of $Q_z \lesssim 1$ indicates reliable z_{phot} quality (i.e., $|\Delta z|/(1 + z_{\text{spec}}) \lesssim 0.05$). There are 67,415 sources with $Q_z < 1$ in our merged catalog, among which 15,322, 16,224, and 35,869 sources are detected in the K_s , z_c , and R bands, respectively. Figure A.11 shows histograms of magnitudes in the detection bands for all sources and those with $Q_z < 1$, respectively. Typically, sources with lower Q_z values tend to be brighter, e.g., the median magnitudes are $K_s=22.6$, $z_c=23.8$, and $R=24.4$ mag for sources with $Q_z < 1$, and $K_s=23.5$, $z_c=24.1$, and $R=24.8$ mag for all sources, respectively.

A.6.4 z_{phot} Quality

We find 2845 matches between our sources and the z_{spec} catalogs for non-X-ray objects (see Table A.2; also see Section A.6.2 for our matching approach). Then we use the z_{spec} data to evaluate our z_{phot} quality (for evaluation of X-ray objects, see Section A.7.4). We obtain $\sigma_{\text{NMAD}} = 0.029$ for those 2845 sources. The median value of $\Delta z/(1 + z_{\text{spec}})$ is -0.013 and there are 156 ($156/2845 = 5.5\%$) outliers. More specifically, we find $\sigma_{\text{NMAD}} = \mathbf{0.024}$ with 2.7% outliers for sources brighter than $R = 23$ mag, $\sigma_{\text{NMAD}} = 0.035$ with 7.4% outliers for sources fainter than $R = 23$ mag, $\sigma_{\text{NMAD}} = 0.026$ with 3.9% outliers for sources having $z < 1$, and $\sigma_{\text{NMAD}} = 0.034$ with 9.0% outliers for sources having $z > 1$. Figure A.12 demonstrates our z_{phot} quality. The top three panels are, from left to right, z_{phot} vs. z_{spec} , histogram of $\Delta z/(1 + z_{\text{spec}})$, and $\Delta z/(1 + z_{\text{spec}})$ vs. R -band magnitude for the 2845 sources, respectively. The bottom three panels are the same as the top panels but are limited to the sources with $Q_z < 1$. From comparison between the top and bottom panels, we find the criterion of $Q_z < 1$ filters out many outliers. The z_{phot} quality is also related to the number of available bands, e.g., $|\Delta z|/(1 + z_{\text{spec}}) \sim \mathbf{0.041}$ when 12 bands (upper limits not counted) are available while $|\Delta z|/(1 + z_{\text{spec}}) \sim \mathbf{0.027}$ when all 15 bands are available.

We compare our work with [364], which is the most relevant work where they estimated z_{phot} for sources in the central H-HDF-N area based on broadband

photometry from C04 and some other broadband photometry, using the ZEBRA template-fitting code [386]. The major differences of our work from [364] are (1) we include additional high-quality data that have become available only recently (e.g., the K_s band from W10 as well as the IRAC data from the Spitzer Heritage Archive and [370]); (2) we derive uniform PSF-matched photometry rather than compiling a number of magnitudes of various origins and different derivation methodologies; (3) our catalog consists of 131,678 sources, many more than the 48,858 sources in [364], due to our larger solid-angle coverage (i.e., the entire H-HDF-N field), deeper data, different catalog-construction approach, and inclusion of lower-significance sources; and (4) our z_{phot} estimation does not involve apparent training procedures. [364] reached $\sigma_{\text{NMAD}} = 0.025$ and an outlier fraction of 5.0% (outliers defined as having $|\Delta z|/(1 + z_{\text{spec}}) > 0.20$ therein) with training procedures applied; however, their blind-test results showed that the real z_{phot} quality should be worse by a factor of a few.

A.7 The Final Catalog

A.7.1 Absolute Photometry

Our approach of PSF-matched photometry extraction is designed to obtain accurate colors rather than absolute fluxes, and it underestimates the fluxes because the aperture diameter is fixed at 1.5 times the PSF size ($\sim 70\%$ of light encircled for point-like sources) for all sources in each band. To convert the aperture photometry to the absolute one, we make use of FLUX_AUTO in SExtractor’s output of the detection band, i.e., the K_s , z_c , or R band. The algorithm of FLUX_AUTO adopts a flexible aperture size for each source [387], and FLUX_AUTO has been widely used to obtain absolute photometry (e.g., [360]; W10). If a source has detection in the X (representing K_s , z_c , or R) band, then we obtain absolute flux of Y (representing any of the 17 bands), $f_{Y,\text{final}}$, as

$$f_{Y,\text{final}} = c \times f_{Y,\text{aper}} \times \frac{f_{X,\text{AUTO}}}{f_{X,\text{aper}}}, \quad (\text{A.9})$$

where c is the correction factor to convert FLUX_AUTO to absolute flux ($c = 1.06$ in our case, according to Page 39 of the SExtractor manual for version 2.13). The

above procedure conserves colors, which indicates that the same z_{phot} results would be obtained with either the relative or absolute photometry.

We compare our K_s -band absolute photometry (without applying zero-point offsets) with that of W10 for the common sources that have $\geq 5\sigma$ significance, and find a median offset of ~ 0.10 mag and a scatter of 0.15 mag. No straightforward comparison can be made between our absolute photometry and that of C04, because C04 adopted a different approach to obtain absolute photometry, i.e., using isophotal fluxes of SExtractor rather than auto fluxes that we adopted.

A.7.2 Absolute Astrometry

In the astrometry correction procedure (see Section A.3), we align all images to the astrometric frame of the C04 images that were well aligned with each other thus being optimal for obtaining accurate colors. However, this astrometry might have subtle systematic errors. To account for this, we match our sources with those detected by the VLA 1.4 GHz observations [377] using a $1.0''$ matching radius. Then we use GEOMAP and GEOXYTRAN (IRAF tasks) to correct our astrometry so that it is more consistent with that of the VLA data. As in Section A.3, we also adopt a 4th-order polynomial correction that is applied to the entire catalog. The median values of the coordinate offsets applied are $0.28''$ (RA) and $-0.17''$ (DEC).

A.7.3 Star/Galaxy Classification

We classify a source by fitting its photometry with a set of 235 stellar templates at $z=0$ and another set of 259 galaxy templates at $z = z_{\text{phot}}$. The stellar templates are taken from the *Le Phare* photometric redshift and simulation package [388, 389], which consist of 231 stellar spectra that include all normal spectral types and luminosity classes [390, 391] and 4 white dwarf spectra [392]. The galaxy templates are the PÉGASE2.0 templates (259 in total; [393]) taken from the EAzy package. For the purpose of star/galaxy separation, the fitting is done via the single template mode (STM) rather than the linear combination mode (LCM) of EAzy, because the former yields slightly more consistent results with the *BzK* method [394] that separates effectively stars from galaxies. In this mode (STM), we use a 5% error in place of the template error function, since the template error function is designed for the default template set in the LCM. We discard all IRAC data for

the purpose of star/galaxy separation because the stellar templates of [390] do not cover wavelengths longer than $2.5 \mu\text{m}$. We classify a non-spectroscopic source as a star only if it satisfies the following two criteria: (1) $\chi_{\text{star}}^2 < \chi_{\text{gal}}^2$; and (2) if the source has $S/N > 5$, we then require additionally that its major axis to minor axis ratio (from SExtractor) be in the range of 1.0–1.5; where χ_{star}^2 is the fitted χ^2 using the 235 stellar templates at $z=0$ and χ_{gal}^2 is the fitted χ^2 using the 259 galaxy templates at $z = z_{\text{phot}}$.

Finally, our method identifies a total of 4959 star candidates (with the 229 spectroscopic stars being counted). Among them, 25 are best-fitted by a white dwarf template. To verify the accuracy of our method, we also make a *BzK* diagram. In Figure A.13, we only plot sources that have reasonably accurate photometry in the relevant three bands (i.e., $\text{err_mag}_B + \text{err_mag}_{z_c} < 0.5$ and $\text{err_mag}_{z_c} + \text{err_mag}_{K_s} < 0.15$). We find that our template fitting method is consistent with the *BzK* star/galaxy classification scheme. As expected, if the sources with larger photometric errors are also plotted in Figure A.13, then the star/galaxy separation is not as good, but it is still reasonable. For spectroscopic sources, we misclassified 13 galaxies as stars (out of a total of 3126; $13/3126=0.4\%$) and 24 stars as galaxies (out of a total of 229; $24/229=10.5\%$) according to the above criteria. Of those 24 misclassified stars, about one half are very bright thus suffering from issues of bad pixels and/or saturation, and the other half or so are blended with nearby sources to some degree.

A.7.4 AGNs

We match our sources (using the optical and near-infrared positions as well as the K_s -band magnitude distribution) with the 2 Ms CDF-N (A03; see Figure A.3 for coverage) main X-ray source catalog (using X-ray positions) utilizing the likelihood-ratio matching technique presented in [79]. There are 462 non-stellar X-ray sources matched (13 additional X-ray stars matched), with 281 having z_{spec} (see Table A.2). The false matching rate is estimated to be $\approx 2\%$. The z_{phot} quality of those X-ray sources is as follows: $\sigma_{\text{NMAD}} = \mathbf{0.037}$, an outlier fraction of 16.7% (i.e., 47 outliers), and $\text{median}(\Delta z / (1 + z_{\text{spec}})) = -0.014$; such z_{phot} quality is worse than that of non-X-ray sources (see Section A.6.4).

There are two main reasons for the worse z_{phot} quality of X-ray sources. First, the

vast majority ($\gtrsim 75\%$; based on studies of deep X-ray surveys; e.g., A03; [395, 396]) of these X-ray sources are active galactic nuclei (AGNs). Typically, many AGNs have different SEDs to normal galaxies and therefore it may not be correct to estimate z_{phot} for AGNs with normal galaxy templates, especially in the case of QSOs whose SEDs are dominated by the central engine. Second, fluxes of AGNs might vary non-periodically on timescales from minutes to decades [397]. [397] took AGN variability into account when deriving z_{phot} based on multi-epoch observations (i.e., one filter has observations in different epochs). However, all our bands were not observed in the same epoch (see Table A.1) and we do not have multi-epoch data for a specific band. Therefore our photometry might differ from a snapshot SED, thus being likely to be subject to uncertainties due to AGN variability.

To improve the z_{phot} quality of X-ray sources, we add three additional QSO templates to the previous template set when estimating z_{phot} for X-ray sources. The first two are the BQSO and TQSO templates from the SWIRE library [398], both of which are type 1 QSO but with different IR/optical flux ratios; the third one is the optical-to-near-infrared composite QSO template from [399], and is built from spectra of QSOs at different redshifts. As in Section A.7.3, we use a 5% error instead of the template error function, because the template error function is designed for normal galaxies rather than AGNs (B08). Other EAzy parameters are the same as those in Section A.6.1.2. Notably, the LCM algorithm naturally mixes the QSO and stellar light. The resulting z_{phot} quality is improved appreciably: $\sigma_{\text{NMAD}} = \mathbf{0.035}$, an outlier fraction of 12.5% (i.e., 35 outliers), and $\text{median}(\Delta z / (1 + z_{\text{spec}})) = \mathbf{-0.014}$. Figure A.14 demonstrates this improvement in z_{phot} quality by showing plots of z_{phot} quality before and after the introduction of the above three QSO templates. Overall, our z_{phot} quality of X-ray sources appears comparable to those presented in other similar works, e.g., [364].

It can also be seen in Figure A.14 that a small fraction of X-ray sources that were fit well (and thus have good z_{phot}) without adding the QSO templates are no longer fit well when adding the QSO templates, and vice versa. This is due to degeneracy. To examine the effect of degeneracy introduced by adding these three QSO templates, we compare z_{phot} results obtained for the 462 X-ray sources, using only the eight galaxy templates shown in Figure A.9 and using both the eight galaxy templates and the three QSO templates, respectively. We find a nominal $\sigma_{\text{NMAD}} = 0.015$ and a nominal outlier fraction of 6.5%, indicating that the effect

of this degeneracy is insignificant.

A.7.5 Advice on Using Our Catalog

The users of our catalog should be careful given that we do not apply a significance cut to the sources that are included in our catalog, which might lead to some false detections. Instead, we choose to provide both the significance level (i.e., S/N) and the redshift quality parameter Q_z in our final catalog (see Section A.7.6), and recommend the users to apply an appropriate S/N and/or Q_z cut according to their specific scientific interests. We note that, as expected, there is a general anti-correlated trend between S/N and Q_z in spite of significant scatter.

Additionally, the users of our catalog should exercise extra caution in making use of the sources lying in the extended H-HDF-N field (i.e., the regions outside the yellow rectangle in Figure A.3), given that, for the sake of completeness, we provide all the sources in the entire H-HDF-N field in our catalog, rather than only those lying within the C04 central H-HDF-N field. The sources in the extended field might potentially suffer from issues such as additional astrometry distortions and large background noise (see Figure A.3). The latter could cause large photometric errors and additional false detections (C04). Unfortunately, it is rather difficult to assess z_{phot} quality in the extended field where there are not any z_{spec} data. We thus provide a flag indicating whether a source is located in the central or extended H-HDF-N field in our final catalog (see Section A.7.6) so that the users could proceed with known caveats.

A.7.6 Catalog Details

The H-HDF-N photometric catalog is presented in Table A.6. The details of the 53 columns are given below.

1. Column 1 gives the source sequence number (i.e., ID, ranging from 1 to 131,678). We list sources in order of increasing right ascension.
2. Columns 2 and 3 give the J2000.0 right ascension and declination, respectively. They are consistent with the VLA radio astrometry (see Section A.7.2).
3. Column 4 gives the z_{phot} value, which corresponds to the highest peak in the corresponding z_{phot} probability distribution output by EAzY.

4. Column 5 gives the alternative z_{phot} value denoted as z_{alt} if available. In the z_{phot} probability distribution, if a source has other peaks in addition to the highest one (corresponding to z_{phot}) and satisfies the following two conditions, i.e.,

$$\frac{|z_{\text{peak}} - z_{\text{phot}}|}{1 + z_{\text{phot}}} > 0.15, \text{ and} \quad (\text{A.10})$$

$$p(z_{\text{peak}}) > 0.5 \times p(z_{\text{phot}}), \quad (\text{A.11})$$

where $p(z_{\text{peak}})$ and $p(z_{\text{phot}})$ are the values in the probability distribution quoted at redshifts of z_{peak} and z_{phot} , respectively; we then define z_{alt} as the redshift that corresponds to the highest peak among those peaks. 34% of all sources in our catalog have z_{alt} values, while for sources with $Q_z < 1$ the fraction is 13%. We set $z_{\text{alt}} = 0$ for stars and $z_{\text{alt}} = -1$ for sources whose z_{alt} values are not available.

5. Columns 6–11 give the 68% (1σ), 95% (2σ), and 99.7% (3σ) lower and upper limits on z_{phot} , respectively, which are calculated as

$$\alpha/2 = \int_0^{z_{\text{low}}} p(z) dz, \quad (\text{A.12})$$

$$\alpha/2 = \int_{z_{\text{up}}}^8 p(z) dz,$$

where $\alpha = 0.317$, 0.046, and 0.003, respectively, and $p(z)$ is the probability distribution of redshift. These limit values are output by EAzY. Note that our z_{phot} corresponds to the peak value of $p(z)$, thus in some cases z_{low} might be greater than z_{phot} , or z_{up} might be lower than z_{phot} .⁶ A total of $\sim 7\%$ of sources in our catalog have $z_{\text{low}} > z_{\text{phot}}$ or $z_{\text{up}} < z_{\text{phot}}$. For those sources, the abnormal z_{low} or z_{up} value should not be used.

6. Column 12 gives the source type: values of -2 , -1 , 0 , and 1 indicate white dwarfs (25 sources), other stars (4934 sources; see Section A.7.3), non-X-ray sources (126,257 sources), and X-ray sources (462 sources; see Section A.7.4), respectively. If a source is classified as a star, then we do not count it as an X-ray nor non-X-ray source, set its z_{phot} and corresponding confidence ranges as 0, and set Q_z as -1 . We refer whoever interested in X-ray stars (a total of 14 in our catalog) to

⁶To give an extreme example, if a source has $z_{\text{phot}} = 0.01$ (i.e., the z_{phot} probability distribution peaks at the minimum z_{phot} grid value of 0.01), then its z_{low} is very likely to be greater than z_{phot} , because z_{low} has to be large enough to make the integral reach $\alpha/2$ in the left-hand side of Eq. A.12.

both this column and Column 18.

7. Column 13 gives the redshift quality parameter Q_z (see Section A.6.3). Generally, lower Q_z values indicate better z_{phot} quality. We suggest a criterion of $Q_z < 1$ for reliable z_{phot} . There are 67,415 sources with $Q_z < 1$ in our catalog.

8. Column 14 gives the detection significance or signal-to-noise ratio (S/N), defined as

$$\text{S/N} = \frac{\text{flux}}{\text{background noise}}, \quad (\text{A.13})$$

where flux and background noise (see Section A.5.4) are for the detection band (see Section A.6.3). The users of our catalog are recommended to apply an appropriate cut based on Q_z and/or S/N to filter out sources of poor photometry and thus z_{phot} quality, in order to fulfill effectively their specific science goals.

9. Column 15 gives the detection band: letters of K, Z, and R indicate K_s -, z_c -, and R -band detections, respectively. If a source is detected in multiple bands, the first letter indicates the adopted detection catalog according to the lowest Q_z criterion (see Section A.6.3). After applying this criterion, the numbers of sources selected from the K_s , z_c , and R catalog are 46447, 25478, and 59753, respectively.

10. Columns 16 and 17 give the z_{spec} value and its reference index, respectively, if available. We only include secure z_{spec} in this work. The reference indexes are listed in Table A.2. Situations where a source has more than one reference are dealt with in Section A.2.2. If z_{spec} for a source is not available, then both values are set to -1 . There are a total of 3355 sources having z_{spec} , including 2845 non-X-ray sources, 281 X-ray sources, and 229 stars.

11. Column 18 gives the source index in the A03 2 Ms CDF-N main catalog if it has a match therein (see Section A.7.4). For the sources not matched to A03, the value of this column is set to -1 . The number of sources matched to A03 is 475, including 462 non-stellar X-ray sources and 13 X-ray stars.

12. Column 19 gives a flag indicating whether the source is in the C04 central H-HDF-N region: 0 stands for being outside of the central region (i.e., in the extended region; 53,636 sources) and 1 stands for being in the central region (78,042 sources). The properties of the sources in the central region are of better overall quality than those outside (see Section A.5.3).

13. Columns 20–53 give the photometry (with zero-point offsets not being applied) and corresponding errors in magnitudes. The order is U band, error of

U band, B band, error of B band, and so forth (the band order is the same as that in Table A.1). If the photometry of a source in one band is not available (due to, e.g., being outside of the field of view or saturated), then we set corresponding columns to values of -99 . If the flux is less than its error (both in units of μJy), we apply an upper limit, i.e., set the flux to the value of the error (see A.5.4). The $S3$ - and $S4$ -band photometry is presented without zero-point offsets, which was not used in z_{phot} calculation (see A.6.2). All the photometry has been corrected to the absolute photometry based on FLUX_AUTO algorithm in SExtractor (see A.7.1).

Figure A.4: Histograms of R -band magnitude (Top) and z_{spec} (Bottom) for all non-stellar z_{spec} sources.

Figure A.5: Source density maps of coordinate offsets between the K_s and R bands. The top and bottom panels are based on data before and after astrometry correction. The black crosses indicate the median values of coordinate offsets. The contours represent different levels of source density, with color-coded scales shown in the insets. After the correction, the number of matched sources (with a matching radius of $0.5''$) increases from 11,530 to 16,697 (i.e., a 44.8% increase; note that the relatively small number of sources in this comparison is due to the application of much more stringent source-detection criteria than those presented in Section A.5.2).

Figure A.6: Encircled fraction of light versus aperture diameter. Note that the curves of the *U* band and the smoothed *J* band are effectively identical.

Figure A.7: Source density plots for our zc band (red squares) and the *HST* z (F850lp) band of the GOODS-N catalog (blue diamonds). Only sources with $\geq 3\sigma$ significance are counted. For direct comparison, we only consider our zc -band sources that are located within the GOODS-N region. The GOODS-N z (F850lp)-band magnitudes are the MAG_AUTO magnitudes in SExtractor that are corrected by the same correction factor as mentioned in Section A.7.1.

Figure A.8: $VRzc$ color-color plots for the spectroscopic stars in our catalog (black bullets; only those with photometry errors less than 0.1 mag in all the three bands are plotted) and the model stars derived with stellar templates (red stars). (Left) The case of before zeropoint correction to our spectroscopic stars. (Right) The case of after zeropoint correction derived with stellar templates.

Figure A.9: Galaxy templates adopted in this work, including the six EAZY v1.00 default templates (black curves), the one taken from [381] (red curve), and a 50-Myr-old galaxy template generated by GALAXEV (blue curve).

Figure A.10: (Top-left) Plot of $|\Delta z|/(1+z_{\text{spec}})$ versus Q_z , where each 50 sources are binned into one data point. (Top-right) Histograms of Q_z for the z_{spec} sources (black curve) and all sources (red curve). (Bottom-left) A typical best-fit SED template for a low- Q_z source. (Bottom-right) A typical best-fit SED template for a high- Q_z source. The insets in the bottom panels show the z_{phot} probability distributions with the peaks being normalized to unity.

Figure A.11: Histograms of magnitudes in the detection bands for all sources (top panel) and those with $Q_z < 1$ (bottom panel). Sources detected in the K_s , z_c , and R bands are plotted as black, blue, and red curves, respectively.

Figure A.12: Plots of z_{phot} versus z_{spec} (Left), histograms of $\Delta z/(1+z_{\text{spec}})$ (Middle), and plots of $\Delta z/(1+z_{\text{spec}})$ versus R -band magnitude (Right) for all non-X-ray z_{spec} sources (2845 in total; the top row) and all non-X-ray z_{spec} sources with $Q_z < 1$ (2744 in total; the bottom row). Red solid lines indicate $\Delta z/(1+z_{\text{spec}}) = 0$ and red dashed lines indicate $\Delta z/(1+z_{\text{spec}}) = \pm 0.15$. The σ_{NMAD}^+ and σ_{NMAD}^- running curves are computed according to Equation A.1 for sources with $\Delta z/(1+z_{\text{spec}}) > 0$ and $\Delta z/(1+z_{\text{spec}}) < 0$ (in bins of $\Delta R = 1$ mag) and shown as green and blue curves, respectively.

Figure A.13: BzK map for star/galaxy classification. Only sources with reliable B , z_c , and K_s photometry (i.e., $\text{err_mag}_B + \text{err_mag}_{z_c} < 0.5$ and $\text{err_mag}_{z_c} + \text{err_mag}_{K_s} < 0.15$) are plotted as black dots. Spectroscopically-identified stars are marked as blue asterisks; candidate stars selected by our template-fitting and morphological criteria are marked as green filled triangles.

Figure A.14: The top two panels are plots of z_{phot} versus z_{spec} and the histogram of $\Delta z/(1+z_{\text{spec}})$ for X-ray sources (281 in total) before adding AGN templates when estimating z_{phot} . The bottom two panels are the same as the top two panels but after adding AGN templates. Red solid lines indicate $\Delta z/(1+z_{\text{spec}}) = 0$ and red dashed lines indicate $\Delta z/(1+z_{\text{spec}}) = \pm 0.15$.

ID (1)	$\alpha_{J2000.0}$ (2)	$\delta_{J2000.0}$ (3)	z_{phot} (4)	z_{alt} (5)	L68 (6)	U68 (7)	L95 (8)	U95 (9)	L99 (10)	U99 (11)	Type (12)	Q_z (13)	S/N (14)	Detect (15)	z_{spec} (16)
1	188.52433	62.348192	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	-1	-1.000	16.3	Z	-1.000
2	188.52454	62.299627	0.184	1.152	0.411	3.259	0.080	4.796	0.013	6.185	0	33.2	3.21	Z	-1.000
3	188.52457	62.306804	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	-1	-1.000	11.6	Z	-1.000
4	188.52474	62.379926	0.138	2.682	0.245	2.562	0.044	2.792	0.011	2.910	0	6.19	2.54	RZ	-1.000
5	188.52486	62.334587	0.694	-1.000	0.383	1.012	0.060	1.931	0.011	2.650	0	0.163	4.91	Z	-1.000

Table A.6: H-HDF-N photometric catalog. The full table contains 53 columns of information for the 131,678 sources (see Section A.7.6 for the descriptions of the columns.)

(This table is available in its entirety in a machine-readable form in the online journal. A portion is shown here for guidance regarding its form and content.)

A.8 Summary

Following the procedures outlined in Figure A.1, we have derived z_{phot} for 131,678 sources in the entire H-HDF-N region (including both the central and extended areas) based on 15 broadband images, i.e., the U , B , V , R , I , z_c , z_o , J , H , K_s , HK' , $A1$, $S1$, $A2$, and $S2$ bands. PSF-matched photometry is extracted in order to obtain accurate colors that are the key to achieving high-quality z_{phot} , given that the PSFs of our imaging data differ significantly. We compute the zero point of each band to eliminate systematic offsets and then estimate z_{phot} with EAzy (however, we do not apply the zero-point offsets to the photometry presented in our final catalog). Two additional galaxy templates are added to the EAzy default template set in order to obtain z_{phot} with higher accuracy. We classify the sources in our catalog as stars or galaxies based on SED fitting and complementary morphological parametrization. Furthermore, we match our sources with the A03 2 Ms CDF-N main-catalog X-ray sources using a likelihood-ratio matching technique, resulting in 462 non-stellar X-ray sources. To evaluate our z_{phot} quality, we compare our z_{phot} with z_{spec} when available and find $\sigma_{\text{NMAD}}=0.029$ with an outlier fraction of 5.5% for the 2845 non-X-ray spectroscopic galaxies. More specifically, we find $\sigma_{\text{NMAD}}=0.024$ with 2.7% outliers for sources brighter than $R = 23$ mag, $\sigma_{\text{NMAD}}=0.034$ with 7.4% outliers for sources fainter than $R = 23$ mag, $\sigma_{\text{NMAD}}=0.026$ with 3.9% outliers for sources having $z < 1$, and $\sigma_{\text{NMAD}}=0.034$ with 9.0% outliers for sources having $z > 1$. This z_{phot} quality is comparable to those presented in previous similar works. The above z_{phot} procedure yields a relatively poor z_{phot} quality for X-ray sources (281 X-ray sources have z_{spec}), with $\sigma_{\text{NMAD}}=0.037$ and an outlier fraction of 16.7%. To improve this situation, we add three additional AGN templates, and obtain an improved z_{phot} quality for X-ray sources, with $\sigma_{\text{NMAD}}=0.035$ and an outlier fraction of 12.5%. We make our catalog publicly available and provide guidance on how to make use of it.

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Disclaimer

The findings and conclusions do not necessarily reflect the view of the funding agencies.

Appendix B | Long-Term X-ray Variability of Typical Active Galactic Nu- clei in the Distant Universe

B.1 Introduction

Variability studies are valuable in probing the physical properties of active galactic nuclei (AGNs) [400, 401]. Simple light-travel time arguments enable a first-order estimation of the sizes of the radiation-emitting regions. More detailed reverberation-based studies provide size estimates of different components; e.g., the correlations among multi-color light curves give temperature profiles of accretion disks [402]; time lags between the continuum and emission lines indicate the radius of broad-line region (BLR) [403]; and delays of the near-infrared (NIR) dust emission compared to the optical disk emission constrain the inner size of the dusty torus [404]. Changes in absorption provide insights into the absorbing matter: e.g., variability of broad absorption line (BAL) troughs reveals wind properties [405], and variations of optical reddening and X-ray absorption indicate a clumpy nature of the ambient gas [406, 407]. In AGN jet studies, the rapid variability of blazars' γ -ray emission often indicates small emitting regions and the relativistically beamed nature of the radiation [408, 409].

X-ray variability is of great importance among AGN variability studies. In AGN spectral energy distributions (SEDs), luminous X-ray emission is almost universal and often a significant contributor to the total source power [107]. X-ray variability is

generally of larger amplitude and more rapid compared to that at longer wavelengths [400,401], indicating that the high-energy radiation is probing the immediate vicinity of the supermassive black hole (SMBH). For the majority population of obscured AGNs, the penetrating nature of X-rays often allows variability studies of emission as well as absorption [410,411].

Intensive X-ray variability analyses have been performed for the radio-quiet AGNs that are the majority population. Studies of broadband X-ray continuum variability have found that local Seyfert 1s (i.e., unabsorbed AGNs) are highly X-ray variable, and that the variation amplitude generally decreases as luminosity increases [412,413]. This amplitude-luminosity relation might be a byproduct of a primary amplitude-SMBH mass relation [413]. Seyfert 2s, especially the Compton-thick (obscuration column density $N_{\text{H}} \gtrsim 1.5 \times 10^{24} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) ones, tend to be less X-ray variable than Seyfert 1s at least on time scales of hours or less [411,414,415]. Studies of distant AGNs, such as optically selected quasars, have also reported prevalent X-ray variability (e.g., [416], G12 hereafter; [47]) and a similar amplitude-luminosity relation as seen in local Seyfert galaxies [417–420]. Compared to the X-ray continuum, the narrow Fe K emission-line components are less variable [421], consistent with the picture that they originate from the outer disk or torus. Recent works [422,423] reveal short-timescale (minutes) lags of the broad Fe K emission-line components relative to the continuum, suggesting they are emitted from the inner disk illuminated by the continuum X-rays. X-ray photoelectric absorption variability has also been found in many Seyfert 2s [424,425]. Modeling of the observed absorption variations suggests this absorption originates in gas clouds in the BLR or torus orbiting the central source [407,426–428]. X-ray absorption variability has also been widely investigated in warm absorbers, BAL quasar winds, and ultra fast outflows (UFOs), usefully characterizing wind properties [210,429–432].

The X-ray variability of AGNs generally shows a red-noise power spectral density [433]; i.e., AGNs vary by larger amplitudes on longer time scales. X-ray variability analyses on longer time scales thus have a better chance of detecting variability in data of a given signal-to-noise ratio, thereby providing physical insights about the nature of the AGNs. Long-term variability studies are also helpful in evaluating the effects of AGN variability upon statistical inferences made about source populations in single-epoch X-ray surveys. Furthermore, long-term X-ray variability studies might capture novel AGN phenomena; e.g., “changing-

Reference	Med. Max. $\log \Delta t_{\text{rest}}$	Med. Counts	z	$\log L_X$	N
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
This work	8.3	1399	0.6–3.1	42.7–44.5	68
A00	5.7	63	0.6–2.0	43.8–45.0	86
Pao04	7.3	64	0.3–2.1	41.0–43.9	186
Pap08	6.3	280	0.6–2.7	43.1–44.7	66
G12	7.3	130	0.4–3.0	43.6–45.2	264
L14	7.4	350	0.5–2.3	43.2–44.7	638
S14	8.1	–	1.8–4.3	45.4–45.7	7

Table B.1: Summary of Variability Studies of Distant AGNs. (1) A00: [417]; Pao04: [418]; Pap08: [419]; G12: [416], L14: [420]; S14: [47]. For Pao04, we only include sources with redshift information. (2) Sample median of maximum rest-frame time spans, where Δt_{rest} is in units of seconds. (3) Sample median of net counts. We do not calculate the median counts of S14 due to large fluctuations in counts among their seven sources. (4) Redshift range. We adopt the 10th–90th percentile ranges. (5) X-ray luminosity range (10th–90th percentile). (6) Number of sources.

look” events [434, 435], emission-state changes [436], and torus-eclipse events [427]. Variability analyses on time scales of years can probe the regime of mechanical instabilities of the accretion disk (assuming a $\sim 10^8 M_\odot$ SMBH; see, e.g., [401]).

Motivated by the importance of X-ray variability studies, especially on long time scales, we here explore the X-ray variability of the X-ray brightest radio-quiet AGNs in the Chandra Deep Field-South (CDF-S; e.g., [396]; B. Luo et al., in preparation, L16 hereafter). We take advantage of the data products from the observations by *Chandra* of the CDF-S. The observations span ≈ 15 yr and are well separated, enabling us to characterize long-term variability properties of distant AGNs. The rest-frame time scales probed in this study are among the longest for X-ray variability studies of distant AGNs (see Figure B.1), and they are the longest for an X-ray selected AGN sample. Table B.1 summarizes the basic sample properties in this work and previous variability studies of distant AGNs. Furthermore, the long exposure times, low source-cell backgrounds, and state-of-the-art source-extraction techniques ([241, 396]; L16) yield high-quality data products, allowing us to perform, in addition to photometric analyses, reliable basic spectral analyses. We assess variability of both intrinsic (absorption-corrected) X-ray luminosity and absorption, and study their dependence on time scale and source properties.

The paper is structured as follows. We describe the observations, data reduction,

Figure B.1: X-ray luminosity as a function of maximum rest-frame time span. Different colors indicate samples from different studies (A00: [417]; Pao04: [418]; Pap08: [419]; G12: [416], L14: [420]; S14: [47]). The X-ray luminosities from the literature are derived assuming a power-law photon index of 1.8. The X-ray luminosities of our sources are the mean values detailed in Section B.3.2.1. The maximum rest-frame time spans for A00, Pao04, and Pap08 are calculated assuming that each source is present in all observations; this assumption might overestimate time spans for some sources. The rest-frame time spans probed in this work are among the longest for X-ray variability studies.

and sample selection in Section B.2. In Section B.3, we perform both photometric and spectral variability analyses and investigate variability dependences on source properties and time scales. We discuss our results and draw conclusions in Section B.4.

Throughout this paper, we assume a cosmology with $H_0 = 70 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$, $\Omega_M = 0.3$, and $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.7$. We adopt $N_{\text{H}} = 8.8 \times 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ as the value of the column density of Galactic absorption [90]. Quoted uncertainties are at the 1σ (68%) confidence level, unless otherwise stated. We adopt the standard naming convention for *Chandra* CDF-S sources, i.e., “CXOCDFS J033XXX.X–27XXXX”; for simplicity, we drop the “CXOCDFS” and quote as “J033XXX.X–27XXXX”

directly.

B.2 Data and Sample

B.2.1 Observations and Data Reduction

This work is based on the *Chandra* CDF-S data. The observations were taken from October 1999 to January 2015 with a total observation time of 5.7 Ms (referred as 6 Ms, hereafter). In total, there are 84 observations utilized with median exposure time ≈ 60 ks. All of the 84 observations were performed using the Advanced CCD Imaging Spectrometer imaging array (ACIS-I; [437]; see L16 for more observation details). The data products were processed from level 1 files (L16) using CIAO v4.7 with CALDB v4.6.7. Spectra and photometry from each observation were extracted using ACIS Extract v4864 [438]. For each source, AE constructs observation-specific polygonal extraction apertures. The apertures are chosen to maximize S/N, based on simulations of point spread functions (PSFs).

Since most CDF-S sources have low S/N in single observations, we bin data from neighboring observations as one “epoch” to enhance the signal-to-noise ratio (S/N). We have binned the observations so that each epoch consists of observations totaling about 1–2 Ms of exposure time, resulting in a photometric/spectral set of four epochs for each source. Our bins were chosen to include as much data as possible in the shortest possible span of time, in order to minimize variability effects within the bins. The bin widths range from about several months to one year. Due to cosmological time dilation, the rest-frame total time span and bin width are a factor of $1 + z$ shorter than the observed-frame values. Table B.2 shows our observation-binning approach. This binning process is carried out using the MERGE_OBSERVATIONS stage of AE. We do not include *XMM-Newton* CDF-S data in our analyses, since cross-calibration between *Chandra* and *XMM-Newton* spectra can be problematic [103], and the *XMM-Newton* data have substantially higher background. Also, most of the *XMM-Newton* observations ($\sim 85\%$ of the exposure time) were taken within about 1.5 years [439], and thus are not suitable for year-scale variability studies.

Epoch	Start Date	End Date	Bin Width (yr)	Exp. ^a (Ms)	Obs. ^b
1	Oct. 1999	Dec. 2000	1.19	0.94	11
2	Sept. 2007	Nov. 2007	0.12	0.97	12
3	Mar. 2010	July 2010	0.34	1.98	31
4	June 2014	Jan. 2015	0.57	1.85	30

Table B.2: Observation Binning. a. Total exposure time of observations in each bin. b. Number of observations in each bin.

B.2.2 Sample Selection

To perform reliable analyses, we select our sources based on the following criteria:

1. Classified as an AGN in the L16 catalog;
2. Not identified as a radio-loud AGN by [102].
3. More than 600 total net counts (i.e., background-subtracted, 0.5–7 keV) in the full 6 Ms exposure; and
4. Off-axis angle $< 8'$.

The first criterion classifies AGNs based upon the X-ray luminosity, X-ray spectral shape, X-ray-to-optical flux ratio, X-ray-to-radio luminosity ratio, and optical emission-line properties, and it is described in more detail in Section 4.4 of [396]. The second criterion excludes the sources possibly affected by jet-linked emission in their X-ray spectra, to avoid dealing with the significant additional complexity of such emission [440]. This criterion removes only 6 sources that satisfy the other three criteria. The third constraint guarantees suitable photon statistics for variability characterization and spectral fitting; given the observed X-ray variability of our sources, we do not have any problematic cases where, e.g., one bin contained most of the counts and the others had very poor counting statistics (see Sections B.3.1 and B.3.2.2). The fourth criterion discards sources with large off-axis angles, which have generally poorer S/N due to the degraded PSF, and it also guarantees each source is covered by almost all observations.

Sixty-eight sources are selected with 649–11283 counts; the median number of counts is 1399. Figure B.2 shows the distribution of our counts. Our sources generally have more counts than those in previous studies, usually by substantial factors (Table B.1), allowing improved source characterization. The faintest selected sources have fluxes (observed-frame 0.5–7 keV; see Section B.3.2.2 for flux

calculation) of $\approx 1 \times 10^{-15}$ erg cm $^{-2}$ s $^{-1}$, similar to the full-band source-detection limit of the *Chandra* COSMOS-Legacy survey [217]. We are thus characterizing in this work the AGNs responsible for producing much of cosmic accretion power; our measurements probe ≈ 20 –3 times below the knee luminosity, L_X^* , of the X-ray luminosity function at $z = 0.5 - 4$ [10, 13].

The spectroscopic and photometric redshift data are compiled by L16. For each source, we adopt the spectroscopic redshift (z_{spec}) either marked as “secure” by L16 or consistent with the photometric redshift (z_{phot}) measurement (i.e., z_{phot} differs from z_{spec} by less than 10%). Otherwise, if z_{spec} is not available or disagrees with z_{phot} , we adopt z_{phot} because “insecure” z_{spec} are less reliable than z_{phot} . Those insecure z_{spec} are often based on spectra with few features, e.g., a tentative single absorption line, but z_{phot} are derived from SED fitting of $\gtrsim 15$ photometric bands [79, 242]. In total, we have 55 z_{spec} and 13 z_{phot} . The z_{phot} quality is generally high (fractional errors \sim a few percent) thanks to the wide multi-band photometric coverage used to derive z_{phot} [79, 242]. The redshift and intrinsic X-ray luminosity L_X ¹ distributions of the sample are plotted in Figure B.3, with the L_X values for some representative local AGNs marked for comparison purposes. The median L_X of our sources is 4×10^{43} erg s $^{-1}$, several times larger than that of the whole CDF-S AGN sample ($\approx 8 \times 10^{42}$ erg s $^{-1}$, L16); the median redshifts of the two samples are similar (≈ 1.5). Many local well-known AGNs have L_X within our luminosity coverage, and thus our sources, at least in this sense, appear to be distant analogs of these local AGNs.

We classify a source as type I if any broad emission line is reported in the redshift literature (20 sources); if only narrow emission lines/absorption lines are reported (35 sources) we assign a type II classification. We caution that there might be some intrinsic type I objects misclassified as type II due to, e.g., lack of spectral coverage of the hydrogen Balmer lines [441] or the spectral S/N not being sufficient to identify broad lines. If the spectral classification of a source is not available in the literature, it is classified based on fitting of the spectral energy distribution [242]: if its rest-frame optical color is blue (i.e., rest-frame $u - g < 0.8$)² we classify it as type I, otherwise as type II. This color-classification scheme results

¹Absorption-corrected X-ray luminosity in the rest-frame 2–10 keV band; we use the epoch-mean value (see Section B.3.2.1).

²This threshold generally separates our type I and type II AGNs classified by spectral features; see, e.g., [442] and [292] for the effectiveness of optical color classifications.

in 4 type I and 9 type II AGNs, in addition to the spectral classification. Therefore, our sample consists of 24 type I and 44 type II AGNs. The optical classification is broadly consistent with X-ray classification approaches (i.e., using the epoch-mean $N_{\text{H}} = 10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ as the threshold for type II; see Section B.3.2.1) despite some exceptions (see Figure B.8). Type I sources generally have more counts than type II sources; their median counts are 2199 and 1098, respectively. Table B.3 lists the properties of individual sources in our sample.

BAL quasars often show heavy and complex X-ray absorption despite their type I nature [443, 444]. It is of interest to investigate their X-ray variability behavior [431, 445]. There are 8 type I quasars in our sample, if we define quasars as AGNs with $L_{\text{X}} > 10^{44} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$.³ One of our objects has been reported as a BAL quasar (J033209.4–274806, e.g., [447]) at $z = 2.81$; it is X-ray luminous ($L_{\text{X}} \approx 3 \times 10^{44} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$) and highly obscured ($N_{\text{H}} \approx 2 \times 10^{23} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) with an intrinsic power-law photon index $\Gamma = 1.68$ (see Section B.3.2). This small number of BAL quasars is expected considering only $\approx 20\%$ of type I quasars are BAL quasars [448, 449].

Three of our sources, J033247.8–274232 at $z = 0.98$, J033211.3–275213 at $z = 3.74$, and J033212.9–275236 at $z = 2.56$, are potentially detected in the *NuSTAR* hard band (8–24 keV; [450]). The matching between *Chandra* and *NuSTAR* sources was performed by [450]. J033247.8–274232 has an almost unambiguous *NuSTAR* counterpart, because it is the only bright *Chandra* source within $23''$ (≈ 3 times the typical *NuSTAR* positional uncertainty) of the *NuSTAR* source position. J033211.3–275213 and J033212.9–275236 are matched to a single *NuSTAR* source, and are both $\approx 15''$ from the *NuSTAR* counterpart. There are no other bright *Chandra* sources within $23''$ of this *NuSTAR* source position. Therefore, one of these two high-redshift *Chandra* sources likely has a *NuSTAR* hard-band detection.

³Corresponding to $L_{\nu}(2500 \text{ \AA}) \sim 10^{30} \text{ erg s}^{-1} \text{ Hz}^{-1}$ calculated from the $\alpha_{\text{OX}}-L_{\nu}(2500 \text{ \AA})$ relation presented in [446].

Name (CXOCDFS)	RA	DEC	z	Δz	Opt. type	Off-Axis	Counts	P_{PF}	P_{HR}	E_{peg}	<i>goodness</i>	Γ
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)	(13)
J033158.1–274833	52.99210	–27.80943	0.74	n/a	IIs	6.69	1366.0	0.00	32.75	0.50	10.2	1.52
J033158.2–275041	52.99283	–27.84490	3.31	0.09	Ic	7.05	2684.8	0.00	86.68	0.96	0.5	1.72
J033200.3–274319	53.00150	–27.72209	1.04	n/a	Is	7.96	3598.1	0.00	60.04	0.50	1.0	1.78
J033201.5–274327	53.00663	–27.72420	2.73	n/a	Is	7.67	2772.0	0.00	15.30	0.66	4.8	1.72
J033202.4–274600	53.01026	–27.76675	1.62	n/a	Is	6.18	2012.5	0.00	61.65	0.50	7.3	1.65

Table B.3: Source Properties. The full table contains 21 columns of information for 68 sources. (This table is available in its entirety in a machine-readable form in the online journal. A portion is shown here for guidance regarding its form and content.)

Column (1): Standard name of *Chandra* CDF-S sources.

Columns (2) and (3): J2000 coordinates.

Column (4): Adopted redshift. See L16 for redshift references.

Column (5): 1σ errors of photometric redshift. n/a indicates a spectroscopic redshift has been used.

Column (6): Optical spectral type (see Section B.2.2 for the classification scheme). Is (IIs): type I (II) from spectral classification; Ic (IIc): type I (II) from color classification. The spectral classifications are from [73–75, 303, 447, 451, 452].

Column (7): Off-axis angle in units of arcminutes.

Column (8): Full-band (0.5–7 keV) total available net counts (not aperture corrected).

Columns (9) and (10): p -value of photon-flux and hardness-ratio variability, respectively (Section B.3.1). Both are in units of %.

Column (11): The lower end of the normalization band used in *peppwrlw*, in units of keV (Appendix B.5.1).

Column (12): *goodness* of the spectral fitting (*wabs* \times *zwabs* \times *peppwrlw* model), in units of % (Section B.3.2.1).

Column (13): Power-law photon index.

Columns (14) and (15): Epoch-mean values of intrinsic L_X (rest-frame 2–10 keV, in units of erg s^{-1}) and N_{H} (in units of cm^{-2}), respectively (Section B.3.2.1).

Columns (16) and (17); Metrics (ΔAIC_L and ΔAIC_N) of the significance of L_X and N_{H} variability, respectively (Section B.3.2.3).

Columns (18) and (19): Normalized excess variance of L_X variability ($\sigma_{\text{exc},L}^2$) and its uncertainty, respectively (Section B.3.2.5).

Columns (20) and (21): Normalized excess variance of N_{H} variability ($\sigma_{\text{exc},N}^2$) and its uncertainty, respectively (Section B.3.2.5). We only calculated this quantity for the 35 sources with all four epochs having $\delta N_{\text{H},i}/N_{\text{H},i} < 0.4$ (see Appendix B.5.1); n/a indicates the other 33 sources.

B.3 Data Analyses

B.3.1 Photometric Variability

B.3.1.1 Method

We use full-band (0.5–7 keV) photometry to analyze photon-flux (PF , i.e., count rate per unit area, in units of counts $\text{s}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$) variability. For each epoch of a source, we calculate PF as

$$PF_i = \frac{net_counts_i}{effarea_i \times exptime_i}, \quad (\text{B.1})$$

and its uncertainty

$$\delta PF_i = \frac{\delta net_counts_i}{effarea_i \times exptime_i}, \quad (\text{B.2})$$

where the subscript i denotes the epoch; net_counts_i and δnet_counts_i ⁴ are background-subtracted counts and corresponding error, respectively; $effarea_i$ and $exptime_i$ are the effective area and exposure time, respectively. The effective area is approximated as the average ancillary response file (ARF) weighted by the average CDF-S AGN spectrum, i.e., a $\Gamma = 1.4$ power law with Galactic absorption; see, e.g., [418]. This procedure accounts for the varying sensitivity of *Chandra* among different epochs due to, e.g., quantum-efficiency degradation and gaps between CCDs, since these factors are considered by AE when calculating the ARF. Figure B.4 shows light curves of the 6 sources with the most counts.

To identify variable sources, we calculate the statistic

$$X_{PF}^2 = \sum_{i=1}^4 \frac{(PF_i - \langle PF \rangle)^2}{(\delta PF_i)^2}, \quad (\text{B.3})$$

where $\langle PF \rangle$ is the unweighted mean of PF_i [461].⁵ For sources with large numbers of counts, the probability distribution of PF approaches the normal distribution, and thus X_{PF}^2 should follow the χ^2 distribution with three degrees of freedom ($\chi_{\text{dof}=3}^2$). Our sources have at least 600 total net counts (at least ~ 150 counts or

⁴We use the average of upper and lower 1σ errors here, which are calculated by AE using [323].

⁵We have tested using the mean weighted by $1/(\delta PF_i)^2$, and obtained similar results. This is also true for the hardness-ratio variability.

Figure B.2: The histogram of total net counts of our 68 sources. The red and brown bars indicate type I and type II AGNs. The vertical dashed lines indicate the median counts of this work and previous studies, respectively (A00: [417]; Pao04: [418]; Pap08: [419]; G12: [416], L14: [420]). Note that A00 and Pao04 have very similar median counts. We do not show the median counts of [47] due to large fluctuations in counts among their seven sources. Our sample only includes bright sources with counts greater than 600. Our type I AGNs generally have more available counts than their type II counterparts.

S/N ~ 12 per bin). Therefore $\chi^2_{\text{dof}=3}$ should be a good approximation of X^2_{PF} . To verify this point and find an accurate p -value (P_{PF}) from X^2_{PF} , we adopt a Monte Carlo simulation strategy similar to that in [418] and [462]. The null hypothesis is that PF remains constant in the four epochs at PF_{mean} . To perform the simulations, we need to know model counts in each epoch. We convert PF_{mean} to the net counts expected in each epoch as

$$net_counts_i^{\text{model}} = PF_{\text{mean}} \times effarea_i \times exptime_i. \quad (\text{B.4})$$

We obtain the model source counts (not background subtracted) and model back-

Figure B.3: Upper panel: Redshift histogram for our 68 sources. The blue and green bars indicate sources with spectroscopic redshifts and photometric redshifts, respectively. Lower panel: Absorption-corrected X-ray luminosity (2–10 keV, rest-frame) histogram. The red and brown bars indicate type I and type II AGNs, respectively. The values are the epoch-mean L_X described in Section B.3.2.1. Along the top of the panel, we label the typical absorption-corrected L_X values for some representative type I (red) and type II (brown) AGNs in the local universe. The 4-digit and 5-digit numbers indicate NGC and IRAS sources, respectively. The L_X data were compiled from the literature [410, 453–460]. Our sources cover wide ranges of both z and L_X . In terms of L_X , our sources appear to be distant analogs of many local Seyfert galaxies and moderate-luminosity quasars.

Figure B.4: Light curves of the 6 sources with the most counts. The red dashed horizontal lines indicate the unweighted mean of photon fluxes for each source. The horizontal error bars indicate the bin width of each epoch. The rest-frame time of epoch 1 is set to 1 yr. Some source properties are labeled on the corresponding panels. All of the 6 sources show photon-flux variability (i.e., $P_{PF} < 5\%$).

ground counts as

$$\begin{aligned} src_counts_i^{\text{model}} &= net_counts_i^{\text{model}} + \frac{bkg_counts_i^{\text{observed}}}{backscal_i}, \\ bkg_counts_i^{\text{model}} &= bkg_counts_i^{\text{observed}}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.5})$$

where *backscal* is the factor produced by AE that scales background counts (usually obtained in a large aperture) to the source-extraction aperture. We use $src_counts_i^{\text{model}}$ ($bkg_counts_i^{\text{model}}$) as the mean in a Poisson distribution to simulate src_counts_i (bkg_counts_i), and extract photometry following the algorithm in AE.⁶ We obtain the X_{PF}^2 for a simulated data set (10000 simulations) following the same procedures as described above. We perform Kolmogorov–Smirnov (KS) tests between the simulated X_{PF}^2 distributions and the $\chi_{\text{dof}=3}^2$ distribution. The resulting KS statistics for our sources have median 0.015; this small value indicates our simulated X_{PF}^2 distributions are very similar to the $\chi_{\text{dof}=3}^2$ distribution.

We define the hardness ratio (*HR*) for a source in an epoch as

$$HR_i = \frac{PF_{i,hard} - PF_{i,soft}}{PF_{i,hard} + PF_{i,soft}}, \quad (\text{B.6})$$

where $PF_{i,hard}$ and $PF_{i,soft}$ are photon fluxes as defined above but for the hard band (2–7 keV) and soft band (0.5–2 keV), respectively. We estimate the error of *HR* from error propagation as

$$\begin{aligned} \delta HR_i &= \frac{2PF_{i,hard}PF_{i,soft}}{(PF_{i,hard} + PF_{i,soft})^2} \times \\ &\sqrt{\left(\frac{\delta PF_{i,hard}}{PF_{i,hard}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\delta PF_{i,soft}}{PF_{i,soft}}\right)^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.7})$$

To identify *HR*-variable sources, we calculate

$$X_{HR}^2 = \sum_{i=1}^4 \frac{(HR_i - \langle HR \rangle)^2}{(\delta HR_i)^2}, \quad (\text{B.8})$$

where $\langle HR \rangle$ is the unweighted mean of HR_i .

We perform similar simulations as above to convert X_{HR}^2 to a *p*-value (P_{HR}).

⁶See Section 5.10 of the AE manual available at http://www2.astro.psu.edu/xray/docs/TARA/ae_users_guide.

The null-hypothesis is that HR_i is constant and equals HR_{mean} over the four epochs. We approximate the model full-band net counts as the sum of the observed hard-band and soft-band net counts,

$$\begin{aligned} net_counts_{i,full}^{\text{model}} = & \hspace{15em} \text{(B.9)} \\ & net_counts_{i,hard}^{\text{observed}} + net_counts_{i,soft}^{\text{observed}}. \end{aligned}$$

The model hard-band and soft-band net counts are calculated by

$$\begin{aligned} net_counts_{i,hard}^{\text{model}} = & \hspace{15em} \text{(B.10)} \\ & net_counts_{i,full}^{\text{model}} \times \\ & \left(\frac{net_counts_{i,hard}}{net_counts_{i,hard} + net_counts_{i,soft}} \right)^{\text{model}} \\ = & net_counts_{i,full}^{\text{model}} \times \\ & \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \left(\frac{net_counts_{i,hard} - net_counts_{i,hard}}{net_counts_{i,hard} + net_counts_{i,soft}} \right)^{\text{model}} \right) \\ = & net_counts_{i,full}^{\text{model}} \times \frac{1 + HR_{\text{mean}}}{2} \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} net_counts_{i,soft}^{\text{model}} = & \hspace{15em} \text{(B.11)} \\ & net_counts_{i,full}^{\text{model}} - net_counts_{i,hard}^{\text{model}}, \end{aligned}$$

respectively.

Knowing $net_counts_{i,hard(soft)}^{\text{model}}$, we obtain $src_counts_{i,hard(soft)}^{\text{model}}$ and $bkg_counts_{i,hard(soft)}^{\text{model}}$ using Equation B.5. Similar to the case of X_{PF}^2 , the simulated X_{HR}^2 distributions are close to the $\chi_{\text{dof}=3}^2$ distribution. The KS statistics derived from comparing simulated X_{HR}^2 distributions and $\chi_{\text{dof}=3}^2$ have median 0.023.

B.3.1.2 Results

The histograms of P_{PF} and P_{HR} are presented in Figure B.5. Using $P = 5\%$ as the threshold for variability ($\sim 68 \times 5\% \lesssim 4$ false positives expected), 90% (61/68) and 16% (11/68) of our sources display PF variability and HR variability, respectively. All of our six sources with the most counts are variable (see Figure B.4).

Changing the threshold to $P = 1\%$ ($\sim 68 \times 1\% \lesssim 1$ false positive expected) leads to a PF -variable fraction and a HR -variable fraction of 84% (57/68) and 9% (6/68), respectively. This PF -variable fraction (84%) is higher than that of optically selected Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS, [349]) quasars under the same confidence level (i.e., 65%; the sample is from G12 with the same count constraint of 600 applied). This result supports an intrinsic anticorrelation between variability amplitude and X-ray luminosity (see Section B.3.2.6), considering those SDSS quasars are generally ≈ 10 times more X-ray luminous than our sources (see Table B.1 and Section B.3.2.3). However, this behavior might also be a result of different rest-frame time samplings (see Figure B.1). With the $P = 5\%$ threshold, almost all (23/24) type I AGNs and 86% (38/44) of type II AGNs are PF variable; 13% (3/24) of type I AGNs and 18% (8/44) of type II AGNs are HR variable. The higher PF -variable source fraction for type I sources might be due to their higher numbers of counts (Figure B.2). Type II sources are more likely to be HR variable despite their smaller numbers of counts. However, Fisher’s exact test shows that the dependences of variable source fractions on optical spectral type are not statistically significant.

B.3.1.3 Variability Within Each Epoch

We also use each *Chandra* observation as a bin to analyze the variability within each epoch ($\lesssim 1$ yr, observed-frame). The observation lengths range from about 30 to 100 ks (see L16). We calculate P_{PF} and P_{HR} for each source within each of the four epochs. The method is the same as described in Section B.3.1.1. PF variability is still significant: the PF -variable (i.e., $P_{PF} < 5\%$) source fractions are 49%, 29%, 56%, and 38% for each bin, respectively.⁷ We find the variable source fraction is higher for sources with more counts, likely due to their higher S/N. We do not detect statistically significant HR variability: the HR -variable (i.e., $P_{HR} < 5\%$) source fractions are 3%, 3%, 1%, and 3%, respectively, consistent with the expected false-positive rate. This result is likely due to the low S/N in this dataset compared to that of the binned data.

More detailed analyses based on such a binning strategy will be presented in another paper (X. C. Zheng et al., in preparation). Those analyses suggest

⁷Besides random fluctuations, there are many factors, including total exposure time and epoch bin width, that can affect the detected variable source fraction for each epoch.

that short-term (days-to-months) variability of our sources by large amplitudes (e.g., more than a factor of two) is rare, similar to our results on long time scales (Sections B.3.2.2 and B.3.2.5).

B.3.2 Spectral Variability

B.3.2.1 Method

The photometric analyses in Section B.3.1 roughly evaluate the spectral normalization and shape changes. To characterize the spectral variability more accurately as well as gain improved physical insights, we perform spectral fitting for each source. The fitting is based on full-band (observed-frame 0.5–7 keV) spectra to maximize the available counts. Given our high-quality X-ray spectra (with a median full-band S/N ≈ 17 in each epoch) owing to the good angular resolution and low source-cell background of *Chandra*, we can still do reliable spectral fitting even though the counts per epoch (median ~ 350) are moderate. Note that we are typically accessing penetrating rest-frame X-rays up to $\approx 10 - 30$ keV.

We use XSPEC v12.9.0i [89] to carry out spectral fitting. Counts are not binned over different ACIS pulse height amplitude (PHA) channels, and the Cash statistic [88] is used for fitting. Considering the available counts, we adopt a simple fitting model of a power law with Galactic and intrinsic absorption $wabs \times zwabs \times pegpwlw$ (see [463] for the $wabs$ and $zwabs$ models). We adopt $pegpwlw$ (normalized over a finite energy band) instead of the widely used $powerlaw$ (normalized at observed-frame 1 keV) for the reasons described in Appendix B.5.1. We fix the redshift ($zwabs$) as the adopted value in Section B.2.2. The allowed ranges of N_{H} ($zwabs$) and Γ ($pegpwlw$) are set to $10^{19} - 10^{24} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and $1.2 - 2.4$, respectively. The counts of our sources in each epoch (median ~ 350) generally cannot constrain Γ effectively; e.g., [464] found that even a simple $powerlaw$ model would require $\gtrsim 1000$ counts to obtain an uncertainty (90% confidence level) of Γ within 0.2. Studies of quasars and local luminous AGNs show that spectral variability generally follows a “softer when brighter” behavior [416, 465–467].⁸ However, based on the empirical X-ray flux– Γ relations given by those studies, the Γ

⁸This behavior likely changes when the Eddington ratio is low (i.e., $\lesssim 10^{-3}$; e.g., [467, 468]), but the Eddington ratios for our sources are likely to be higher than this threshold, considering their luminosities (see Figure B.3) and that they are the X-ray brightest AGNs in the CDF-S.

variability amplitudes for our sources are expected to be small and not detectable given the counts we have in each epoch. For example, flux variability by a factor of two (about the upper limit of our flux-variability amplitudes; see Section B.3.2.2) only produces $\Delta\Gamma \approx 0.1$. Motivated by this expected near constancy of Γ , we thus simultaneously fit the spectra of all four epochs by linking their photon indexes Γ (*peppwrlw*), assuming no substantial Γ variability. Considering the low source-cell backgrounds and high count numbers for our sources, we do not specifically model the background but employ the XSPEC default background modeling strategy.⁹ The *norm_i* (i.e., normalization of *peppwrlw*) and *N_{H,i}* (*zwabs*) are set free and not linked across epochs, where subscripts *i* denote the epoch indexes. This spectral fitting yields best-fit model parameters, i.e., Γ_{fit} , *norm_i*, and *N_{H,i}*, and the errors of *norm_i*. The errors of *N_{H,i}* are estimated with the method detailed in Section B.5.1. This method is critical for obtaining accurate errors of *N_{H,i}* for the reasons explained in Section B.5.1. The Γ_{fit} distribution is shown in Figure B.6. The distribution is similar to that found by [469], except that our dispersion is smaller likely due to our larger numbers of counts. We set both Galactic and intrinsic absorption to none and calculate the absorption-corrected X-ray luminosity in the rest-frame 2–10 keV band for each epoch. The unweighted-mean luminosity (absorption column density) of the four epochs is denoted as $L_X(N_H)$ and widely used throughout this paper.

Since we fit the unbinned spectra with the Cash statistic, the spectral-fit quality cannot be inferred directly from the best-fit statistic, e.g., χ^2/dof in the minimum χ^2 fitting case. Instead, we perform goodness-of-fit Monte Carlo simulations for each source in XSPEC.¹⁰ XSPEC simulates 1000 spectra from the best-fit parameters, and calculates the fraction (*goodness*) of simulated spectra with KS statistic less than that of the observed spectrum. Here, the KS statistic is used to describe the “similarity” between a spectrum and the model, similar to χ^2 in the minimum χ^2 fitting case. In other words, *goodness* can be interpreted as the confidence level to reject the model. The distribution of *goodness* is presented in Figure B.6. The fits are acceptable (*goodness* < 50%, e.g., [470]) for all our sources. The worst case is J033218.3–275055 with *goodness* = 44%, a Compton-thick candidate reported in the literature [469, 471]. A detailed discussion of this source is presented in

⁹See <https://heasarc.gsfc.nasa.gov/xanadu/xspec> for details.

¹⁰For more details, see <https://heasarc.gsfc.nasa.gov/xanadu/xspec/manual/XSappendixStatistics.html> and <http://xraygroup.astro.noa.gr/Webpage-prodec/documentation.html#good>

Section B.5.2.

B.3.2.2 Flux Variability over 15 Years

Long-term X-ray variability may affect physical inferences about X-ray source populations; e.g., the star-formation vs. AGN-activity connection may be affected by \sim Myr timescale AGN variability (e.g., [26]). It is thus of interest to assess whether X-ray variability on the longest observable time scales (i.e., between epoch 1 and epoch 4) substantially affects the appearance of the overall X-ray source population.

Figure B.7 displays the full-band fluxes of epoch 1 and epoch 4. Applying Spearman’s test on the fluxes of epoch 1 and epoch 4 yields $\rho = 0.82$ and a p -value of 10^{-17} ; the large value of ρ indicates a good association of ranks. In general, the brightest (faintest) sources remain the brightest (faintest) after 15 years. Only 11 (11/68 = 16%) sources have flux changes greater than a factor of two. Qualitatively similar results are obtained when we pair any two of our available epochs.

The rarity of extremely variable sources in the distant universe over long time scales is broadly consistent with a recent study focusing on low-redshift AGNs [472]. Our results prove that, at least on a 15-year observed-frame time scale, basic inferences about distant AGN source populations are not strongly affected by variability, e.g., the expected star-formation vs. AGN-activity connection is unlikely to be hidden by AGN variability on a rest-frame time scale of $\sim 5 - 10$ years. These results also show that X-ray changing-look AGNs are rare, and they constrain the frequency of other types of novel long-term X-ray variability (see Section B.1). Setting direct X-ray constraints on much longer time scales is unfortunately limited by, e.g., the age of X-ray astronomy. Cosmic X-ray surveys often bin observations performed over 1–15 years; our results indicate that long-term variability is not likely to affect the interpretation of such survey results greatly.

B.3.2.3 Identification of L_X - and N_H - Variable Sources

We identify L_X - and N_H -variable sources using the Akaike information criterion [253]. The AIC is based on information theory and does not assume a particular model-fitting technique or distribution of uncertainties [254, 473, 474]. AIC is defined as $AIC = C + 2k$, where C is the fitting statistic (i.e., the Cash statistic in our case)

and k is the number of free parameters in the model.¹¹ Models with smaller AIC are considered to be more probable.

For each source, we calculate AIC (denoted as AIC_0) for the spectral-fitting results in Section B.3.2.1. To evaluate the significance of L_X variability, we link $norm_i$ in all spectra of the four epochs,¹² and redo the fitting. Other settings of the model are the same as in Section B.3.2.1. We calculate AIC for the new fitting results, denoted as AIC_1 . We use the difference $\Delta\text{AIC}_L = \text{AIC}_1 - \text{AIC}_0$ to evaluate the significance of L_X variability. If $\Delta\text{AIC}_L > 4$ [254],¹³ we assign this source as an L_X -variable source. Similarly, we identify N_H -variable sources by calculating the AIC difference ΔAIC_N between N_H -linked and unlinked models and comparing it with the threshold of 4. The ΔAIC_L and ΔAIC_N for each source are listed in Table B.3.

The resulting L_X - and N_H -variable source fractions are 74% (50/68) and 16% (11/68), respectively. Four of the 11 N_H -variable sources are HR -variable (Section B.3.1).¹⁴ The other 7 sources have large P_{HR} values ($> 10\%$). One reason for this result is likely to be that the definition of HR (Equation B.6) uses observed-frame 2 keV as the boundary between the soft and hard bands. This choice of 2 keV is just by convention. It corresponds to different rest-frame energies for different sources and might not be sensitive in selecting some N_H -variable sources. We checked the 4-epoch spectra of the 7 sources, and found that 2 keV as a boundary is either too high or too low to detect their N_H variability effectively.

Most (10/11) N_H variable sources are also L_X variable. The median ΔAIC_L (ΔAIC_N) for L_X -variable (N_H -variable) sources is 43 (6.2). Therefore, our L_X variability is generally more significant than N_H variability. The BAL quasar J033209.4-274806 shows L_X variability ($\Delta\text{AIC}_L = 4.9$) but not N_H variability

¹¹Note that we do not need to use the AICc, the corrected AIC designed for the cases where sample size n is $\approx k^2$. This is because our $n =$ number of spectral PHA bins for all four epochs together (≈ 2000) is much greater than k^2 (≈ 50).

¹²Hereafter, we use parameter $norm$ to evaluate L_X variability, since L_X is proportional to $norm$ for a given source assuming no Γ variability.

¹³We have also performed classic χ^2 tests for variable source identification, assuming our errors are Gaussian. For both L_X and N_H variability, we find good correlations between ΔAIC and $\chi^2_{\text{dof}=3}$, with $\Delta\text{AIC} = 4$ corresponding to $\chi^2_{\text{dof}=3} \approx 10$ (i.e., p -value $\approx 2\%$). However, we prefer the AIC approach because it does not rely on the assumption of Gaussian errors.

¹⁴s Our AIC method selects variable sources at a significance level of $\approx 98\%$ (see Footnote B.3.2.3). Only 6 sources show HR variability at this significance level (i.e., $P_{HR} < 2\%$), and all 4 N_H -variable and HR -variable sources are included among these 6.

($\Delta\text{AIC}_N = -2.7$). We investigate three significantly variable sources, J033226.5–274035, J033259.7–274626, and J033229.9–274530, as illustrative examples in Section B.5.3. Notably, J033229.9–274530 transitions from an X-ray unobscured to obscured state. The positions of the identified variable sources in the L_X - z and L_X - N_H planes are indicated in Figure B.8. G12 performed similar variability analyses but for optically selected SDSS quasars. Their quasars are included in the L_X - z plot to demonstrate the differences between their sample and ours. Luminosities for the G12 objects are estimated assuming a power law with $\Gamma = 1.8$. The typical luminosity of our sources is generally about one order of magnitude lower than that of the SDSS quasars at a given redshift. The majority ($\approx 60\%$) of the X-ray obscured quasars (i.e., $N_H > 10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and $L_X > 10^{44} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$) in our sample are L_X -variable, supporting the idea that we are observing their central X-ray emitting regions directly. Also, 7 of our 11 optically classified type II quasars show L_X variability (Figure B.8). The well-studied optically classified type II quasar at $z = 3.70$ in the CDF-S [471, 475] is not included in our sample due to its limited number of available counts (see Section B.2.2).

B.3.2.4 Relation Between L_X and N_H Variability

If the observed N_H variability were caused by changes of the ionization parameter of the obscuring matter, an anticorrelation between L_X and N_H variability might be expected; when L_X rises, the obscuring matter would become more ionized and generally less opaque. We performed a Spearman’s test on $L_{X,i}/L_X$ and $N_{H,i}/N_H$ for the 10 sources together that show both L_X and N_H variability, but do not find a significant anticorrelation. There is also no significant anticorrelation produced if we expand the Spearman’s test to all sources. Therefore, the N_H variability is not likely to be primarily driven by changes of ionization parameter. Nevertheless, some ionization-driven N_H variability might still exist if there are year-scale time delays between L_X and N_H variability due to, e.g., a low density of the absorber [476, 477].

B.3.2.5 Variability Amplitude Estimation

In this section, we illustrate and evaluate our method to quantify variability amplitude, and the results are used in all subsequent material. We use the normalized excess variance (σ_{exc}^2 , e.g., [461, 478]) to estimate intrinsic variability scale for L_X

(N_{H}) of each source. σ_{exc}^2 is calculated as

$$\sigma_{\text{exc}}^2 = \frac{1}{N\langle x \rangle^2} \sum_{i=1}^N [(x_i - \langle x \rangle)^2 - (\delta x_i)^2], \quad (\text{B.12})$$

where N is the number of epochs (i.e., 4); x_i and δx_i are the best-fit $norm_i$ ($N_{\text{H},i}$) and its 1σ error $\delta norm_i$ ($\delta N_{\text{H},i}$), respectively; $\langle x \rangle$ is the unweighted mean of $norm_i$ ($N_{\text{H},i}$). The error of σ_{exc}^2 is estimated as $s_D/(\langle x \rangle^2 \sqrt{N})$, where

$$s_D^2 = \frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{i=1}^N [(x_i - \langle x \rangle)^2 - (\delta x_i)^2 - \sigma_{\text{exc}}^2 \langle x \rangle^2]^2. \quad (\text{B.13})$$

is the variance of the summed terms $(x_i - \langle x \rangle)^2 - (\delta x_i)^2$ in Equation B.12. We calculate the L_X σ_{exc}^2 ($\sigma_{\text{exc},L}^2$) for each source. We only derive the N_{H} σ_{exc}^2 ($\sigma_{\text{exc},N}^2$) for the 35 sources with all four epochs having $N_{\text{H},i}$ fractional errors $\delta N_{\text{H},i}/N_{\text{H},i} < 0.4$ (Section B.5.1).

The results are listed in Table B.3. While $\sigma_{\text{exc},L}^2$ and $\sigma_{\text{exc},N}^2$ are designed to measure intrinsic variability under ideal conditions, they may also be affected by the available counts [479]. However, the biases are minimized for high S/N, as is the case for our data (Section B.3.2.1). Indeed, Spearman's test demonstrates no significant dependence of $\sigma_{\text{exc},L}^2$ and $\sigma_{\text{exc},N}^2$ on the number of counts.

B.3.2.6 Variability Dependence on Luminosity, X-ray Absorption, and Redshift

It has been well established that the strength of AGN X-ray flux variability decreases as luminosity increases on time scales from minutes to about a year [413, 418]. Also, studies of local Seyfert galaxies show that more obscured sources tend to be less variable on short time scales [411, 414]. Therefore, it is of interest to investigate the dependence of long-term (years) variability on luminosity and absorption level. Figure B.9 shows the dependence of $\sigma_{\text{exc},L}^2$ on L_X . The unweighted mean of $\sigma_{\text{exc},L}^2$ decreases toward higher luminosity. For each bin, the error on the mean is calculated as the standard deviation of individual $\sigma_{\text{exc},L}^2$ divided by \sqrt{N} , where N is the number of sources in the bin [i.e., Equation 13 of [479]; but note that a power index of 2 is missing in their summed term]. The mean value in each bin can well represent the typical variability amplitude of the sources in the bin,

despite the large error bars for individual sources [479]; the median has not been established to represent the typical variability amplitude. Spearman’s test applied to the individual sources shows a significant anticorrelation between $\sigma_{\text{exc},L}^2$ and L_X (Spearman’s $\rho = -0.31$, p -value= 0.009). This anticorrelation is mainly caused by the $\sigma_{\text{exc},L}^2$ difference between quasars ($L_X > 10^{44}$ erg s $^{-1}$) and other AGNs. After removing quasars (only 19 sources), we find no significant relation between L_X and $\sigma_{\text{exc},L}^2$. There is also tentative evidence of an anticorrelation between $\sigma_{\text{exc},L}^2$ and N_{H} : Spearman’s $\rho = -0.23$, p -value= 0.06. However, this result might be a byproduct of the $\sigma_{\text{exc},L}^2$ - L_X relation, since in our counts-limited sample (i.e., > 600 net counts required) heavily obscured sources tend to be more luminous compared to less-obscured sources (see Figure B.8). This interpretation is supported by the fact that no significant $\sigma_{\text{exc},L}^2$ - N_{H} relation is found for luminosity-controlled samples ($L_X \leq 10^{44}$ erg s $^{-1}$ and $L_X > 10^{44}$ erg s $^{-1}$).

The anticorrelation between $\sigma_{\text{exc},L}^2$ and L_X is unlikely to be a bias caused by the available counts, since we are in a high S/N regime (see Section B.3.2.5). Another bias might exist considering that we are probing generally shorter time scales for more luminous sources, since they have relatively high redshifts (see Figure B.8), increasing the effects of time-dilation. To test this point, we drop the first-epoch data for the low-redshift sample ($z < 2$, median $z = 1.0$), while keeping all data for the high-redshift sample ($z \geq 2$, median $z = 2.8$). Hence, the observed-frame total time spans are about 8 and 15 years for the low- and high-redshift samples, respectively (see Table B.2). The median values of the rest-frame total time spans are both about 4 years [low-redshift: $8/(1+1.0)$, high-redshift: $15/(1+2.8)$]. We calculate $\sigma_{\text{exc},L}^2$ for this data set and find Spearman’s $\rho = -0.29$, p -value= 0.015, similar to the results derived from the original data set. The results are also similar if we drop the fourth-epoch data instead of the first-epoch data for the low-redshift sample. We conclude the anticorrelation between $\sigma_{\text{exc},L}^2$ and L_X is not caused by a bias of different rest-frame time spans. A bias might also arise from the fact that our observed-frame full energy band corresponds to different rest-frame energy bands. There is some evidence of energy-dependent variability reported in studies of Seyfert galaxies [413, 480]. To estimate this effect, we fit the spectra of the rest-frame 2–10 keV band for each source. We calculate the luminosity excess standard deviation ($\sigma_{\text{exc},L,\text{rest}}^2$) and its uncertainty. The derived $\sigma_{\text{exc},L,\text{rest}}^2$ matches well with $\sigma_{\text{exc},L}^2$, with only six cases showing 2σ or higher deviation from $\sigma_{\text{exc},L,\text{rest}}^2 = \sigma_{\text{exc},L}^2$,

i.e.,

$$|\sigma_{\text{exc},L,\text{rest}}^2 - \sigma_{\text{exc},L}^2| > 2\max(\delta\sigma_{\text{exc},L,\text{rest}}^2, \delta\sigma_{\text{exc},L}^2), \quad (\text{B.14})$$

where $\delta\sigma_{\text{exc},L,\text{rest}}^2$ and $\delta\sigma_{\text{exc},L}^2$ are the uncertainties of $\sigma_{\text{exc},L,\text{rest}}^2$ and $\sigma_{\text{exc},L}^2$, respectively. In agreement with $\sigma_{\text{exc},L}$, $\sigma_{\text{exc},L,\text{rest}}^2$ is also anticorrelated with L_X : Spearman's $\rho = -0.30$, p -value = 0.012.

Several previous studies suggest that at a given luminosity level, sources at higher redshifts tend to have stronger X-ray variability [417, 418, 481]. To assess this point, we perform Spearman's test on $\sigma_{\text{exc},L}^2$ and redshifts for luminosity-controlled samples ($L_X \leq 10^{44}$ erg s $^{-1}$ and $L_X > 10^{44}$ erg s $^{-1}$). The results show no significant correlation between $\sigma_{\text{exc},L}^2$ and redshift for both samples. However, the majority of the $L_X \leq 10^{44}$ erg s $^{-1}$ and $L_X > 10^{44}$ erg s $^{-1}$ sources are at $z \lesssim 2$ and $z \gtrsim 2$ (Figure B.8), respectively. Thus, we cannot test the redshift dependence over a wide redshift range.

We do not find significant $\sigma_{\text{exc},N}^2$ dependence on L_X , N_H , or z for the 35 sources with $\sigma_{\text{exc},N}^2$ calculated (i.e., the sources with all four epochs having $\delta N_{H,i}/N_{H,i} < 0.4$).

B.3.2.7 Variability Dependence on Optical Spectral Type and Color

Type I AGNs have a higher L_X variable source fraction than their type II counterparts (83% vs. 68%), likely due to their higher numbers of counts (Figure B.2). Also, type I AGNs have a higher fraction of N_H variable sources (21% vs. 14%). Figure B.10 displays histograms of the $\sigma_{\text{exc},L}^2$ and $\sigma_{\text{exc},N}^2$ distributions for different optical spectral types. There are very few type I AGNs in the $\sigma_{\text{exc},N}^2$ histogram, because most type I AGNs are X-ray unobscured. For the $\sigma_{\text{exc},L}^2$ distributions, a KS test shows no apparent differences between type I and type II AGNs. Since optical spectral type is often related to the rest-frame optical color (e.g., $u - g$; see Section B.2.2), we also check the $\sigma_{\text{exc},L}^2$ dependence on rest-frame $u - g$ color but do not find a significant relation. The similarity of long-term (years) X-ray variability between type I and type II AGNs has also been found by previous studies of both distant AGNs [420] and local Compton-thin Seyfert galaxies [411, 414], though Seyfert IIs tend to be less variable than Seyfert Is on short time scales (minutes to hours) [414, 415].

B.3.2.8 Variability Dependence on Time Scale

Considering that our light curves are sparsely sampled (with four epochs), we cannot investigate the variability dependence on time scale for each source individually. Instead, we consider our entire sample as an ensemble and investigate its L_X (N_H) variability on different time scales. We calculate the “structure function” (SF , i.e., ensemble-averaged fractional variability amplitude between two observations) as a function of rest-frame time interval (Δt_{rest}).

First, for each epoch pair of a source (6 pairs in total for each source) we obtain a variability factor

$$f_v = \frac{\Delta x}{\bar{x}} = \frac{x_2 - x_1}{(x_2 + x_1)/2}; \quad (\text{B.15})$$

and its uncertainty from error propagation

$$\delta f_v = \frac{x_1 x_2}{\bar{x}^2} \times \sqrt{\left(\frac{\delta x_1}{x_1}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\delta x_2}{x_2}\right)^2}, \quad (\text{B.16})$$

where x_1 and x_2 are the best-fit $norm_i$ ($N_{H,i}$) of two different epochs; δx_1 and δx_2 are their 1σ errors. Each f_v is associated with a Δt_{rest} between two epochs. We then bin f_v with similar Δt_{rest} and calculate the SF [482] as

$$SF = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2} \langle |f_v|^2 \rangle - \langle (\delta f_v)^2 \rangle}, \quad (\text{B.17})$$

where the angle brackets denote average values in the Δt_{rest} bin. We estimate the uncertainties of the SF from bootstrapping,¹⁵ and the results are displayed in Figure B.11.

Our 19 quasars generally have weaker variability (Section B.3.2.6) and shorter Δt_{rest} (due to cosmological time dilation; see Figure B.8). Hence, they might cause the L_X SF to be lower at shorter Δt_{rest} . To avoid this bias, we do not include them when calculating the L_X SF . The resulting L_X SF is relatively flat as a function of time scale, with perhaps a suggestion of rising toward longer time scales.

The fractional variability amplitude of N_H is generally smaller than that of L_X , and appears to increase as Δt_{rest} increases. In the N_H SF calculations, we only include the 35 sources with all four epochs having $\delta N_{H,i}/N_{H,i} < 0.4$ (Section B.5.1).

¹⁵We calculate the confidence interval as the range between the 16th and 84th percentiles.

B.4 Summary, Discussion, and Future Prospects

In this paper, we have performed long-term (up to ≈ 15 yr, observed-frame) X-ray variability analyses for the 68 X-ray brightest radio-quiet AGNs in the uniquely deep CDF-S; most of these objects are at redshifts of 0.6–3.1, providing access to penetrating rest-frame X-rays up to $\approx 10 - 30$ keV. AGNs like those studied here produce a significant fraction of cosmic accretion power; in this sense, they are the typical AGNs of the Universe. We have performed both photometric and spectral variability analyses, and studied the dependence of variability on source properties and time scale. We summarize our main results in Section B.4.1. In Section B.4.2, we interpret the L_X variability in the context of AGN PSD. We present practical future extensions to this work in Section B.4.3.

B.4.1 Summary of Main Results

The main results are the following:

1. Photometric analyses (Section B.3.1) show that at above a 95% confidence level, 90% (61/68) and 16% (11/68) of our sources are variable in photon flux (PF) and hardness ratio (HR), respectively. Our results confirm the prevalence of X-ray PF variability for typical AGNs in the distant universe [418, 420]. A large fraction of sources ($\sim 50\%$) is also found to be PF -variable within single epochs. However, HR variability is generally insignificant within single epochs ($\lesssim 1$ yr, observed-frame).
2. Spectral analyses (using a $wabs \times zwabs \times pegrwlw$ model; see Section B.3.2) demonstrate that the L_X - and N_H -variable source fractions are 74% (50/68) and 16% (11/68), respectively. Among the X-ray obscured quasars, the L_X -variable source fraction is also high ($\approx 60\%$); this includes the BAL quasar (J033209.4–274806). Large-amplitude flux variability is rare; most sources (84%) have flux changes within a factor of 2 over 15 yr (observed-frame, see Section B.3.2.2). We do not find a significant anticorrelation between L_X and N_H variability, as might be expected for a photoionized absorber (see Section B.3.2.4).
3. We have quantified the fractional variability scale by calculating the normal-

ized excess variance (σ_{exc}^2) for each source (see Section B.3.2.5). Quasars with $L_X > 10^{44}$ erg s $^{-1}$ generally have smaller variability amplitudes than less-luminous AGNs. We have not found any significant dependence of L_X variability amplitudes on optical spectral type, consistent with the results of [420]. Therefore, we appear to be observing the X-ray emission of most type II AGNs directly from the central engine; this can occur if X-rays are able to penetrate the obscuring material.

4. We have calculated SFs to illustrate the variability dependence on rest-frame time scale (Section B.3.2.8). The L_X SF is relatively flat; the N_H SF appears to rise toward longer time scales.
5. A Compton-thick AGN candidate [471] in our sample (J033218.3–275055) shows notable X-ray variability. Motivated by [471], we used a reflection-dominated $wabs \times zwabs \times pexmon$ model to perform spectral analyses. The results indicate that both the reflection flux and the N_H are variable (see Section B.5.2). The variability time scale (\approx a year) indicates the size of the reflecting material is $\lesssim 0.3$ pc. Nevertheless, it is also possible that the observed X-ray flux is a combination of both transmitted and reflected radiation, and the observed high-energy flux variability is mainly caused by the variable transmitted component.
6. We have identified a source in our sample (J033229.9–274530) that transitions from X-ray unobscured to obscured states over a ≈ 3 yr rest-frame time scale (see Section B.5.3). The source is a type I object at $z = 1.21$ with $L_X \approx 7 \times 10^{43}$ erg s $^{-1}$. Its L_X is higher when it is less X-ray obscured. The angular size of an X-ray eclipsing cloud is estimated to be several degrees (viewed from the central SMBH). However, there is no corresponding optical spectral-type transition, suggesting that the X-ray eclipsing material is too small to block most of the broad-line emission.

B.4.2 Interpretation from Power Spectral Density

The observed low L_X variability amplitudes of quasars can be plausibly explained by the AGN PSD, which describes variability power as a function of frequency. An

AGN PSD can often be well modeled as a broken power law [433]

$$\text{PSD}(\nu) = \begin{cases} \text{PSD}_{\text{amp}}\nu^{-1}, & \text{if } \nu < \nu_{\text{bf}}; \\ \text{PSD}_{\text{amp}}\nu_{\text{bf}}\nu^{-2}, & \text{if } \nu \geq \nu_{\text{bf}}. \end{cases} \quad (\text{B.18})$$

The normalization PSD_{amp} is roughly constant (0.017 ± 0.006), according to studies of Seyfert galaxies [483]. The low-frequency power law extends at least to several-year time scales in local Seyfert galaxies [484]. ν_{bf} is related to both SMBH mass (M_{BH}) and bolometric luminosity (L_{bol}) as [485]

$$\begin{aligned} \nu_{\text{bf}} &\sim 50 \left(\frac{M_{\text{BH}}}{10^8 M_{\odot}} \right)^{-2} \left(\frac{L_{\text{bol}}}{10^{45} \text{ erg s}^{-1}} \right) \text{ yr}^{-1} \\ &\sim 10 \left(\frac{L_{\text{X}}}{10^{44} \text{ erg s}^{-1}} \right)^{-1} \left(\frac{k_{\text{bol}}}{50} \right)^{-1} \left(\frac{\lambda_{\text{Edd}}}{0.1} \right)^2 \text{ yr}^{-1} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.19})$$

where λ_{Edd} and k_{bol} are the Eddington ratio and bolometric correction factor for L_{X} (2–10 keV), respectively. Given a PSD of a source, the $\sigma_{\text{exc},L}^2$ can be estimated as [419, 483]

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{\text{exc},L}^2 &= \int_{\nu_{\text{lf}}}^{\nu_{\text{hf}}} \text{PSD}(\nu) d\nu \\ &= \text{PSD}_{\text{amp}} \ln \left(\frac{\nu_{\text{hf}}}{\nu_{\text{lf}}} \right), \text{ if } \nu_{\text{hf}} < \nu_{\text{bf}}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.20})$$

The integral bounds for our study are

$$\begin{aligned} \nu_{\text{lf}} &\sim \frac{1+z}{t_{\text{span}}} \text{ and} \\ \nu_{\text{hf}} &\sim \frac{1+z}{t_{\text{bin}}}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.21})$$

respectively, where $t_{\text{span}} = 14.3 \text{ yr}$ is the observed-frame total observation span and $t_{\text{bin}} = 0.46 \text{ yr}$ is the observed-frame median bin width of the four epochs. For an AGN with $L_{\text{X}} = 10^{44} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$ and $\lambda_{\text{Edd}} \sim 0.1$, the typical bolometric correction factor is $k_{\text{bol}} \sim 50$ [108], and the typical redshift is ≈ 2 (see Figure B.8). Thus, Equations B.19 and B.21 yield $\nu_{\text{bf}} \sim \nu_{\text{hf}} \sim 10 \text{ yr}^{-1}$. For AGNs with higher luminosity (i.e., quasars), both k_{bol} and z tend to be larger. ν_{hf} and ν_{bf} will increase and decrease, respectively (assuming the same λ_{Edd}); e.g., for a typical quasar at $z \sim 3$

with $L_X \sim 3 \times 10^{44}$ erg s $^{-1}$ (see Figure B.8), ν_{bf} will increase by a factor of ~ 1.3 due to z , and ν_{hf} will decrease at least 3 times due to L_X and k_{bol} .¹⁶ Therefore, ν_{hf} is likely to be higher than ν_{bf} for quasars (Equations B.19 and B.21), i.e., the integral range in Equation B.20 covers the power law with slope -2 that drops strongly toward high frequency. The resulting $\sigma_{\text{exc},L}$ for quasars should thus be smaller than for other AGNs, consistent with observations (Section B.3.2.6). For a non-quasar AGN, we might be sampling only the low-frequency part of its PSD with slope -1 (i.e., $\nu_{\text{hf}} < \nu_{\text{bf}}$); Equations B.20 and B.21 result in an approximately constant $\sigma_{\text{exc},L}^2$ value of 0.059 ± 0.021 , regardless of source properties. This $\sigma_{\text{exc},L}^2$ value is generally lower than the observed values for our non-quasar AGNs (see Figure B.9), casting doubt on the universality of the constant-amplitude PSD model (e.g., [413]; M. Paolillo et al., in preparation).

B.4.3 Future Work

Considering reasonably in-depth studies of the long-term X-ray variability of typical distant AGNs, it will be difficult to surpass greatly the present work for a considerable period of time; this is primarily due to the unmatched CDF-S exposure obtained over the extended period of ≈ 15 yr. Additional X-ray variability studies should be done for the large population of X-ray fainter CDF-S AGNs (see Figure B.8; e.g., X. C. Zheng et al., in preparation), although it will be more difficult to characterize these systems individually in depth. If *Chandra* continues to operate for another ≈ 10 yr, as appears plausible [486], obtaining additional CDF-S exposure in several years could lengthen our time baseline to up to ≈ 25 yr in total. The *Advanced Telescope for High Energy Astrophysics* (*Athena*; e.g., [487]), planned for launch in ≈ 13 yr, has the best current prospects for substantially advancing long-term X-ray variability studies of typical AGNs in the distant universe. Owing to its greatly improved photon collecting area, it will obtain much better photon statistics for its deep-field AGNs. With suitable observation scheduling, it could efficiently perform a study similar to that in this work but for many more objects and with tens of epochs of observations spanning a wide range of timescales. The prime deep-survey field for *Athena* is arguably the CDF-S, and *Athena* variability studies could build upon the long-term baseline of *Chandra* CDF-S observations

¹⁶The L_X (and related k_{bol}) has a stronger effect than z . This is why we attribute L_X rather than z to be a major factor affecting variability in Section B.3.2.6.

utilized in this work.

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Disclaimer

The findings and conclusions do not necessarily reflect the view of the funding agencies.

B.5 Supplementary Materials

B.5.1 Error Estimation of Model Parameters

As described in Section B.3.2.1, we fit spectra of the four epochs simultaneously with a $wabs \times zwabs \times pegpwlw$ model. The photon index, Γ , is linked across the four epochs, assuming no Γ variability (see Section B.3.2.1 for the justification of this assumption). In this Section, we first explain our choice of $pegpwlw$ over $powerlaw$, and then describe our method to estimate the errors of $N_{H,i}$.

As an illustrative example, we show the $norm_i$ - Γ confidence contours of the first two epochs of J033217.1–275220 resulting from fitting with a model of $wabs \times zwabs \times powerlaw$ (see the upper panel of Figure B.12). The contours, as expected, show positive correlations between $norm_i$ and Γ . Since no overlapping region exists between the two 99% confidence contours, the probability of the two epochs having both the same $norm_i$ and Γ is very low [$< (1 - 99\%)^2 = 0.01\%$]. Therefore, the $norm_i$ variability must be very significant ($> 1 - 0.01\% = 99.99\%$) under our assumption of constant Γ . However, if we evaluate the $norm_i$ variability by checking the 1-dimensional (1D) errors (2σ) of $norm_i$ (the projected range on the y -axis), the variability seems to be less significant due to the existence of an overlapping interval (blue shaded region). More quantitatively, if we perform a χ^2 test of the $norm_i$ variability using the best-fit values and 1D errors, the resulting significance of variability is only 93%. This apparent discrepancy occurs because when calculating the 1D errors of $norm_i$ by projecting the 2D contours, the positive $norm_i - \Gamma$ correlations and our underlying assumption of constant Γ are “forgotten”. This is evident since the blue-shaded region only covers the two dashed contours at very different Γ , i.e., the same $norm_i$ can be achieved only when the assumption of constant Γ is violated. Reading Figure B.12, Γ would need to change by $\Delta\Gamma \approx 0.2 - 0.3$, and this is larger than any physically expected Γ change (see Section B.3.2.1). Therefore, the errors of $norm_i$ are overestimated under this assumption of constant Γ . This problem is prevalent when using $powerlaw$, since positive correlations exist for almost all sources. However, the positive correlations can be mostly eliminated by replacing $powerlaw$ with $pegpwlw$ (see the lower panel of Figure B.12). $pegpwlw$ differs from $powerlaw$ by having its normalization based on intrinsic flux in a given finite band rather than the flux density at observed-frame

1 keV. We find that setting the normalization band as $E_{peg} - 7$ keV produces nearly horizontal $norm_i$ - Γ contours for all sources, where E_{peg} is the minimum between 0.5 keV and the observed-frame e -folding energy (E_{fold}) caused by intrinsic photoelectric absorption. Technically, we obtain the photoelectric cross section σ_{photo} as a function of energy [463], and solve the equation $\langle N_H \rangle \times \sigma_{photo}[E_{fold} \times (1 + z)] = 1$ to obtain E_{fold} ,¹⁷ where the factor $1 + z$ is to convert observed-frame to rest-frame energy.

Similar positive correlations are also, as expected, prevalent in the $N_{H,i}$ - Γ contours. However, we are not aware of any model choices that can eliminate these correlations (as for the choice of *pegpurlw* in the $norm_i$ case). Alternatively, if intrinsic Γ (Γ_{intr}) were given, one could fix $\Gamma = \Gamma_{intr}$ and estimate the errors of $N_{H,i}$. But in reality, Γ_{intr} is not perfectly known. We thus adopt an approximation, i.e., fixing $\Gamma = \Gamma_{fit}$. The idea is to approximate Γ_{intr} as Γ_{fit} . Admittedly, compared to fixing $\Gamma = \Gamma_{intr}$, this approximation might overestimate or underestimate the errors of $N_{H,i}$. To evaluate this possible issue, we fix Γ at the 90% confidence lower and upper limits of Γ_{fit} , respectively, and then estimate the errors. The lower and upper limits approximate the boundaries of possible Γ_{intr} values. If fixing Γ at these boundaries results in similar errors as fixing Γ at Γ_{fit} , we conclude that our approximation (i.e., fixing $\Gamma = \Gamma_{fit}$) gives accurate errors of $N_{H,i}$ for a given source. Figure B.13 shows the results. The dependence of estimated fractional error $\delta N_{H,i}/N_{H,i}$ on Γ is stronger when the error is larger. In Figure B.13, at $\delta N_{H,i}/N_{H,i} = 0.4$ (the vertical dashed line), fixing Γ at its 90%-confidence lower and upper limits of Γ_{fit} results in $\delta N_{H,i}/N_{H,i} \lesssim 0.55$ and $\gtrsim 0.25$, respectively (the dash-dotted lines). Since Γ_{intr} is very likely within the range of the 90% limits of Γ_{fit} , fixing $\Gamma = \Gamma_{intr}$ (if it were perfectly known) should give $\delta N_{H,i}/N_{H,i}$ within the range of $\approx 0.25 - 0.55$. Therefore, fixing $\Gamma = \Gamma_{intr}$ would lead to $\delta N_{H,i}/N_{H,i}$ deviating from that obtained by our approximation (fixing $\Gamma = \Gamma_{fit}$) by $\lesssim 15\%$ (i.e., $15\% = 0.15 = 0.55 - 0.4 = 0.4 - 0.25$). For epochs with $\delta N_{H,i}/N_{H,i} < 0.4$, this value should be even lower. In the analyses where errors on $N_{H,i}$ are being used (Sections B.3.2.6 and B.3.2.8), we only include the 35 sources with all four epochs having $\delta N_{H,i}/N_{H,i} < 0.4$. This criterion guarantees that the $N_{H,i}$ fractional errors estimated by fixing $\Gamma = \Gamma_{fit}$ differ from those estimated by fixing $\Gamma = \Gamma_{intr}$ by $\lesssim 15\%$. Though not ideal, this criterion is a practical solution for our N_H variability

¹⁷We first fit the spectrum using an arbitrary normalization band and calculate the $\langle N_H \rangle$ from the best-fit $N_{H,i}$. The best-fit $N_{H,i}$ is independent of the exact choice of energy band.

analyses, balancing between the accuracy of error estimation and the sample size.

B.5.2 A Highly Variable Compton-Thick Candidate

J033218.3–275055 is a bright Compton-thick candidate AGN at $z = 1.54$ reported in the literature [469, 471]. It is classified as an optical type II object. It shows a strong Fe K α emission line with a rest-frame equivalent width (REW) of ≈ 1.2 keV [471]. Our spectral fitting confirms its highly obscured nature ($N_{\text{H}} = 3 \times 10^{23}$ cm $^{-2}$). Both its L_{X} and N_{H} values are variable ($\Delta\text{AIC}_L = 38$ and $\Delta\text{AIC}_N = 5.1$). However, its high *goodness* (44%) and low Γ (1.2, i.e., our allowed lower limit, see Section B.3.2.1) indicate the model $wabs \times zwabs \times peggurlw$ is likely inappropriate (see Figure B.6). Thus, motivated by [471], we use the model $wabs \times zwabs \times pexmon$ [93, 94] to fit the data. We set the *pexmon* model to be fully reflection dominated and fix the inclination angle at 60° . We link the Γ (*pexmon*) of all four epochs, and set $norm_i$ (*pexmon*) and $N_{\text{H},i}$ (*zwabs*) free (not linked). The fitted spectra of the reflection-dominated model are shown in Figure B.14, and the detailed fitting results are presented in Table B.4.

Despite having the same number of degrees of freedom as the previous model ($wabs \times zwabs \times peggurlw$), the new fitting results in a *goodness* = 8% and best-fit $\Gamma = 1.80$, values that are more common among the *goodness* and Γ distributions for our overall sample (see Figure B.6). Also, the new model has AIC much smaller than the previous model ($\Delta\text{AIC} = 54$), indicating a significant improvement in the fit quality. Thus, we consider this reflection-dominated model to be more physically plausible than the simple transmission-dominated model. Following Section 2.4.1 of [94], this Γ value (i.e., 1.80) results in an REW of Fe K α (*pexmon*) of ≈ 1.4 keV, consistent with [471]. Similar to the approach in Section B.3.2.3, we test the significance of reflection-flux and N_{H} variability by linking $norm_i$ (*pexmon*) and $N_{\text{H},i}$, respectively. The increased AIC values (i.e., 39 and 4.2) are both greater than 4, indicating both the reflection flux and N_{H} are variable (Section B.3.2.3). The confidence contours are shown in Figure B.15. Both the absorption and continuum are weak in epoch 1; they rise in epoch 2 and then drop in epoch 3; in epoch 4, they rise again. The amplitude of flux variability is large; e.g., the flux in epoch 4 is almost twice that in epochs 1 and 3. The variability time scale (\approx a year) constrains the size of the reflecting material to be $\lesssim 0.3$ pc.

Epoch	Γ	N_{H} (10^{22} cm^{-2})	flux ^b ($10^{-15} \text{ erg cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$)
1	1.80	$5.61^{+2.88}_{-2.38}$	$4.16^{+0.34}_{-0.40}$
2	–	$17.00^{+4.80}_{-4.40}$	$5.47^{+0.44}_{-0.46}$
3	–	$7.81^{+2.89}_{-2.52}$	$3.71^{+0.26}_{-0.26}$
4	–	$17.80^{+3.60}_{-3.30}$	$6.64^{+0.33}_{-0.35}$

Table B.4: Spectral Fitting^a Results of the Compton-Thick Candidate (J033218.3–275055). a. The spectral fitting model is $wabs \times zwabs \times pexmon$ (see Section B.5.2). b. Full-band (0.5–7 keV) model flux, not corrected for Galactic or intrinsic absorption.

However, there is a possible alternative explanation for the observed high-energy flux variability of this source, though our reflection-dominated model explains the data satisfactorily. The observed X-ray emission might be a combination of both transmitted and reflected radiation. In this scenario, the transmission component is variable and results in the observed high-energy flux variability, while the reflection component is stable. To test this scenario, we use a $wabs \times zwabs \times (pegpurlw + pexmon)$ model. We assume that the *pegpurlw* and *pexmon* components share the same non-variable Γ , and the normalization of *pexmon* is the same across epochs. The N_{H} (*zwabs*) and the normalization of *pegpurlw* are allowed to vary across epochs. Other parameters of the *pexmon* component are the same as for the reflection-dominated model. This composite model yields $\Gamma = 1.5$ and *goodness* = 5%, similar to that of the reflection-dominated model. The resulting transmitted flux almost completely shuts down at epoch 1 and epoch 3 (more than an order of magnitude smaller than at epoch 2 and epoch 4). Such strong variability is not likely to be realistic, considering the general variability amplitudes of our sources (see Section B.3.2.2). Nevertheless, more complex transmission-reflection hybrid models might produce more physically plausible results, though they cannot be constrained well owing to the available number of counts.

B.5.3 Three Significantly Variable Sources

As illustrative examples, we investigate three significantly variable sources. The first source, J033226.5–274035 ($z = 1.03$), is our brightest source; it also has the most significant L_{X} variability. The second source, J033259.7–274626 ($z = 0.42$), is also L_{X} -variable, but has counts typical in our sample; this source is shown as a representative sample member. The third source, J033229.9–274530 ($z = 1.21$),

has the most significant N_{H} variability; it transitions from an X-ray unobscured to obscured state. Their fitted spectra and $L_{\text{X}}-N_{\text{H}}$ confidence contours are shown in Figure B.16.

J033226.5–274035 has the largest number of total net counts (≈ 11000). It has $\Delta\text{AIC}_L = 1059$ and $\Delta\text{AIC}_N = 15$, indicating both L_{X} and N_{H} variability. The ΔAIC_L is the largest among those of our sources. Its L_{X} in the second epoch is about two times the L_{X} in the other epochs. Its N_{H} is generally low: N_{H} only has upper limits in the first three epochs and rises to $\approx 4 \times 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ in the last epoch. J033226.5–274035 and another bright (net counts ≈ 6500) and variable source ($\Delta\text{AIC}_L = 38$, $\Delta\text{AIC}_N = 5.1$), J033218.3–275055, are also identified as optically variable sources by [488] based on their r -band variability.

J033259.7–274626 has total net counts of ≈ 1300 , similar to the median counts of our sample (1399). It has $\Delta\text{AIC}_L = 165$, indicating significant L_{X} variability. Its L_{X} values in the first two epochs are about three times higher than those in the last two epochs. It is X-ray obscured (i.e., $N_{\text{H}} > 10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) with no significant N_{H} variability detected ($\Delta\text{AIC}_N = -0.9$).

J033229.9–274530 has $\Delta\text{AIC}_L = 144$ and $\Delta\text{AIC}_N = 83$ with a total net counts of ≈ 5000 . It is the most significantly N_{H} variable source (i.e., has maximum ΔAIC_N). The N_{H} values in the first two epochs are low (consistent with zero). The N_{H} rises in epoch 3 and reaches $\approx 2 \times 10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ in epoch 4. Its L_{X} in epoch 1 is ≈ 2 times higher than L_{X} in the other epochs. The X-ray type transition happens between epochs 2 and 4, and thus corresponds to a rest-frame time scale $t_{\text{tran}} \sim 3$ year. If we interpret the transition as an “eclipse” event, this long time scale indicates the eclipsing material is located at a distance larger than that of the BLR from the central engine. This is because BLR-cloud eclipses are likely to happen on much shorter time scales (hours to days; e.g., [426, 489]). Assuming that the eclipsing material is in a single “cloud” within the inner torus region, its distance (r) from the central engine is $\sim 0.1 \text{ pc}$.¹⁸ Applying Kepler’s 3rd law, we can calculate its

¹⁸The distance is estimated from the empirical relation between the inner torus radius and X-ray luminosity obtained from dust reverberation-mapping studies [404].

orbital period

$$\begin{aligned}
 t_{\text{orbit}} &= 2\pi \frac{r^{\frac{3}{2}}}{(M_{\text{BH}}G)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \\
 &\sim 300 \left(\frac{M_{\text{BH}}}{10^8 M_{\odot}} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \text{ yr.}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{B.22}$$

Then we can estimate the angular size of the cloud, θ (viewed from the central SMBH), as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \theta &\sim \frac{t_{\text{tran}}}{t_{\text{orbit}}} \times 360^{\circ} \\
 &\sim 4^{\circ} \left(\frac{M_{\text{BH}}}{10^8 M_{\odot}} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{B.23}$$

To investigate if the optical spectral type also changes, we have compiled three optical spectra from the literature [73, 490, 491] and obtained a new spectrum on November 8, 2015. The new observation was performed using the IMACS Short-Camera of the 6.5m Magellan Telescope. The four spectra are presented in Figure B.17. In all four spectra, the broad Mg II $\lambda 2798$ line is detected. In the first and third spectra, the C III] $\lambda 1909$ line is also detected.¹⁹ Thus, the optical spectral type of this source remains type I in all four spectra. The lack of optical spectral-type transitions indicates the X-ray eclipsing material is not large enough to block most emission from the BLR. This result is consistent with recent studies of optical spectral-type transition AGNs that suggest significant changes (~ 10 times) in luminosity as the main cause of transitions [492, 493].

¹⁹We do not perform quantitative analyses, since all of the spectra cannot be reduced uniformly.

Figure B.5: The histograms of P_{PF} (upper panel) and P_{HR} (lower panel). The red and brown bars indicate type I and type II AGNs, respectively. The vertical black dashed lines in both panels indicate the value of 5%, our variability criterion. The leftmost column indicates all sources with P_{PF} (P_{HR}) $< 0.1\%$. Photon-flux variability is generally more common than hardness-ratio variability.

Figure B.6: Upper panel: best-fit Γ histogram. Lower panel: *goodness* histogram. The *goodness* distribution indicates the $wabs \times zwabs \times pegpurlw$ model generally describes our data acceptably.

Figure B.7: Flux (epoch 4) vs. flux (epoch 1). The fluxes are calculated from our spectral-fitting results (see Section B.3.2.1), and are not corrected for Galactic or intrinsic absorption. The energy band is observed-frame 0.5–7 keV (i.e., full-band). The red dashed line indicates no flux change; the red dotted lines indicate flux changes by a factor of 2. The ranks of fluxes are similar in the two epochs. Thus, X-ray variability over 15 years does not significantly affect the appearance of the overall X-ray source population.

Figure B.8: Upper panel: L_X vs. z . The open circles, crosses and solid circles indicate L_X -variable, N_H -variable, and non-variable sources, respectively. A source can be both L_X -variable and N_H -variable. Red and brown colors indicate type I and type II sources, respectively. The green and the blue points indicate G12 quasars and the rest of the AGNs in L16. At a given redshift, our sources are generally less luminous than G12 quasars and more luminous than the other L16 AGNs. The dashed horizontal line indicates our definition of quasars (i.e., $L_X > 10^{44} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$, see Section B.2.2). Lower panel: L_X vs. N_H . The symbols have the same meanings as for the upper panel. The horizontal and vertical dashed lines indicate our definition of quasars and the common definition of X-ray obscured AGNs (i.e., $N_H > 10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-2}$), respectively.

Figure B.9: $\sigma_{\text{exc},L}^2$ vs. L_X . L_X values are the mean values in Section B.3.2.1. Gray points indicate each individual source. The red squares indicate the mean value of each bin. The red horizontal error bars indicate the bin widths; the red vertical error bars indicate the errors on the mean values calculated analytically (see Section B.3.2.6). The green shaded region indicates the $\sigma_{\text{exc},L}^2$ expected from a power-law PSD with a slope of -1 (see Section B.4.2). Our $\sigma_{\text{exc},L}^2$ decreases at high luminosity. This is likely caused by the fact that our highest sampling frequency exceeds the PSD break frequency of the luminous sources (Section B.4.2).

Figure B.10: Upper panel: the $\sigma_{exc,L}^2$ histogram. The red and brown colors indicate type I and type II AGNs, respectively. A KS test shows the dependence of $\sigma_{exc,L}^2$ on optical type is not significant. The rightmost column indicates all sources with $\sigma_{exc,L}^2 > 0.2$. Lower panel: $\sigma_{exc,N}^2$ histogram. Only the 35 sources with $\sigma_{exc,N}^2$ calculated are shown here (Section B.3.2.7). The rightmost column indicates all sources with $\sigma_{exc,N}^2 > 0.04$.

Figure B.11: Structure functions (SFs) as a function of rest-frame time interval, Δt_{rest} . The blue square points and the red circle points indicate the observed SFs for L_X and N_H , respectively. The SF for L_X is calculated based on non-quasar ($L_X < 10^{44}$ erg s $^{-1}$) sources only to avoid a bias (Section B.3.2.8). The error bars of the SFs indicate 1σ uncertainties calculated from bootstrapping; the error bars of Δt_{rest} indicate the bin width.

Figure B.12: $norm_i - \Gamma$ confidence contours of the first two epochs of J033217.1–275220 resulting from modelling with $wabs \times zwabs \times powerlaw$ (upper panel) and $wabs \times zwabs \times pegpurlw$ (lower panel). Black and red colors indicate epochs 1 and 2, respectively. The solid, dashed, and dotted curves indicate 1σ (68%), 2σ (95%), and 99% confidence contours, respectively. The horizontal solid lines indicate the 2σ uncertainty ranges of $norm_i$. In the upper panel, the 99% confidence contours do not overlap, indicating highly significant variability of $norm_i$ (i.e., $> 99.99\%$ confidence level; see Section B.5.1). However, the two projected $norm_i$ uncertainty ranges have an overlapping interval (blue shaded region), and a χ^2 test shows that the significance level of $norm_i$ variability is only 93%. Thus, the errors of $norm_i$ are overestimated under the assumption of constant Γ . In the lower panel, this issue does not occur.

Figure B.13: Fractional errors $\delta N_{H,i}/N_{H,i}$ obtained by fixing Γ at the 90% confidence limits of Γ_{fit} vs. those obtained by fixing Γ at the best-fit value. The green upward-pointing and blue downward-pointing triangles indicate the fractional errors obtained by fixing Γ at the upper and lower limits of Γ_{fit} , respectively. The red solid line indicates the ideal situation, i.e., the estimated fractional errors are not affected by fixing Γ at different values. The vertical red dashed line indicates our threshold, i.e., only sources with all four epochs having $\delta N_{H,i}/N_{H,i} < 0.4$ are included in the analyses where errors on $N_{H,i}$ are being used. Its intersection points with the approximate outer envelopes of the blue and green triangles are indicated by the horizontal red dash-dotted lines, and their deviations from $\delta N_{H,i}/N_{H,i} = 0.4$ (the horizontal red dashed line) are ≈ 0.15 (15%, as marked). Our sample consists 68 sources with each of them having 4 epochs. Thus, there are 272 (68×4) pairs of triangles plotted (though some are located out of the plotted ranges and are not shown). Note that for each source, the $\delta N_{H,i}/N_{H,i}$ (x -axis) are different for different epochs.

Figure B.14: Upper panel: unfolded (i.e., intrinsic) spectra for the Compton-thick candidate J033218.3–275055 using fitting model $wabs \times zwabs \times pexmon$. The solid lines indicate best-fit model photon-flux density. Different colors indicate different epochs. The vertical dashed line indicates the energy of Fe $K\alpha$ line (i.e., rest-frame 6.4 keV). Data are binned for display purposes only. Note that the flux in the high-energy band (less affected by absorption) varies significantly. Lower panel: ratio of observed and model photon flux.

Figure B.15: Confidence contours of the normalizations of p_{exmon} and N_{H} for source J033218.3–275055, the Compton-thick candidate. The solid and dashed curves indicate 1σ and 2σ confidence contours, respectively. Different colors indicate different epochs, and the epoch indexes are also labeled beside the corresponding contours.

Figure B.16: Upper panels: unfolded (i.e., intrinsic) spectra for J033226.5-274035, J033259.7-274626, and J033229.9-274530, respectively. The solid lines indicate best-fit model photon flux. Different colors indicate different epochs, and the epoch indexes are also labeled beside the corresponding spectra. Data are binned for display purposes only. Middle panels: the corresponding ratios of observed and model photon-flux density. Lower panels: the corresponding L_X - N_H confidence contours. J033226.5-274035 has significantly higher luminosity in epoch 2. The luminosity of J033259.7-274626 drops by a large factor (≈ 3) since epoch 3. For J033229.9-274530, the spectral shape changes obviously among epochs.

Figure B.17: Normalized optical spectra of J033229.9–274530 at $z = 1.21$. The observation dates and the references are listed in the upper-right corner of each panel (C01: [490]; M05: [73]; P09: [491]). The Mg II $\lambda 2798$ broad emission line is present in all four spectra.

Appendix C | Fast Extragalactic X-ray Transients in *Chandra* Surveys

C.1 Introduction

X-ray observations can provide uniquely insightful views of many astronomical phenomena such as accretion and mergers of compact objects (e.g. [80]; [494]). The X-ray sky is variable. Main-sequence stars (especially dwarfs) have strong flares powered by magnetic reconnection, generally lasting minutes to hours [495, 496]. X-ray binaries have various variability behaviors such as pulsations, bursts, and quasi-periodic oscillations [497, 498]. Active galactic nuclei (AGNs) typically have red-noise variability, with characteristic amplitudes being $\lesssim 0.3$ dex on timescales of $\lesssim 10$ years [48, 421, 499, 500].

Recently, a new type of X-ray variability phenomenon has been revealed in the form of two relatively faint X-ray transients found in the *Chandra* observations of the *Chandra* Deep Field-South (CDF-S XT1 and XT2; [38]; Xue et al. submitted). Both transients are fast ($T_{90} \approx 10$ ks,¹ observed-frame). Their origins are found to be extragalactic, with optical/near-infrared (NIR) counterparts at $z \approx 2.1$ (photometric redshift) and $z = 0.74$ (spectroscopic redshift), respectively. Both transients have $\gtrsim 100$ counts detected, corresponding to enormous amounts of energy release ($\gtrsim 10^{48}$ erg, assuming isotropic emission). Due to the lack of simultaneous multiwavelength observations and the small sample size of transients, the physical origins are not well determined with some possibilities being off-axis

¹ T_{90} is defined as the time interval between the arrival times of the 5%-th photon and the 95%-th photon.

gamma-ray bursts, tidal-disruption events, mergers of neutron stars, and shock-breakout events. In this paper, we regard CDF-S XT1 and XT2 as the same “type” of transients considering their observational similarities in flux, timespan, and extragalactic origin, although their physical causes might be different.

Given the short timescales ($T_{90} \approx 10$ ks) and large numbers of counts ($\gtrsim 100$) for CDF-S XT1 and XT2, such transients should be easy to detect in any $\gtrsim 10$ ks *Chandra* exposure. The two transients are both detected in a small survey area (≈ 480 arcmin²) and relatively short timespan (2014 October and 2015 March), indicating that a large population of X-ray transients might exist. [38] performed a preliminary transient search in the *Chandra* source catalog (CSC; [350]), which compiled *Chandra* observations before 2010 August 10. They did not find transients similar to the CDF-S transients. However, this CSC search is not conclusive, because the CSC is not dedicated to discover fast transients and thus potential transients might be missed or poorly/incorrectly characterized. Also, many CSC sources have only a single short *Chandra* visit, making it difficult to ascertain the transient and quiescent levels. The CSC sources also generally lack deep optical/NIR observations, preventing further studies of the physical nature of potential transients.

To mitigate the above issues, in this work, we search for similar transients in *Chandra* archival observations of X-ray surveys. We develop a method to identify transients in a single *Chandra* exposure, which is applicable to any *Chandra* imaging observation. In the surveys, most X-ray sources have been visited by two or more *Chandra* exposures, allowing us to inspect transients with multi-epoch X-ray data and study their quiescent behaviors. Deep multiwavelength data are critical in clarifying the physical origins of X-ray transients. CDF-S XT1 and XT2 have optical/NIR counterparts with $V \gtrsim 25$ mag and $H \gtrsim 24$ mag ([38]; Xue et al. submitted), well beyond the detection limit of wide-field surveys such as SDSS [349] and UKIDSS [501]. [502] discovered an X-ray transient in one *Chandra* archival observation, but were not able to clarify its physical origin due to the lack of deep multiwavelength data. Our selected X-ray surveys are accompanied by deep multiwavelength observations, allowing identifications of optical/NIR counterparts for the selected transients.

This paper is organized as follows. We describe our X-ray data, transient selection, optical/NIR counterparts, and transient event rate in §C.2. We summarize our results and discuss future prospects in §C.3. Throughout this paper, we assume

Survey	Area	Total Exp.	Obs. Num.	Src. Num.	Reference
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
CDF-S	0.13	6.9	101	1008	[67]
CDF-N	0.12	2.0	20	683	[241]
DEEP2	3.28	3.7	139	2976	[329, 340]
UDS	0.33	1.2	25	868	[330]; Suh et al. in prep.
COSMOS	2.20	4.5	117	4016	[217, 218]
E-CDF-S	0.31	1.0	9	1003	[241]
All	6.38	19.3	411	10554	–

Table C.1: Properties of X-ray Surveys Analyzed in this Work. (1) X-ray survey name. (2) Survey area in deg^2 . (3) Total exposure time in Ms. (4) Number of *Chandra* observations. (5) X-ray source number. (6) References where the survey details and source catalog are presented. Additional information about the CDF-S, CDF-N, and E-CDF-S can be found in [195].

a cosmology with $H_0 = 70 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$, $\Omega_M = 0.3$, and $\Omega_\Lambda = 0.7$. Quoted uncertainties are at the 1σ (68%) confidence level, unless otherwise stated. Quoted optical/infrared magnitudes are AB magnitudes.

C.2 Data and Analyses

C.2.1 X-ray Data

In this work, we analyze the *Chandra* survey data from the CDF-S, CDF-N, DEEP2, UDS, COSMOS, and E-CDF-S regions. The survey properties are summarized in Table C.1. DEEP2 includes the full field of EGS (DEEP2-1) and three other fields (DEEP2-2, DEEP2-3, and DEEP2-4) with shallower ($\approx 10 \text{ ks}$) exposures.

The total exposure time of these surveys is 19 Ms. All the surveys are at high Galactic latitude ($|b| \gtrsim 40^\circ$), matching our main interest of searching for extragalactic transients. Also, these surveys have deep multiwavelength coverage, allowing us to study the physical origins of the transients (§C.1 and §C.2.4).

C.2.2 Transient Selection

We download all the *Chandra* data products of observations related to the surveys, and run the CHANDRA_REPRO script in CIAO 4.10.² The CHANDRA_REPRO script

²Our analyses do not include observation 1431 (CDF-S), which consists of two separate exposures. The event 2 files for the two separate exposures cannot be obtained with CHANDRA_REPRO script.

performs standard cleaning and calibration processes,³ and yields a clean event file for each observation.

For each event file, we extract the 0.5–7 keV photons of each X-ray source presented in the X-ray catalogs (see §C.2.1). Since the *Chandra* background is extremely low, any sources with $\gtrsim 10$ net counts should be detected by the X-ray surveys. This level of counts is much lower than that of our transient-selection sensitivity (see below), and thus we should not miss any transients due to their absence in the X-ray catalogs. The total events are extracted from an aperture of $1.5 \times R_{90}$, where R_{90} is the radius encircling 90% of the X-ray counts. We adopt R_{90} as a function of off-axis angle from Table A1 of [96]. The background events are extracted from an annulus with inner and outer radii of $1.5 \times R_{90}$ and $1.5 \times R_{90} + 20$ pixels. The background area is 9 times larger than the source area for a typical source at an off-axis angle of $5'$. If the background region covers a nearby X-ray source, we mask the source (also with radius of $1.5 \times R_{90}$), and do not include the masked area when estimating the background. We note that changing the source and background extraction regions slightly will not affect our qualitative results. We denote the numbers of total events and background events (scaled by source area divided by background area) as N and N_{bkg} , respectively.

After the extraction process, we now have an array of photon arrival times for each source in the observation. Below, we denote N_1 and N_2 as the numbers of counts at $t = (t_{\text{bgn}}, t_{\text{m}})$ and $t = (t_{\text{m}}, t_{\text{end}})$, respectively, where t_{bgn} and t_{end} are the times when the exposure starts and ends, respectively, and $t_{\text{m}} = (t_{\text{bgn}} + t_{\text{end}})/2$. Since typical *Chandra* observations are continuous and uninterrupted by background flares ($\approx 1\%$ of exposure time), our two-part division of the exposure is legitimate.

We select a source in an observation as a transient candidate if it satisfies all of the following criteria (Method 1):

- (A) $N > 5 \times N_{\text{bkg}}$;
- (B) $N_1 > 5 \times N_2$ or $N_2 > 5 \times N_1$;
- (C) N_1 is outside of the 5σ Poisson confidence interval of N_2 ;
- (D) N_2 is outside of the 5σ Poisson confidence interval of N_1 .

³http://cxc.harvard.edu/ciao/ahelp/chandra_repro.html

Criterion A filters out faint sources that have low signal-to-noise ratios (S/N). This criterion is helpful in avoiding false detections caused by rare background flares, since flares can dominate the detected counts for faint sources. Criterion B selects sources that have large differences in count rates of the first-half and second-half exposures. Criteria C and D guarantee the differences selected by criterion B are statistically significant. Method 1 selects 15 transients. We visually inspect the background light curves of these transients, and do not find significant flares.

Method 1 is not efficient in selecting transients that happen at $t \approx t_m$, because these transients will have similar N_1 and N_2 . To overcome this defect, we also select transients with the following method. We denote N'_1 as the number of counts at $t = (t_{\text{bgn}}, t_{\text{q1}})$ plus that at $t = (t_{\text{q3}}, t_{\text{end}})$, where t_{q1} and t_{q3} are the first and third quartiles of the observation time, and N'_2 as the number of counts at $t = (t_{\text{q1}}, t_{\text{q3}})$. We also select a source as a transient candidate, if it satisfies (Method 2)

$$(A') N > 5 \times N_{\text{bkg}};$$

$$(B') N'_1 > 5 \times N'_2 \text{ or } N'_2 > 5 \times N'_1;$$

$$(C') N'_1 \text{ is outside of the } 5\sigma \text{ Poisson confidence interval of } N'_2;$$

$$(D') N'_2 \text{ is outside of the } 5\sigma \text{ Poisson confidence interval of } N'_1.$$

Method 2 selected two additional transients that are missed by Method 1.

We note that loosening the selection criteria above slightly (e.g. changing Criterion A to “ $N_1 > 4 \times N_2$ or $N_2 > 4 \times N_1$ ”) does not lead to additional extragalactic transients. We assess the efficiency of our transient-search algorithm with simulations in §C.4.1. We find that our method is able to detect transients down to ≈ 30 net counts (peak flux $F_{0.5-7 \text{ keV}} \approx 2 \times 10^{-13} \text{ erg cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$), assuming light-curve shapes similar to CDF-S XT1 or XT2. This detection limit works not only for a typical ≈ 50 ks exposure, but also for a short exposure of ≈ 10 ks.

C.2.3 Selection Results

A total of 17 transients are selected. Their X-ray properties are listed in Table C.2. ID1 and ID2 are CDF-S XT1 and XT2, respectively. Their successful selection indicates that our method of transient searching is effective at selecting fast X-ray transients (§C.4.1). We have checked the X-ray images of the transients in both

sky and detector coordinates. For each source, the events are concentrated and extended in sky and detector coordinates, respectively. This indicates that the transients are physical X-ray sources rather than hot pixels, because hot pixels will lead to extended (concentrated) patterns in the sky (detector) coordinates caused by *Chandra* dithering.

For each transient, we calculate the hardness ratio for the observation where the transient is identified. Here, hardness ratio is defined as $(H - S)/(H + S)$, where H and S are hard-band (2–7 keV) and soft-band (0.5–2 keV) net counts, respectively. The uncertainty is calculated with BEHR, a Bayesian code for hardness ratio estimation [503]. The results are listed in Table. C.2. In Fig C.1, we show the distribution of hardness ratios. The spectral shapes of XT1 and XT2 are harder than most of the other transients.

In Fig. C.2 (left), we show the light curves of the transients during the observation when the transient happens. The light curves are derived from the X-ray events extracted in §C.2.2, and are binned by 5-count intervals. The data points in these light curves indicate total count rates, including contributions from the source and background. The estimated average background count rate is marked as the dashed line in each panel of Fig. C.2 (left). [502] discovered an ultrafast transient lasting only $\lesssim 0.1$ ks in a *Chandra* observation of galaxy cluster ACO 3581. In §C.4.1, we show that our transient-search algorithm is able to detect such ultrafast transients with $\gtrsim 30$ net counts. However, from Fig. C.2 (left), we do not find such transients, as our transients all last longer than ~ 1 ks.

The duration of XT1 and XT2 tend to be shorter than other transients (Fig. C.2 left). The T_{90} values of XT1 and XT2 are $5.0_{-0.3}^{+4.2}$ ks and $11.1_{-0.6}^{+0.4}$ ks, respectively (see [38] and Xue et al. submitted for details). We do not derive T_{90} for other transients, because T_{90} cannot be derived for many transients that extend beyond the *Chandra* exposures (e.g. ID3 and ID7 in Fig. C.2 left). Also, unlike XT1 and XT2, many of the other transients have non-zero fluxes in the quiescent states, and thus their T_{90} calculation requires careful subtraction of the quiescent fluxes, which is beyond the scope of this work.

We plot the long-term light curves in Fig. C.2 (right), where each *Chandra* observation is represented by a data point. These data points indicate net count rates, which are background-subtracted. As expected, the transient observation generally has a count rate much higher than other observations. However, unlike

Figure C.1: Hardness-ratio distribution of our selected transients. CDF-S XT1 and XT2 are highlighted with the red color. The spectral shapes of XT1 and XT2 are harder than most of the other transients.

the CDF-S XT1 and XT2 events, most of the other transients have detectable signals in some of the non-transient observations. Also, CDF-S XT1 and XT2 tend to have higher hardness ratios than the rest of the selected transients (Fig. C.1). These differences indicate that most of the new transients are physically distinct from CDF-S XT1 and XT2 (see §C.2.4).

ID	Survey	RA	DEC	Pos. Unc.	Obs. ID	Off. Ang.	N_1	N_2	N'_1	N'_2	HR
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)
1	CDF-S	53.16156	-27.85934	0.32''	16454	4.3'	110	6	1	115	-0.13 ^{+0.09} _{-0.10}
2	CDF-S	53.07648	-27.87339	0.31''	16453	4.1'	1	122	3	120	-0.32 ^{+0.08} _{-0.09}
3	CDF-S	53.17535	-27.95053	0.27''	16177	9.5'	37	317	141	213	-0.46 ^{+0.06} _{-0.07}
4	CDF-S	53.20694	-27.91498	0.25''	17677	7.9'	184	23	166	41	-0.35 ^{+0.07} _{-0.09}
5	CDF-N	189.02046	62.33728	0.20''	957	6.6'	12	69	64	17	-0.54 ^{+0.08} _{-0.12}
6	CDF-N	189.35679	62.28019	0.30''	967	4.6'	0	16	15	1	-0.94 ^{+0.12} _{-0.06}
7	DEEP2	215.07414	53.10650	0.36''	9875	6.7'	61	8	47	22	-0.72 ^{+0.08} _{-0.12}
8	DEEP2	214.96015	52.74344	0.26''	9456	6.6'	48	19	4	63	-0.63 ^{+0.12} _{-0.14}
9	DEEP2	252.12761	34.96337	0.53''	8636	7.5'	6	59	44	21	-0.62 ^{+0.09} _{-0.12}
10	UDS	34.48317	-5.09118	0.96''	17305	0.7'	0	25	6	19	-0.53 ^{+0.15} _{-0.18}
11	COSMOS	149.75403	2.14188	0.30''	8021	4.0'	4	34	18	20	-0.80 ^{+0.09} _{-0.14}
12	COSMOS	149.82641	2.71812	0.30''	15214	5.9'	13	105	29	89	-0.58 ^{+0.07} _{-0.09}
13	COSMOS	149.56678	1.81249	0.10''	15220	3.5'	5	63	40	28	-0.69 ^{+0.08} _{-0.10}
14	COSMOS	149.94567	1.58063	0.10''	15247	0.5'	6	45	15	36	-0.57 ^{+0.11} _{-0.12}
15	COSMOS	149.96818	2.78045	1.00''	15239	4.8'	2	24	9	17	-0.96 ^{+0.07} _{-0.04}
16	COSMOS	149.99794	2.77972	0.90''	15211	6.5'	25	14	3	36	-0.69 ^{+0.12} _{-0.14}
17	COSMOS	149.86844	2.79341	0.90''	15239	7.8'	6	45	11	40	-0.12 ^{+0.17} _{-0.18}

Table C.2: X-ray Properties of Transients. (1) Transient ID in this work. (2) X-ray survey name. (3), (4), and (5) X-ray source position and positional error from the corresponding survey catalog. The positional error is taken from the survey catalog, and is calculated based on all observations that cover the source (not only the observation in Column 6). For example, ID6 has a lower positional uncertainty than ID15, because the former has more total net counts than the latter (≈ 100 vs. ≈ 25). (6) *Chandra* ID of the observation where the transient is identified. (7) Off-axis angle of the transient in the observation. (8), (9), (10), and (11) The counts numbers used to select transients (see §C.2.2). (12) Hardness ratio based on the observation in Column 6.

C.2.4 Optical/NIR Counterparts

We have compiled the likelihood counterpart matching results from the survey catalogs (Table C.1). All the transients have optical/NIR counterparts. The counterpart properties are presented in Table C.3. We also match the counterparts with the *Gaia* catalog [504] using a $1''$ matching radius, and mark the sources with non-zero parallax and/or proper motion as “star” in Table C.3. We show the X-ray and optical/IR image cutouts in Fig. C.7.

From Table C.3, ID1 and ID2 (namely CDF-S XT1 and XT2) are likely of extragalactic origin and have already been discussed in detail ([38]; Xue et al., submitted). The other transients are relatively bright (magnitudes $\lesssim 20$), and most of them (except ID13 and ID17) are reliably identified as stellar objects by optical/NIR spectroscopy and/or *Gaia*. We search NED and SIMBAD for ID13 and ID17, but do not find any spectroscopic information. The *HST* images of ID13 and ID17 show that they are point-like sources, indicating that they are either quasars or stars. However, these two sources are classified as stars rather than quasars based on the SDSS color-color diagrams [505]. This result is consistent with the SED fitting of [218] who found the ≈ 30 -band SEDs of the two sources prefer stellar templates rather than galaxy/quasar templates. Also, the two sources have optical-to-X-ray flux ratios (in the non-bursting observations) consistent with those of K/M stars [506]. Therefore, we conclude that ID13 and ID17 are likely stellar objects as well. In summary, all the new transients (aside from CDF-S XT1 and XT2) are likely stellar flares.

C.2.5 Transient Event Rate

Our transient-search algorithm is able to find transients with more than ≈ 30 net counts, corresponding to a peak flux of $F_{0.5-7 \text{ keV}} \approx 2 \times 10^{-13} \text{ erg cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (§C.2.2). However, we do not find any new extragalactic transients, despite searching *Chandra* observations totaling 19 Ms exposure (§C.2.4). This null result is somewhat unexpected considering the notable coincidence of CDF-S XT1 and XT2, which are detected in a small survey area and relatively short timespan (§C.1).

Based on the fact that two transients are detected in the 19 Ms of survey data, we estimate an empirical event rate of $0.10_{-0.07}^{+0.14} \text{ evt Ms}^{-1}$ for a typical *Chandra* imaging observation with 4 CCDs on. The event rate can also be written as

Figure C.2: Light curves for each transient. The left panels are light curves for the observation with the transient, with each bin including 5 counts. The horizontal dashed lines indicate the estimated average background count rates. The right panels are long-term light curves with each data point representing a *Chandra* observation. The transient observation is highlighted in red color. The horizontal dashed lines indicate a net count rate of zero.

Figure C.3: Light curves for each transient (continued).

Figure C.4: Light curves for each transient (continued).

Figure C.5: Light curves for each transient (continued).

Figure C.6: Light curves for each transient (continued).

ID (1)	Source (2)	Mag (3)	RA _c (4)	DEC _c (5)	Offset (6)	z (7)	z type (8)	<i>Gaia</i> (9)
1	CANDELS	$H = 27.1$	53.16157	-27.85936	0.07''	2.14	phot	n/a
2	CANDELS	$H = 24.3$	53.07659	-27.87329	0.50''	0.74	spec	n/a
3	GEMS	$z = 13.1$	53.17507	-27.95064	0.95''	0.00	spec	n/a
4	CANDELS	$H = 15.6$	53.20693	-27.91504	0.21''	0.00	spec	star
5	WIRCam	$K_s = 16.3$	189.02037	62.33728	0.14''	0.00	spec	star
6	CANDELS	$H = 17.5$	189.35692	62.28008	0.45''	0.00	spec	n/a
7	DEEP2-1	$I = 20.1$	215.07411	53.10657	0.26''	0.00	spec	n/a
8	DEEP2-1	$I = 15.6$	214.95966	52.74351	1.10''	-99.00	n/a	star
9	DEEP2-2	$I = 16.8$	252.12746	34.96339	0.45''	0.00	spec	star
10	HSC	$z = 18.1$	34.48311	-5.09118	0.25''	0.00	spec	star
11	UltraVISTA	$K_s = 16.4$	149.75412	2.14183	0.38''	0.00	spec	star
12	UltraVISTA	$K_s = 15.6$	149.82649	2.71803	0.41''	0.00	spec	star
13	UltraVISTA	$K_s = 15.7$	149.56679	1.81242	0.28''	0.00	phot	n/a
14	UltraVISTA	$K_s = 22.1$	149.94561	1.58073	0.41''	0.00	spec	star
15	UltraVISTA	$K_s = 13.8$	149.96791	2.78048	0.97''	0.00	phot	star
16	UltraVISTA	$K_s = 16.2$	149.99794	2.77960	0.40''	0.00	spec	n/a
17	UltraVISTA	$K_s = 18.2$	149.86856	2.79331	0.57''	0.00	phot	n/a

Table C.3: Counterpart Properties of Transients. (1) Transient ID in this work. (2) Source of the counterpart: CANDELS [65,66], GEMS [507], WIRCam [368], DEEP2 [508], HSC [509], and UltraVISTA [214]. (3) AB magnitude of the counterpart. For ID10, the magnitude is from SDSS, since the X-ray catalog ([330]; Suh et al. in prep.) does not provide magnitude information. (4) and (5) The position of the optical/NIR counterpart. (6) The distance between the X-ray position and the counterpart. (7) and (8) redshift and its type. “0.00” means stellar object. “-99.00” means redshift unavailable. $z = 0.00$ and z type = phot mean the source’s SED prefers a stellar template rather than a quasar/galaxy template. For ID7 and ID9, we adopt the redshifts from SDSS, since redshift information is not provided in the X-ray catalog [340]. (9) *Gaia* classification. “star” indicates the source has non-zero parallax and/or proper motion ($S/N > 5$) measured from *Gaia*; otherwise, “n/a” is listed.

Figure C.7: Optical/NIR image $10'' \times 10''$ cutouts of the transients. Each cutout is centered at the X-ray position. The central red circle denotes the X-ray positional uncertainty, and has a radius $3 \times \Delta X$, where ΔX is the 1σ X-ray positional error listed in Table C.2. The cutouts are from the reddest *HST* band (as labelled) available or the SDSS z band. The *HST* I -band cutouts are from [510], and other *HST* cutouts are from the *Hubble* Legacy Archive (<https://hla.stsci.edu/>).

46_{-30}^{+61} evt yr $^{-1}$ deg $^{-2}$. There are ≈ 240 Ms of *Chandra* archival imaging observations at Galactic latitudes of $|b| > 20^\circ$. We expect that 25_{-16}^{+33} transients of extragalactic origins can be found in these observations. On the other hand, we estimate that a total of 185_{-47}^{+61} stellar flares exist in these observations, since 15 stellar flares are identified in the 19 Ms of survey data.

We will perform an extensive *Chandra* archival search in a separate paper (Quirola Vázquez et al. in prep.). From our results (§C.2.4), the stellar X-ray transients found in archival data are likely to have bright optical/NIR counterparts (magnitudes $\lesssim 20$), and thus their stellar nature can be largely determined with current wide-field surveys, e.g. SDSS, UKIDSS, and *Gaia*. In contrast, the

counterparts of extragalactic transients will likely be faint in the optical/NIR, and follow-up observations with large ground-based telescopes will be helpful to study their properties such as redshift and host-galaxy stellar mass. These counterparts may also be studied with future deep wide-field surveys such as LSST [511] and *Euclid* [512].

Note that our estimated event rate is not directly comparable to that presented in [38], who performed a preliminary CSC search. We are interested in general extragalactic transient phenomena, and any sources with a strong flux rise and/or drop can be identified by our algorithm (§C.2.2). In contrast, [38] focused on sources that are similar to CDF-S XT1. For example, they did not consider sources with recurrent outbursts or persistent X-ray fluxes.

C.3 Summary and Future Prospects

We have performed a systematic search for X-ray transients in 19 Ms of *Chandra* surveys, including CDF-S, CDF-N, DEEP2, UDS, COSMOS, and E-CDF-S. Our main results are summarized below.

1. We developed a method to select transients within a *Chandra* observation (§C.2.2). From simulations, we show that our method is efficient in discovering transients with $\gtrsim 30$ net counts (peak flux $F_{0.5-7 \text{ keV}} \approx 2 \times 10^{-13} \text{ erg cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$; §C.4.1).
2. Our selection yields 17 transients (§C.2.3), including CDF-S XT1 and XT2 which have been reported in previous works ([38]; Xue et al. submitted). All the transients have optical/NIR counterparts (§C.2.4). Except for CDF-S XT1 and XT2, all other transients are stellar objects.
3. The lack of new extragalactic transients in our search indicates that such objects are rare (§C.2.5). We estimate an event rate of $0.10_{-0.07}^{+0.14} \text{ evt Ms}^{-1}$ or $46_{-30}^{+61} \text{ evt yr}^{-1} \text{ deg}^{-2}$, corresponding to a total of 25_{-16}^{+33} events in *Chandra* archival observations at $|b| > 20^\circ$.

Future work could also search *XMM-Newton* survey data for extragalactic transients (e.g. the EXTraS project; [513]). A broad (not restricted to surveys) search of *Chandra* and *XMM-Newton* archival data can also be performed (§C.2.5).

Future X-ray missions such as *Athena* [514,515] and the *Einstein Probe* [516] with large etendues might be able to find hundreds of extragalactic transients, and sample studies will be feasible then.

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Disclaimer

The findings and conclusions do not necessarily reflect the view of the funding agencies.

C.4 Supplementary Materials

C.4.1 Efficiency of Transient Selection

In this Section, we assess the efficiency of our transient selection method (§C.2.2) with Monte Carlo simulations. The simulations are based on a fixed light-curve shape. Since our main goal is to search for fast extragalactic transients analogous to CDF-S XT1 and XT2, we adopt a light-curve model similar to the best-fit models of these two transients ([38]; Xue et al. submitted). The light-curve shape in the

model is described by

$$\text{cntR}(t) \propto \begin{cases} 0, & t < 0 \\ t, & 0 \leq t < t_1 \\ t^{-0.1}, & t_1 \leq t < t_2 \\ t^{-2}, & t \geq t_2 \end{cases} \quad (\text{C.1})$$

where cntR is the count rate in units of counts s^{-1} . Here, we follow the convention that the transient starts at $t = 0$. At $t = (0, t_1)$, the cntR rises to the peak value. This time interval is very short ($\lesssim 100$ s for both CDF-S XT1 and XT2), and thus the exact functional form is not important. Here, we adopt a basic form of a linear rise and set $t_1 = 50$ s. At $t = (t_1, t_2)$, the light curve is roughly in a plateau. This plateau only exists for XT2 (2.3 ks) but not for XT1, and we adopt $t_2 = t_1 + 1$ ks. At $t > t_2$, the adopted cntR is a power-law decline with an index of -2 , which is between those of XT1 (-1.5) and XT2 (-2.2). We note that changing the model parameters slightly (e.g. changing t_1 to 100 s) does not significantly affect our simulation results. We plot the adopted light-curve model in Fig. C.8. The T_{90} for this light-curve setting is 9.4 ks, similar to those of XT1 and XT2. This similarity is expected, because our model in Eq. C.1 is based on the light-curve shapes of XT1 and XT2. The light curve is normalized so that the total net counts equals to a constant value, and we test different normalizations below.

We utilize the adopted light-curve model to simulate light curves. In the simulations, we assume a background of 6×10^{-5} cnt s^{-1} , which is the median value for all X-ray sources in our studied surveys. This background level only corresponds to ≈ 3 background counts for a typical 50 ks exposure. Following the convention in §C.2.2, we denote t_m as the midpoint of exposure time. Since the transient starts at $t = 0$, t_m actually means the relative time between the exposure midpoint and the transient start time. For a given set of net counts, exposure time (exp), and t_m , we can simulate the probability of transient detection following the procedures described below.

First, we simulate light curves in the time interval of $t = (-\text{exp}, \text{exp})$. We divide $t = (-\text{exp}, \text{exp})$ into small bins with $\Delta t = 10$ s. We then calculate the expected total counts in each bin. Using these values, we generate the counts in each bin with a Poisson distribution, which gives a simulated light curve. We repeat

Figure C.8: The light-curve model adopted in our simulations (§C.4.1). The light-curve shape is similar to those of CDF-S XT1 and XT2. The time (x -axis) zero point is chosen such that the transient starts at $t = 0$. In the plot, the total net counts is normalized to 100, for display purpose only. In the simulations, we test different normalizations.

the procedures and generate 1,000 light curves. We apply both Method 1 and Method 2 (§C.2.2) for these light curves and calculate the fraction of successful detections. We adopt this fraction as the detection probability for a given set of net counts, exposure time, and t_m .

Fig. C.9 shows our simulation results. For transients with net counts above ≈ 30 , the detection probability is high ($\gtrsim 70\%$). This result is true even for our shortest exposures (≈ 10 ks). Therefore, we adopt net counts of ≈ 30 as our detection limit. This level of counts corresponds to a peak flux of $F_{0.5-7 \text{ keV}} \approx 2 \times 10^{-13} \text{ erg cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for our adopted light-curve shape. This flux calculation is based on PIMMS,⁴ assuming a photon index of $\Gamma = 2$. We have also tested light-curve models similar to the ultrafast transients found by [502], and find similar detection limits (≈ 30 net counts).

⁴<http://exc.harvard.edu/toolkit/pimms.jsp>

Figure C.9: Probability of transient detection as a function of exposure midpoint (see §C.2.2). The probability is calculated based on simulations (§C.4.1). The time (x -axis) zero point is chosen such that the transient starts at $t = 0$. As labelled, different panels are for different net counts, different exposure times. There are some “glitches” on the curves, which are related to our transient-detection algorithm. For example, when the transients happens at $t \approx t_m$, the efficiency of Method 1 is low (see §C.2.2).

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Vita

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Research

- Black Hole-Galaxy Coevolution
- X-ray Transients
- X-ray Surveys

Education

- Ph.D. Astronomy, The Pennsylvania State University (2019)
- B.S. Astronomy, University of Science and Technology of China (2014)

Selected Awards

- Press Release: Black Holes are Outgrowing Their Galaxies (2018)
- Chandra Cycle 19 Archive Proposal: “Where do Monsters Grow?” (2017)
- Downsborough Graduate Fellowship (2017)

Recent Publications

- Yang, G., Brandt, W. N., B. Darvish, C.-T. J. Chen, ... & J. R. Trump (2018) “Does black-hole growth depend on the cosmic environment?”. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 480(1), 1022
- Ding, N., Luo, B., Brandt, W. N., Paolillo, M., Yang, G., Lehmer, B. D., ... & Zheng, X. C. (2018). “Variability-selected low-luminosity active galactic nuclei candidates in the 7 Ms Chandra Deep Field-South.” *ApJ* 868(2), 88
- Chen, CT J., W. N. Brandt, B. Luo, P. Ranalli, G. Yang, D. M. Alexander, F. E. Bauer et al. (2018) “The XMM-SERVS survey: new XMM–Newton point-source catalogue for the XMM-LSS field.” *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 478, (2), 2132